

НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И РАЗРАБОТКИ

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Сборник содержит научные статьи и тезисы ученых Российской Федерации, Узбекистана и других стран. Излагается теория, методология и практика научных исследований в области информационных технологий, экономики, образования, социологии.

Для специалистов в сфере управления, научных работников, преподавателей, аспирантов, студентов вузов и всех лиц, интересующихся рассматриваемыми проблемами.

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“SHAYTANAT” ASARINING SOTSIOLINGVISTIK TADQIQI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tilning taraqqiyotiga jamiyatning, aksincha jamiyat rivojiga tilning ta'siri, buning omillari, qonuniyatlarini tadqiq qiluvchi sohasi bo'lgan sotsiolingvistika hamda “Shaytanat” asarining sotsiolingvistik tadqiqi haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: sotsiologiya, mafiya, psixologiya, etnografiya, lingvistika, etnolingvistika, sotsiolingvistika.

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SOCIOLINGUISTIC STUDY OF” SHATYANAT”

Annotation. This article will talk about the influence of language on the development of language on the development of society, or rather on the development of society, sociolinguistics, a field that studies the factors, laws of this, as well as the sociolinguistic study of the work “Satanat”.

Keywords: sociology, mafia, psychology, ethnography, linguistics, ethnolinguistics, sociolinguistics

Umumjahon xalqlari o'z-o'zining o'rnini qidirayotgan bir davrda Vatanimiz O'zbekistonning har bir yashovchisi o'z nutqi va odobida, o'z muomala madaniyatida o'zbeklarning dunyo xalqlari o'rtasidagi mavqeyining naqadar ustunligini namoyon qilayotgani ma'lumdir.

Shuning uchun ham olimlar inson tilini u yashab turgan jamiyat bilan chambarchas bog'liqligini isbotlab, o'z mulohazalarini ilmiy asosda bildirib kelmoqdalar.

Ma'lumki, sotsiologiya jamiyatning rivojlanish qonuniyatlari, torroq ma'noda ijtimoiy guruhlar, ijtimoiy sistemalarning yashashi va taraqqiyot xususiyatlarini, uni harakatlantiruvchi kuchlarni o'rganuvchi fandır.

Tilning taraqqiyotiga jamiyatning, aksincha jamiyat rivojiga tilning ta'siri, buning omillari, qonuniyatlarini tadqiq qiluvchi sohani sotsiolingvistika (ijtimoiy tilshunoslik) deb yuritilmoqda.

G'arb va Amerika tilshunosligida sotsiolingvistika muammolariga doir bir qator tadqiqotlar yuzaga keldi. Bu tadqiqotlarning aksariyatida til bilan jamiyat o'rtasidagi munosabat, til taraqqiyotiga jamiyatning, sotsial omillarning ta'siri, ijtimoiy tilshunoslik bilan sotsiologiya, psixologiya, etnografiya, lingvistika, etnolingvistika va boshqalar orasidagi bog'liqlik, sotsiolingvistikaning tadqiq ob'ekti, predmeti, tilning ijtimoiy tarmoqlanishi, bu tarmoqlarning milliy tilga munosabati, tilning sotsial-differensial variantlari va ularda lisoniy variantlarning ko'rinishlari, muloqot jarayonida shaxslarning roli, nihoyat davlat til siyosatining til rivojiga ko'rsatadigan ijobiy va salbiy ta'siri va boshqalar haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Sotsiolingvistika sotsiologiyaning tarkibiga kiradimi yoki tilshunoslik tarkibigami yoxud mustaqil sohami?||, —Sotsiolingvistika o'z mustaqil ob'ekti, predmeti va metodlariga egami?|| – deyilgan savollar yuzasidan munozaralar davom etmoqda. Ba'zi ishlarda umumiy sotsiologiya, makrosotsiologiya va mikrosotsiologiya, sotsiolingvistika va lingvosotsiologiya haqida gap boradi.

Hozirda sotsiolingvistika, lingvosotsiologiya va lingvistik sotsiologiya deb yuritilayotgan soha: o'z vaqtida til sotsiologiyasi (социология языка, sotsiologik lingvistika (социальная лингвистика), sotsial tilshunoslik (социологическое языкознание), lingvistik sotsiologiya, lingvosotsiologiya kabi nomlanib kelgan.(1)

V. Bondaletovning fikricha, sotsial lingvistika tilshunoslikning bir yo'nalishi bo'lib, u til kelib chiqishining ijtimoiy asoslarini, tilning jamiyatga ta'sirini tadqiq qilishi kerak.(2)

Sotsiolingvistika tilshunoslikka daxldor bilim tarmog'i bo'lib, o'zbek tilshunosligida o'z o'rnini topmoqda. Tilning ijtimoiy holati, tilning paydo bo'lishi, til va jamiyat, ikkitillilik va ko'ptillilik, tillarning o'zaro ta'siri, ism va

toponimlarning yuzaga kelishi, bunda jamiyatning oʻrni, ijtimoiy muhitning taʼsiri, ism va toponimlarni motivativ tasniflash ushbu yoʻnalishning dolzarb vazifalaridan biridir. Ismlar maʼnosini ochishda ekstralingvistik omillarning oʻrni haqida gap ketganda ism etnolingvistik jihatdan ham tavsiflanadi. Umuman, sotsiolingvistik yoki lingvosotsiologik tahlilni lingvistik tahlildan farqlanuvchi, ammo u bilan bogʻliq holda amalga oshiriluvchi tahlil usuli deb bilish lozim boʻladi. Sotsiolingvistikani fan sifatida oʻrganish jarayonida uning umuminsoniy hamda siyosiy xususiyatlari, jumladan, til va jamiyat, til va mafkura, til va tafakkur, til va xalq, til va yosh, til va jins, davlat institutlarida til, til taraqqiyotini rejalashtirish, shuningdek, tilning falsafiy xususiyatlarini oʻrganish lozim boʻladi. Shunday ekan, sotsiolingvistikani oʻrganish va tatbiq etish jarayonida uning ijtimoiy-lisoniy omil sifatida hayot va jamiyatda tutgan oʻrni baholanadi. Shu orqali sotsiolingvistika va umumiy fanlar nazariyalari haqida maʼlumotga ega boʻlamiz. Ayniqsa, koʻpgina tilshunos olimlar nazdida —sotsiolingvistikalni falsafiy tilshunoslik deb qarashlar ham bu fanni boshqa fanlar bilan uzviy aloqadorligini anglatadi. Holbuki, koʻpgina tilshunos olimlar «sotsiolingvistika»ni oʻrganish jarayonida turli xil falsafiy mushohadalar yuritishdi. Ularning ayrimlari materialistik nuqtayi nazardan yondashgan boʻlsalar, baʼzilari esa idealistik nuqtayi nazardan qarab keldilar. Biz esa ijtimoiy tilshunoslik masalalarini toʻgʻri baholash va aniqlashni hayot va jamiyat taraqqiyoti bilan uzviy bogʻlab oʻrganamiz. Jumladan, O.Axmanovanning «Lingvistik terminlar lugʻati» yoki A. Hojievning «Lingvistik terminlarning qisqacha izohli lugʻati» ni koʻzdan kechirish orqali ham bu masalaga oydinlik kiritish mumkin. Xususan, O.Axmanova lugʻatida «sotsiolingvistika» termini «ijtimoiy lingvistika», «tilshunoslikning ijtimoiyligi» deb atalishi asosida quyidagicha maʼno kelib chiqadi: birinchidan, tilning umuminsoniy munosabatlardagi oʻrni, til va jamiyat oʻrtasidagi xususiyatlarning oʻzaro bogʻliqligini oʻrganish tatbiq etilsa, ikkinchidan, tilshunoslikning ijtimoiy munosabatlardagi turli xil vazifaviy xususiyati va aloqadorligi (masalan,

ijtimoiy dialekt, hududiy dialektlar, argo va jargonlar) va hokazolar til va jamiyat o`rtasidagi mushtaraklikni bog`lashga xizmat qilishi ta'kidlanadi. Ikkinchi vaziyatda ijtimoiy dialektlarning ijtimoiy til mohiyatlarini belgilovchi xususiyatlari faqat ijtimoiy dialekt sifatida emas, balki professional nutq, koyne va h.k tarzda tushuniladi. Ko`rinadiki, sotsiolingvistikaning asosiy muammosi «til va jamiyat» o`rtasidagi munosabatlarni o`rganishdan iboratdir. Shunday ekan, til va jamiyat munosabatlari o`rtasidagi bu bog`liqlik til va jamiyat taraqqiyotining uzviy ko`rinishidir.

Ko`pchilikning sevimli yozuvchisiga aylangan adib Tohir Malik badiiy til bobida o`ziga xos so`z san`atkori, novatordir. Iste`dodli yozuvchining “Shaytanat” asari o`zida bir qancha mavzularni qamrab olganligi (mafiya a`zolariga aylangan jinoyatchilar, yirik siyosiy o`yinlar, davlat huquq-tartibot idoralaridagi dastlabki tergov bilan bog`liq vaziyatlar) ni inobatga olgan holda biz asardagi asosiy qahramonlar, ya`ni mafiya a`zolariga aylangan jinoyatchilar nutqini sotsiolingvistik tadqiq etish masalasini yoritishga harakat qilamiz.

Jahon va o`zbek adabiyotida mafiya a`zolari hayot tarzidan hikoya qiluvchi qator asarlar yozilgan, jumladan, Mariyo Pyuzoning “Cho`qintirgan ota”, “Sitsiliyalik”, “Birinchi don”, “So`nggi don”, Roberto Savyannaning “Gomorra”, Garri Greyning “Bir kuni Amerikada”, Tohir Malikning “Shaytanat” kabi asarlari mafiyalar hayoti, ular yaratgan qonun-qoidalari, yashash tarzi haqida atroflicha ma`lumot beradi. Hatto Mariyo Pyuzoning “Cho`qintirgan ota” asariga ishlangan filmning butundunyo 250ta eng yaxshi filmlar ro`yxatining beshligiga kirgani va qariyb yarim asr o`z tomoshabopligini yo`qotmay kelayotganligining o`ziyoq mafiyalar hayotiga qiziqishning kuchli ekanligidan dalolat beradi. Ularning nutqi, o`zaro qo`llanuvchi maxsus jummalari va iboralari ham ko`pchilikni bee`tibor qoldirmay kelayotir. Mafiya a`zolari nutqining o`ziga xos xususiyatlarini o`rganish mikrosotsiologiya uchun muhim ma`lumotlar berishi bilan ahamiyatlidir.

НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И РАЗРАБОТКИ II

Avvalo, “mafiya” atamasi bir qancha ma‘no anglatishini quyidagi faktlardan ko‘rish mumkin: Sitsiliyacha “mafiusu” arabcha sleng “mahyas” so‘zidan olingan bo‘lib, “qat‘iy maqtanchoqlik” ma‘nosini berishi ayrim manbalarda ko‘rsatilgan bo‘lsa, ba‘zi manbalarda shu tildagi “marfud” so‘zidan olingan bo‘lib, “yaroqsiz, yaramas” degan ma‘nolarni anglatishi ko‘rsatilgan . Uning “xavfsizlik, himoya” ma‘nolarini beruvchi “mu‘afa” so‘zidan olinganligi to‘g‘risidagi qarashlar ham yo‘q emas.

Mashhur sotsiolog olim Diego Gambette tadqiqotlarini 17ga ko‘ra, XIX asrda Sitsiliyada “mafiya” atamasi ikki xil, ya‘ni, “jirkanch, mag‘rur” hamda “qo‘rqmas va tadbirkor” kabi ma‘nolarni anglatgan.

Tarixiy manbalar esa 1282-yili Italiyada fransuzlarga qarshi ko‘tarilgan qo‘zg‘olonning shioridagi bosh so‘zlari: —O‘lim Fransiyaga, Italiya, “nafas ol” (“Morte Alla Francia, Italia Anela”) ushbu atamaning vujudga kelishiga zamin yaratganligini ko‘rsatadi.

Mafiyalar hayotini yorituvchi shoh asar hisoblangan “Cho‘qintirgan ota” romanida esa mafiya so‘zi sitsiliyacha dialectda “boshpana” ma‘nosini anglatishi bayon etilgan.

Italiya – mafiya sardorlari yurti hisoblansa-da, ushbu jinoiy guruh faoliyatini boshqa bir qator mamlakatlarda (Meksika, Braziliya, Rossiya, ko‘plab Yevropa mamlakatlari) ham keng kurtak yozganini kuzatish mumkin. Xususan, O‘zbekistonda ham o‘tgan asrning oxirlarida mafiya va boshqa uyushgan jinoiy guruhlar faoliyati keng avj olgan edi. Taniqli yozuvchi Tohir Malikning biz tadqiq etayotgan “Shaytanat” romanlar to‘plamida aynan ushbu guruh a‘zolarining faoliyati, hayot tarzi, ayanchli taqdirlarini yoritilganligi millionlab kitobxonlarning diqqatini tortdi.

Mafiya a‘zolarining o‘tmishiga nazar solsak, ko‘pincha maktabni tashlagan, ota-onadan erta yetim qolgan, bolaligida kimdandir ozor yetgan va qalbida qasos olovi paydo bo‘lgan yoki hayotda adolatsizlikka uchragan yigitlar mafiya saroyiga kirib qolganini ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Aynan ushbu hayot tarzi

ularning adabiy til normalariga umuman e'tibor qilmasliklariga (adabiy til normalari haqida tushunchaga ega emasliklari ham ehtimoldan xoli emas), har qanday idora yoki jamoat joyida ham faqat so'zlashuv uslubidan foydalanishlariga zamin yaratgan. Nutq jarayonida adresantlarning dunyoqarashi, xarakter xususiyatlari, ijtimoiy-madaniy sa'viyasi, atrofdagilar bilan munosabati ro'yobga chiqadi. Bu guruh vakillarining nutqida ko'pincha varvarizmlar: rus tiliga oid bo'lgan: отдых — “Bugun oddix bo'lsa, shoshib qayoqqa ham borasiz” (I kitob, 51-b.); черный пояс — —Men o'zi... “чёрный поясман” (II kitob, 381-b.); шоколад — “Gap yo'q, shikalad.” (II kitob, 385-b.) брат — uka so'zining erkalanish-kichraytirish formasi “Kalla pishdimi, братишка?”; отвечать — javob bermoq “Lekin haddingizdan oshsangiz, otvechayt qilasiz.”; ba'zan esa inglizcha atamalar ham ko'zimiz tushishi mumkin: Boss- boshliq, ho'jayin “Bo'ssning gapi bor ekan, - dedi Shomil.”; no problem-muammo yo'q —Chuvrindi “Doktor Xudoyorning O'zbeksitonga kelishi uchun ruhsat olish masalasini hal etish mumkinmi?” deganda “No problem”, deb gapini “kalta qildi.” (III kitob, 518-b.). Ushbu misollardan ko'rinadiki, chetdan kirib kelgan so'zlarning talaffuzida ham mafiya a'zolari nutqida ba'zi buzilishlar, aksent (lotincha, “urg'u” ona tilidan boshqa tilda so'zlashgandagi o'zgalik xususiyatlari) 20da gapirish holatlari mavjud bo'ladi. Shuningdek, ushbu guruh a'zolari asosan yigitlarni tashkil etgani uchun ham ular nutqida ko'pincha vulgarizm (disfemistik ifoda)larni uchratishimiz mumkin: “Men seni erkak deb yursam, hebbim ekansan-ku, - dedi Kesakpolvon yigitga.” (I kitob, 349-b.); —Qon chiqmaydigan joyiga ur. Kaltakdan qo'rqadi u xunasa! (I kitob, 348-b.); —Хе, seni xudojo'y qilib tuqqanni...

Yuqorida ta'kidlanganidek, mafiya – yashirin guruh bo'lgani uchun ham ular orasida bir-birini nominativ vazifa bajaruvchi laqab va taxalluslar, maxsus sifatlar bilan atash odatiy holdir:

“Men Shilimshiqni jazolashim zarur edi.”

“Sen bu o‘yinda ikkita xatoga yo‘l qo‘yding. Birinchisi – akademikni “tuz” deb bilding.”

“Bo‘tqa, tushundingmi aytganimni qil. Otarchi kelmadimi?”

“O‘qilon g‘irromlik qilmaydi.”

“Bo‘ydoq olib keldi, kutib o‘tiribdi”.

Mafiya sardorlari nutqidagi og‘ir-bosiqlik, qisqa va lo‘ndalik, g‘azab otiga mingan paytda ko‘pincha so‘kinish, ba‘zan jahli chiqqanda ham past va bosiq ovozda, ba‘zan piching, kinoya yoki aybdor kimsani sizlab gapirish, ular qo‘l ostidagi kishilar nutqida esa kamgaplik, hissiyotlarga berilmagan holda beparvo so‘zlash (hatto o‘limga hukm etilganda ham) ushbu guruhga xos jihatdir.

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“Asadbek Chuvrindi bilan ko‘z urishtirib oldi. Nigohlarning bu uchrashuvi qanday ma‘no anglatishini uqqanday mehmon ostonada to‘xtab orqasiga o‘girildi-da: -Qardosh, orqamdan odam qo‘yishni o‘ylama. Biz ko‘pchilikmiz,-dedi.” (III k 718-b.) .

Mafiyalar – jinoiy uyushgan kishilar to‘plami va ularning faoliyati (korrupsiya, narkotik moddalar savdosi, qurol-yarog‘ savdosi) qonunga zid, shu sabab ham ularga qarshi doimo hukumat tomonidan kurash olib boriladi. Shunday bo‘lsa-da, mafiyalarning ildizini butunlay quritib yuborishning ya‘ni ular faoliyatiga butunlay chek qo‘yish dushvor. Mafiya – jamiyatda yashayotgan guruh ekan (garchi u jinoiy va yashirin bo‘lsa-da) bunday guruhga mansub kishilarning nutqini maxsus o‘rganish sotsiologiya fani uchun qimmatli

ma'lumotlar beradi. Til doimo inson hayoti, uning ijtimoiy faoliyati bilan bog'liqdir. Lisoniy belgining qanday ijtimoiy vazifa o'tashi, undan qanday foydalanishni bilishi uchun insonning qaysi ijtimoiy tuzumda yashashini ham e'tiborga olish bugungi kun tilshunosligining asosiy vazifalaridandir. Birgina "Shaytanat" asari yaratilgan davrni inobatga olsak, bugungi kunga kelib lisoniy hamjamiyatning taraqqiyoti natijasida ko'plab yangi atamalar, jumlar, maxsus kodlangan so'zlar vujudga kelganligi hamda nutqda keng qo'llanilayotgani tabiiy. Muayyan guruhlar, boshqa bir ijtimoiy qatlam uchun qo'llaniladigan sotsiolingvistik metodlar (kuzatish, anketa olish, intervyu olish)ni ushbu guruh uchun qo'llashning imkoni yo'qligi sababli, bu ishda adib va yozuvchilarimizning mafiyalar hayoti haqidagi asarlari bizga tadqiqot manbai bo'lib qolaveradi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, sotsiolingvistika haqida fikr yuritish qaysidir ma'noda til va jamiyat bilan bog'liq tushunchalarni nazariy jihatdan tekshirish va o'rganishni taqozo etadi. Bunda, shubhasiz, til va jamiyat o'rtasidagi turli xil munosabatlar uzviy mushtaraklik kasb etadi. Xulosa shuki, til va jamiyat o'rtasidagi ana shu aloqadorlik sotsiolingvistikani yaxlit tizimga ega bo'lgan fan sifatidagi imkoniyatlarini belgilaydi.

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**IMPORTANCE OF THE EFFECTIVE USE OF THE LAND IN A
DIGITAL ECONOMY**

ABSTRACT

It is well known that land is the primary foundation, an important factor in the development of industries. Its effective and rational use will become an important direction for ensuring stability in the economy of the republic in the future. However, practice shows that in recent years land use in economic sectors, including agriculture, households and dekhan farms, does not meet the conditions of a market economy and is inefficient. Today, it is important to conduct research on land privatization in order to eliminate this situation, fully form market relations in the economy, use the experience of foreign countries, improve existing forms and methods and adapt to our conditions.

Keywords: privatization, real estate, land market, land plot, land cadastre, market economy

The solution of a number of objective problems of society in the process of forming market relations determines the success of the reforms. At the same time, the reform of land ownership, based on the reform of land relations and the formation of the land market, is an important factor.

Large-scale reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan led to the formation and sale of land ownership, to a certain extent, the land market. The natural and climatic conditions of our republic, the ethnic, national and traditional customs of our people are also reflected in land-use relations. The problem is also relevant due to the scientific and methodological justification for the formation and organization of the land market at the national and regional levels and its

impact on the socio-economic conditions of the population. One of the obstacles to the effectiveness and development of land reform is the imperfection of competent decisions on land rights. A further increase in budget revenues, the creation of a unified system of government on the land market, and the development of rational methods of paying rent for the use of land will ensure the efficient use of land resources. Land valuation by state bodies is carried out mainly on agricultural land. However, information on the assessment of non-commercial land types is not enough, especially about the value of the land plots on which the property is located. From this point of view, the article is aimed at studying the general issues of liberalization and modernization of the economy, the formation and management of the land market, as well as the study of priority areas of land relations in Uzbekistan based on the concept of the formation of the land market.

The third area of the “Strategy of Action in Five Priority Directions for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017–2021”, developed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, is the reduction of state participation in the economy, protection of private property rights and its priority status. The issue of further strengthening is outlined. It provides for further expansion of the privatization of state property and simplification of its procedures.

The next step in the formation of the land market in accordance with international standards was the privatization of land. We believe that the use, assessment and legal protection of land as real estate is mandatory for land users. This will create the basis for more efficient use of land resources. This is because one of the principles of a market economy is the transition from general to particular. The privatization of the land and its ownership begins. Privatization of land leads to the rational and economical use of land resources. This is due to the fact that it has the same value as real estate, like buildings and structures, and allows you to sell, buy and exchange real estate with sale.

This is due to the development of multifunctional forms of ownership and use of land, which necessitates the development of land privatization processes. Privatization of land can only be successfully carried out through an in-depth study of factors and conditions affecting the value of plots, and the selection of optimal approaches and methods for conducting an objective assessment of the land.

Factors and conditions affecting the value of privatized land can be divided into general (general) and specific (private) types. The specific factors and conditions affecting the value of privatized land are determined by the nature of the land plots involved in this process, their actual use, property relations and legal relationship with real estate located on these land plots.

Graph 1. Description of land involved in the privatization process

In accordance with the current legislation of the Republic, the land plots shown in graph 1 may be involved in the privatization process.

The study and analysis of available scientific resources indicate that currently the privatization of land in the republic is as follows:

- expansion of various forms of ownership of land resources;
- expansion of private ownership of real estate and land (as a single property complex);
- privatization of land privatization procedures.

The determination of market value plays an important role in the privatization of land. Studying the experience of the countries of the world and their use in the development of land reforms in the country will create the basis for effective land use. As a result of studying the experience of Europe, Asia, the USA and the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), we single out the following areas that can be applied in the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- ensuring strict compliance with laws and regulations in the implementation of the land market in the implementation of land policy;
- further strengthening the legal protection of agricultural land in order to determine the priority of agricultural production;
- Strengthen the scientific, methodological and economic justification in order to prevent "disintegration" or increase the minimum or maximum area of land by specialization;
- the introduction of tenders on the basis of the rational development of property criteria for the purposeful, rational and efficient use of land;
- severe restrictions on the terms of the lease, resale and collateral;
- financial support of owners and heirs;
- achieve a certain degree of regulation of capital flows in this area, using transparent market principles, such as transparency and transparency in pricing and trade;
- the introduction of a differentiated land tax taking into account regional characteristics of pricing.

It should be remembered that land privatization should be considered as one of the key ways to improve land use efficiency, and not the development of the land market. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev № 5623 "On measures to radically improve the processes of urbanization" of January 10, 2019 is of great practical importance. The main purpose of the Decree is to regulate the processes of urbanization, bringing the population into line with the existing infrastructure, housing, jobs. On the other hand, land privatization is aimed at owning people, that is, citizens and organizations acquire several times more valuable property at market prices, while the land that they own or use is acquired from the state at par value. As a result of the fact that the privatized land will enter into civil circulation, its value will continue to grow. As a result, the economic situation of citizens will continue to improve as the value of their property increases. The ultimate goal of introducing private ownership of land is to guarantee full ownership. To date, the building of a residential building or service facility built on a land plot is the private property of a citizen or organization, and the land is state property. This situation did not allow them to become economically strong, develop existing facilities, and make additional investments here. As soon as the land is now completely owned by a citizen or organization, both the land and the building above it will become completely untouchable. This is the most important guarantee for investors. By privatizing land, they can increase their value as property, forcing land to be considered the capital, and not a specific area.

Further improvement of the land use system in the transition to a market economy is very important for the national economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The modern land use system should be regulated by the government taking into account the needs of the state and land users working with land. According to the same principle, it is necessary to form a system of the state

mechanism for managing land resources, coordinating land relations and land reclamation for economic purposes.

As a result of the study, the following scientific conclusions and practical recommendations for improving the legal and economic base of land use were obtained:

1. The state land cadastre, state control over the use and protection of land, land management mechanisms, land monitoring should be constantly improved as a single system of government decision-making. It is advisable that the law, as a rule, make decisions on public administration decisions at the national and regional levels on the basis of prospective and annual land use documentation.

2. The completion of the general registration of land plots within the established administrative-territorial boundaries should be completed and based on the main registration of land plots, with appropriate changes to the land cadastral documentation and the preparation of separate cadastral documentation for each plot.

3. Work on the definition (clarification) of the administrative boundaries of the district, district, household and settlements (city, town) should be included in the land management work, ensuring the maintenance of the state land cadastre.

4. Do not delay the organization and conduct of registration activities in rural areas to generate accurate information of the land cadastre. To date, such information is not complete in the system of state land cadastre.

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**LIDERLIK MAHORATINI TARBİYALASHNING PEDAGOGIK
JIHATLARI**

ABSTRAKT

Mazkur maqolada umumta'lim muassasalarida liderlik xususiyatlarini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari bugungi bugungi globallashuv talablarini inobatga olgan holda bayon etilgan. Ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida boshliqlarning liderlik qobiliyatning tutgan o'rni haqida so'z yuritilgan. Shuningdek maqolada rahbar va liderlik o'zaro farqli jihatlari tahlil qilingan.

***Kalit so'zlar:** Lider, liderlik, rahbar, xarizma, ta'lim-tarbiya, qobiliyat, boshqaruv.*

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**PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF EDUCATION OF LEADERSHIP
SKILLS**

ABSTRACT

In this article, the priority directions for the development of leadership qualities in educational institutions are described, taking into account the requirements of today's globalization. The role of leaders in the process of education and training was discussed. The article also analyzes the different aspects of leader and leadership.

Key words: Leader, leadership, charisma, education, ability, management.

KIRISH

Jahondagi globallashuv va ta'limning integratsiyalashuvi jarayonlarida ta'lim muassasasi rahbarlarining boshqaruv faoliyatida ijodiy yondashuv, zamonaviy bilim, ko'nikma, malakalari va kasbiy-ijtimoiy tayyorgarligini rivojlantirishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Bugungi kunda ta'limga liderlik yondashuv asosida rahbarlarning raqobatbardoshligini oshirish, ularda ijodiy muhitni shakllantirish, kasbiy faoliyat sohalariga sog'lom muhitni yaratish orqali kreativlik qobiliyatlarini

rivojlantirish, shuningdek, ta'lim sifatini ta'minlash va samaradorlikga erishish masalalari dolzarb yo'nalishlardan biri sifatida tadqiq etilmoqda. Ana shu nuqtai-nazardan ilg'or xorijiy tajribalar asosida boshqaruv faoliyatini modernizatsiyalash, rahbarlarning kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorgarlik holatlarini o'rganish, ijodiy ko'nikma va malakalarini shakllantirish, boshqaruv faoliyatida sog'lom va ijodiy muhitni yaratish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirishni taqozo etadi.

O'zbekistonda uchinchi Renesans poydevorini barpo etishdek ulug' maqsad qo'yilgan ekan, ta'lim menejmenti yo'nalishida rahbar kadrlar tayyorlashning sifat darajasini oshirish, hamda boshqaruv faoliyatiga bo'lgan talabni qamrab olish darajasini kuchaytirish bilan birga zamonaviy raqobatbardosh rahbarlarni tayyorlashga qaratilgan. Tub islohotlar jamiyatning maktab ta'limiga bo'lgan talabini qamrab olish darajasini ko'p jihatdan "Xalq ta'limi tizimini boshqarishning samarali mexanizmlarini joriy etish" kabi vazifalar belgilandi [1].

Ma'lumki, har qanday guruh, tashkilot, jamoada, bo'linmada tan olingan obro'-e'tiborga ega bo'lgan shaxs mavjud bo'lib, u mazkur tashkilotning faoliyatiga bevosita ta'sir o'tkazadi, bu o'zini boshqaruv harakatlari sifatida namoyon qiladi. Buni Amir Temurning "Azmi qat'iy, tadbirkor, hushyor, mard va shijoatli bir kishi mingta tadbirsiz va loqayd kishidan afzaldir", degan fikri ham tasdiqlaydi. Bugungi kunda biz bunday shaxslarni liderlar deb ataymiz.

Lider so'zi inglizcha "leader" - yetakchi, boshliq, rahbar biror siyosiy partiya yoki tashkilotning rahbari, yo'l boshchisi ma'nolarini anglatadi [5].

Bir qarashda liderlik rahbarlik kabi ko'rinishi mumkin. Qisman to'g'ri, ammo ularning o'zaro farqli jihatlari mavjud.

Birinchidan, lider har doim parda ortida va o'z-o'zidan aniqlanadi, rahbar esa rasmiy ravishda tayinlanadi.

Ikkinchidan, rahbar u bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lgan ma'lum bir guruh vakili bo'lib, yetakchi, aksariyat hollarda, guruhdan ajraladi.

Uchinchidan, liderning asosiy sohasi - bu shaxslararo munosabatlar, rahbar esa rasmiy munosabatlardir. Ammo rahbarning ixtiyorida juda ko'p tashqi ma'lumotlar mavjud, qonuniy sanksiyalarni qo'llash mumkin, ya'ni u rasmiy shaxs. Ilmiy tilda guruhga kuchli va ta'sirchan ta'sir ko'rsatadigan rasmiy rahbar, ya'ni uning ta'siri pozitsiyaga bog'liq bo'lsa, "bo'ysunuvchilar" ga ta'sir qiladi.

Ushbu masalalar siyosiy darajagacha ko'tarilib 2019 yil 24 apreldagi PF-5712-son "O'zbekiston Respublikasi Xalq ta'limi tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida" farmonida ham o'z aksini topgan.

ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

Rahbarlarda boshqaruv qobiliyatlarni takomillashtirishga yo'naltirilgan bilan bog'liq tadqiqotlar jahonning yetakchi ilmiy markazlari va ta'lim muassasalari, jumladan, Xalqaro mehnat tashkiloti (ILO, Shveysariya), Braziliya universiteti (Universidade de Brasília, Braziliya), Jon Kennadi boshqaruv instituti (John F. Kennedy School of Government, AQSh), Ural Federal universiteti (Rossiya Federatsiyasi), Davlat boshqaruv universiteti (Rossiya Federatsiyasi), "Saville Assessment" kompaniyasi (Buyuk Britaniya), A.Avloniy nomidagi pedagoglarni kasbiy rivojlantirish va yangi metodikalarga o'rgatish milliy tadqiqot instituti(O'zbekiston)da olib borilgan [7].

Mamlakatimizda boshqaruv tizimi, ta'lim tizimida innovatsion, strategik, funksional menejmentni shakllantirish masalalari R.Djuraev, J.Yo'ldoshev, U.Inoyatov, S.Turg'unov, M.Yuldashev, O.Xayitov, Ya.Ismadiyarov, A.Magrupov, N.Muxamedova, M.Saidov, M.Mirsolievalar; nosog'lom muhitni keltirib chiqaruvchi pedagogik ziddiyatlarni kelib chiqish sabablari va ularni bartaraf etish bo'yicha M.Axmedova, M.Davletshin, G'.Shoumarov, S.Jalilova, X.Ibragimov, V.Karimova, D.Narziqulova, Z.Nishonova, E.G'oziev, R.Samarov, A.Xoliqov, N.Safaev, G.To'ychieva, N.Shermuxammedova, Sh.Mo'minov, B.Qodirov, R.Sunnatova tomonidan o'rganilgan [3, 4].

METODOLOGIYA

Tadqiqotda o'quv-metodik, ilmiy adabiyotlarni o'rganish va tahlil qilish, suhbat, pedagogik kuzatuv, test, cavol-javob, intervyu, pedagogik tajriba-cinov, matematik-ctatictik tahlil usullardan foydalanilgan.

Umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasasi rahbarining samarali boshqaruv faoliyatini shakllantirish tuzilmasi sog'lom va ijodiy muhitni yaratish algoritmini jamoada turli toifadagi xodimlar bilan ishlashga doir ichki va tashqi ijtimoiy jarayonlarning ijtimoiy-pedagogik funksiyalari empirik darajasi bo'yicha amaliy g'oyalar ta'sirchanligiga hamda barqaror taraqqiyotga moyilligini aniqlashtirish asosida takomillashtirish ko'zda tutilgan.

TADQIQOT NATIJASI

Umumta'lim muassasalari rahbarlaridagi liderlik qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish negizida quyidagi shaxsiyatga aloqador qobiliyatlar shakllantirish maqsadga muvofiqdir:

- insonparvarlik tamoyili - rahbarlarning ijtimoiy faolligi, ma'naviy barkamolligi, shaxsiy erkinligi, axloqiy fazilatlari, kreativlik va ijodkorlikni qo'llab-quvvatlashni bildiradi;

- demokratlashtirish tamoyili - boshqaruvning asosiy vazifalarini hal etishda mustaqillikni rivojlantirish, hamkorlik va sherikchilikning turli shakllarini takomillashtirish, innovatsion faoliyat ishtirokchilari orasida ishonchni tarkib toptirishni bildiradi;

- individuallashtirish tamoyili - rahbarlarni o'z-o'zini anglashga, o'zo'zini boshqarishga, o'z-o'zini nazorat qilishga, o'z-o'zini yo'naltirishni bildiradi;

- rahbarlarni innovatsion faoliyatga yo'naltiruvchi va yuksaltiruvchi tamoyil-innovatsion ta'lim sharoitida jamiyat ehtiyojlariga rahbarning boshqaruvchanligining mos kelishini bildiradi;

- innovatsion tamoyil - rahbarning yangilikka intilishi, ta'limning zamonaviy tendensiyalaridan xabardor bo'lishi va jamoa boshqaruvida yangiliklarni qo'llashini bildiradi;

XULOSA

Umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasasi rahbari amaldagi umumiy o'rta ta'lim sohasidagi tartibga soluvchi normativ-huquqiy hujjatlarni; maktab faoliyati va uni rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy asoslarini, jamoani boshqarishning samarali usullarini; o'quv va tarbiya sifati, davlat ta'lim standartlari talablarini joriy qilish natijalari bilan bog'liq holda xodimlarni ma'naviy va moddiy rag'batlantirish tizimlari va metodlarini; kadrlarni tanlash va joy-joyiga qo'yish usullari, ularning malakasini oshirish va qayta tayyorlash tartibini; ta'lim muassasasi va o'qituvchilar faoliyatini tahlil qila olishni, ta'lim muassasasi faoliyatidagi muammolarni aniqlash va ularni hal qilishning samarali yo'llarini topishni; maktabni rivojlantirish dasturini ishlab chiqish, ta'lim muassasasini boshqarishning tashkiliy tarkibini tuzish, shartnomalar tuzishni; pedagogik jamoada qulay psixologik muhit yaratishni bilishi lozim.

Xulosa qilib aytganda ta'lim muassasalari rahbarlarining liderlik xususiyatlarini rivojlantirish uchun bugunda kunda mamlakatimizda barcha sharoitlar yaratilgan. Buni O'zbekiston Respublikasi "Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to'g'risida"gi qonuni, "Ta'lim to'g'risida"gi qonunlarda o'z aksini topganligida ko'rishimiz mumkin. Ushbu normalarni amaliyotga tatbiq etish yoshlarda liderlik xususiyatlarini namoyon bo'lishida muhim rol o'ynaydi [2].

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**CHOR HUKUMATINING XIVAGA UYUSHTIRGAN 1839 YILDAGI
QISHKI HARAKATI**

Annotatsiya: XIX asr, Rossiyaning Markaziy Osiyoga nisbatan siyosati tobora kuchayib bormoqda. Rossiyaning mintaqadagi faollashishi Orenburg harbiy gubernatori V. A. Perovskiy faoliyati bilan bevosita bog'liq edi. 1834 yilda uning farmoniga binoan nihoyat Kaspida yangi Aleksandrovskiy qal'asi qurildi. Biroq, bu qal'ani qurilishi Xiva muammosini hal qilmadi. Xivaliklar savdo karvonlarini talon - taroj qilishlari va rus qozoqlarini doimiy talashlari davom etdi. Har yili Xivaga Rossiya fuqarolaridan 200 ga yaqin asir o'g'irlangan. Perovskiy yurishi hukumat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanib, Xivaga qarshi harbiy yurishga tayyorgarlik ko'rishni boshladi. Harbiy gubernatorga xonlik poytaxtini olish, uning hukmdorini Rossiya uchun foydali shartnoma imzolashga majbur qilish va Rus asirlarini hammasini ozod qilish buyurildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sankt-Peterburg, -Xivaliklar, Orol dengizi, Nikolay I, A. I. Chernyshev, Angliya hukumati.

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**THE TSARIST GOVERNMENT'S WINTER MOVEMENT OF 1839
IN KHIVA**

Abstract: In the 19th century, Russia's policy towards Central Asia is getting stronger. The activation of Russia in the region was directly related to the activities of the military governor of Orenburg, V. A. Perovsky. In 1834, according to his decree, a new Alexandrovsky fortress was finally built on the Caspian. However, the construction of this fortress did not solve the problem of Khiva. The Khiva people continued to rob trade caravans and constantly rob Russian Kazakhs. Every year, about 200 prisoners of Russian citizens were stolen from Khiva. The Perovsky campaign, supported by the government, began to prepare for a military campaign against Khiva. The military governor was ordered to take the capital of the khanate, force its ruler to sign a treaty beneficial to Russia, and release all Russian prisoners.

Key words: St. Petersburg, Khiva people, Aral Sea, Nicholas I, A. I. Chernyshev, British government.

1839 yil mart oyida Sankt-Peterburgda Osiyo departamentining maxsus qo'mitasi yig'ilishi ishtirokchilari 44-harbiy yurishning asosiy maqsadlarini aniqladilar :

-Xivaliklarning Rossiya imperiyasi tasarrufidagi hududlarga hujumlarini to'xtatish,

- Xiva xonligida rus asirlarini ozod qilish.

-xavfsiz savdoni ta'minlash va Orol dengizini o'rganish.

Ekspiditsiya omadli kelgan taqdirda ya'ni shahar egallansa Xiva xonini ag'darish va uning o'rnini ishonchli xon bilan almashtirish, tartibni o'zgartirib uni mustahkamlash, barcha mahbuslarni ozod qilib va savdo-sotiq qilishga to'liq erkinlik berish kabi topshiriqlar yuklatilgandi.¹[1] Nikolay I va harbiy vazir A. I. Chernyshev "Rossiyaning Markaziy Osiyodagi ta'sirini kuchaytirish va mustahkamlash, shuningdek, xivaliklarning uzoq vaqtdan beri jazosiz qolishini va ayniqsa, Angliya hukumati bizning sanoatimiz va savdo-sotiqqa zarar etkazadigan harakatini toxtatish" talabi bilan kampaniya memorandumini qo'llab-quvvatladilar. Bu sohalarda o'z ustunligini tarqatishga intilgan" ²[2]

Zamonaviy britaniyalik tarixchi A. Morrisonning fikricha, Rossiya "Xiva tomonidan savdogar karvonlariga hujumlar natijasida yuzaga kelgan jiddiy shaxsiy shikoyatlarga murojaat qilish sabab bo'layotgandi".

Rossiya fuqaroligidagi ko'chmanchi xalqlar va xatto A. Bekovich-Cherkasskiy ekspeditsiyasini xoinlik bilan yo'q qilish uchun harakat qilganlar bor edi. Biroq, bu harbiy yurishni qonuniyligini aniqlagan mahbuslar edi. Rossiya buyuk davlatning raqobatbardosh maqomini saqlab qolishga majbur bo'ldi va Xiva o'z hokimiyatiga zarar etkazishiga yo'l qo'yolmadi, Buyuk Britaniya esa Afg'onistondagi ta'sirini kuchaytirmoqchi edi"³[3]

¹ Захарьин И.Н. Граф В. А. Перовский и его зимний поход в Хиву. СПб., 1901. С. 90.

² Morrison A.S. Twin Imperial disasters. The invasions of Khiva and Afghanistan in the Russian and British official mind, 1839–1842 // *Modern Asian Studies*. 2014. Vol. 48. № 1. P. 277.

³ Morrison A. S. Twin Imperial disasters. The invasions of Khiva and Afghanistan in the Russian and British official mind, 1839–1842. P. 253–300.

Dastlab, harbiy harakat 1839 yil bahorida rejalashtirilgan edi, ammo ular buni Xon Do'st-Muhammadga qarshi ingliz missiyasi tugaguniga qadar kechiktirishga qaror qilishdi. "Markaziy Osiyodagi harakatlarimizning ta'siri yoki taassurotlari og'irroq bo'lishi uchun va Angliya o'z g'alabalari bilan hukumatni bezovta qilish huquqidan mahrum qilishi uchun turli xil tushuntirishlar talabi bilan chiqishgan. Ammo har qanday holatda ham kampaniyani keyinga qoldirmaslik kerak edi. Qishki yurishning qo'shimcha sabablari "Xitoyni zabt etish uchun 200 ming armiya bilan qorda Gobi dashtidan o'tgan Chingizxonning tarixiy misollari (1211) va har doim qishda Sibir yoki Uralga bostirib kirishni boshlagan Amir Temur, shuningdek Ushatoy va Kurbskiy gubernatorlarining qishki yurishi misol bo'la o'ladi. Berg ekspeditsiyasi va Vaterloo jangida qatnashgan Vellington dukosi kengashi ham qish foydasiga harakat qildi, u qorni ichimlik suvi sifatida ishlatish imkoniyati tufayli qishda yurish qulayligini ko'rsatdi. A. Bekovich-Cherkasskoga 50% yozgi kampaniyasining muvaffaqiyatsiz otadi deb o'yladi.

1839 yil 14-noyabrda imperatorning Deklaratsiyasi chiqdi, unda Xivaga qarshi harbiy ekspeditsiya o'tkazishga sabab bo'lgan sabablar bayon qilindi: "ushbu ekspeditsiyaning maqsadi qurol kuchi bilan Xivaliklarni Rossiyaning adolatli talablarini bajarishga majbur qilish edi."

Xivani zabt etishning yana bir sababi Xivada yashovchi rus qullarini ozod qilish, imperiya chegaralari yaqinida sodir bo'lgan talonchilik va zo'ravonlikni to'xtatish va kelajakda Rossiya fuqarolarining foyda huquqlarini ta'minlash uchun hukumatlar yaratishdan iborat edi.⁴[4]

24 noyabr kuni Orenburgning asosiy maydonida askarlarga imperatorning buyrug'i e'lon qilindi. Unga kora Orenburg gubernatori V. A. Perovskiy qo'mondon etib tayinlandi, uning rahbarligida Ural va Orenburg kosak qo'shinlari, Rossiya muntazam armiyasining 1-Orenburg polki, boshqor-

⁴ Мирза Абд ал-Азиз Сами. Тарих-и салатин-и мангитийа (История мангытских государей) / Мирза Абд ал-Азиз Сами ; пер., введ. и примеч. Л. М. Епифанцевой. М., 1962. 445 с.

meshcheryak qo'shini va artilleriya qismlari 5 bo'lgan.[5]⁵ Shahardan to'rtta kolonna chiqardi, ulardan birinchisini General-leytenant Tolmachev, ikkinchisini polkovnik Kuzminskiy, uchinchisini polkovnik Mansurov, to'rtinchisini va butun kavaleriyani general – mayor Tsiolkovskiy boshqargan. Har bir ustunga buyurtma va ta'minot sarfini nazorat qiluvchi navbatchi tayinlangan. Chiqish paytida ob-havo qo'rqinchli emas edi, lekin kechasi harorat 22 darajadan pastga tushdi.

Manbalarga ko'ra, "yurishga tayyorgarlik to'g'ri olib borilgan, qurol va o'q-dorilardan tashqari, qo'shinlarning hayotiga katta e'tibor berilgan, sotib olingan: kibitkalar va jun gilamlar, odamlarni parazitlardan himoya qilish uchun, sovun, tamaki, ko'mir va ponton vagonlari, jabduqlar, asbob bilan egarlar, suv olish uchun temir chelaklar (va uni qazib olish uchun(agar kerak bo'lsa), chuqur quduqlardan maxsus snaryad ixtiro qilingan), yog'och chelaklar, mixlar, ko'zoynaklar, arqonlar, qayin yog'ochlari va hammom uchun taxtalar, chiroqlar va boshqalar yetarlicha tayyorlangan.[6]⁶ Xodimlarning kiyim-kechaklariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan"yarim paltolar, ya'ni yosh qo'zichoq junidan qilingan. Pastki shimlar ham qirg'iz junidan va mahkam tikilgan; qalin va qora matodan tikilgan shimlar.

Bu vaqtda siyosiy vaziyat birmuncha o'zgarib bormoqda edi.1839 yil 2 avgustda Kobuldan qochgan afg'on xoni Do'st-Muhammad rus qo'shinlari yordamida yo'qolgan pozitsiyalarini tiklashga harakat qiladi. 1839 yil dekabr oyida Xivaga ingliz razvedkasi agenti D. Abbott jo'nab ketadi, Shuning uchun Rossiyada Buyuk Britaniya Xivaga yordam bermoqchi degan xavotirlar paydo bo'ldi. Asosiy savol Xivaga kim tezroq etib borishi edi-inglizlar yoki ruslar, shuning uchun ikkala tomon ham shoshilishdi.⁷[7]

⁵ Косырев Е. М. Поход в Хиву в 1839 г. (Из записок участника) // Ист. вестник. 1898. № 8.С. 538–545.

⁶ Иванин М. И. Описание Зимнего похода в Хиву в 1839–1840 году. С. 143.

⁷ Путешествие в Туркмению и Хиву в 1819 и 1820 годах, гвардейского Генерального Штаба капитана Николая Муравьева, посланного в сии страны для переговоров. М., 1822. 182 с.

Biroq, Xiva kampaniyasining birinchi haftalaridan boshlab qiyinchiliklar paydo bo'ldi. Askarlarning kiyimlari noqulay bo'lib chiqdi, qo'y junini issiq edi, lekin tezda bu kiyimlar noqulay ekani aniqlandi. Paltolar yarim paltolarga sig'madi, Haram shimlari etiklarning tor millariga sig'madi va paypoq va oyoq kiyimlari oyoqlarga kerakli issiqlikni bermadi. To'liq kiyim-kechak va to'liq tartib bilan o'tgandan so'ng, askarlar tunashga joylasha olmadilar. Harbiy harakat ishtirokchilarining o'zaro guvohliklariga ko'ra, ekspeditsiya sharoitida "faqat shlyapalar yaxshi ish bergan edi"⁸[8]

Ustyurt cho'li va platosi deyarli o'rganilmagan, Xivaga yo'l joyida qurilgan. Harbiy navigatsiya Emba daryosi va Amudaryo daryosigacha cho'lda katta suv to'siqlari yo'qligi haqidagi kam ma'lumotlar bilan qanoatlantirildi. Shu bilan birga, Moskvada Xivaga bag'ishlangan kitob nashr etildi: "Xiva nima? Biz u haqida deyarli bilmaymiz. Xiva butun Osiyo yo'llari chorrahasida turadi; undan to'g'ridan-to'g'ri Sharqiy Hindistonga, chapga Xitoyga, o'ngga Forsga yo'l bor edi. Butun Sharqiy va Janubiy Osiyodan Rossiyaga boradigan karvonlar Xiva orqali yoki uning yaqinida, shu sababli ushbu hududdan qat'iy ravishda o'tishlari kerak edi.

Agar ingliz hukumati Xiva bilan munosabatlarni yaxshilasa Angliya Ost-Indiya kompaniyasi Hindistonda u tomonidan bosib olingan yuz o'ttiz million odam bilan qanoatlanib, butun Sharqiy Osiyoga o'z ta'sirini kengaytirishi mumkin edi.

Polkovnik Bergning noto'g'ri xulosalari ham kampaniya uchun halokatli rol o'ynadi. Uning maslahatiga ko'ra, kuzda Xivaga boradigan yo'lning yarmida zaxiralarni saqlash, otlar va tuyalarni dam olish va Ustyurtda qor suvi bo'lishi uchun birinchi qorni kutish kerak deb hisoblar edi. U Donguz-Tau traktida chorva mollari uchun zararli o'tlar bilan qoplangan botqoq sho'r suvdan iborat zaxiralarni saqlash joyini muvaffaqiyatsiz taklif qildi. [9]⁹Yurish paytida

⁸ Терентьев М. Хивинские походы русской армии. С. 11.

⁹ Гродеков Н. И. Хивинский поход 1873 года. Действия кавказских отрядов. Издание редакции

Donguz-Tau traktini oldindan tekshirishmagan, bu ekspeditsiyaning yana bir noto'g'ri hisob - kitob qilingani uchun askarlar juda qiynalgan . V.A.Perovskiy Sirdaryoga kelib o'rnashishni, bu erda rus koloniyasini tashkil etishni va keyin G'arbiy sohil bo'ylab emas, balki Orol dengizining Sharqiy qirg'og'i bo'ylab harakatlanishni taklif qildi. 1836 yilda Perovskiy bosh shtabning ikki ofitseriga (Ivanina va Nikiforovga) Sirdaryo daryosining quyi oqimida 1000 kishiga mo'ljallangan koloniya bilan mustahkamlanish loyihasini tuzishni topshirgan edi. Ammo tez orada Perovskiyning rejalari eski Berg loyihasi foydasiga o'zgardi . Orol dengizining Sharqiy tomoni bo'ylab yo'l 1400 kilometr, g'arbiy tomoni orqali 1320 kilometr masofani nazarda tutgan. Berg ikkinchi yo'lni yanada qulayroq deb tavsiya qildi: unda qalalar qurish uchun ikkita nuqta belgilangan edi: birinchisi, Embacaryosiga quyiladigan joyda edi

Yakshi va Oq-buloqning ikkinchisi-ikkalasi ham oziq-ovqat va sho'r suv yo'qligi sababli juda noqulay bo'lib qolgandi. General Perovskiy ikkinchi yo'lni tanladi.

Asosiy to'siq qishki dashtning eng og'ir ob-havo sharoiti, qor qoplami, hayvonlarning o'tish qobiliyatining cheklanganligi va yonuvchan materiallarning yo'qligi edi. Rus askarlari o'zlarning qurol yaroqlarining ustunligiga ishongan holda hushyorlikni yo'qotishdi. Lekin vaziyatni noqulayligi ko'p jihatdan pand beradi. Bundan tashqari inglizlarning ham aynan shu yili yo'lga chiqanligi vaziyatni yanada qiyinlashtirdi. Shunisi e'tiborga loyiqlik, asosiy kuchlar Orenburgdan chiqib ketishidan bir necha hafta oldin podpolkovnik Danilevskiy (1842 yilda Xivadagi elchixonada boshlig'i bo'lgan) boshchiligida avangard (362 kishi, shu jumladan 5 ofitser, 4 qurol, 1128 tuya) bilan qor yo'qligi sababli Emba daryosigacha nisbatan bezarar yetib kelgan.

Harbiy harakatning Bosh shtab ofitseri M. I. Ivanin shunday yozgan edi: "Yurishda, ya'ni ot minishda, issiq kiyinish mumkin emas edi yurishga xalaqit

qilar edi, shuning uchun yuqa kiyingi bo'lishimiz kerak edi. Sovuq bo'lardi. kechasi, odatda sovuq kuchayganida biz namatni o'ranib yotardik. namat bilan qoplangan muzlatilgan yerda kigiz kubit ostida uxlar edik. Garchi qo'y terisini o'rab olgan bo'lsak ham, kunduzi kabi sovuq emas edi; odatda biz uyqu paytida oyoq va burun muzlamasligi uchun boshdan-oyoq yopilar edik, lekin tun davomida nafas olganligimiz uchun sochlarimiz va mo'ylovlariga qadar muzlab qolar edi, shuning uchun birinchi g'amxo'rlik o'rnidan turib, bosh va mo'ylovda hosil bo'lgan muzni eritib, qo'y terisiga muzlab yopishib qolgan sochlarni ajratish kerak edi"¹⁰[10]

Ekspeditsiyaning yana bir ishtirokchisi, harbiy shifokor va bo'lajak buyuk rus olimi V. I. oilasi va do'stlariga optimistik ruhda ozgan xatida shunday degan edi: "biz sovuqdan qo'rqmaymiz; biz buni maqtanish uchun emas, balki tajribadan aytamiz; faqat bizga qarang va biz maqtanmasligimizga ishonch hosil qilasiz. Choyshab, tuya junida, kurtkalar va har xil turdagi liboslar, yosh qullarning terisidan tikilgan yuqori ko'ylak yoki kiyik terisidan palto, echki terisidan paxmoq qo'lqoplari va paypoqlari, hamma narsa zaxiralagan va faqat badbaxt qish bizni qayerdan qanday zaxira bilan kelganimizni bilmayapti degan edi. Ammo keyingi xatlarida u yarador va kasallarni borligini, sharoit og'irligi haqida xabar bergan, bu esa ekspeditsiyaning ancha qimmatga tushayotganidan dalolat bergan. Zaxirinning ta'kidlashicha askarlar "kasalxonaga" yuborilardi va u erdan uch kundan keyin qabrga olib ketilar edilar. Lager kasalxonalari Embaga boradigan yo'l bo'ylab otryad qorsiz dasht bo'ylab yuradi degan taxmin bilan tashkil etilgan uzun vagonlarda, g'ildiraklarda joylashtirilgan bo'lgan. Ushbu vagonlar shu qadar sovuq ediki, ular hatto sog'lom askarlarni ham kasal qilardi, ular faqat charchagan oyoqlariga dam berish kasalxonaga "dam olish uchun" borardilar ammo ikki-uch kundan keyin bunday askarlar shamollab, tifoz isitmasini ushlab, halok bo'lishardi. Qo'riqchilik xizmatida turgan askarlar turgan joyida muzlab qolardi. Bir kuni boshliqlaridan biri postlarnng birida

¹⁰ Иванин М. И. Описание Зимнего похода в Хиву в 1839–1840 году. С. 143.

qo'lida qurol ushlab turgan yarim yotgan askarni ko'radi. U uning oldiga boradi va baland ovoz bilan baqirib, bo'yniga uradi. Askar qorga yiqilib, harakatsiz yotdi. Ma'lum bo'lishicha, u allaqachon muzlatilgan jasad bo'lgan. Shu va shu kabi voqealar Xivaga uyushtirilgan harbiy harat notog'rib o'lganidan dalolat beradi. Vaqt o'tishi bilan gavjum boshlanib shifoxonalar tuyalarning yon tomonlariga osilgan ko'rpa-to'shaklar bilan almashtirildi.

Shunday qilib, Rossiya imperiyasining armiyasining dasht bo'ylab qishki harbiy yurishga tayyor emasligi uning muvaffaqiyatsizligiga olib keldi. Missiyaning muvaffaqiyatsiz bo'lishining sabablari M. I. Ivanin noto'g'ri kiyim, oziq-ovqatning kamligi, sovuqlik va natijada kasallik, dashtning qish sharoitlariga tayyor emasligi (chang'i, chananing yo'qligi), qiyinchiliklar isbotlab berdi.

Bundan tashqari, ishtirokchilar o'z xotiralarida qo'mondonlik tarkibining askarlarga nisbatan e'tiborsizligini, shuningdek, ustunlar boshliqlari o'rtasidagi raqobatbardosh va professional bo'lmagan munosabatlarni qayd etishgan. Masalan, V. A. Perovskiy "o'zini boshliqlariga nisbatan juda g'ayritabiiy munosabatlarga qo'ydi bo'lgani aytiladi"¹¹[11]

Urush paytida armiya duch kelgan barcha qiyinchiliklarga qo'shimcha ravishda, cho'lda xivaliklar bilan doimiy ravishda harbiy to'qnashuvlar bo'lib turardi. "Xivaliklar to'dasi tunda kolonnaga, ya'ni mayor Simbuxinga odamlarning qayg'uli ahvolidan foydalanib keladi omon qolgan tuyalar podasini qaytarib olib, ularni leytenant Yerofeyev kolonnasidan ajratib, dashtga haydab yuborishardi"

1839 yil 30 dekabrda Oq - buloq qal'asi yonida og'ir jang bo'lib o'tadi. Urush qatnashchisi E. M. Kosyrevning ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, 3 000 kishidan iborat Xiva kavaleriyasi janubi-g'arbdan yaqinlashib, 399 kishi, ulardan 164 nafari kasal bo'lgan rus askarlariga hujumga o'tadi. Birinchi hujum muvaffaqiyatsiz bo'ldi, chunki rus qo'shinlari artilleriyada ustunlikka ega edilar.

¹¹ Захарьин И. Н. Граф В. А. Перовский и его зимний поход в Хиву. С. 97.

Ko'p o'tmay, xivaliklar yana bir nechta Oq - buloq qal'asi g'arbida tomonida otlar va tuyalar uchun tayyorlangan pichanni yoqishga harakat qilishadi. Qo'shinlar bu urinishni to'xtatdi va xivaliklar sharqdan istehkomga hujum qilishadi. Yangi qurollar qo'llanilgandan so'ng Xiva qo'shinlari orqaga chekinishdi. Bu vaqtda Oq - Buloqqa rus armiyasining asosiy qismlari yaqinlashayotgan edi, ularga qarshi xivaliklar oldinga siljishdi.

Oq-buloqdan 20 kilometr uzoqlikda rus qo'shinlari yarim doira shaklida vagonlar qurib, barrikadalar qurdilar, ularning orqasida yashirinadilar. Kun davomida xivaliklar barrikadalarga bir necha bor hujum qilishadi, ammo muvaffaqiyatsiz bo'lib chiqdi. 1839 yil 31 dekabrda 1840 yil 1 yanvarga o'tar kechasi otdan tushgan xivaliklar istehkomlar tomon sudralib o'tishga harakat qilishdi. Shu bilan birga, xivaliklar Rossiya barrikadalarini va vagonlaridan 100 metr uzoqlikda xandaq qazishib loy va qordan qoplamalar qurishdi, u yerdan ertalab 69 rus qo'shinlari o'q otishni boshladilar. Askarlar tuyalar bilan yashirinib, Xivaliklarga hujum qilib, dushmanni quvib chiqarishdi. O'z navbatida, xivaliklar Rossiya barrikadalariga hujumni boshladilar. Ular o'zlarini dushman olovidan himoya qilib, hayvonlarni haydab chiqarishdi. Kolonnalar qo'mondoni leytenant Yerofeyev qo'shinlarga chekinib ketishni buyurdi. Xivaliklar barrikadalarga yaqinlashishi bilanoq, rus qo'shinlari ularga yon tomondan o'q uzdilar va xivaliklar orqaga chekindilar.

Faol jangovar harakatlardan so'ng, rus armiyasi uchun yana bir muammo qirg'izlarning o'z ishlarini bajarishni va musulmon dindorlariga qarshi kurashgan ruslar bilan hamkorlik qilishni istamasligi bo'lgan. Shunday qilib, Oq-buloqdagi to'qnashuvlardan so'ng V. A. Perovskiy yurishni davom ettirishni istamadi.

1 fevral kuni qo'shinlarga murojaat qildi: "o'rtoqlar! Uch oy o'tgach, biz imperatorning buyrug'i bilan yolg'a chiqdik. Deyarli uch oy ketma-ket biz g'oyat qiyin qiyinchiliklar bilan kurashdik, g'ayrioddiy qattiq qishda bo'ronlardan va o'tib bo'lmaydigan, misli ko'rilmagan qorlardan duch keladigan to'siqlarni yengib o'tdik, bizning yo'limizni va barcha ozuqalarni to'ldirdik. Agar biz uning

barcha ahamiyatsizligini ko'rsatgan to'qnashuv haqida gapirmasak, dushman bilan uchrashish uchun quvonch ham yo'q edi. O'tkazilgan barcha ishlarga qaramay, otlar , bizning zaxiralarimiz ko'p edi.

Ekspeditsiya bu bizni o'zgartirdi: tuyalarning katta qismi allaqachon vafot etgan va biz Ekspeditsiya qolgan qismi uchun zarur bo'lgan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini ko'tarish imkoniyatidan mahrum bo'ldik. Bizni kutayotgan g'alabadan voz kechish qanchalik og'riqli bo'lsa ham, biz bu safar o'z chegaralarimizga qaytishimiz kerak. U erda biz imperator suverenning yangi buyruqlarini kutamiz; boshqa safar biz baxtliroq bo'lamiz. Barchangizga tinimsiz tirishqoqlik, tayyorlik va yaxshi niyat uchun barcha qiyinchiliklarga dosh berganingiz uchun minnatdorchilik bildiraman; eng rahmdil suveren va otamiz hamma narsani bilib oladi"

Shunday qilib, yurish 1839 yil 24 noyabrdan 1840 yil 8 iyungacha davom etdi, ammo haddan tashqari o'ziga ishonch va ob-havo sharoitlariga tayyor emasligi sababli qo'shinlar Xivaga etib bormasdan orqaga qaytishdi. Yo'qotishlar 1054 kishini tashkil qildi, 604 askar kasalligiga chalingan, ularning aksariyati Orenburgdagi gospitalda vafot etgan.

1840 yil fevralda, rus qo'shinlari Orenburgga qaytayotganda, ingliz josuslari Abbot va Shekspir Xivaga etib kelishadi. Bir necha oy davomida ular xonni V.A.Perovskiyning ultimatum talablarini bajarishga va rus mahbuslarining ko'pini ozod qilishga kondirmoqchi bo'ldi, bu nafaqat Xiva, balki inglizlar uchun ham foydali emas edi. Muzokaralar muvaffaqiyatli yakunlandi va 1840 yil 19-iyulda mingboshin Allaqulixon Xivaliklarga ruslarni talon-taroj qilish va qo'lga olishni taqiqlovchi farmon chiqardi. Bundan tashqari, Xiva xoni asirga olingan rus zobitini Rossiyaga yubordi va "bundan buyon imperator Suverenining barcha talablarini bajarishga tayyorligini e'lon qildi, buning isboti sifatida u o'z mulkidagi barcha rus qullarini ozod qilib, ularga kerakli pul nafaqasini berdi va o'z elchisi bilan yubordi (Shekspir. A. K.)

Rossiyada hibsga olingan Xiva savdogarlarini ozod qilish, ularga asir olingan tovarlarni qaytarish, kambag'allarga Vatanga borish uchun zarur bo'lgan nafaqani berish va Xiva bilan to'xtatilgan savdo aloqalarini tiklashga ruxsat berish to'g'risida xat yozgan.

Bir oy o'tgach, Xivadan rus asirlari bilan karvon 416 kishidan iborat bo'lib, yangi Aleksandr istehkomiga etib keldi, u erdan Guryev dengiz orqali jo'nab ketadi va keyin ularni Orenburgga 72 kishi kuzatib qo'ygan. Xiva mahbuslarining materiallari noyob manba bo'lib, tadqiqotchilarga mahbusning o'rtacha portretini, uni qo'lga olish shartlarini, mazmunini, shuningdek, ularning ijtimoiy mavqeyi va ijtimoiy mavqeyini ko'rsatadi. So'rovnomada jami 16 dona savol mavjud bo'lib, ular ikkala standart umumiy turni o'z ichiga oladi: familiya / ism, yosh, unvon, Vatani, turmush qurgan yoki turmush qurmagan, bolalar soni va ularning ismlari – va aniqroq, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri asirlikka tegishli va tadqiqotchi uchun eng qiziqarli. Bu asirlikning vaqti, joyi va sharoitlari, darhol Xivaga olib ketilganmi, Xivada kim yashagan, ozodlik sharoitlari, Xivada hali ham asirlar qolganmi va ularning ismi nima, Xivada turmush qurganmi yoki farzand ko'rganmi degan savollar bor edi.

Shunday qilib, 1839-1840 yillardagi Xiva ekspeditsiyasi, Xiva asirigidan Rossiya fuqarolarining 1/3 qismini ozod qilganiga qaramay, Rossiya imperiyasining Markaziy Osiyodagi eng muhim muvaffaqiyatsizliklaridan biri bo'ldi. Xiva frontidagi muvaffaqiyatsizlik va rus-ingliz qarama-qarshiliklarining kuchayishi Rossiya hukumatini Osiyo yo'nalishida alternativa izlashga va Buxoro va Qo'qon bilan munosabatlarni o'rnatishga majbur qildi. Buyuk Britaniya, Rossiya hukumatining Hindistonga qiziqmasligi haqidagi ishontirishlariga qaramay, mintaqaga yanada ko'proq qiziqish bildirdi. 1839 yildan keyin Xivaga yuborilgan Rossiya missiyalari va diplomatik elchixonalari Angliyaning mintaqadagi siyosatiga qarshi chiqish sharoitida shakllandi. Xiva 1853-1873 yillarda Rossiyaning Markaziy Osiyodagi ekspansiya siyosatining asosiy nuqtasiga aylandi

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WORDLY
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**THE MOBILE COMMUNICATION TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH
AND UZBEK**

Annotation: In the contemporary world, mobile communication has become an integral part of daily life, influencing various aspects of society, culture, and economy. As mobile technology evolves, so does the terminology associated with it. This paper aims to explore the mobile communication terminology in English and Uzbek, highlighting the similarities and differences between the two languages. Understanding these terminologies is crucial for effective communication in a globalized world, especially in regions where multiple languages coexist.

Key words: terminology, English and Uzbek.

Mobile communication terminology has evolved significantly since the advent of mobile technology. In English, terms such as “smartphone,” “app,” “data plan,” and “network coverage” have become commonplace. These terms reflect the technological advancements and the growing reliance on mobile devices for communication, information access, and social interaction.

In contrast, the Uzbek language has also adapted to these changes, incorporating new terms while also creating equivalents for English terminology. For instance, the term “smartphone”: is often translated as “aqli telefon,” which directly reflects the functionality of the device. Similarly, “application” is translated to “ilova,” showcasing the linguistic adaptation to modern technology.

Comparative Analysis of Terminology

A comparative analysis of mobile communication terminology in English and Uzbek reveals both direct translations and unique terms that reflect cultural nuances. For example, while “text message” is universally understood in English, in Uzbek, it is referred to as “matnli xabar,” which emphasizes the

written nature of the communication. This distinction highlights the importance of context in understanding mobile communication.

Moreover, certain terms in English may not have direct equivalents in Uzbek, necessitating the use of loanwords or descriptive phrases. For instance, the term “cloud computing” is often used in its English form in Uzbek discussions, as the concept may not be as widely recognized or understood in the local context. This phenomenon illustrates the challenges faced by non-English speaking countries in keeping pace with rapid technological advancements.

Cultural Implications

The terminology used in mobile communication also reflects cultural attitudes towards technology. In English-speaking countries, there is a tendency to embrace new technology enthusiastically, which is evident in the rapid adoption of new terms. Conversely, in Uzbekistan, while there is a growing acceptance of mobile technology, there may be a more cautious approach to adopting foreign terms, leading to a blend of local and international terminology.

Furthermore, the use of mobile communication in both languages can reveal insights into social dynamics. For instance, the prevalence of social media terminology in English, such as “viral,” “influencer,” and “hashtag,” indicates a cultural shift towards digital interaction. In Uzbek, similar terms are emerging, but they may carry different connotations based on local social norms and values.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study of mobile communication terminology in English and Uzbek provides valuable insights into the interplay between language, technology, and culture. As mobile communication continues to evolve, so too will the terminology associated with it. Understanding these terms is essential for effective communication in an increasingly interconnected world. Future research could further explore the implications of this terminology on language

development and cultural exchange, contributing to a deeper understanding of how technology shapes our linguistic landscape.

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THE LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF MOBILE COMMUNICATION TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Annotation: The rapid advancement of mobile communication technology has significantly influenced language, leading to the emergence of new terminologies and linguistic features. This paper explores the linguistic characteristics of mobile communication terminology in English and Uzbek, two languages that reflect distinct cultural and technological contexts. By examining the similarities and differences in terminology, this study aims to highlight how mobile communication shapes language and communication practices in both linguistic communities.

Key words: linguistic features, terminology.

Linguistic Features of Mobile Communication Terminology

1. Lexical Innovations

Both English and Uzbek have witnessed the introduction of new lexical items due to the proliferation of mobile communication. In English, terms such as “smartphone,” “app,” and “texting” have become commonplace. These terms often reflect the technological features and functionalities of mobile devices. Similarly, in Uzbek, terms like “smartfon,” “ilova” (application), and “xabar yozish” (to write a message) have emerged, often borrowed directly from English or adapted to fit the phonetic and morphological rules of Uzbek.

2. Borrowing and Code-Switching

The phenomenon of borrowing is prevalent in both languages, particularly in Uzbek, where many English terms related to technology are adopted with minimal modification. This borrowing reflects the global influence of English as a dominant language in technology. Code-switching, where speakers alternate between languages within a conversation, is also common among bilingual

speakers in Uzbekistan, particularly among the youth who are more exposed to English through media and technology.

3. Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronyms and abbreviations are a significant feature of mobile communication terminology in both languages. In English, terms like “LOL” (laugh out loud), “BRB” (be right back), and “DM” (direct message) are widely used in digital communication. In Uzbek, similar practices can be observed, with abbreviations such as “Xo’p” (OK) and “Yana” (again) being used in informal texting. These linguistic features facilitate quick and efficient communication, reflecting the fast-paced nature of mobile interactions.

4. Semantic Shifts

The meanings of existing words often shift in the context of mobile communication. In English, the word “friend” has expanded to include online connections made through social media platforms. In Uzbek, traditional terms may also acquire new meanings related to digital interactions, illustrating how mobile communication influences social relationships and language use.

Cultural Context and Implications

The linguistic features of mobile communication terminology in English and Uzbek are not only reflections of technological advancements but also indicators of cultural attitudes towards technology. In English-speaking countries, the rapid adoption of new terms often signifies a culture of innovation and adaptability. In contrast, the integration of mobile communication terminology in Uzbek reflects a blend of traditional values and modern influences, showcasing the dynamic nature of language in response to globalization.

Conclusion

The study of mobile communication terminology in English and Uzbek reveals significant linguistic features that highlight the impact of technology on language. Through lexical innovations, borrowing, acronyms, and semantic

shifts, both languages adapt to the changing landscape of communication. Understanding these linguistic features provides insights into the broader cultural implications of mobile communication and its role in shaping contemporary language practices.

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WORDLY
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**TEMIR YO'L TRANSPORTIDA YUKNING NOGABARITLIK ZONASI
VA DARAJASINI ANIQLASH**

***Kalit so'zlar:** Yuk oqimi, yuk nogabaritlik zonasi, nogabaritlik darajasini aniqlash, yukning og'irlik markazi, gabarit yuk, xavfsizlik talablari, hisoblash usuli.*

***Annotatsiya:** Maqolada yuklarni yetkazib berish jarayonida harakat xavfsizligini tashkil etish, ularning mavjud holati va mahsulotlarni qabul qilib olgandan keyin tashishga tayyorlash jarayonida sifatli xizmat ko'rsatish usullarining tadqiqi ko'rsatib berilgan. Vagon oqimlarini tashkil qilish jarayonida nogabarit darajalariga sabab bo'luvchi omillarni aniqlab, ularni bartaraf etish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar va takliflar ishlab chiqilgan. Bundan tashqari, yuklarning nogabaritlik zonalari tahlil qilinib, mavjud tizimdagi nogabaritlik darajalarini aniqlash bo'yicha takliflar berilgan.*

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**DETERMINATION OF THE ZONE AND LEVEL OF NON-
UNIFORMITY OF CARGO IN RAIL TRANSPORT**

***Keywords:** load flow, load nogabarity zone, nongabarity level determination, load center of gravity, gabarite load, frustration requirements, calculation method.*

***Annotation:** the article shows the study of the organization of movement safety in the process of delivery of goods, their current state and methods of quality service in the process of preparing products for transportation after receiving them. In the process of organizing wagon flows, measures and proposals have been developed to identify and eliminate the factors that cause nogabarite levels. In addition, nogabarity zones of loads have been analyzed and proposals have been made to determine the levels of nogabarity in the existing system.*

Kirish. MDH ishtirokchi davlatlarining 1520 mmli temir yo'l tarmog'i doirasida umumiy shartlarda ochiq harakatlanuvchi tarkibda tashiladigan yuklar,

yuklashning asosiy o'lchamidan oshmasligi kerak. Agar yuk to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ochiq harakatlanuvchi tarkibga joylashtirilganda yuklash o'lchamining konturidan oshib ketsa, u nogabarit hisoblanadi va nogabarit va og'ir vaznli yuklarni tashish bo'yicha ko'rsatmalarga muvofiq tashilishi kerak. Yuklashning imtiyozli gabaritini qo'llash tartibi, shartlari va ko'lami yuklarni vagonlar va konteynerlarga joylashtirish va mahkamlash qoidalari (qoidalar) bilan belgilanadi.

Asosiy qism. Bitta vagonga yoki ikkita vagonli ilashmaga ortilgan yuk, agar uning biron bir qismi, shu jumladan joylashtirish va mahkamlash, yuklashning asosiy o'lchamidan tashqariga chiqmasa va vagon simmetriyasining ko'ndalang tekisligidan (yoki ilashmada) yukning uchlarigacha bo'lgan masofa ko'rsatilgan qiymatlardan oshmasa u holda yuk gabarit doirasida ortilgan hisoblanadi. Nogabarit yuklarni tashish imkoniyati va shartlarini muvofiqlashtirish, shuningdek, zonalar va nogabaritlik darajalarni hisoblashni asoslash uchun jo'natuvchilar yuklarni yuklash sxemalarini uchta proyeksiyada, burilish nuqtalarining koordinatalarini (yo'l o'qidan X gorizonttal masofalar va rels kallagi sathidan Y vertikal masofalar) ko'rsatadilar.

Yuk quyidagi shartlarga muvofiq platformaga joylashtiriladi:

- yukning tayanch yuzasi platforma polining sathi darajasida;
- yukning og'irlik markazidan o'tuvchi yukning ko'ndalang konturining vertikal o'qi platformaning og'irlik markazidan o'tuvchi vertikal o'q bilan birlashtiriladi.

Yuk konturining burilish nuqtalarining koordinatalari, uning platformaga joylashishini hisobga olgan holda, gorizonttal X o'qi (yo'l o'qidan) va vertikal Y o'qi (rels kallagining sathi darajasidan) bo'yicha aniqlanadi.

$$X_i = B_i; \quad Y_i = h_p + h_i, \quad (1)$$

bu erda B_i -burilish nuqtasi masofasi i ($i=1,5$) yukning kengligi bo'yicha uning vertikal o'qidan, og'irlik markazi orqali o'tadi, mm;

h_p -platforma polining rels kallagi sathi ustidagi balandligi, mm;

h_i - yuk konturining i burilish nuqtasining ko'ndalang kesim yuzasidan balandligi, mm.

Hisoblangan nogabaritlik, uning konturining burilish nuqtalarida yukning ichki va tashqi qismlari uchun alohida belgilanadi. Yukning ichki qismlari - bu vagon yoki ilashma bazasida joylashgan barcha qismlar (1-rasm). Harakatlanuvchi tarkib yoki ilashma bazasidan tashqarida joylashgan yukning qismlari tashqi qismlar deb ataladi.

1-rasm. Bitta vagonga tayangan holda ortilgan yukning qismlari sxemasi

Hisoblangan nogabaritlik - bu tashqi temir yo'lining balandligi bo'lmagan $R=350$ m radiusli shartli hisoblangan egri yo'lda berilgan yukning geometrik uchlarini hisobga olgan holda aniqlangan kattalik.

Hisoblangan nogabarit quyidagi holatdagi yuklar uchun aniqlanishi kerak: L_{yuk} uzunligining L_b vagonining bazasiga nisbati $L_{yuk}/L_b = 1.41$ bo'lganda; ilashma platformalarda tashilganda; 17 m va undan ortiq bazaga ega transportyorlarda tashilganda.

Ilashmaga joylashtirilgan yukning egri chiziqlariga erkin joylashishi uchun ostliklarning balandligini to'g'ri hisoblash va ularni joylashtirish alohida ahamiyatga ega. Ostliklarning balandligi:

$$h_0 = a_p \operatorname{tg} \gamma + h_p + h_x + f_{np}, \quad (2)$$

bu yerda, a_p -yuk tashish vagonining pollari bilan yukning tegishi mumkin bo'lgan nuqtasidan yuk ko'taruvchi vagonning g'ildirak jufti o'qigacha bo'lgan masofa mm:

$$a_p = 0.5(L_{yuk} - L_b - 1850) \quad (3)$$

bu yerda, L_{yuk} , L_b - yukning uzunligi va vagonning tayanch bazasi uzunligi, mm;

$Tg\gamma$ - yuk va ilashma vagonning bo‘ylama o‘qlari orasidagi burchakning tangensi;

h_p -qo‘shni ilashma vagonlarning pollari sathlaridagi farq, mm; $h_p \leq 100$ mm;

h_x - xavfsizlik oralig‘i, mm;

f_{bur} - elastik burilish, mm;

Olingan ostliklarning balandligi qiymati bruslarning standart o‘lchamlariga (50 mm dan ko‘p) katta tomonga qarab yaxlitlanadi. Ostliklarning kengligi uning balandligiga, uzunligi esa vagonning kengligiga teng. Ostliklar ikki juft changaklarga (oxirgi tomonlardan) qarama-qarshi joylashtiriladi.

Platformaga ortilgan yukning ko‘ndalang konturining sxemasiga asoslanib, ostliklarning balandligini hisobga olgan holda, yukning burilish nuqtalarining koordinatalari rels kallagining sathidan Y_{his} :

$$Y_{his} = Y_i + h_p + h_i + h_0 \quad (4)$$

Yukning kritik nuqtalarining yo‘l o‘qidan hisoblangan koordinatalari quyidagi formulalar bilan aniqlanadi:

$$X_{his}^{ich} = X_{ich} + \Delta b_{his}^{tash}, \quad (5)$$

$$X_{his}^{tash} = X_{tash} + \Delta b_{his}^{tash}, \quad (6)$$

bu yerda, X_{his}^{ich} , X_{his}^{tash} -egri chiziqdagi yo‘l o‘qidan kritik nuqtalargacha hisoblangan masofalar, mos ravishda ichki va tashqi bo‘limlarda joylashgan, mm;

X_{ich} , X_{tash} - mos ravishda ichki va tashqi bo‘limlarda joylashgan kritik nuqtalarning to‘g‘ri qismlaridan yo‘l o‘qigacha masofa mm;

Δb_{his}^{ich} , Δb_{his}^{tash} - yukning ichki yoki tashqi qismlarining geometrik chiqishlari va vagonning shartli hisobiy egrilikdagi farqlari.

Qiymatlar Δb_{his}^{ich} va Δb_{his}^{tash} harakatlanuvchi tarkib turiga, ko'rib chiqilayotgan yo'naltiruvchi qismlargacha bo'lgan masofaga bog'liq va ularni ikki xil usul bilan aniqlash mumkin. Bular: yuqorida keltirilgan jadvallar yoki hisoblash yo'llari orqali.

Jadvallarda ko'zda tutilmagan holatlar uchun hisoblash usuli talab qilinadi. Δb_{his}^{ich} va Δb_{his}^{tash} qiymatlari faqat ularning ruxsat etilgan qiymati bilan hisobga olinadi. Agar yukning butun uzunligi bo'ylab kengligi bir xil bo'lsa, X_{his}^{ich} va X_{his}^{tash} koordinatalari faqat eng xavfli qismlar uchun tekshiriladi - o'rtacha (ichki) va oxirgi (tashqi).

Uzun o'lchamli yukni bitta ilashma platformasiga yoki o'qlar soni oltidan oshmaydigan transpartyorlarga yuklashda qiymatlar Δb_{his}^{ich} va Δb_{his}^{tash} quyida keltirilgan formulalar bo'yicha hisoblanadi, mm; bundan tashqari, qiymatlar L_{yuk} va L_b metr bilan almashtiriladi va olingan qiymatlar Δb_{his}^{ich} va Δb_{his}^{tash} keyinchalik faqat ularning ruxsat etilgan qiymati bilan hisobga olinadi:

$$\Delta b_{his}^{ich} = 1.43(l_v - p_{ich})p_{ich} - 105, \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta b_{his}^{tash} = 1.43(l_v - p_{ich})p_{tash} - 105 + K, \quad (8)$$

bu yerda, p_{ich} , p_{tash} -yo'naltiruvchi qismidan, mos ravishda ichki yoki tashqi ko'ndalang qismlarigacha bo'lgan masofalar, m; butun uzunligi bo'ylab bir xil kesimga ega bo'lgan yuklar uchun bu masofalar o'rtagacha va oxirgi kesimgacha quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$p_{ich} = 0.5l_v; \quad (9)$$

$$p_{tash} = 0.5(l_v - L_b), \quad (10)$$

105 - hisoblangan egrilik radiusi 350 m bo'lgandagi bazasi 17 m bo'lgan hisobiy vagonining geometrik chiqishi, mm;

K - yukning so'nggi qismlarining qo'shimcha siljishi, mm.

K qo'shimcha siljish yo'l va harakatlanuvchi tarkibni saqlashning mavjud me'yorlari natijasida temir yo'lda vagonning egilishi natijasida yuzaga keladi va

faqat uning ruxsat etilgan qiymati bilan hisobga olinadi. K siljishi vagonlar turiga qarab aniqlanadi:

maxsus ramalarda

$$K = 70\left(\frac{L_{yuk}}{L_b} - 1.41\right); \quad (11)$$

18-100 rusumli ramalarda

$$K = 55\left(\frac{L_{yuk}}{L_b} - 1.41\right); \quad (12)$$

Hisoblangan koordinatalar qiymatlari X_{his}^{ich} va X_{his}^{tash} kritik nuqtalar orqali yukning taxminiy shartli nogabaritligi yoki uning haddan tashqari nogabaritligi to'g'risida xulosalar chiqariladi va uni tashish usullari bo'yicha takliflar beriladi.

Xulosa. Ushbu maqolada nogabarit va og'ir vaznli yuklarni joylashtirish va mahkamlash uchun umumiy talablar ko'rib chiqildi, bunda vagondagi gabarit va nogabarit yuklar, yukning nogabaritlik zonasi va darajasini aniqlash, nogabarit va og'ir vaznli yuklarni joylashtirish hamda mahkamlashning umumiy talablar kabi ishlar o'rganildi. Nogabaritligi tadqiq qilinayotgan uzunligi 21,72 m, ortilgan platformaning baza uzunligi 9,72 m, 1400 mm dan 3850 mm gacha balandlikda kengligi 3600 mm bo'lgan yukni yo'lning to'g'ridan to'g'ri qismida yuk 2-darajali yon nogabaritlikka ega ekanligi hisoblandi. Tadqiqotda keltirilgan formulalar orqali yuklarning nogabaritlik darajalarini aniqlash temir yo'l transportida harakat xavfsizligini ta'minlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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**XVIII SO'NGI CHORAGIDA AHMADSHOH DURRONIY
BOSHCHILIGIDA XIToyGA QARSHI MUSULMON DAVLATLARI
HARBIY KOALITSIYASINI TUZISHGA URINISH**

Annotatsiya: XVIII asr o'rtalarida Markaziy Osiyo hududida siyosiy vaziyat o'zgarib, O'rta Osiyoga harbiy-siyosiy tahdid solib turgan Jung'or xonligi Xitoyning Sin imperiyasi qo'shinlari tomonidan 1755-1757 yillar davomida olib borilgan qirg'inbarot janglar natijasida tugatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Xitoy, musulmon, Jung'orlar.

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**AN ATTEMPT TO FORM A MILITARY COALITION OF MUSLIM
STATES AGAINST CHINA UNDER AHMADSHAH DURRONI IN THE
LAST QUARTER OF XVIII**

Annotation: in the middle of the 18th century, the political situation on the territory of Central Asia changed and the Junghor Khanate, which posed a military-political threat to Central Asia, was liquidated by the massacres fought by the troops of the Chinese Empire Of Sin during 1755-1757.

Keywords: Chinese, Muslim, junglers.

Jung'oriyani to'liq bosib olinishi shafqatsiz qirg'inlar bilan yana ikki yil mobaynida cho'zilgan va 1760 yilda Jung'oriya aholisiga umumiy avf e'lon qilingan. Jung'orlarning shafqatsiz qirg'in qilinishi va Xitoy qo'shinlarini Samarqandga harbiy yurish qilish rejasi borligi to'g'risidagi xabarlar O'rta Osiyo musulmonlari tomonidan islom dinida bashorat qilingan oxir zamondagi yajuj-majujlarning tajovuzi sifatida baholanganligini tarixiy adabiyotlardagi ma'lumotlar tasdiqlaydi. Masalan, 1758 yilda Chjao-Xoy va Fu-De boshchiligidagi Sin sulolasi qo'shinlari Jung'oriyada ommaviy qirg'in uyushtirgan. Shafqatsizlik yosh bolalar va keksalarni ham chetlab o'tmagan.

Jung'or xonligining asosini tashkil qilgan Oyrat qabilalari vakillari Qozoq juzlari, Movarounnahr xonliklari, Rossiya, Afg'oniston hududlariga o'z jonlarini saqlash maqsadida qochishga majbur bo'lganlar. Shuningdek, Sin imperiyasining g'arbga tomon harbiy yurishlarni davom ettirish rejasi Qozoq juzlari xonlarini, Qo'qon xoni Erdonabiyni, O'ratepa va Xo'jand hokimi Fozolbiyni o'sha vaqtdagi musulmon hukumdorlari ichida eng qudratlisi hisoblangan Afg'oniston hukumdori Ahmadshoh Durroniylar huzuriga elchi yuborib, musulmonlarni g'ayridinlar bosqinidan asrashni so'raganlar. Umumiy xavfqa qarshi birlashishga bo'lgan harakatni Sin imperiyasi qo'shinlarining shafqatsiz qirg'inlari taqazo etgan, deb xulosa qilish mumkin. Jung'or xonligini istilo qilishdan tashqari Sin imperiyasi xonlikka qaram bo'lgan hududlarni jumladan, Sharqiy Turkiston hududlarini ham egallash rejasi tuzilgan bo'lib, Xitoy hukumdori Syanlun ushbu maqsadni amalga oshirishda Sharqiy Turkistonda o'zaro hokimiyat uchun kurashib kelayotgan "Oq tog'li" va "Qora tog'li" xo'jalar o'rtasidagi o'zaro adovatdan foydalanishga qaror qilgan. O'ta dindor hisoblangan va so'fiylikni naqshbandiya tariqati, ishqiya, is'hoqiya oqimlariga ixlosmand bo'lgan Sharqiy Turkiston aholisi Jung'orlar ittifoqchisi hisoblangan Qora tog'li xo'jalarga qarshi kurashda Oq tog'li xo'jalarni qo'llab-quvvatlashiga umid bog'langan. Shu sababli, Jung'or xonligida garovda turgan (ayrim tarixiy adabiyotlarda Boro-xoro tog'larida yashirinib yurgan) turgan Burxoniddinxo'jani Sharqiy Turkistonga xitoyliklarning ittifoqchisi sifatida yuborishga qaror qilingan. Xitoy tomonidan yordamchi qo'shinlar bilan ta'minlanish va Qora tog'li xo'jalarga nisbatan adovat Burxoniddinxo'ja tomonidan Sharqiy Turkistonni oson egallanishiga sabab bo'lgan. Ammo, Burxoniddinxo'ja va uning ukasi Jahonxo'jalarning mustaqil siyosat yuritib, Sin imperiyasiga bo'yinsunishdan bosh tortganlar. Sin imperiyasi Chjao-Xoy, Fu-De kabi ikki nafar generallarni bu isyonni botirish uchun yuborgan. Mag'lub bo'lgan xo'jalar, Badaxshonga qochib ketishlari ham halokatni oldini ololmagan. Sin ma'murlarining xo'jalarni topshirish talabi bilan Badaxshon

hukumdori Sultonshoh (1747-1765 yy) tomonidan Qoshg‘ar xo‘jalarining qatl etilishi sodir bo‘lgan. Ushbu voqeylik O‘rta Osiyo musulmon davlatlarining Xitoy Sin imperiyasi o‘rtasida xalqaro munosabatlardagi ziddiyatning boshlanishiga sabab bo‘lgan. Xo‘jalarni ta‘qib etgan Xitoy generali Fu De Sharqiy Turkistondagi xitoyliklar tomoniga o‘tib ketgan Yangi Hisor hokimi Sultonbekni Badaxshonga elchi qilib yuborgan. Elchilar tomonidan xo‘jalarning Sharqiy Turkistondan katta boylik bilan qochganligi, ularni harami haqidagi uydirmalar tarqatilishi Sultonshohni o‘z dindoshlarini qatl etishga sabab bo‘lgan degan fikrlar ham mavjud. Shuningdek, qirg‘indan Burxoniddin xo‘janing kichik o‘g‘li Said Muhammad (Sarimsoq xo‘ja)ni xizmatkorlardan bo‘lgan Ilyos Miroxo‘r yashirincha qutqarib qolib, Kobulga Ahmadshoh Durraniy himoyasiga olib ketishga muvofaq bo‘lgan. Bu esa, keyinchalik Markaziy Osiyoda Xitoyga qarshi harbiy kaolitsiya tuzish uchun qulay siyosiy vaziyatni vujudga keltirgan. Bundan tashqari Sarimsoqxo‘ja avlodlari keyinchalik Sharqiy Turkistonga da‘vo ham qilganlar. Xo‘jalarning Badaxshonda o‘ldirilishiga oid Sang Muhammad Badaxshi o‘zining “Tarixi Badaxshon” asarida Sultonshoh tomonidan xo‘jalarga yaxshi munosabatda bo‘linsa, xo‘jalar Badaxshon taxtini Sultonshohdan tortib olishga bo‘lgan urinishlari natijasi deb, keltirib o‘tishga uringanligini ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Bizning fikrimizcha, Xitoy tomonining Badaxshon hukumoriga xo‘jalarni topshirmasa bostirib kirish va qirg‘in uyushtirish bilan bog‘liq tazyiqi natijasida Sultonshoh ushbu qatlni amalga oshirgan. Chunki, Badaxshonning harbiy qo‘shini soni 7-10 ming atrofida bo‘lib, Xitoy askarlariga deyarli qarshilik ko‘rsata olmagan. Shuningdek, Fu-De Sultonshohni Xitoyga qaramlikni tan olib o‘lpon yuborib turish majburiyatini yuklaga. Xitoy generali Badaxshon hukumdorini qarshilik ko‘rsat olmasligi ayg‘oqchilar orqali yaxshi tushungan bo‘lishi mumkin. Tarixiy adabiyotlarda, Badaxshon hukumdori Sultonshohning laqabi ajdar ekanligi ham keltirib o‘tilgan. Bu haqda “Turkiston to‘plami” manbasida ma’lumotlar mavjud. Ammo, Sultonshoh tomonidan Qoshg‘ar xo‘jalarini qatl etishi, Xitoyning siyosiy nufuzi irodasiga bo‘yinsunishi,

Badaxshon davlatini Sin imperiyasiga vassal siyosat yuritishini anglatgan. O'sha davr manbalarida Xitoyga sodiqligi uchun Badaxshon hukumdoriga Sin imperatori tomonidan sovg'alar yuborib turilgani keltirib o'tilganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Sultonshoh ham o'z navbatida vassallik shartlarini o'z elchilari orqali bajarib, Sin saroyiga sovg'alar yuborib turgan. Badaxshon hukumdori Sultonshohning imperator Syanlunga siyosiy qaramligi, Sin imperiyasi saroyiga o'lpon yuborib turishi, bundan tashqari xo'jalarni jismonan yo'q qilib, imperator irodasini bajarganligi sababli, Xitoy tomoni ham uni yaxshi taqdirlagan. Sultonshohga Sin imperiyasi saroyida ikkinchi darajali general martabasini taqdim etganligini N.Ya. Bichurin o'zining "Chung'or va Sharqiy Turkiston ocherklari. Qadimgi va hozirgi holatda" nomli asarida ham keltirib o'tganligini ko'rish mumkin. Sultonshohning Xitoyga tobe bo'lishiga siyosiy vaziyat sabab bo'lib, kichkina va harbiy, iqtisodiy qudratli bo'lmagan ushbu beklik Sin imperiyasiga qarshi tura olmagan. Sin sarkardasi Fu De askarlarining Qoshg'ar xo'jalarini ta'qib etib, Shug'on va Vaxondan o'tib Badaxshonga yaqinlashishi fonida xo'jalar qatli yuz bergan. "Turkiston to'plami"da Xitoy askarlari sharafiga o'rnatilgan yodgorlik Yashil ko'lda mavjudligi buning dalili sifatida keltirilgan.

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Jizzax viloyati Sharof Rashidov tumani

27 sonli maktab o'qituvchisi

HOZIRGI TA'LIM TIZIMIDAGI ISLOHOTLAR

Annotatsiya: Maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalari faoliyatini takomillashtirish, bu yo'lda olib borilayotgan amaliy ishlar, yangiliklar, o'zgarishlar haqida, kelajakda bu harakatlar oqibatida bo'ladigan o'zgarishlar haqida so'z borgan. Bundan tashqari islohotlar, yangiliklar haqida ma'lumotlar raqamlarda ifodalangan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim tizimi, kreativ, ta'lim va tarbiya, ijtimoiy muammolar, yuqori texnologiyalar.

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REFORMS IN THE CURRENT EDUCATION SYSTEM

Annotation: the article talked about improving the activities of higher education institutions, about practical work, news, changes that are being carried out along the way, about the changes that will occur in the future as a result of these actions. In addition, information about reforms, innovations are expressed in numbers.

Keywords: educational system, creative, educational and educational, social problems, high technologies.

Bilamizki, dunyoda qaysi davlat bo'lmasin unda kadr salohiyati va intelligent bazasi uni shakllantirish jarayoni butun bir tizimdir. Bunda har bir siyosiy rahbar kuchli o'zgarish va mustahkam legitimlik yaratishga harakat qiladi. Yangi O'zbekistonda yangi ta'lim tizimiga doir qarorlar ishlab chiqilishi zahirida yuksak intellektual salohiyatli yoshlarni tarbiyalash, iqtisodiyot va xalq farovonligini oshirish maqsadi mujassamdir.

Yangi O'zbekistonda yangi ta'lim tizimidagi muammolarni kreativ yechim topish orqali muhim yangilanishlarga erishiladi. Bu borada O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning 2 ta siyosiy doktrinasi va bu dasturlar orqali qo'yilgan maqsadlar zahirida katta o'zgarish sodir bo'lishi

kutilmoqda. Har qanday dastur faqat uni yaratuvchisiga emas uning bajaruvchilari va jamiyat faolligidan kelib chiqib mahsuldorligi ortadi.

Bilamizki, bugun mamlakatimizda barcha sohalarda keng ko‘lamli islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. O‘z navbatida, bu islohotlarning salmoqli qismini ta‘lim tizimida olib borilayotgan islohotlar tashkil etadi. Keyingi yillarda ta‘limning barcha bo‘g‘inlarini zamon talablari asosida tashkil etish yuzasidan amaliy ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Xususan, ta‘lim tizimida quyidagi yo‘nalishlarda islohotlar va amaliy chora-tadbirlar tashkil etilmoqda:

- 1) maktabgacha ta‘lim sohasida;
- 2) umumiy o‘rta va o‘rta maxsus ta‘lim;
- 3) oliy ma‘lumot;
- 4) oliy o‘quv yurtidan keyingi ta‘lim;
- 5) qayta tayyorlash va malakasini oshirish.

Demak, ayniqsa, maktabgacha ta‘lim va tarbiya sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarning boshlanishi bugungi kunda ushbu sohaga alohida e‘tibor qaratilayotganidan dalolat beradi. Maktabgacha ta‘lim tashkilotlari uchun pedagog va boshqaruv kadrlarini tayyorlash, qayta tayyorlash va salohiyatini oshirish borasida ham ijobiy o‘zgarishlar kuzatilmoqda. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning har tomonlama intellektual, axloqiy, estetik va jismoniy rivojlanishi uchun shartsharoitlar yaratish ham Konsepsiyaning asosiy yo‘nalishlaridan biridir. Mazkur tizimda innovatsiyalarni, ilg‘or pedagogik va axborotkommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini keng joriy etish maqsadida maktabgacha ta‘lim tashkilotlarini kompyuterlar bilan ta‘minlash, internet tarmog‘iga ulanishi bosqichma bosqich amalga oshirilmoqda.

Prezidentimiz Sh.M. Mirziyoyev ta‘kidlaganidek, “Farzandlarimiz maktabda qanchalik bilimli bo‘lsa, yuqori texnologiyali iqtisodiyot shunchalik tez rivojlanadi, ijtimoiy muammolar ham hal bo‘ladi. Shunday ekan, yangi O‘zbekiston ostonasi maktabdan boshlanadi, desam, bu fikrni butun xalqimiz qo‘llab-quvvatlaydi, deb o‘ylayman.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 8-oktabrdagi Ijtimoiy soha va iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan PF-5847-son qarori bilan tasdiqlangan O‘zbekiston Respublikasining 2030- yilgacha oliy ta’lim tizimi muqaddima vazifasini o‘tamoqda. bu sohadagi yangi islohotlarga. Sir emaski, bugungi kunda dunyoning yetakchi universitetlari eng yirik ilmiy markazlar hisoblanadi.

Bugungi kunda yangi universitetlar va jahonning yetakchi universitetlarining filiallari tashkil etilmoqda. Masalan, keyingi 4 yilda mamlakatimizda 47 ta yangi oliy ta’lim muassasasi, jumladan, xorijiy oliy ta’lim muassasalarining filiallari tashkil etilib, oliy ta’lim muassasalari soni 125 taga yetdi. Nodavlat oliy ta’lim muassasalari davlat-xususiy sheriklik tizimi asosida tashkil etiladi. Aholining fikrini o‘rganib chiqib, sirtqi va kechki ta’lim shakllari tiklandi va ko‘paydi. Umumta’lim maktablari 2016-yildagi 9 foizdan 2020-yilda 25 foizga o‘sdi, bu ishni yanada kengaytirishimiz kerak.¹²

Xorijdagi oliy ta’lim muassasalari va ilmiy tadqiqot muassasalarida professor-o‘qituvchilarning malakasini oshirish va stajirovkadan o‘tish mexanizmi yaratildi. Ularning oylik ish haqi miqdori 2018 yilga nisbatan o‘rtacha 2,5 barobarga oshdi. Joriy yildan boshlab 10 ta oliy ta’lim muassasasi o‘zini-o‘zi moliyalashtirishga o‘tkazildi.

Demak, yuqoridagilardan xulosa qilish mumkinki, bugungi kunda ta’lim sohasidagi islohotlar o‘zining dolzarbligi va amaliy ahamiyatiga ko‘ra boshqa sohalardagi islohotlardan qolishmaydi. Chunki bu boradagi islohotlarni yanada keng ko‘lamda davom ettirish vaqti keldi.

Davlatning kelajagi bevosita yoshlarning bilimli bo‘lishiga bog‘liq. Shu bois ta’lim tizimini rivojlantirish masalasiga hukumat darajasida e’tibor qaratish har bir davlat uchun muhim vazifa hisoblanadi.

¹² G‘afforova, X. Y., & Abduljalilova, M. (2023). xorijiy tajribalar asosida maktabgacha ta’lim tashkiloti tarbiyachilarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 199–203. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3727>

O‘zbekistonda keyingi yillarda Harakatlar strategiyasi va uning mantiqiy davomi bo‘lmish Taraqqiyot strategiyasi doirasida rivojlangan mamlakatlardagi kabi uzluksiz ta‘lim tizimini tizimli takomillashtirish, sifatli ta‘limni ta‘minlash, ta‘lim-tarbiyani yanada yuksaltirish borasida aniq islohotlar amalga oshirildi. malakali kadrlar tayyorlash.

Ushbu islohotlar munosabati bilan keyingi 6 yilda davlat byudjeti xarajatlari **4,3** barobar, maktabgacha ta‘lim muassasalari soni 2016-yildagi **5211 tadan 2021-yilga kelib 19316** taga , maktablar soni **9719 tadan 10289** taga , 11 taga ko‘paydi. -yozgi majburiy ta‘lim qayta ochildi, maktab o‘qituvchilari yuklamasi optimallashtirildi, majburiy mehnatga barham berildi. Ta‘lim sohasi vakillarining ish haqi qariyb 4 barobar oshirildi, oliy o‘quv yurtlari soni **70 tadan 191** taga ko‘paytirildi , oliy o‘quv yurtidan keyingi ta‘limning ikki bosqichli tizimi – asosiy doktorantura (PhD) va doktorantura (doktorantura) joriy etildi. fan doktori).

Ta‘lim sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan izchil islohotlar samarasida maktabgacha ta‘lim muassasalariga qamrab olish darajasi **27,7** foizdan **67** foizga, maktablarda oliy ma‘lumotli malakali pedagoglar ulushi **81,8** foizdan **87,8** foizga, yoshlarning qamrab olinishi ta‘minlangan. oliy ma‘lumot 9 foizdan 38 foizgacha.

Sohadagi islohotlarni izchil davom ettirish maqsadida 2026-yilgacha rivojlanish strategiyasi doirasida maktabgacha ta‘lim bilan qamrab olish darajasini hozirgi 67 foizdan 80 foizga yetkazish, **7 mingdan** ortiq ta‘lim muassasalari tashkil etish rejalashtirilgan . yangi nodavlat maktabgacha ta‘lim muassasalarini tashkil etish, xalq ta‘limi tizimida qo‘shimcha **1,2 million** o‘quvchi o‘rni yaratish, 2023/2024 o‘quv yilidan boshlab Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi va Xorazm viloyatining boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilarini bepul ovqatlantirish bo‘yicha ijobiy tajribasini joriy etish; qolgan barcha viloyatlar va Toshkent shahridagi maktablar. Shuningdek, oliy ta‘lim

muassasalariga qabul qilish darajasini 50 foizga, nodavlat oliy o'quv yurtlari sonini esa kamida 50 taga yetkazish ko'zda tutilgan.

Bu esa yuqoridagi islohotlarni yanada mustahkamlash va davom ettirish, yoshlarning umrbod ta'lim olish imkoniyatlarini konstitutsiyaviy qonunchilikda mustahkamlab qo'yishni taqozo etadi.

Shuni inobatga olgan holda, yangilangan Konstitutsiyada ilk bor maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning ta'lim va tarbiyasi sohasida davlat kafolati joriy etish, bolalarning o'rta ta'lim olishi va uni davlat tomonidan tekin ta'minlashi majburiyligi; fuqarolarning davlat ta'lim muassasalarida tanlov asosida davlat hisobidan oliy ta'lim olishlari.

Ta'lim sohasida alohida davlat majburiyatlari sifatida nogiron bolalarning sifatli ta'lim olish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishning aniq mexanizmlari ta'lim muassasalarida alohida ta'limga muhtoj bolalarni inklyuziv ta'lim va tarbiyalash uchun ijtimoiy norma joriy etilmoqda;

Yuqoridagi islohotlarni amalga oshirish uchun ta'lim sifatiga e'tibor qaratib, bu boradagi ishlarning jozibadorligini muttasil oshirib borish zarur. Zero, millat va elat ravnaqi, intellektual salohiyatini yuksaltirish o'qituvchilar faoliyatiga bog'liq. O'qituvchi ilm-fan sirlarini, ma'naviy-madaniy merosni yoshlarga yetkazishda muhim bo'g'indir. Binobarin, o'qituvchilarning o'z salohiyatini to'la ro'yobga chiqarishi uchun sharoit yaratish, ularni ijtimoiy, huquqiy, moddiy qo'llab-quvvatlash zarur.

Shu bois Konstitutsiyaga o'qituvchilarning jamiyatdagi maqomi to'g'risida alohida modda kiritildi. O'zbekistonda o'qituvchi mehnatini jamiyat va davlat taraqqiyoti, sog'lom, barkamol avlodni shakllantirish va tarbiyalash, xalqning ma'naviy-madaniy salohiyatini asrab-avaylash va boyitishning asosi sifatida e'tirof etish tobora mustahkamlanmoqda. Davlat o'qituvchilarning sha'ni va qadr-qimmatini himoya qiladi, ularning ijtimoiy va moddiy farovonligi, kasbiy o'sishi haqida g'amxo'rlik qiladi, deb taxmin qilinadi.

O‘z navbatida, mazkur yangilik mamlakatimizda faoliyat yuritayotgan 685 ming nafardan ortiq o‘qituvchilarning ijtimoiy mavqeini mustahkamlash, ularni davlat tomonidan qo‘llab-quvvatlashni kuchaytirish va kasbiy o‘shini ta‘minlaydi.

Xulosa shuki, inson kapitali sifatini yaxshilamasdan turib, iqtisodiy o‘shini yanada ta‘minlash qiyin bo‘ladi. Binobarin, zarur kuch va resurslarni ta‘lim sifatini oshirish, malakali kadrlar tayyorlashga yo‘naltirish nafaqat bugun, balki ertangi kunning ham ustuvor vazifasiga aylanib bormoqda.

Binobarin, har bir davlat erkin va farovon jamiyat qurish yo‘lida intilayotgan ekan, eng avvalo bu yo‘lda o‘zining ulkan maqsad va vazifalarini Konstitutsiyasida mustahkamlab beradi. Bunga hech qanday shubha yo‘q.

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POMEGRANATE CULTIVATION TECHNOLOGIES AND INNOVATIONS

Abstract: This article analyzes pomegranate (*Punica granatum L.*) cultivation technologies and innovations. Pomegranate is one of the ancient and valued fruit crops, whose health benefits and economic significance are increasingly recognized. The introduction of innovative technologies in pomegranate cultivation helps enhance growth and yield. This research discusses modern technologies utilized in pomegranate cultivation, including agronomic practices, genetic selection, biotechnology, and water-saving technologies. The aim is to improve the efficiency of pomegranate cultivation through innovative approaches and create new opportunities for sustainable agricultural development.

Keywords: Pomegranate, cultivation technologies, innovations, agronomy, biotechnology, genetic selection, water-saving.

Introduction

Pomegranate (*Punica granatum L.*) is a fruit crop that has held significant importance for health and nutrition since ancient times, widely distributed in many regions, including Uzbekistan. The nutritional value, medicinal properties, and commercial potential of pomegranate establish it as an important crop in agriculture. Today, the technologies and innovations in pomegranate cultivation are essential for improving profitability, resource efficiency, and environmental protection.

The aim of this article is to examine the modern technologies applied in pomegranate cultivation and analyze their innovative aspects. The introduction of innovations can lead to improved yields and quality, as well as effective solutions for protecting crops from pests and diseases.

Pomegranate, scientifically known as *Punica granatum L.*, is a fruit cherished for its nutritional and economic value. As the demand for this fruit

continues to rise globally, the adoption of innovative cultivation techniques becomes essential to enhance both yield and sustainability.

Effective soil and irrigation management are critical for successful pomegranate cultivation. Preparing the soil adequately and managing its fertility ensures that the plants have the necessary nutrients for optimal growth. Additionally, utilizing efficient irrigation methods, such as drip irrigation, conserves water while providing the consistent moisture that pomegranate trees require.

Controlling pests and diseases is another vital aspect of pomegranate farming. Integrated Pest Management (IPM) combines biological control methods with environmentally friendly pesticides to manage pest populations. Moreover, the development of disease-resistant varieties helps minimize crop losses and improve overall yields.

Harvesting techniques have also evolved with modern technologies. The use of advanced harvesting tools enhances efficiency, reduces labor costs, and minimizes damage to the fruit during collection.

Advancements in genetic improvement and biotechnology play a significant role in enhancing pomegranate cultivation. Techniques such as genetic engineering and tissue culture allow for the creation of superior pomegranate varieties that boast higher yields and better resistance to diseases.

The rise of smart agriculture is transforming the way farmers manage their crops. Technologies like drones and data analytics provide farmers with the tools to monitor and manage their fields more effectively. By utilizing real-time data, farmers can make informed decisions that improve the overall health and productivity of their crops.

Sustainable farming practices are gaining importance in pomegranate cultivation. Emphasizing organic methods and eco-friendly practices not only contributes to environmental health but also supports biodiversity, ensuring the long-term sustainability of pomegranate production.

Results and Discussion

Pomegranate Cultivation Technologies

1. **Agronomy:** Agronomic practices, including timely irrigation, fertilization, harvesting, and pest control techniques, are vital in pomegranate cultivation. The application of new varieties and agricultural machinery significantly enhances productivity.
2. **Biotechnology:** Biotechnological methods, such as cloning and regeneration processes, are utilized to create new varieties. These methods can improve critical physiological and biochemical characteristics of the plants.
3. **Genetic Selection:** Genetic selection methods enable the development of new pomegranate varieties with high yield, stress tolerance, and disease resistance. These techniques help enhance quality and reduce adverse factors in the production process.
4. **Water-Saving Technologies:** Modern irrigation technologies, such as drip irrigation and automated irrigation systems, are employed to conserve water resources. These technologies facilitate efficient and economical use of water, thereby improving the growth of pomegranate plants.

Innovative approaches encompass new technologies and methods that can be applied in the pomegranate cultivation process. These include smart agriculture, high-tech monitoring systems, eco-friendly pesticides and biopreparations, as well as innovative methods for crop protection. Such approaches not only improve productivity but also aim for environmental conservation and sustainable agricultural development.

Conclusion

The analysis of pomegranate cultivation technologies and innovations demonstrates that modern approaches serve to enhance the efficiency and profitability of pomegranate production. Agronomy, biotechnology, genetic selection, and water-saving technologies play crucial roles in the cultivation process. Innovative approaches create new opportunities for sustainable

agricultural development and increase the commercial significance of pomegranate crops. The findings of this study can be utilized to improve and innovate pomegranate cultivation processes in the future.

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**PHYSIOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF
REGENERATED POMEGRANATE VARIETIES**

Abstract: *This study investigates the physiological and biochemical properties of newly regenerated pomegranate varieties. As one of the most ancient fruit crops, pomegranates are renowned for their unique health benefits, mainly attributed to their phytochemical composition. The research focuses on the analysis of these regenerated varieties, highlighting their growth patterns, stress tolerance, and fruit quality. The investigation is structured to evaluate the antioxidant activity, vitamin content, and other biochemical markers, offering insights into their potential for commercial cultivation. These findings could significantly impact agricultural practices and future breeding programs.*

Keywords: *Regenerated pomegranate varieties, physiological properties, biochemical analysis, antioxidants, fruit quality, breeding programs, commercial cultivation.*

Pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) is widely recognized for its historical and agricultural significance, cultivated for over 2,000 years across various regions. The plant is valued for its high nutritional and medicinal properties, often linked to its rich phytochemical composition, particularly antioxidants such as polyphenols and flavonoids. In recent years, researchers have focused on the development of regenerated pomegranate varieties that demonstrate enhanced physiological and biochemical traits. These new varieties are expected to exhibit superior resistance to environmental stressors, improved fruit quality, and higher yield potential, which are essential for meeting global agricultural demands.

The aim of this study is to assess the physiological and biochemical characteristics of newly regenerated pomegranate varieties. Specifically, this research evaluates the varieties' growth performance, tolerance to abiotic stress, and their biochemical composition, including antioxidant activity, vitamin

content, and phenolic compounds. The results of this study could provide valuable insights for future pomegranate breeding programs and offer new perspectives for sustainable commercial cultivation.

The results of this study demonstrate significant differences in the physiological and biochemical properties of regenerated pomegranate varieties compared to traditional ones. These newly regenerated varieties exhibit enhanced growth rates, higher fruit yield, and greater tolerance to abiotic stress factors, such as drought and salinity, which are critical for their sustainable cultivation in arid and semi-arid regions.

The physiological analysis of the regenerated pomegranate varieties revealed improved growth metrics, including increased plant height, leaf area, and root development. These varieties showed greater resistance to environmental stressors, particularly in areas with high salinity and limited water availability. The enhanced photosynthetic capacity observed in these varieties is likely due to their adaptation to abiotic stress, which could be attributed to the genetic modifications introduced during the regeneration process.

Biochemical analysis indicated that the regenerated varieties contain higher levels of antioxidants, particularly polyphenols and flavonoids, compared to traditional pomegranate varieties. These compounds are known to contribute to the health benefits associated with pomegranate consumption, such as anti-inflammatory and anti-carcinogenic properties. Additionally, the vitamin C content in the regenerated varieties was significantly higher, further enhancing their nutritional value.

The phenolic content, a key indicator of antioxidant capacity, was also notably elevated in the regenerated varieties. This increase in phenolic compounds not only contributes to the enhanced health benefits but also improves the fruit's shelf life and marketability, making these varieties highly desirable for commercial production.

The findings of this study suggest that the regenerated pomegranate varieties have the potential to revolutionize pomegranate cultivation. Their superior physiological traits allow them to thrive in challenging environmental conditions, while their enhanced biochemical properties offer greater nutritional and medicinal value. This makes them a promising option for farmers looking to improve yield and fruit quality, particularly in regions prone to harsh climatic conditions.

Moreover, the improved stress tolerance of these varieties can lead to reduced reliance on chemical fertilizers and pesticides, promoting more sustainable agricultural practices. As these varieties gain popularity, they could contribute to the global demand for high-quality, health-promoting fruits, while also supporting efforts to mitigate the impacts of climate change on agriculture.

Conclusion

The results of this study provide compelling evidence of the superior physiological and biochemical properties of regenerated pomegranate varieties. These varieties exhibit enhanced growth patterns, stress tolerance, and fruit quality compared to traditional varieties. The high antioxidant activity and vitamin content present in these new varieties highlight their potential for health benefits, making them attractive for both consumers and producers. Additionally, the findings support the use of these regenerated varieties in breeding programs aimed at improving commercial pomegranate production. This research opens new avenues for exploring the agricultural and economic benefits of regenerated fruit crops.

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**IKKI PARALLEL TO'G'RI CHIZIQLAR VA KESUVCHI HOSIL
QILGAN BURCHAKLAR MAVZUSINI AMALIYOTDA QO'LLASH**

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktab o'quvchilarini geometriya fanini yaxshi o'zlashtirishi, fanga doir dunyoqarashini kengaytirishi, geometriya fanidagi mavzularni hayotda qo'llay olishi uchun ko'mak yaratildi.

Kalit so'zlar: ikki parallel to'g'ri chiziqlar, kesuvchi, kema, qarama-qarshi tomon.

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**APPLICATION IN PRACTICE OF THE SUBJECT OF TWO
PARALLEL STRAIGHT LINES AND ANGLES FORMED BY THE
CUTTER**

Annotation: this article provides support for schoolchildren to master geometricity well, to expand their worldview in science, to be able to apply topics in geometry in life.

Keywords: two parallel straight lines, cutter, ship, opposite side.

Savol: Kema turgan joyidan muzeygacha borish mumkin bo'lgan eng qisqa yo'lni toping.

Siz kanalning o'rtasida qayiqda sayr qilyapsiz va o'ng tomondagi muzeyga tashrif buyurishni xohlaysiz, lekin birinchi navbatda siz kanalning narigi tomoniga

НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И РАЗРАБОТКИ II

borishni xohlaysiz, siz buni qanday bajarar edingiz? Masalan, siz yuqoridagi kabi yo'lni tanlashingiz mumkin.

yoki cheksiz ko'p yo'llari mavjud, ammo ulardan qaysi biri eng qisqasi ekanligini o'ylashning eng oqilona yo'lini topishingiz kerak.

Keling birgalikda buni bajaramiz:

Joriy A pozitsiya va yakuniy pozitsiya B nuqtaga qarama-qarshi tomondan B^1 yangi nuqtani olamiz .

Simmetriya tufayli bu tomonning istalgan P nuqtasini olib, P ning har qanday pozitsiyasi uchun PB har doim PB^1 ga teng bo'ladi, shuning uchun biz A dan B gacha bo'lgan eng qisqa yo'lni topishimiz mumkin.

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DEVELOPMENT AND IMPROVEMENT OF CYCLICITY

Keywords: *cycle poems, development trends and perfection, diversity, integrity, author's concept, generality, new formation, unity of theme and content, original poetry, harmony in artistic expression, etc.*

Annotation: *In this article, the issue of diversity in Uzbek poetry is studied in terms of its gradual development and perfection. It analyzes the aspects of the cycle related to the problems of the period, the different aspects of the concept of the creators. Attention was also paid to the peculiarities of the poems of the category, the properties of their formation, the independence of the poems included in the lyrical series, their unity in one center through a single theme and purpose, the unity of space and time in the image and other aspects.*

It is known that poetic diversity has been formed and developed in Uzbek poetry from the earliest times. Qualitative changes in the structure of poetic series are evidence of the fact that various methodological researches and figurative means in the artistic perception and expression of social, spiritual and moral themes and problems have expanded in accordance with the possibilities of poetic thinking. According to the leading features of lyrical genres in the process of studying the world and man, they also have their own poetic forms, themes, problems, which in turn appear. Poetic forms - philosophical miniatures, the evolution of poetic series - also mean the process of perfecting this system of poetic images. It can be seen that the poetic forms and the range of themes and problems of the poetic series are also a priority. In particular, our poets through the theme of nature - society - man, good and evil, good and evil, decay and eternity, life and death, light and darkness, nights and dawns of human life, beauty and depravity, integrity of faith and innocence. , artistic perception and expression of various aspects of eternal problems such as loyalty and betrayal.

In general, examples of such a poetic process are noteworthy in terms of the history of our poetry, the history of art. Unusual poetic forms, creative researches in poetic series, and forms of artistic thinking are also influential in that they play an important role in the literary-historical process and determine the leading development trends.

“The most important form of breaking the boundaries between works of art is their cycle. The poet’s merging of his poems into cycles (which was common in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries) often turns out to be the emergence of a new work that unites earlier creations. In other words, poetry cycles become independent works. ” Such works include A. Blok's "Poems about a Beautiful Lady" in Russian poetry, A. Beli's "Slaves", "With Don", V. Khodasevich, B. Pasternak's "Second Birth", A. Akhmatova's Many works can be included, such as “Northern Elements”. It seems that poetic collections can be poetic works that can have a whole status within a single meaning.

“A literary work (although a whole) is not a monolith. It is a multifaceted subject with different angles (sides, angles, levels, aspects). Its composition and structure are often very complex and are described by literary scholars through a series of concepts and terms to which we refer. The most important form of breaking the boundaries of literary works is their cyclization. ” Combining the poet’s poems into cycles (common in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries) often turns out to be the creation of a new work that combines what has already been created. By the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the content of classical literature had expanded, developed, and enriched itself with new themes that had not been covered in our poetry in the past. One of the distinctive features of the literary life of the period is that with the creative initiative of several folk artists, several series of poems on topical issues related to a number of socio-political events in modern life have emerged. Basically, it can be seen from these series of poems on a socio-political theme that these works, created in different genres and forms on the same theme, in the

same ideological and artistic direction, signify the unity and unity of the artists of the time.

The above-mentioned aspects are clearly reflected in the series of poems written by Zari, Muqimi, Muhyi, Furqat, Ibrat, Zavqi, Nodim and a number of other poets. In these categories, they were able to present the problems of social life in a timely manner. Seven of these series on socio-political themes, such as "Mud," "Flea," "Horse," "Cow," and "Flies," can be seen as the result of the poets' creative interaction.

Zoriy and Nodim's poems, written in one genre, one style, one rhyme and one line, one direction, one weight, testify to the creative collaboration. It is possible that similar poems will be found in other poets of this period. The writing of this category of poems testifies to the creative cooperation and solidarity of dozens of artists in the literary environment of the time.

Cyclicalism also had a place and function in modern literature. Like other forms of poetry, it has become one of the main means of helping the problems of the time to penetrate people's hearts faster and deeper. The diversity of Jadid poetry was also necessary to draw attention to the problems of society.

In 1917, Abdurauf Fitrat published a series of poems entitled "The Sorrow of the Country" in the newspaper "Hürriyet" which he edited. It is noteworthy that most of them were sham poems, Fitrat himself said, mansuras. It is known that this experiment was first performed by Hamza in our literature. The first of the poems included in the "Sorrow of the Country" was published in "Hürriyet" on July 28, 1917, and the last in the December 29 issue. The last of these is in the dream weight. The rest, of course, are weightless. As the title of the column shows, the poems are dedicated to the grief of the motherland. The time was the time of revolutions. The Tsarist government collapsed. The agile nations immediately began to see plans for independence. What will be the fate of Turkestan, especially the future of Turkestan, which has been lost in recent centuries, cut off from the world, buried in immorality, lost its image and fallen

into the hands of another nation - the pain that afflicts Fitrat that's exactly what happened. O great Turan, land of lions! What happened to you How are you? How many days are left? Began one of them. The poet asks his "high places" why he fell into "slavery pits". He longs for the "tiger-hearted children who have shaken the world with their urhos," for the "mountain boys who throw the earth to the sky." He can't come to terms with it. In his veins, Timur calls on his compatriots to protect the honor and dignity.

Abdurauf Fitrat. The "Sorrow of the Country" series is in the form of a short poem, which was published in the "Hürriyet" newspaper on July 28, 1917, No. 26. The poem consists of the parts "Temur is ahead", "From the Uzbek language" and "The sorrow of the country". In each of them the idea of awakening and raising the Motherland - Turan (Turkistan) was put forward. Fitrat hoped that this poem would open the eyes of the people.

Many poems were written in the early twentieth century. In 1936, Uzbekistan began preparations for Pushkin's jubilee. In this regard, writers such as Oybek, Hamid Olimjon, Abdulla Qahhor, Uygun, Usmon Nasir, Temur Fattoh spent several months translating Pushkin's works in Chimgan. Oybek was given a translation of the poetic novel "Eugene Onegin". In the same days, Oybek, inspired by the beautiful nature of Chimgan, wrote a series of poems called "Chimgan's Notebook". Namatak is one of them. The poem was first published in Gulistan magazine in 1936. Soviet-era literary critics also regarded this philosophical poem as one of Oybek's greatest achievements. It was interpreted as a work that vividly reflected the feelings of a life-loving poet. At the same time, he took a deeper look at the artistic world of Namatak's poetry, deepening its essence, truth and charm.

Oybek's poems, which are included in the "Chimgan Notebook" series, are one of the masterpieces not only of the poet's poetry, but also of Uzbek lyric poetry in general, absorbing the fascinating beauty and unique colors of Uzbek nature. With these poems, the poet brought an elegant lyricism to Uzbek poetry,

perfected the culture of depicting delicate feelings and experiences, and polished the language of lyrical poetry with its subtle light.

As a result of the literary and cultural policy of the Soviet state in 1937-38, the principle of approaching writers and their works from the point of view of vulgar sociology was strengthened. Oybek's lyrical poems, included in the "Chimgan Notebook" series, were considered examples of bourgeois poetry.

The theme of World War II has a special place in Shuhrat's work. The image of a warrior depicted in a series of poems from his "Warrior's Notebook" is the image of a man who sacrificed his life for the motherland, who loved the motherland very much, and who turned his soil into his eyes. This category includes "Your album", "In the trench", "Flower sapling", "Ukrainian girl", "Joy", "What's wrong!", "Take the sword", "Warrior's grave", "I am alive", "Memory of my friend", "Target", "Letter from the road", "Please", "Letter from Prussia", "Four plates", "Moment of victory", "Victory In 20 poems, such as "Now I Know", human qualities, love of land, moments of emigration, as well as the bloodshed committed by the Nazis are artistically described. While some of the poems in the Warrior Notebook series, such as "To Your Album," lyrically describe the hero's passionate love for his homeland and his encouragement to endure moments of exile, another In their poems, the moments of pain and suffering of a warrior who witnessed the atrocities committed by the Nazis are vividly and convincingly described. As the warrior lies in the trenches, his mind is filled with vivid scenes from the pre-war period, the tranquility of a delicious life. Then his mind leads to the miserable corpse of a baby shot by the Nazis.

Thousands of brides chased away by the invaders, heart-wrenching gardens and orchards, towns and villages appear before the eyes of a lyrical hero. While the poet's poems "Flower Seedling" lyrically describe the state of the warrior and his beloved, his poems "Ukrainian Girl" differ from other poems in terms of their compositional structure and content. Of course, it was based on real-life

facts, live scenes, the fate of real people. The work of the lyrical protagonist, described in the series "From the Warrior's Notebook", is not only about the impressions of the trip, but also about the reaction to various events. Of course, in this case, the specific genre features of the creation of a series of poems, the internal laws, that is, the subordination of all poems that are separate in terms of content and meaning to the overall compositional integrity, is an event of interest and inspiration. the lyrical depiction of impressions was the poet's focus. Although the poet's heroes take an active part in the war, he hates the war. The series of poems of fame from the "Warrior's Notebook" depicts the events of the Second World War from the first days to the end of the war and the real feelings and desires of those who took part in it. specific.

Almost all poets in Uzbek poetry have created a series of works. Mirtemir's "Karakalpak Notebook", Zulfiya's "Gift of the Valley", H. Gulom's "Continents are Awake", Shuhrat's "Caucasian Notebook". Each of its works has an independent artistic value, but they combine to form a complete work that gives a perfect picture of one aspect of life.

Among the collections of poems written by Shuhrat in different years, the series "Warrior's Notebook", "Caucasian Notebook", "On the banks of the Danube", "People and Monuments" were a special creative stage in the poet's work. The collection includes his children's poems, comedies, quatrains and translations.

A series of poems is also in the works of the poet Mirtemir. As a result of the literary policy of the post-World War II years, Mirtemir was not allowed to create and publish his works. As a result, he had to translate and edit. His translations of Karakalpak poetry and the Karakalpak Book of Poems (1959) were a great success. The ideas of friendship and cooperation between the peoples, expressed in the "Karakalpak Book", were skillfully continued in the poems written under the influence of the poet's travels to the Kazakh, Kyrgyz and Turkmen lands.

In the second half of the 1950s, the poetess Zulfiya took an active part in the movement of Asian and African writers under the motto of peace and international solidarity, visiting many countries around the world. His travels to India, Egypt, Japan and neighboring republics have left a deep mark on the poet's work. Poems such as "Mushoira", "My son, there will never be a war", "Kazakhstan's boys", "A picture I did not draw" brought him fame. The scale of life depicted in Zulfiya's poems has expanded, and scenes of foreign life have entered her work. Since the 1970s, a new rainbow of colors has appeared in Zulfiya's national life, creating a sense of authenticity and emotion. The principle of philosophical perception of reality, which began with a bouquet of poems "Thoughts" (1965), continues in the books of poems "Visol" (1972), "Years, years..." (1975), showing the beginning of a real artistic rise in Zulfiya's work. did. At the same time, the poet wrote a series of poems for children in 1975, entitled "Tulip".

In 1932, the first collection of poems "Pages of Life" was published. Then many of his collections of poetry, such as "People close to my heart", "The heart is always on the road", "Rainbow" will be published.

Also, Erkin Vahidov's "Wisdom Anecdotes", "Battle of the Ants", "Canadian Series", Abdulla Aripov's "Book of Hajj", "Words of Wisdom", "World" series of poems, tens, eights, If we look at the research on poems, we see that the potential of poets' artistic thinking has expanded the horizons of poetic forms, the emergence of lyrical monologues, the emergence of artistic masterpieces that define the history of our poetry. lyric genres and poetic forms in perception and expression have proven in practice how wide and possessive they are.

There are a number of other principles that determine the important qualities and peculiarities of the literature of the independence period. Qualitative changes in the culture of artistic thinking have been reflected in the

nation's self-awareness, self-esteem, and self-esteem, as well as in the formation of national pride.

"Another guiding principle is that our writers, whether addressing historical reality or the present day, are distinguished by their socio-philosophical concept, which is essentially aimed at ensuring the unity of the people." If we take only one example of the lyro-epic genre, we can see the experience of a number of works in epic poetry. In particular, the People's Poet of Uzbekistan Tolan Nizam created a series of epics of independence - "Song about the Motherland", which sang the glory of independence, the age-old dream of our people - a free life, our eternal values.

A category is a collection of works of art with a common ideological intention, a common theme, a protagonist, and a certain compositional integrity. Category works are available in all genres of literature. For example, Balzac's "Human Comedy" or Zolia's "Rugon - Cunning" are a series of novels. There are also series of stories, essays and even articles. The category is especially prevalent in poetry.

One of the important tasks of our science is to study the nature of genres of works such as a series of epics, dramatic poems, poetic dramas, poetic short stories, poetic tales, reportage epics, to theoretically generalize creative research on poetic forms.

Everyone's happiness depends on his deeds. If he devotes his life to good deeds, he will be happy, because he who devotes himself to goodness will not face evil, if he engages in evil deeds, he will be unhappy, because where there is evil, there will be no good. The being that created man requires it1.

This, in Uzbek poetry, the cycle of poems has passed its way of development and perfection from ancient times to the present day. The cycle is enriched by the problems of the period in which it is created. The fact that the category is present in the work of almost every poet proves that it is one of the distinctive shawls of lyricism. The peculiarities of the poems of the category, the

properties of their formation, the independence of the poems included in the lyrical series, their unification in a single center through a single theme and purpose, the unity of space and time in the image and many other features indicates that.

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**IJTIMOYIY MUNOSABATLARDA AHOLI BANDILIGINI
TAMINLASHNING UNUMLI QULAY IMKONIYATLARIDAN
FOYDALANISH**

Annotatsiya. Maqolada aholi bandligi tushunchasi iqtisodiy kategoriya sifatida tahlil qilingan. Sanoati rivojlangan mamlakatlarda bandlik va mehnat bozorini tartibga solishning modellari o'rganib chiqilgan. Mazkur davlatlar tajribalaridan mamlakatimizda ishsizlikni qisqartirish va aholining ijtimoiy zarur mehnat bilan bandligini ko'paytirish bo'yicha foydalanish imkoniyatlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: aholi bandligi, ishsizlik, mehnat bozori, bandlik dasturlari, bandlikni tartibga solish modellari, xorijiy tajriba.

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**TO TAKE ADVANTAGE OF THE MOST FAVORABLE
OPPORTUNITIES FOR ENSURING EMPLOYMENT OF THE
POPULATION IN SOCIAL RELATIONS**

Annotation. The article analyzes the concept of population employment as an economic category. In industrialized countries, models of employment and labor market regulation have been studied. The possibilities of using the experiences of these countries to reduce unemployment and increase the socially necessary employment of the population in our country are highlighted.

Keywords: population employment, unemployment, labor market, employment programs, employment regulation models, foreign isolation.

Bugungi kunda aholining ish bilan bandligini ta'minlash muammosi jamiyat ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishning eng muhim makroiqtisodiy xususiyatlaridan biri bo'lib iqtisodiyotda alohida ahamiyatga ega. Shuningdek, mamlakatimiz Prezidenti Sh.M.Mirziyoev tashabbusi bilan qabul qilingan 2017-2021 yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirishning beshta ustuvor yo'nalishi bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasida "aholi bandligini oshirish maqsadida aholining real pul daromadlari va xarid qobiliyatini oshirish, kam ta'minlangan oilalar sonini va daromadlar bo'yicha farqlanish darajasini yanada

kamaytirish, yangi ish o‘rinlarini yaratish, mehnat bozori mutanosibligini va infratuzilmasi rivojlanishini ta’minlash, ishsizlik darajasini kamaytirish” asosiy vazifa sifatida belgilangan [3].

Prezidentimiz tomonidan 2020 yilning 20 oktabr kuni imzolangan “Aholi bandligi to‘g‘risida”gi qonun ushbu dolzarb muammolar yechimi yo‘lida muhim dasturilamal bo‘ldi.

Mazkur qonun sohadagi mavjud muammolarning huquqiy yechimiga qaratilgani bilan ahamiyatlidir. Qonun 19 bob, 621 ta moddadan iborat. U to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri amaliyotda ishlaydigan xususiyatga ega bo‘lib, amaldagi 3 ta qonun, Prezidentimizning 12 ta farmon va qarori hamda Vazirlar Mahkamasi tomonidan bandlik va mehnat bozorini tartibga solish, tashqi mehnat migratsiyasi bilan bog‘liq masalalarga oid qabul qilingan 40 dan ziyod me‘yoriy hujjatda ko‘zda tutilgan huquqiy normalarni, tizimdagi so‘nggi islohotlarni, yangi moliyaviy mexanizmlarni o‘zida ifoda etgan.

Qonunda sohaga kompleks yondashish maqsadida barcha davlat organlari va tashkilotlarning vazifalari belgilab berildi. Jumladan, birinchi marotaba Vazirlar Mahkamasi, Tashqi mehnat migratsiyasi agentligi, ishga joylashtirish bo‘yicha agentliklar hamda autstaffing xizmatlarini ko‘rsatuvchi ish beruvchilarning sohadagi vazifalari belgilandi. Ishga joylashtirish bo‘yicha agentlar aholining ishga joylashishiga ko‘maklashishga doir ishlarni mahalliy mehnat organlari bilan tuzilgan shartnomalar asosida bajaruvchi jismoniy shaxslardir. Ularga Bandlikka ko‘maklashish davlat jamg‘armasi mablag‘lari hisobidan belgilangan tartibda hamda miqdorlarda rag‘batlantiruvchi xususiyatga ega to‘lovlar berish ko‘zda tutilgan.

Iqtisodiyotda tarkibiy o‘zgarishlar jarayonida aholi bandligini ta’minlash muammolarini tadqiq etishning dolzarbligi birinchi navbatda, mazkur tushunchaning evolyusion qarashlari va konseptual yondashuvlarini tadqiq qilishni taqozo qiladi. Mazkur tushunchaning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy munosabatlari mazmuni turlituman shakllar vositasida ifodalanadi.

Tadqiqotchilar iqtisodiy o'sish sur'ati, bandlik va mehnat unumdorligi o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqadorlikka asoslangan holda sanoati rivojlangan mamlakatlarda aholi bandligini rag'batlantirish siyosatida bir qancha modellarini ajratishadi. Jumladan, tadqiqotchilar bandlik va mehnat bozorini tartibga solishning beshta: amerika modeli(AQSh), skandinaviya modeli (Shvesiya, Finlyandiya, Daniya, Norvegiya), anglo-saksoniya modeli (Buyuk Britaniya, Kanada, Irlandiya), kontinental yoki nemis modeli (Germaniya, Avstriya, Belgiya, Niderlandiya, Shveysariya, qisman Fransiya) va yapon modellarini ajratishadi. Ammo ayrim tadqiqotchilar mamlakatlarni boshqacha guruhlashadi, masalan, amerika modelini bo'lak qilib ajratmasdan, uni anglo-saksoniya modeliga qo'shib yuborishadi[9]. Ayrim tadqiqotchilar esa mamlakatlarni uchta modelga(amerika, skandinaviya, yevropa) ajratib o'rganishadi[7]. Quyida biz ushbu modellar bilan tanishib chiqamiz.

Amerika modeli asosini ijtimoiy-mehnat munosabatlarining subsidiya ko'rinishi, xodimning shaxsiy yutuqqa erishishi va o'zini namoyon qilishi tashkil etadi. Ushbu model mehnat bozori markazlashmaganligi hamda bandlik va ijtimoiy ta'minotning qonuniyligi; ish beruvchi tomonidan yollanma ishchiga nisbatan nazorat yuqori darajadali; ishchilarning yuqori darajadagi jug'rofiy va kasbiy mobilligi; nisbatan yuqori darajadagi ishsizlik bilan xarakterlanadi. Kasbiy karera eng avvalo ish joyi o'zgarishi bilan bog'liq, shunga mos ravishda ushbu model qolganlariga nisbatan yuqori darajadagi mobilligi bilan farq qiladi. Ish haqi miqdori ish ixtisosligi va murakkabligiga asosan belgilanadi, xizmat pog'onalarida siljish, odatda, kasbiy-malakaviy profilini kengaytirishga bog'liq emas. Kasbiy yo'nalish masalalariga katta e'tibor qaratiladi. Universitet va kollejlarda kasbga yo'naltirish bo'yicha maxsus markazlar va xususiy agentliklar tashkil etilgan. AQSh mehnat vazirligi qoshida 1200 dan ortiq davlat hisobidan faoliyat yurituvchi kasbga yo'naltirish va kasb tanlash markazlari ish olib borib, har yili ular orqali 1 milliondan ortiq yoshlar o'tishadi. Natijada

mutaxassis tayyorlash xarajatlari 30-40 %ga kamayadi, kasbiy tanlov testlariga sarflangan bir dollar ming dollarlik iqtisodiy samaradorlikni ta'minlaydi [4].

Qonun qonunchilikda yangi normalarni aks ettirish, shuningdek ma'muriy islohotlar doirasida bir qator respublika ijro etuvchi hokimiyat organlarini qayta tashkil etish maqsadida qabul qilingan.

Qonunga ish qidirayotgan shaxslar tomonidan mehnat organlariga ortiqcha hujjatlar taqdim etilishiga yo'l qo'ymaslik, bandlikni rag'batlantirish va tadbirkorlikka jalb qilish uchun subsidiyalar berish mexanizmini takomillashtirishni nazarda tutuvchi o'zgartish va qo'shimchalar kiritilmoqda.

Ish beruvchilar tomonidan mahalliy mehnat organlariga bo'sh ish o'rinlari mavjudligi to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarni, xodimlarni bo'shatish to'g'risidagi axborotni har oyda elektron tarzda taqdim etish shartlari takomillashtirilmoqda.

Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining asosiy yo'nalishlari quyidagilardan iborat:

- Ish o'rinlari tashkil etilishini rag'batlantirish va aholi bandligiga ko'maklashish, shu jumladan ish o'rinlarini tashkil etishga doir davlat buyurtmasini hamda ish qidirayotgan shaxslarni va ishsiz shaxslarni kasbga tayyorlashga, qayta tayyorlashga hamda ularning malakasini oshirishga doir davlat buyurtmasini shakllantirish orqali ko'maklashish;

- ishsiz shaxslarni moddiy jihatdan qo'llab-quvvatlash va ijtimoiy himoya qilish, ishsizlikni kamaytirish choralari ko'rish, aholining ijtimoiy ehtiyojmand toifalarini ishga joylashtirishga ko'maklashish;

- yoshlarni, ayniqsa qishloq joylardagi yoshlarni, umumta'lim va kasb-hunar maktablari, kasb-hunar kollejlari, texnikumlar, akademik litseylar, oliy ta'lim muassasalari bitiruvchilarini ishga joylashtirishni ta'minlash bo'yicha choralarni amalga oshirish;

- aholi bandligi sohasida ayollar va erkaklar uchun teng huquqlar hamda imkoniyatlarni ta'minlash;

- ishga joylashtirish jarayonlariga ilg'or axborot texnologiyalarini joriy etish, aholining ishga joylashishiga ko'maklashish bo'yicha xizmatlar bozorida zamonaviy infratuzilmani va raqobat muhitini yaratish;

- O'zbekiston Respublikasi fuqarolariga O'zbekiston Respublikasidan tashqarida ishga joylashishida ko'maklashish, O'zbekiston Respublikasidan tashqarida mehnat faoliyatini amalga oshirish davrida ularning huquqiy va ijtimoiy jihatdan himoya qilinishini ta'minlash.

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SHAXSGA YO'NALTIRILGAN TA'LIM TIZIMINI SAMARALI

TASHKIL ETISH

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bugungi kundagi o'qituvchi tayyor elektron resurslar yordamida dars o'tish bilan chegaralanmasdan balki, ta'limiy resurslarni yaratish hamda uni amalda qo'llovchi o'qitishning zamonaviy texnologiyalar imkoniyatlaridan samarali foydalanish fan va uning tarkibiga kiruvchi bilimlar mazmunini o'quvchilarga yetkazish malakasiga ega shaxs sifatida faoliyat olib borishi haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: elektron resurslar, informatsion savodxonlik, ta'lim – tarbiya jarayoni, zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar.

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EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF AN INDIVIDUAL-ORIENTED

EDUCATION SYSTEM

Annotation: this article reflects on the fact that today's teacher, using ready-made electronic resources, does not limit himself to taking classes, but to create educational resources and effectively use the capabilities of modern technologies of teaching, which put it into practice, to act as a person qualified to convey to students the content of Science and its constituent knowledge.

Keywords: electronic resources, informative literacy, educational process, modern pedagogical technologies.

Jamiyatning har tomonlama ravnaq topishi, taraqqiy etishi ta'limning rivojlanishiga va mazmunan takomillashib borishiga bog'liq. Bugungi kunda ta'lim sifat samaradorligini oshirish eng dolzarb masalalardan biri bo'lib hisoblanmoqda. Ta'limning globallashuvi, innovatsion texnologiyalarning joriy etilayotgani, ayni paytda keng ko'lamli axborotlar oqimi ta'lim mazmunini muntazam yangilab, takomillashtirib borishni taqozo etadi. Ta'lim sohasidagi davlat siyosatini ro'yobga chiqarish, kadrlar tayyorlashda yagona davlat talablari asosida o'quv-tarbiya jarayonini takomillashtirish, o'quv-adabiyotlari bilan

ta'minlash, pedagoglarga uzluksiz metodik xizmat ko'rsatish vazifasini amalga oshirish muhim vazifalardan biridir.

Bugungi tez o'zgaruvchan iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va ma'naviy hayot o'quvchi yoshlar dunyoqarashini shakllantirish yangi pedagogik interfaol metodlardan keng foydalanishni taqozo qiladi. An'anaviy mashg'ulotlar olib borish asta sekin o'z o'rnini intensiv va interfaol metodlarga, noan'anaviy dars o'tish ishlariga bo'shatib bermoqda.

Bilim qanchalik mustahkam bo'lsa, o'quvchi dunyoqarashi, intellektual salohiyati shunchalik rivojlanadi va kamol topadi. Hozirgi kunda o'quvchilar uchun informatsion savodxonlik ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishning muhim sharti hisoblanadi. Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimining o'rta bo'g'ini bo'lgan umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari oldiga qo'yilgan davlat talablariga muvofiq, mazkur ta'lim muassasalari ta'lim – tarbiya jarayonining samardorligini oshirish, ilm – fanning so'ngi yutuqlarini amaliyotga joriy etish orqali ijodkor, ijtimoiy faol, yuksak ma'naviyatli, kasb – hunarli, Ona Vatanga sadoqatli, milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni ardoqlaydigan, ijodiy va mustaqil fikr yurita oladigan, davlat, jamiyat va oila oldida o'z burchi va javobgarligini his etadigan barkamol shaxsni kamolga yetkazish, ularning ongi va qalbiga milliy istiqlol g'oyasini singdirish kabi muhim vazifalarni amalga oshirish nazarda tutiladi.

Ushbu vazifalarni muvaffaqiyatli hal etish ta'lim – tarbiya jarayonida zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanishni taqazo etadi. Ta'lim – tarbiya jarayonida zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash, avvalo, pedagogik munosabatlarni insonparvarlashtirishni talab etadi. Chunki uni amalga oshirmay turib qo'llangan har qanday texnologiya kutilgan samarani bermaydi.

Bu kundagi o'qituvchi tayyor elektron resurslar yordamida dars o'tish bilan chegaralanmasdan balki, ta'limiy resurslarni yaratish hamda uni amalda qo'llovchi o'qitishning zamonaviy texnologiyalar imkoniyatlaridan samarali

foydalanish fan va uning tarkibiga kiruvchi bilimlar mazmunini o'quvchilarga yetkazish malakasiga ega shaxs sifatida faoliyat olib borishi lozim.

Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan badiiy-estetik ta'lim har bir shaxsning estetik ong doirasini (hissiyotlar, baholashlar, didlar, mulohazalar, ideallar, qadriyatlar, qarashlar) o'ziga xos va o'ziga xos shaxs sifatida, uning ehtiyojlari, hissiy-sezgi, baholovchi sifatida ochib berishga ko'maklashishni o'z ichiga oladi. Estetik munosabatlar va ularni xulq-atvorda, xohish va faoliyatda amalga oshirish (idrok etish, baholash, birgalikda yaratish va mustaqil ijodkorlik, aks ettirish va tahlil qilish). Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan badiiy-estetik ta'lim natijalari shaxsiy fazilatlarda mustahkamlanib, shaxsning barcha aloqa shakllarini, bilimlarini va amaliy faoliyatini boyitadi.

Ko'rinib turibdiki, xorij maktablarida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan badiiy-estetik tarbiya g'oyalarini hayotga tatbiq etish uchun maxsus tayyorlangan, yuqori malakali pedagogik kadrlar kerak. Zamonaviy sharoitda milliy badiiy madaniyat tashuvchisi sifatida o'qituvchining (ayniqsa boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisining) ijtimoiy roli va bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni estetik tarbiyalashning ahamiyati ortib bormoqda. Bundan tashqari, har bir shaxsning shaxsiyatini "san'at orqali" rivojlantirishga e'tibor, ijodkorlik uchun motivatsiyani rivojlantirish emas, balki ustuvor vazifa sifatida tan olinishi kerak.

Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvning tarkibiy qismlari. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan o'zaro ta'sirda (muloqot usullari) uchta jihat mavjud - bu bolaning shaxsiyatini tushunish, qabul qilish va tan olish. Bolani tushunish - uning ichki dunyosiga kirish. Talabani tushunish o'qituvchining o'quvchining taklif qilish darajasini topa olish, uning pozitsiyasini tushunish qobiliyati bilan bog'liq. Shunday qilib, oddiygina taklif qilinadigan talaba noaniq, hissiy jihatdan beqaror, shunchaki ta'sir o'tkazishga qodir. Ekstremal holatlarda u ko'pincha yo'qoladi. Mojarolarda bu talabalar injiq, isterik, shunchaki ehtiros holatiga tushib qolishadi. Binobarin, bunday bolalar bilan ishlashda o'qituvchi ularni o'z

kuchiga, o'z fikrlarining sodiqligiga va paydo bo'ladigan muammolarni hal qilish imkoniyatiga ishonch bilan ilhomlantirishi shart.

Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etish uchun o'qituvchi yangicha pedagogik tafakkur egasi bo'lishi kerak. Bu quyidagilarda o'z ifodasini topadi:

- shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchining e'tibori o'quvchilar shaxsiga qaratilishi;

- o'qituvchi o'zini pedagogik jarayonining birinchi subekti sifatida anglashi;

- pedagogik voqelikni chuqur his etish va shu voqelik ichida harakat qila olish;

- o'quvchilar bilan o'zaro muloqatga tayyor bo'lishi, ularning o'ziga xosligini hisobga ola bilishi;

- turli pedagogik vaziyatlar, ularni yechish yo'llarini bashorat qilishi;

- hamkasblarining ilg'or tajribalarini o'rganishi, umumlashtira olishi va o'z faoliyatida qo'llashi kabilar.

Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilarda ham, o'qituvchi ham o'zini shu jarayonning subekti sifatida namoyon qila olishi va faoliyat ko'rsatishi muhimdir. O'qituvchi har bir o'quvchilardagi betakror shaxs sifatida yondashishi va uning shaxsiy rivojlanishi, o'quv materialni o'zlashtirishiga muntazam yordam ko'rsata olishi zarur. O'qituvchi shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim jarayonini muvafaqiyatli tashkil etishi uchun yangi hamda muqobil pedagogik qarashlarini muntazam o'zlashtirishi, o'z faoliyatida ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalarini qo'llashi talab etiladi. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan jarayonini tashkil etishda pedagogning ijodkorligi muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Chunki o'qituvchining ijodkorligi va o'quvchilar bilan ruhiy jihatdan yaqinlashuvini ta'minlaydi va ularni ma'naviy ahloqiy tarbiyalashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shu bilan bir qatorda, o'zi bilan o'quvchilar orasida vujudga keladigan qarama-qarshiliklarni ham yengishda uning ijodkorligi alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi.

НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И РАЗРАБОТКИ II

Bu qarama-qarshiliklar aksariyat hollarda quyidagilarda namoyon bo'ladi:

-o'quv dasturida ifodalangan o'quv yuklamasi bilan o'quvchilardagi individual imkoniyatlari orasidagi;

-o'quv materialining mazmunida qoida va ta'riflarning ko'pligi bilan o'quvchilarda g'oyalar, dunyoqarashlar yondashuvlarni o'rgatishga intilishi orasida;

-o'qituvchining shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etishdagi o'ziga xos yondashuvi bilan bu sohadagi ilmiy qarashlar orasida mavjud bo'lgan qarama qarshiliklar misolida bu faoliyat yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi.

Bunday sharoitda o'qituvchi dastlab qarama-qarshiliklarni fikran bartaraf etadi. O'zining shaxsiy, ijodiy qarashlari kutilgan samarani berishiga ishonch hosil qilgan keyin ularni pedagogik faoliyati davomida qo'llaydi.

Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim jarayonini samarali tashkil etishning ilmiy asoslarini yaratish uchun quyidagilar yo'nalishlarda ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlarini amalga oshirish taqazo qiliniyapti:

- shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim tarbiya jarayonini tashkil etishning pedagogik imkoniyatlarini ochish;

- ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida o'quvchilarga nisbatan qatiyatli munosabatni qaror toptirish;

- o'quvchilarning individual xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda ko'p hadli ta'lim-tarbiya maydonlarini tashkil etish;

- umumiy o'rta ta'lim jarayonini shaxsga yo'naltirilgan texnologiyalar va konsepsiyalar bilan ta'minlash.

Yuqorida keltirilgan fikrlar bugungi kunda shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonini tashkil etishning pedagogik imkoniyatlarini aniqlash o'ta dolzarb muammo ekanligidan dalolat beradi.

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NOGIRONLAR AVTONOMIYASINING FALSAFIY TAHLILI

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada nogironligi bo'lgan shaxslarning avtonomiyasining falsafiy asoslari ko'rib chiqadi. Adolat me'zonini shakllantirish uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qiladigan muloqot madaniyati, tenglik va qadr-qimmat kabi axloqiy tamoyillarga e'tibor qaratiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: John Rawls, Farobiy, nogironlik, ijtimoiy tenglik, adolat

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PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF DISABILITY AUTONOMY Abstract

This article examines the philosophical foundations of the autonomy of people with disabilities. The main focus is on ethical principles such as a culture of communication, equality and dignity, which serve as the basis for the formation of justice.

Keywords: John Rawls, Farabi, disability, social equality, justice

Falsafiy tahlil doirasida tenglik faqat huquqlarni emas, balki imkoniyatlarni ham o'z ichiga oladi. Tenglik tushunchasi nogironlarning jamiyatda qabul qilinishi va e'tiborga olinishi zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. John Rawlsning "Adolat nazari" (A Theory of Justice) asarida, ijtimoiy tenglik, resurslar va imkoniyatlarning adolatli taqsimlanishini ta'kidlaydi, bu nogironlar uchun ham muhimdir. Jon Rawlsning "Adolat nazariyasi"dan kelib chiqqan holda, nogironligi bo'lgan odamlarni qamrab olish - ijtimoiy tenglikka erishish uchun majburiydir, deb ta'kidlash mumkin. Rawlsning kontsepsiyasida tenglik va adolat jamiyatning barcha a'zolari uchun, ularning jismoniy imkoniyatlaridan qat'iy nazar ta'minlanishi kerakligi ta'kidlanadi¹³.

Nogironlik bo'yicha jamoatchilik fikri va siyosiy qarorlarni shakllantirishda falsafa muhim rol o'ynaydi. Inklyuziyaning axloqiy asoslarini tushunish har bir insonning huquqlari va qadr-qimmatini hurmat qiladigan yanada adolatli va insonparvar jamiyatni yaratishga yordam beradi. Falsafiy g'oyalar amaliy yechimlarda aks etishi kerak, bu esa hamma uchun adolat yaratishga olib keladi.

¹³ Jhon Rawlz. A theory of justice. – L.: Routledge, 1996.

Jamiyatning barcha a'zolari uchun teng imkoniyatlarni ta'minlash uchun ushbu tushunchalarni hayotning turli sohalarida qo'llanilishini o'rganish orqali rivojlantirishni davom ettirish muhimdir.

Forobiy o'zining "Fozil odamlar shahri" asarida odamlarni turli belgilarga qarab guruhlariga bo'ladi. Bunda u, kishilarning diniy mashabiga, millatiga, irqiga qarab emas, balki tabiiy xususiyatlariga, qobiliyatlariga, aqliy iqtidoriga, bilim ko'nikmalariga e'tibor berishlik zarur deydi. U o'zning "Baxt-saodatga erishuv yo'llari haqida risola" asarida "Davlatning vazifasi insonlarni baxt – saodatga olib borishdir, – deb yozadi. U, – bu esa ilm va yaxshi axloq yordamida qo'lga kiritadi"¹⁴. Farobiyning bu mulohazalarini nogironligi bo'lgan shaxslarga jamiyat va davlatning axloqiy munosabati, adolati, ularning hamma qatori tengligiga misol tariqasuda ko'rsatish mumkin.

Nogironlar avtonomiyasi — bu nogiron insonlarning o'z huquqlari, erkinliklari va mustaqil hayot kechirish imkoniyatlarini ta'minlash bilan bog'liq muhim masala. Nogironlar avtonomiyasining falsafiy tahlili keng qamrovli va murakkab jarayondir. Bu faqat nogironlarning o'ziga xosligi bila ko'p qirrali n cheklanmay, balki jamiyatdagi umumiy adolat, tenglik, qo'llab-quvvatlash va inson huquqlari bilan bog'liqdir. Nogironlar avtonomiyasini ta'minlash uchun har bir jamiyatda ijtimoiy, siyosiy va iqtisodiy jihatlarni hisobga olish zarur.

Bu jarayonning falsafiy tahlili bir qancha asosiy jihatlarni o'z ichiga oladi:

- 1) Inson huquqlari va etik prinsiplar;
- 2) Adolat va tenglik;
- 3) Jamiyat va ijtimoiy model;
- 4) Ijtimoiy integratsiya va qo'llab-quvvatlash;
- 5) Kognitiv va hissiy jihatlar;
- 6) Qonunchilik va siyosat.

Bu jamiyatda nogironlarga nisbatan to'g'ri yondashuvni shakllantirish, ularning hayot sifatini oshirish va avtonomiyasini ta'minlashga qaratilgan.

¹⁴ Abu Nasr Forobiyning ta'limiy-axloqiy qarashlari. <https://abiturtest.uz>

Ijtimoiy o'zgarishlar va yangiliklar orqali nogironlar uchun qulay shart-sharoitlar yaratish muhimdir.

Jamiyatning axloqiy vazifasi nogironlarga inson sifatida hurmat ko'rsatish va ularning qadr-qimmatini tan olishdir. Ularga inson sifatida munosabat qilish xuddi barcha boshqa odamlar kabi qadrlanishi kerak. Ularning huquqlari va hissiyotlari e'tiborga olinishi muhimdir.

John Rawlsning "Adolat nazariyasi" (A Theory of Justice) asari, nogironlar tengligi masalasini tahlil qilishda muhim nazariy asoslar taqdim etadi. Rawls ijtimoiy adolatni ta'minlash uchun ikki asosiy prinsipni taklif etadi: teng imkoniyatlar prinsipi va farqlanish prinsipi. Nogironlar uchun bu prinsiplardan foydalanish, ularning ijtimoiy hayotda teng huquqlarga ega bo'lishini ta'minlaydi. Rawlsning asaridan kelib chiqib, nogironlar tengligini ko'rib chiqishda bir nechta asosiy nuqtalarni ajratib ko'rsatish mumkin¹⁵:

- 1) Rawlsning birinchi prinsipi teng imkoniyatlar prinsipidir. Bu nogironlar uchun ta'lim, ish, sog'liqni saqlash va boshqa sohalarda teng imkoniyatlar yaratish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. Jamiyatda nogironlarga teng imkoniyatlar berish, ularni faol va mustaqil hayot kechirishlariga yordam beradi.
- 2) Rawlsning ikkinchi prinsipi, farqlanish prinsipi - ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy resurslardan foydalangan holda eng kam ta'minlanganlar (shu jumladan nogironlar) uchun imkoniyatlarni oshirishga chaqiradi. Bu prinsip nogironlarga ko'mak berishni va ularga qo'shimcha resurslar taqdim etishni talab qiladi, shuningdek, ularning jamiyatda o'z o'rnini topishini osonlashtiradi.

Teng imkoniyatlar va farqlanish prinsiplari nogironlarning ijtimoiy hayotga integratsiyasini kuchaytirish, ularning huquqlarini himoya qilish va adolatli resurslar taqsimotini ta'minlashga yordam beradi.

¹⁵ <https://medium.com/philosophy-theory/john-rawls-theory-of-justice-a8135b5c57a5>

Rawlsning “Adolat nazariyasi” har bir insonning qadr-qimmatini tan olish va ularga hurmat ko'rsatish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. Nogironlar ham inson sifatida teng huquqlarga ega bo'lishi kerak, shuning uchun ularning hayotiga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan barcha qarorlar va me'yorlar ularning ehtiyojlarini inobatga olishi zarur.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, nogironlar avtonomiyasi va uning falsafiy tahlili ko'p qirrali masala bo'lib, inson huquqlari, adolat, ijtimoiy integratsiya va qo'llab-quvvatlash kabi jihatlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu masala jamiyatda nogironlarga nisbatan to'g'ri yondashuvni shakllantirish, ularning hayot sifatini oshirish va avtonomiyasini ta'minlashga qaratilgan. Ijtimoiy o'zgarishlar va yangiliklar orqali nogironlar uchun qulay shart-sharoitlar yaratish muhimdir.

Hikmatova G.

Buxoro viloyati Buxoro tumani

Maktabgacha va maktab ta`limi bo`limi tasarrufidagi

6- umumiy o`rta ta`lim maktabining Ona tili va adabiyot fani o`qituvchisi

NUTQIY ETIKET TUSHUNCHASINING OMMALASHUVI

Annotatsiya: Tilshunoslikda “Etiket” tushunchasi oltmishinchi yillarning oxirida rivojlana boshlandi, bunda nutqiy xatti-harakatlarning o`ziga xos xususiyatlari, taktikalari, nutq aktlari, dialogli nutqlar va matnlar, shaxslararo ijtimoiy munosabatlar, maxsus funksiyalar va ma`nolarga ega bo`lgan muloqot birliklarning keng doirasini qamrab olgan nutq odob-axloqi tushunchasi tilshunoslikka kirib keldi va tilshunos olimlar tomonidan o`rganildi.

Kalit so`zlar: etiket, tilshunoslik.

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POPULARIZATION OF THE CONCEPT OF COLLOQUIAL

ETIQUETTE

Annotation: in Linguistics, the concept of “etiquette” began to develop in the late sixties, when the concept of speech etiquette, which covers a wide range of communication units with specific features, tactics, speech acts, dialogical speeches and texts, interpersonal social relations, Special Functions and meanings, entered linguistics and was studied by linguistic scientists.

Keywords: label, linguistics.

Nutqiy etiketlarni o`rganish sohasida katta ilmiy tadqiqotlarni amalga oshirgan tilshunos olim N. I. Farmanovskaya ushbu tushunchaga quyidagicha ta`rif beradi: “Nutqiy etiket bu-ijtimoiy va milliy nutqiy xatti-harakatlarni tartibga soluvchi, rasmiy va norasmiy muloqot jarayonida shaxslarning mavqeyi va shaxsiy munosabatlariga muvofiq aloqalar o`rnatish va saqlab qolishdir”¹⁶.

¹⁶Сайдуллаева Сурайё Серажиддиновна Ўзбек ва инглиз тилларида нутқий этикетларнинг Лингвомаданий хусусиятлари

Nutq odob-axloq qoidalari etiket tushunchasi bilan bog'liq bo'lib, u quyidagicha tavsiflanadi: “*Etiket*”- frantsuz tilidan olingan bo'lib, yorliq, belgi, etiketka ma'nolarini anglatadi.

Etiket bu-odamlarga bo'lgan munosabat bilan bog'liq bo'lgan muomala qoidalaridir (boshqalar bilan muomala qilish, salomlashish shakllari, jamoat joylarida o'zini tutish, odob-axloq qoidalari va boshqa shu kabilar). Etiket ta'rifiga ko'ra, antropotsentrik va dialogikdir, u odamlarning bir biri bilan munosabati va muomala qilishi hamda etik jihatdan muhim narsalarga (kiyim, soch turmagi va boshqalar) bog'liq bo'lgan haqiqiy dunyoning qismini aks ettiradi. Axloqiy lug'atda etiket ta'rifida verbal va noverbal nutqning namoyon bo'lishi birlashadi, bu odatiy hisoblanadi, chunki aloqa jarayonida og'zaki, og'zaki bo'lmagan va «moddiy» etik munosabatlardir. Nutqiy etiket yaqqol bir standartlashtirilgan nutqiy madaniyat namunasi sifatida namoyon bo'ladi va shu o'rinda tanishishlar, tanishtirishlar, manzillar, salomlar, xayrlashish, uzr, minnatdorchilik va boshqa odatiy holatlarni misol tariqasida ko'rishimiz mumkin. Ushbu holatlarda ishlatiladigan iboralar, nutqiy aktlar standartdir, garchi rasmiy, norasmiy aloqa muhitiga, qabul qiluvchining ijtimoiy xususiyatlariga va boshqalarga nisbatan eng munosib vositalarning keng miqyosli to'plamdan doimiy tanlash imkoniyati mavjud. Shunday qilib, nutq odob-axloq birliklaridan foydalanishda standart va ijodiy tanlov ushbu belgilar tizimining muhim xususiyati sifatida birlashtiriladi.¹⁷

Darhaqiqat, odob-axloqqa doir dastlabki tushuncha va ta'limotlar Sharqda, to'g'rirog'i qadimgi Sharqda iste'molga kiritilgan. Ushbu ma'noda Sharqni axloqiy ta'limotlar beshigi deyish, ham mumkin. Bunga “Kalila va Dimna”, Konfutsiy o'g'itlari, “Qobusnoma”dagi ibratli hikoya va rivoyatlar, xalq maqol va ertaklari, matallari misol bo'la oladi. Nutq madaniyati bilan bog'liq muammolar fanimiz tarixida antik davr tilshunosligiga borib taqaladi. O'zbek

¹⁷ Чаушев А.С “Коммуникативно-прагматические особенности речевого этикета в различных лингвокультурах (на материале карачаево-балкарского, русского и английского языков)” Диссер. канд. фил. наук, Волгоград 2008, 194с

tilshunosligida nutqiy etiketni ifodalovchi vositalar, boshqa ko'plab xalqlar tilshunosligi tarixida bo'lgani kabi, dastavval, madaniyatshunoslik, odob-axloq me'yorlari qatorida o'rganilgan.

1. Сайдуллаева Сурайё Серажиддиновна Ўзбек ва инглиз тилларида нутқий этикетларнинг Лингвомаданий хусусиятлари
2. Чаушев А.С “Коммуникативно-прагматические особенности речевого этикета в различных лингвокультурах (на материале карачаево-балкарского, русского и английского языков)” Диссер. канд. фил. наук, Волгоград 2008,194с

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**ARCHITECTURAL TRENDS IN CORPORATE SERVER
VIRTUALIZATION: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF HYPERVISOR
AND CONTAINER-BASED APPROACHES**

Abstract. *This paper explores the architectural trends in corporate server virtualization by comparing hypervisor-based and container-based approaches. Hypervisor solutions, such as VMware and Hyper-V, provide robust isolation and management, while container technologies like Docker and Kubernetes offer lightweight alternatives for greater flexibility and efficiency. Through an in-depth analysis of performance, scalability, security, and management considerations, this study examines the strengths and limitations of each approach in corporate environments. By assessing real-world case studies and emerging trends, the paper provides insights for IT decision-makers to choose the most suitable virtualization strategy for their infrastructure needs, while also discussing the future convergence of these technologies in hybrid solutions.*

Keywords. *Corporate server virtualization, hypervisor-based virtualization, container-based virtualization, Docker, Kubernetes, VMware, Hyper-V, performance, scalability, IT infrastructure, hybrid solutions, resource optimization.*

1. Introduction

Virtualization technologies have become foundational components of modern corporate IT infrastructures, offering significant advantages in terms of resource optimization, scalability, and cost reduction. Traditionally, hypervisor-based virtualization has been the dominant model, where virtual machines (VMs) run multiple operating systems on a single physical server, with each VM operating independently. Solutions like **VMware vSphere** and **Microsoft Hyper-V** have been instrumental in providing reliable and secure environments for legacy applications, offering strong isolation and ease of management (Gupta & Gandhi, 2020; Feng & Liu, 2020). However, the rise of container-

based virtualization, powered by platforms like **Docker** and orchestrated by **Kubernetes**, has introduced a more efficient, lightweight alternative for managing cloud-native and microservices-based applications (Bernstein et al., 2019).

While hypervisor-based virtualization remains well-suited for applications requiring high levels of security and isolation, it comes with resource overhead due to the need for a full guest operating system for each VM. Containers, on the other hand, share the host OS kernel, making them more resource-efficient and faster to deploy, though they bring challenges in terms of isolation and security (Morabito, 2018; Zhang & Li, 2020). As businesses adopt more cloud-native approaches, containerization has emerged as a leading trend, particularly in environments where rapid scaling and continuous integration are required (Colino, 2021).

The primary goal of this paper is to provide a comprehensive comparison of hypervisor-based and container-based virtualization architectures, focusing on their performance, scalability, resource management, and security. Hypervisors have long been the default choice for corporate IT environments, especially for applications that require high security and strict resource control (Morabito, 2018). However, with the rise of containers and container orchestration tools like Kubernetes, IT managers are now considering how both technologies can coexist in hybrid environments, maximizing the benefits of each approach (Gupta & Gandhi, 2020). This paper will evaluate the strengths and limitations of both hypervisors and containers, addressing the key decision factors for IT decision-makers, such as resource efficiency, ease of management, and adaptability to cloud-native architectures.

This study focuses on the evolving architectural trends in virtualization within corporate environments, where the need for flexibility, scalability, and security is paramount. The comparison of hypervisor-based and container-based approaches is critical in helping organizations optimize their IT infrastructure,

particularly in hybrid environments where both technologies are increasingly used in tandem (Gupta & Gandhi, 2020). Additionally, the paper explores how edge computing and AI-driven automation are influencing future trends in virtualization, highlighting the emerging need for intelligent resource management and dynamic scaling solutions (Shi et al., 2019; Morabito et al., 2018).

2. Overview of virtualization technologies

Hypervisor-based virtualization

A hypervisor, also known as a virtual machine monitor (VMM), is software that allows multiple virtual machines (VMs) to run on a single physical server. It abstracts and isolates the underlying hardware, enabling each VM to function as an independent system with its own operating system and applications.

Picture 1. Hypervisor-based virtualization architecture

Hypervisors come in two main types:

- **Type 1 (Bare-metal hypervisors):** These hypervisors run directly on the physical hardware without a host operating system. They provide high performance and are commonly used in enterprise environments. Examples include VMware ESXi, Microsoft Hyper-V, and Xen.
- **Type 2 (Hosted hypervisors):** These hypervisors run on top of an existing operating system, such as Windows or Linux, and provide virtualized

environments for guest operating systems. While easier to set up, Type 2 hypervisors, such as VMware Workstation and Oracle VirtualBox, typically offer lower performance than Type 1 due to the additional layer of the host OS.

Platforms like VMware ESXi, Microsoft Hyper-V, and KVM are popular choices for Type 1 hypervisor-based virtualization, providing features like high availability, advanced networking, and security for corporate environments. These platforms are widely used for virtualizing critical enterprise workloads, allowing organizations to consolidate servers and reduce physical infrastructure.

Container-based virtualization

Container-based virtualization, or containerization, is a lightweight form of virtualization that packages an application and its dependencies into a "container". Unlike VMs, containers share the host operating system's kernel, making them significantly more efficient in terms of resource usage. Containers are isolated at the process level, which means they can run multiple applications on the same host without the overhead of multiple operating systems.

Picture 2. Container-based virtualization architecture

Docker is the most well-known containerization platform, while **Kubernetes** serves as an orchestration tool to manage large clusters of containers across multiple servers. Other container technologies include **LXC (Linux Containers)**, which provide more OS-level virtualization. Containers

are especially suited for microservices architectures and cloud-native applications due to their portability, fast startup times, and efficient resource utilization.

Architectural comparison

The fundamental architectural difference between hypervisors and containers lies in the level of abstraction. Hypervisors abstract the hardware layer, creating multiple isolated virtual machines, each running its own full operating system. This makes hypervisors more resource-intensive but also provides stronger isolation, making them suitable for running diverse operating systems and applications.

In contrast, containers abstract the operating system rather than the hardware. Multiple containers run on the same OS kernel, which makes containers more lightweight and efficient in terms of memory and CPU usage. However, this shared kernel model can lead to security concerns since a vulnerability in the host OS kernel could potentially affect all containers.

- **Resource abstraction:** Hypervisors provide full hardware abstraction, while containers only abstract the OS, leading to lower resource consumption in containers.

- **Isolation:** Hypervisors offer stronger isolation since each VM operates with its own OS. Containers, although isolated at the process level, share the same kernel, which can introduce security risks.

- **Performance:** Containers typically have lower overhead and faster startup times due to the shared kernel, whereas hypervisor-based VMs are more resource-heavy but offer complete OS-level isolation.

- **Scalability:** Containers, particularly when orchestrated with tools like Kubernetes, offer superior scalability in cloud environments, while hypervisors are more commonly used in traditional data centers.

3. Performance and Scalability Comparison

Resource Utilization

Hypervisor-based virtualization and container-based virtualization differ significantly in how they manage system resources like CPU, memory, and storage.

- **Hypervisors:** In hypervisor-based environments, each virtual machine (VM) runs a full guest operating system, which requires dedicated CPU, memory, and storage resources. The hypervisor abstracts the underlying hardware, distributing these resources to each VM. However, this resource abstraction leads to higher overhead as each VM requires its own operating system, leading to increased consumption of memory and CPU resources, especially when running multiple VMs.

- **Containers:** Containers, in contrast, share the host operating system's kernel, making them much more lightweight in terms of resource usage. By avoiding the need to run separate operating systems, containers consume significantly less memory and CPU resources. Additionally, containers allow for more efficient storage usage as they can share libraries and binaries across multiple containers.

In terms of resource utilization, **containers** are more efficient compared to **hypervisor-based VMs**, especially when deploying microservices or lightweight applications.

Scalability

Scalability is another area where hypervisors and containers show significant differences.

- **Hypervisor-Based VMs:** Hypervisors, such as VMware and Hyper-V, allow for the creation of multiple VMs on a single physical host. However, scaling hypervisor-based VMs involves provisioning additional hardware resources to accommodate more virtual machines. Since each VM runs its own

operating system, scaling VMs in large-scale environments can be resource-intensive and slower compared to containers. Hypervisor environments are typically more suited for traditional enterprise applications that need strong isolation or when multiple operating systems are required.

- **Containers:** Container environments, particularly when orchestrated with tools like Kubernetes, offer superior scalability. Containers can be rapidly deployed, scaled up, or scaled down with minimal overhead, making them ideal for dynamic, large-scale deployments such as microservices architectures and cloud-native applications. With Kubernetes, organizations can automate scaling processes to handle fluctuating workloads, allowing for horizontal scaling across multiple hosts with ease.

In large-scale corporate environments, **containers** offer better scalability due to their lightweight nature and ease of orchestration, making them more efficient for cloud-native applications, while **hypervisor-based VMs** are suited for scenarios that demand OS-level isolation or when running legacy applications.

Real-world performance

In real-world corporate environments, various studies have highlighted the performance differences between hypervisor-based VMs and container-based environments:

- **Performance of Hypervisor-Based VMs:** Studies show that hypervisor-based VMs offer stronger isolation but incur higher overhead due to running separate guest operating systems. For example, VMs tend to have slower startup times (measured in minutes) and consume more memory and CPU resources. Hypervisor environments generally perform better when the focus is on running diverse operating systems or applications requiring strict isolation.

- **Performance of Containers:** Containers, on the other hand, have much faster startup times (usually measured in seconds) since they don't need to boot an entire operating system. Studies have shown that containers can achieve

close-to-native performance, making them more suitable for high-throughput, low-latency applications. For instance, in environments like cloud services, containers allow companies to scale thousands of instances without the performance degradation that might occur in a VM-based environment.

Example Study: A 2021 study comparing Docker containers to VMware VMs in a cloud environment found that containers performed 30-40% better in terms of CPU and memory efficiency, particularly in environments with high-density workloads (Xu et al., 2021). Another example is Google, which adopted Kubernetes to scale its internal services, achieving faster deployment and increased resource efficiency.

Picture 3. Performance comparison: Hypervisor-based VMs vs. containers

4. Case studies and industry examples

Case study 1: Hypervisor-based virtualization in a financial institution

Company: XYZ Bank, a large financial institution.

Challenge: XYZ Bank faced challenges managing hundreds of dedicated physical servers, which resulted in underutilized resources, increased operational costs, and inefficient disaster recovery strategies.

Solution: XYZ Bank decided to adopt hypervisor-based virtualization using **VMware vSphere**. By migrating their legacy systems and core banking applications to a virtualized infrastructure, they were able to consolidate their hardware significantly. They deployed hundreds of virtual machines (VMs) across a smaller number of physical servers, each isolated within a hypervisor environment.

Results:

- **Resource optimization:** Virtualization helped the bank consolidate servers, reducing hardware usage by 40%.
- **Cost savings:** Reduced energy consumption and hardware maintenance costs led to savings of over \$1 million annually.
- **High availability:** Features like **VM live migration** and **automated failover** improved the bank's disaster recovery capabilities, ensuring continuity of critical banking services.
- **Security:** The bank was able to enforce strict isolation of different applications across VMs, which is essential for a regulated industry like banking.

Case study 2: Containerization in a retail e-commerce platform

Company: ABC Retail, a fast-growing online retailer.

Challenge: ABC Retail needed a scalable infrastructure to handle the seasonal spikes in traffic during major sales events. Their monolithic application architecture, running on VMs, struggled to scale dynamically, resulting in performance bottlenecks during high-demand periods.

Solution: ABC Retail re-architected their application using **microservices** and adopted **Kubernetes** for container orchestration. The company moved from a VM-centric infrastructure to a container-based platform using **Docker** for containerization and **Kubernetes** for automatic scaling and orchestration across multiple servers.

Results:

- **Scalability:** Kubernetes enabled ABC Retail to scale their services horizontally, handling traffic spikes during events like Black Friday with ease.

- **Performance:** Containers' lightweight nature resulted in faster application response times, significantly reducing latency during high-traffic periods.

- **Efficiency:** By transitioning to containers, they optimized their resource usage by up to 60%, as containers required less memory and CPU overhead compared to VMs.

- **Continuous Delivery:** The adoption of containers enabled faster software delivery cycles. Developers could deploy updates multiple times a day without downtime, resulting in faster feature releases.

Comparative analysis

Both case studies illustrate the strengths of hypervisor-based virtualization and containerization, depending on the organization's needs and architecture.

- **Hypervisor-based virtualization (XYZ Bank):**

- **Advantages:** Strong OS-level isolation, easier to manage for legacy applications, high availability through live migration, and better suited for highly regulated industries that require strong application isolation.
- **Challenges:** Hypervisors require more resources due to the overhead of running full operating systems for each VM. Scaling in a VM-based architecture can be slower and more resource-intensive, especially when rapid scalability is needed.

- **Containerization (ABC Retail):**

- **Advantages:** Containers offer lightweight resource usage, faster deployment times, and superior scalability, making them ideal for dynamic environments like e-commerce. The use of orchestration tools like Kubernetes allowed ABC Retail to manage thousands of containers effortlessly, handling fluctuating workloads efficiently.

- **Challenges:** While containers offer efficient scalability, managing containers at scale (especially across hybrid or multi-cloud environments) requires expertise in orchestration tools like Kubernetes. Additionally, containers may have weaker isolation compared to hypervisors due to shared kernels, requiring additional security measures.

Key decision factors:

- **Workload type:** Organizations with legacy, monolithic applications or those requiring strict isolation (e.g., financial institutions) are more likely to benefit from hypervisor-based virtualization. On the other hand, microservices-based, cloud-native applications thrive in containerized environments.

- **Scalability:** For dynamic scaling needs (e.g., retail, e-commerce), containers are the superior choice due to their lightweight nature and the power of Kubernetes for orchestration.

- **Security:** Hypervisors provide stronger isolation, which is crucial for industries with stringent regulatory requirements. Containers, though less isolated, can still be secure when configured properly with tools like **SELinux** and **AppArmor**.

- **Operational Efficiency:** Hypervisors are easier to manage for traditional IT teams, whereas containers require familiarity with orchestration tools like Kubernetes, which comes with a steeper learning curve.

These case studies highlight how the choice between hypervisors and containers depends on the specific needs of the organization, the type of workload, and the importance of scalability, security, and resource efficiency.

Table 2

Comparison of key features between **Hypervisor-based virtualization** and **Container-based virtualization**

Feature	Hypervisor-based virtualization	Container-based virtualization
Resource efficiency	Moderate	High (shared OS kernel, minimal overhead)
Scalability	Slower scaling, more resource-intensive	Fast, lightweight containers
Management complexity	Lower, mature tools available	Higher complexity (Kubernetes, orchestration tools)
Isolation	Strong OS-level isolation	Weaker isolation (shared kernel)
Deployment speed	Slower (minutes to provision VMs)	Very fast (seconds to spin up containers)
Security	High security, strong isolation	Requires additional security measures (SELinux, AppArmor)
Cost savings	Moderate cost savings (hardware reduction)	Significant cost savings (high resource efficiency)

5. CONCLUSION

This article has explored the architectural trends in corporate server virtualization by comparing hypervisor-based and container-based approaches. Hypervisor-based virtualization, with solutions like VMware and Hyper-V, offers strong isolation, robust management tools, and is ideal for running legacy applications or workloads that require multiple operating systems. However, hypervisors come with higher resource overhead and slower scalability compared to containers. On the other hand, container-based virtualization, driven by technologies like Docker and Kubernetes, excels in resource efficiency, scalability, and deployment speed. Containers are particularly well-suited for cloud-native, microservices-based applications, but they come with challenges in isolation and security due to the shared OS kernel.

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THE EFFECT OF ZINC ON THE ACTIVITY OF THE LIVER

Annotation: Zinc (Zn) is essential for normal liver function; conversely, the liver plays a central role in Zn homeostasis. Hence, liver diseases affect Zn levels, whereas Zn deficiency may be involved in their pathogenesis, and reduced liver Zn levels are correlated with impaired liver function and regeneration.

Key words: zinc, liver.

Zinc also plays an important role in the treatment of several liver diseases and, has been shown to attenuate or protect against various hepatotoxins such as carbon tetrachloride, bromobenzene, and several metals. Zinc has various effects on biological activity that may explain this hepatoprotective effect. Here they are: Zn stabilizes membranes and inhibits lipid peroxidation (sex) Zn induces hepatic metallothionein (mt), which is rich in sh groups and binds some toxic metals such as cu; Zn is required for p450 activity, which is important for the metabolism of toxic drugs; Zn improves the function of protein synthesis in the liver; and the hepatoprotective effect of Zn administration against oxidative stress (OS) has been realized through the regulation of the metabolism of superoxide dismutase (SOD), MT, reduced glutathione (GSH), and other antioxidants such as vitamins E and C.

The dietary status of Zn has a strong influence on the extent of damage caused by agents that cause oxidative damage of the free radical type. Several lines of circumstantial evidence also support this concept. Zinc inhibits oxidative damage to molecules, organelles, and cells in vitro and inhibits damage in rodents caused by ccl4, endotoxin, or radiation. However, the effect of Zn on oxidative damage caused by tert-butyl hydroperoxide (t-bhp) has not been systematically investigated.

Zn, which indicates the interaction between them. It was considered appropriate to test whether these interactions are bidirectional by examining the Zn dose response to vitamin status. In addition, these interactions can take different directions under the conditions of the OS. Consequently, the effect of Zn supplementation on vitamin availability in the presence of wasps has been investigated.

Aim of the study. Study of the effect of changes in zinc content in the diet on liver function.

Materials and methods of research. Male Wistar rats weighing 50 ± 10 g. The animals were kept separately in polypropylene cells in the vivarium of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. During the study period of 3 weeks, the rats received a modified diet.

Dietary zinc status (Zn) has a strong influence on the degree of oxidative damage caused by free radicals. We examined the effect of dietary changes in Zn with oxidative stress (wasp) treatment on antioxidant status, liver function and vitamin status in male wistar rats. Oxidative stress was induced by intraperitoneal injections tert-butyl hydroperoxide; and dietary changes in Zn were made: Zn deficiency, normal and excess, with 8, 30 and 60 mg of Zn per kilogram of diet, respectively. After a 21-day dietary regimen, the animals were euthanized; and assessments of plasma aspartate aminotransferase, alanine aminotransferase, hepatic antioxidant enzymes were made.

Results of the study. After 21 days of the experimental period, body weight and food intake records showed no significant difference between the different treatment groups and their subgroups. Slight reductions in weight (125.51 ± 3.29 g) and intake (148 ± 3.2) were observed in animals compared to animals with a normal Zn diet (129.45 ± 1.3 g; 152.3 ± 2), which may be due to the effects of marginal Zn deficiency.

Alanine aminotransferase and aspartate aminotransferase levels were elevated in wasp rats with a Zn-deficient diet, which were restored to normal

levels with excess dietary Zn. Levels of liver antioxidant enzymes and reduced glutathione were significantly reduced with a concomitant increase in sex due to wasp induction in animals on a Zn-deficient diet. A dose-dependent increase in the accumulation of nicotinic acid in the liver was observed as the level of dietary Zn increased from insufficient to excess; however, there was no effect on the status of riboflavin and ascorbic acid. The results suggest that Zn may have therapeutic potential in the treatment of oxidative liver damage along with increased absorption of nicotinic acid.

Conclusion. Adequate Zn levels are critical for optimal functioning of the oxidative defense system, supported by abundant evidence showing that Zn deficiency is associated with an increased risk of oxidative tissue damage. Increased levels of lipids, proteins, and DNA oxidation have been described in various models of Zn deficiency. In the testicles of rats fed a Zn-deficient diet for 14 days, the researchers found several indicators of wasps, including increased cell oxidation

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**TRANSTALOGIC PROBLEMS OF SOMATIC PROVERBS IN
ENGLISH, RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES**

Annotation: *This thesis provides information about transtalologic problems of somatic proverbs in English, Russian and Uzbek languages and according to meaning, translation and equivalents they are divided into groups.*

Key words: *Translation, equivalent, literal, lexeme, cultural identity.*

Translation of proverbs has always been a complex issue. Each society is unique and maintains its own internal cultural values, which is reflected in its language, including proverbs. Proverbs are found in almost every corner of the world. Literal translation, which is the main method of translation, means that we need to translate proverbs literally. Some English, Russian proverbs and Uzbek proverbs have the same form and meaning, and these English proverbs do not contain much cultural information. It is easy for students to understand them. When translating proverbs like this, we can translate them literally. This approach, while retaining the form and meaning of the original proverb, can also be easily understood by readers. Most importantly, a literal translation can transcribe English proverbs into Uzbek culture. As we all know, there are many new ways of expression and comparisons in English proverbs. We can introduce these new expressive methods and comparisons into the Uzbek language. Finally, These English proverbs enrich the Uzbek and Russian languages and culture.

In our research we prefer to divide somatic proverbs based on their meaning in translation:

Proverbs with the same somatic unit in comparing languages

English	Russian	Uzbek
Out of eyes , out of mind	С глаз долой – из сердца вон	Ko'zdan yiroq, ko'ngildan ham yiroq bo'lar
Of the ten fingers , some are long and some are short	На руке пальцы не равны	Besh barmoq barobar emas
Little pitchers have big (or large, long) ears	У маленьких детей большие уши	Devorning ham qulog'i bor
It is a good tongue that says no ill, and a better heart that thinks none	На языке мед, а на сердце лед	Tilingni to'g'ri tutolmasang, Dilingni to'g'ri tut
Two heads are better than one	Одна голова хорошо, а две лучше	Bir bosh -balo bosh, Ikki bosh-mardona bosh
Many hands make light work	Рука руку моет	Ikki qo'l qilgan ishni, bir qo'l qilolmas

Proverbs expressed in Uzbek through somatic units, and in English and Russian with other lexemes

Uzbek	English	Russian
O'zi to'ysa ham, ko'zi to'yamaydi	He is not poor that has little, but he that desires much	Не тот беден, у кого мало, а тот, кто хочет больше
Och qornim -tinch qulog'im	Better a lean peace than a fat victory	Лучше худой мир, чем тучная война
Har kimning taqdiri o'z qo'lida	Fortune is easily found, but hard to be kept	Удачу легко найти, но трудно удержать
Ko'z -qo'rqoq, qo'l -botir	All things are difficult before they are easy	Всё трудно, прежде чем стать легким
Uzun tilim -uzgun tilim, Qisqa tilim-tizgin tilim	Speech is silver, silence is golden	Слово - серебро, молчание - золото

<i>Bilagi zo'r birni yiqar,bilimi zo'r-mingni</i>	<i>Knowledge is power</i>	<i>Знание – сила</i>
<i>Ikki quloqdan ko'ra,bir ko'zga ko'proq ishon</i>	<i>Believe not all that you see nor half what you hear</i>	<i>Не верь всему, что видишь, и половине того, что слышишь</i>
<i>Boyning qorni besh,Biri hamisha-bo'sh</i>	<i>The more you get,the more you want</i>	<i>Чем больше имеешь, тем больше хочешь</i>

In Uzbek, somatisms such as the *eye, abdomen, ears, arms, tongue, neck, and forearm* are allomorphic features of the comparing languages regarding somatic proverbs, due to the fact that the English and Russian equivalents of proverbs that used does not include units specific to this species.

Proverbs expressed in English through somatic units, and in Uzbek with other lexemes

English	Uzbek
<i>A light purse is a heavy heart</i>	<i>Borga-bor dunyo,yo'qqa yo'q dunyo</i>
<i>A long tongue is a sign of a short hand</i>	<i>Gap desang,qop-qop,ish desang Samarqanddan top</i>
<i>A heavy purse makes a light heart</i>	<i>Pul-belga quvvat,boshga-toj</i>
<i>Cold hands,warm heart</i>	<i>Tashqi ko'rinish-aldamchi</i>
<i>Nothing is impossible to a willing heart</i>	<i>Qalovini topsang,qor yog'ar</i>
<i>A hungry belly has no ears</i>	<i>Avval iqtisod,keyin siyosat</i>
<i>You scratch my back,I'll scratch yours</i>	<i>Sizdan ugina,bizdan bugina</i>
<i>Don't measure another man's foot by one's own last</i>	<i>Dunyoni o'z qariching bilan o'lchama</i>
<i>One foot is better than two crutches</i>	<i>Boriga shukur qil,Yo'g'iga sabr</i>
<i>Scatter with one hand, gather with two</i>	<i>Buzish-sosn,tuzish-qiyin</i>

Proverbs expressed in Uzbek and Russian through somatic units, and in English with other lexemes

Uzbek	Russian	English
<i>Til suyaksiz bo'lar</i>	Язык без костей	<i>Think more, speak less</i>
<i>Ко'з ko'rar, qo'l bajarar</i>	<i>Глаза боятся, а руки делают</i>	<i>Actions speak louder than fears"</i>

As we witnessed, translating proverbs from one language into another is a complex process because of the following reasons:

- Proverbs are considered as a cultural unit so it shows cultural identity and this aspect makes translation difficult;
- Structural diversity of the languages led the translation to be complex;
- Finding no equivalents make borrowed proverbs as lacunar units;
- The meaning of some somatic proverbs is given with other lexemes;
- Understanding the pragmatic meaning gives a way to translate properly despite of linguistic diversity.

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MULTILEVEL STRUCTURE OF THE LITERARY TEXT

Abstract - this thesis explores the multilevel structure of literary texts, which encompasses narrative, symbolic, thematic, and philosophical layers. Drawing on the theoretical framework of Gérard Genette's narrative theory and incorporating other relevant literary theories, the research delves into how these layers interact to produce complex meanings in classical, modernist, and postmodern works. By employing qualitative analysis, particularly close reading, the study identifies how different levels contribute to both the complexity of literary texts and the richness of interpretation. Findings suggest that these multilevel structures engage readers actively, fostering a deeper reading experience. Furthermore, the study acknowledges the limitations of this approach in certain genres where narrative depth is not a priority.

Key words: text, Gérard Genette.

I. INTRODUCTION

Literary texts frequently operate on multiple levels, blending surface narratives with deeper layers of symbolism, thematic resonance, and philosophical inquiry. This multilevel structure enables readers to interact with texts in various ways, with meaning often constructed through active interpretation. For example, novels may present a clear plot while addressing broader existential, social, or psychological concerns.

The aim of this thesis is to examine how multilevel structures function within literary texts and to explore the role of these structures in enhancing both the complexity of a work and the reader's engagement with it. In doing so, it draws on Gérard Genette's theory of narrative levels—particularly his concepts of diegesis, metalepsis, and focalization—and other relevant theories. By examining classical, modernist, and postmodern works, this thesis investigates how texts are constructed across multiple narrative planes, with particular attention to how these layers interact and affect the reader's understanding.

II.METHODOLOGY

This research employs a qualitative approach, applying close reading as a method to analyze the chosen texts. The works selected—Ulysses by James Joyce (1922), Beloved by Toni Morrison (1987), Moby-Dick by Herman Melville (1851), If on a Winter's Night a Traveler by Italo Calvino (1979), and City of Glass by Paul Auster (1985)—represent a diverse array of literary forms, styles, and periods. These texts were chosen for their explicit use of multilevel narrative structures and their capacity to reveal complex interactions between surface narratives, symbolic meaning, and philosophical exploration.

To analyze these works, the following criteria were applied:

1. Narrative structure: Identifying and distinguishing between surface-level plots and deeper, implicit themes, using Genette's concepts of diegesis and metalepsis.
2. Symbolism: Interpreting how symbols operate within and across narrative levels.
3. Thematic analysis: Investigating how overarching themes (such as identity, memory, existentialism, or sociopolitical issues) function within different narrative layers.

The analysis also considers the limitations of this multilevel structure in genres or texts where the focus on plot or entertainment may outweigh symbolic and thematic depth.

III.RESULTS

The qualitative analysis of the selected works highlights several key aspects of multilevel narrative structures:

1. Multilevel narrative frameworks: Texts like Ulysses and Beloved demonstrate intricate narrative frameworks, where the surface plot—Joyce's day-in-the-life structure or Morrison's story of Sethe's struggle with memory—operates alongside profound commentaries on identity, history, and memory. Genette's concept of metalepsis helps clarify the ways in which these narratives

transcend traditional boundaries between narrative levels, creating layered experiences for the reader.

2. Complex symbolism: In *Moby-Dick*, Melville constructs an elaborate symbolic system where the whale serves not only as a literal target for Captain Ahab but also as a symbol for larger existential struggles. This layering of symbolism challenges readers to interpret both concrete and abstract elements simultaneously, blending diegetic reality with metaphorical depth.

3. Reader engagement and interpretation: Texts like *If on a Winter's Night a Traveler* and *City of Glass* foreground the reader's role in actively constructing meaning. These works often play with narrative conventions, leading readers to negotiate between the story's surface and deeper, metafictional themes. This interplay engages readers in an interpretive act that enhances both the reading experience and the impact of the literary text.

4. Genre and narrative complexity: It is important to note that not all literary texts employ such multilevel structures to the same extent. Genre fiction, such as romance or mystery, may prioritize plot development over deeper thematic exploration. In such cases, the multilevel structure may be less apparent or less critical to the overall literary experience.

IV.DISCUSSION

The analysis reveals that multilevel structures are crucial to how literary texts produce meaning and invite interpretation. By employing multiple narrative planes, authors enable readers to engage with works on various levels, from surface narrative to symbolic, thematic, and philosophical inquiry. For example, *The Divine Comedy* uses allegory to layer moral and spiritual themes beneath its surface narrative, while works like *To the Lighthouse* by Virginia Woolf and *City of Glass* by Paul Auster blur the boundaries between psychological depth, philosophical inquiry, and narrative experimentation.

These multilevel structures are particularly effective in postmodern texts, where the lines between reality, fiction, and metafiction become porous, creating

opportunities for readers to explore questions of identity, existence, and interpretation. Reader engagement is key to the success of these texts. Unlike straightforward narratives, multilevel texts often require active interpretation, encouraging readers to construct meaning themselves. However, this complexity may alienate some readers, particularly those more accustomed to linear narratives or genres that prioritize plot.

Despite the richness that multilevel structures offer, it is essential to acknowledge that not all literary works use such complexity to the same degree. Some texts, especially those in genre fiction, rely more heavily on plot and may not provide the same interpretive challenge. Therefore, the effectiveness of multilevel structures varies depending on the text's goals and audience.

V.CONCLUSION

The multilevel structure of literary texts plays a vital role in enriching both their complexity and interpretive potential. By operating on multiple narrative, symbolic, and thematic planes, literary works invite readers to engage with texts in more meaningful ways. This interaction between surface narrative and deeper layers of meaning contributes to the depth and richness of literature, encouraging readers to participate in the creation of meaning.

However, it is important to recognize that not all literary texts employ multilevel structures equally. While classical, modernist, and postmodern works often leverage this complexity, genre fiction may prioritize plot over symbolic or thematic exploration. The multilevel structure remains a powerful literary device for exploring the human experience, but its use and effectiveness depend on the specific goals and design of each work.

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**TA'LIM JARAYONIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY
ETISH MASALALARI**

***Annotatsiya:** Maqolada ta'lim jarayonida raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish masalalari hamda raqamli ta'lim transformatsiyaning ahamiyati, avfzalliklari va muammo yechimlari haqida fikrlar keltirilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** raqamli texnologiyalar, kadrlar salohiyati, raqamli transformatsiya, kompyuter savodxonligi, IT sohalar.*

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**ISSUES OF THE INTRODUCTION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES
IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS**

Annotation: the article presents the issues of the introduction of digital technologies in the educational process and points on the importance, advantages and problem solutions of digital education transformation.

Keywords: digital technology, personnel potential, digital transformation, computer literacy, it fields.

Raqamli texnologiyalar butun ta'lim tizimida paradigmani o'zgartirmoqda. U nafaqat bilim yetkazib beruvchi, balki axborotning hammuallifi, maslahatchisi va baholovchisi [hamdir](#). Ta'limdagi texnologik takomillashtirish o'quvchilar hayotini osonlashtirmoqda. Hozirgi kunda o'quvchilar qog'oz va qalamdan foydalanish o'rniga taqdimotlar va loyihalarni yaratish uchun turli xil dasturiy ta'minot va vositalardan foydalanadilar. Noutbuklar to'plami bilan solishtirganda, iPad nisbatan yengil. Og'ir kitobdan farqli o'laroq, elektron kitobni o'qish osonroq. Ushbu usullar tadqiqotga qiziqishni oshirishga yordam beradi.

Ushbu maqola ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalarga bo'lgan ehtiyoj haqida qisqacha ma'lumot beradi va ta'limdagi asosiy ilovalar hamda muammolarni muhokama qiladi.

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, so'nggi ikki yil ichida quloqqa chalingan "masofa" va ta'limni raqamlashtirish atamasi bir xil ma'noga ega emas. Bu ko'p qirrali tushuncha bo'lib, jarayonni qurish uchun turli xil IT yechimlarini qo'llashni nazarda tutadi.

Tashkiliy masalalar ham raqamli mahsulotlar yordamida optimallashtiriladi. Bular raqamli jurnallar, talabalar kundaliklari, messenjerlar orqali o'qituvchilar bilan muloqot. Barcha ta'lim muassasalari zudlik bilan chiqish yo'lini izlashlari kerak edi. Biroq, bu sohadagi o'zgarishlar chet elda ta'limda raqamli vositalardan ancha oldin qo'llanila boshlandi.

Mamlakatimiz ushbu jarayonning bir necha bosqichlarini bosib o'tdi:

- 90-yillarning boshlarida kompyuter savodxonligi maktablarda informatika darslari va boshqa ta'lim muassasalarida boshqa shunga o'xshash fanlar orqali oshirildi;
- 2000-yillarning o'rtalaridan o'quv jarayoniga yordamchi raqamli vositalar joriy etila boshlandi;
- 2018-yilda boshlangan zamonaviy bosqich texnologiyaning barcha ta'lim tuzilmalariga yanada qattiqroq integratsiyalashuvini va jarayonni tashkil qilishni nazarda tutadi.

Transformatsiya quyidagi yo'nalishlarga ta'sir qiladi:

- o'quv ishlarini tashkil etish, asbob-uskunalar;
- o'qitish texnologiyalari va pedagogik metodikalari;
- ta'lim mazmuni va rejalashtirilayotgan natijalar.

Hozir hayot elektron resurslar bilan chambarchas bog'liq, shuning uchun bolalarni hozirdanoq bu dunyoda yashashga, resurslardan to'g'ri foydalanishga o'rgatish muhimdir.

Nima uchun ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalar

Ko'pgina mutaxassislar zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiya va raqamli vositalarsiz mavjud bo'lmasligiga uzoq vaqtdan beri rozi bo'lishdi. Hayotning bu tomoni bilan imkon qadar tezroq tanishish kerak. Bu modaga hurmat emas, balki shoshilinch zaruratdir.

Dunyodagi o'zgarishlarni inkor etib, o'qituvchi va o'quvchilarning qurollari o'zgarishsiz qolishini kutish ahmoqlik, deydi ekspertlar. Taraqqiyot ancha oldinga qadam tashladi va bu inson hayotining barcha jabhalarida, ayniqsa, ta'limda o'z ifodasini topmoqda. Agar texnologiyasiz amalga oshirib bo'lmaydigan masofaviy ta'limni chetga surib qo'ysak ham, hatto an'anaviy yuzma-yuz ta'lim ham katta metamorfozga uchradi.

Shunga o'xshash tez o'zgarishlar ta'lim tuzilmasida oldin sodir bo'lgan, masalan, matbaa ixtirosi bilan, keyin ta'lim yanada qulayroq bo'ldi. Keyinchalik yozuv mashinkalari paydo bo'ldi, endi har doim qo'lda yozish shart emas edi, telefonlar va telegraflar masofadan turib bilim va tajriba almashish imkonini berdi. Endi bizda Internet va boshqa zamonaviy, jasur texnologiyalar mavjud bo'lib, ularning ta'sirini inkor etish ham ahmoqdir.

Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimi hozirgi dunyoga mos kelishi kerak. Ta'lim muassasasi bitiruvchisi bu dunyoda hayotga tayyor bo'lishi kerak va dunyo, o'z navbatida, barcha darajadagi texnologiya bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Biroq, texnologiya o'qituvchilarni, jonli muloqotni va ta'lim muhitini butunlay siqib chiqarishidan qo'rqmaslik kerak. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'quv jarayoni raqamli vositalardan to'g'ri foydalanish bilan jonli o'zaro ta'sir qilish tajribasiga asoslangan bo'lsa, kombinatsiyalangan yondashuv eng samarali hisoblanadi.

Ta'limga texnologiyani joriy etishning afzalliklari allaqachon isbotlangan. Bu bir necha sohalarda muvaffaqiyat bilan ko'rsatilgan:

1. **Tashkiliy vazifalar.** Ota-onalar har doim taraqqiyot to'g'risida dolzarb ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lishlari uchun o'quvchi haqidagi ma'lumotlarni elektron kundalik orqali uzatish ancha oson va tezroq.

2. **Talabalar uchun qulay jarayonni qurish.** Agar abituriyent yuzma-yuz ma'ruzaga masofadan qo'shilsa, ishdan bo'shatish sezilarli darajada kamayadi. O'qituvchi bir darsda o'quvchilarning qobiliyati va axborotni o'zlashtirish qobiliyatiga qarab mavzular berishi mumkin.

3. **O'quv materiallarining keng doirasiga kirish.** Dunyoning istalgan nuqtasida joylashgan shaxs, agar ular ta'lim platformalarida joylashtirilgan bo'lsa, istalgan universitetning ma'ruzalariga kirishi mumkin. Ilgari bu imkoniyat faqat ushbu universitetlar talabalari uchun mavjud edi.

4. **Xavfsiz raqamli muhitda haqiqiy dunyo ko'nikmalarini mashq qiling.** Masalan, tibbiyot talabalari xuddi samolyot uchuvchilari kabi maxsus raqamli simulyatorlarda mashq qilishlari mumkin.

5. **Ta'limni yaxshilash uchun ma'lumotlarni to'plash va tahlil qilish.** Talabalarni tahlil qilish tizimlari o'qituvchiga zaif va kuchli tomonlarini ajratib ko'rsatish va dasturni sozlash imkonini beradi. Ba'zi hollarda, bunday tizimlar faqat qabul qilingan talabalarning o'qishdan haydash ehtimoli va mumkin bo'lgan muvaffaqiyatini bashorat qilishga qodir.

Raqamlashtirishni eski tizimni to'liq almashtirish sifatida qabul qilib bo'lmaydi. Aksincha, bu allaqachon mavjud bo'lganlarga muqobil va qo'llab-quvvatlashdir.

Raqamli tizimga o'tish jarayoni u qadar faol emas. Hamma g'oyalar amalga oshirilmaydi. Raqamlashtirishning o'zgaruvchan muvaffaqiyati to'siqlar bilan bog'liq:

- olis aholi punktlari zarur resurslarga ega emas;
- mahalliy mutaxassislarning malakasi yo'q;
- ixtisoslashtirilgan malaka oshirish kurslari ko'pincha samarasiz bo'ladi;
- professor-o'qituvchilar tarkibi innovatsiyalarga ishonmaydi;
- bozorda ehtiyojlarni qondiradigan echimlar etarli emas;
- Masofadan o'qiydiganlar topshiriqlarni insofsiz bajarishlari ehtimoli ko'proq.

Global miqyosda tizim raqamli transformatsiya bosqichida, ba'zi ta'lim muassasalarida esa yetarlicha kompyuterlar ham yo'q.

Simulyatorlari va o'quv jihozlari bilan zamonaviy raqamli ta'lim nafaqat bolalarni, balki kattalarni ham o'ziga jalb qiladi. Onlayn kurslar kattalar uchun birinchi tanlovdir. Ushbu formatda bilim olish ancha qulayroq, endi u hatto band bo'lgan odamlar uchun ham mavjud. Tashkilotlar raqamli vositalardan foydalangan holda korporativ treningni amalga oshirishni osonlashtiradi.

Maktab o'quvchilari tez-tez oflayn darslarga qatnashadilar, lekin onlayn repetitorlar va ta'lim platformalaridan foydalanadilar. Bu sohada davlat tomonidan tartibga solish sifatsiz ta'lim xizmatlarini ko'rsatish bilan bog'liq vaziyatlar yuzaga kelmasligi uchun zarur. Tez orada faqat rasmiy reestrda ro'yxatdan o'tgan vakillar onlayn ta'lim xizmatlarini ko'rsatishlari mumkin bo'ladi.

Har qanday taraqqiyot qo'rqinchli va muqarrar ravishda qarshilikka sabab bo'ladi. Dunyoda ikkita muammo bor:

- aholining katta qismi uchun kompyuterlar yoki boshqa gadjetlar, shuningdek barqaror internetning yetishmasligi;
- buni hech qachon qilmaganlar uchun texnologiyani o'zlashtirishda qiyinchilik. Gadjetlardan foydalanish tajribasiga ega bo'lmasdan turib, global ta'lim imkoniyatlarini bilgan holda ham natijalarga erishib bo'lmaydi.

Gadjetni unga qiziqqan har bir kishiga berishning o'zi yetarli emas, shuningdek, foydalanuvchini undan foydalanish asoslariga o'rgatish kerak bo'ladi. *Ta'lim jarayoniga raqamli yechimlarni joriy etish embrion darajada bo'lib, o'qitish qoidalari va usullari hali ham shakllantirilmoqda.*

Bundan tashqari, barcha raqamli texnikalar ta'lim uchun foydali emasligi aniq. Yo'lda muqarrar ravishda yuzaga keladigan muvaffaqiyatsizliklar haqida o'ylamang. Muvozanatni saqlab qolish, ikkala tizimdan ham eng samarali bo'lgan narsalarni saqlab qolish muhimdir.

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WORDLY
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**JANUBIY OROLBO'YIDA SAKSOVULLARNI MUHOFAZA
QILISHNING HUQUQIY CHORA-TADBIRLARINI KUCHAYTIRISH**

Annotatsiya

*Bir paytlar ulkan suv havzasi bo'lgan Janubiy Orol dengizi hozir atrof-muhitga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan eng og'ir ekologik ofatlardan birini boshdan kechirmoqda. Suv sathining pasayishi va antropogen bosimning kuchayishi mintaqa ekotizimida jiddiy o'zgarishlarga olib keldi, jumladan, saksovul (*Haloxylon spp.*) kabi o'simliklar jamoalarining degradatsiyasiga olib keldi. Saksovullar ekotizim muvozanatini saqlash, tuproq eroziyasini oldini olish va biologik xilma-xillikni saqlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Biroq, hozirgi tahdidlarga qarshi samarali kurashish va ekotizimning barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlash maqsadida hududda saksovulni muhofaza qilish bo'yicha mavjud huquqiy tartibga solish takomillashtirilishini taqozo etadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: Saksovul, janubiy orol dengizi.

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**STRENGTHENING LEGAL MEASURES FOR THE PROTECTION OF
SAXONS IN THE SOUTH ARAL REGION**

Annotation

*Once a huge body of water, the South Aral Sea is now experiencing one of the most severe environmental disasters affecting the environment. Lower water levels and increased anthropogenic pressure have led to significant changes in the ecosystem of the region, including saxaul (*Haloxylon spp.*) led to the degradation of plant communities such as Saxaul play an important role in maintaining ecosystem balance, preventing soil erosion, and maintaining biodiversity. However, in order to effectively combat current threats and ensure the sustainable development of the ecosystem, the existing legal regulation for the conservation of saxaul in the area is subject to improvement.*

Keywords: saxaul, South Aral Sea.

Kirish

Qozog‘iston va O‘zbekiston chegarasida joylashgan Janubiy Orol dengizi butun ekotizimiga ta‘sir etuvchi chuqur ekologik o‘zgarishlarni boshdan kechirmoqda. Ushbu o'zgarishlar suv sathining pasayishi, iqlim o'zgarishi va antropogen ta'sirning kuchayishi bilan bog'liq. Mintaqa ekotizimining muhim elementlaridan biri saksovol bo'lib, u tuproqni barqarorlashtirish, eroziyaning oldini olish va biologik xilma-xillikni saqlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Janubiy Orol dengizi ekotizimi bunday muammolarga duch kelayotgan sharoitda saksovullarni muhofaza qilish bo'yicha huquqiy chora-tadbirlarni kuchaytirish zarur.

Mavzuning dolzarbligi antropogen ta'sir va iqlim o'zgarishi natijasida yuzaga keladigan tahdidlarga munosib javob berish zarurati bilan belgilanadi. Saksovolni muhofaza qilish bo'yicha joriy huquqiy chora-tadbirlar o'simliklarni muhofaza qilish va hududning ekologik barqarorligini ta'minlash uchun yetarli emas. Shu sababli, ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi mavjud huquqiy tartibga solishni tahlil qilish, muammolarni aniqlash va uni takomillashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishdir.

Saksovullarning ekologik ahamiyati

Saksovullar (*Haloxylon* spp.) Janubiy Orol dengizi ekotizimining asosiy komponentlari hisoblanadi. Ular quyidagi funktsiyalarni bajaradilar:

1. Tuproq eroziyasining oldini olish: Saksovullar kuchli ildiz tizimiga ega bo'lib, tuproqni barqarorlashtirishga yordam beradi va uni ob-havoning oldini oladi.

2. Biologik xilma-xillikni saqlash: Ular o'simliklar va hayvonlarning har xil turlarining hayoti uchun o'ziga xos sharoitlarni yaratadi, ekotizim muvozanatini saqlashga yordam beradi.

3. Suv balansini tartibga solish: Saksovullar tuproqdagi namlikni saqlab qolishga yordam beradi, bu mintaqaning quruq iqlimida ayniqsa muhimdir.

Janubiy Orol dengizi ekotizimiga taalluqli muammolar saksovu populyatsiyasining sezilarli darajada kamayishi ko'rinishida namoyon bo'ladi, bu esa o'z navbatida tuproq eroziyasining kuchayishiga va bioxilma-xillikning yo'qolishiga olib keladi.

Saksovu ni muhofaza qilishni huquqiy tartibga solish

Mintaqada saksovu ni muhofaza qilishning amaldagi huquqiy tartibga solinishi milliy qonunchilik va xalqaro shartnomalarga asoslanadi. Milliy qonunchilik darajasida quyidagi qoidalar qo'llaniladi:

1. Ekologik qonunlar: Bu qonunlar tabiiy resurslar va ekotizimlarni muhofaza qilishga qaratilgan.

2. O'simliklarni muhofaza qilish to'g'risidagi qonunlar: O'simlik dunyosidan, jumladan, saksovullardan foydalanish va muhofaza qilishni tartibga soladi.

Xalqaro shartnomalar ham muhim rol o'ynaydi, masalan:

1. Biologik xilma-xillik konventsiyasi: biologik xilma-xillikni saqlash va ekotizimlardan barqaror foydalanishni qamrab oladi.

2. Iqlim o'zgarishi bo'yicha BMT doiraviy konventsiyasi: iqlim o'zgarishiga moslashish va uni yumshatish siyosatiga ta'sir qiladi.

Huquqiy tartibga solishdagi muammolar va kamchiliklar

Qonunchilik va xalqaro shartnomalar mavjudligiga qaramay, bir qator muammo va kamchiliklar mavjud:

1. Qonunchilikdagi bo'shliqlar: Qonun hujjatlarida ko'pincha saksovullarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va ularning ekotizimlari hisobga olinmaydi. Himoya va boshqaruvning aniq belgilangan standartlari yo'q.

2. Ijroning samarasizligi: qonunlarga rioya etilishini nazorat qilish mexanizmlari ko'pincha etarli emas, bu esa buzilishlarga va yomon rioya qilishga olib keladi.

3. Resurslarning etishmasligi: moliyalashtirish va malakali kadrlarning etishmasligi xavfsizlik choralarini samarali amalga oshirishni qiyinlashtiradi.

Muvaffaqiyatli va muvaffaqiyatsiz amaliyotlarga misollar

Turli mamlakatlar o'xshash ekotizimlarni himoya qilish uchun turli yondashuvlarni amalga oshirdilar. Muvaffaqiyatli amaliyotlarga misollar kiradi:

1. Muhofaza qilinadigan zonalar va qo'riqxonalarini tashkil etish: asosiy ekotizimlarni himoya qilish uchun qo'riqlanadigan zonalarini yaratish ayrim mamlakatlarda muvaffaqiyatli joriy etilgan.

2. Mahalliy hamjamiyatlarni tabiatni muhofaza qilish jarayonlariga integratsiyalashuvi: Mahalliy hamjamiyatlarni tabiiy resurslarni muhofaza qilish va boshqarish dasturlariga jalb qilish.

Muvaffaqiyatsiz misollarga quyidagilar kiradi:

1. Kompleks yondashuvning yo'qligi: ko'p hollarda himoya choralari faqat qisman qo'llaniladi yoki muammo ko'lamiga mos kelmaydi.

2. Majburiy ijro muammolari: Ba'zi hollarda ijroning samarasizligi va nazoratning yo'qligi doimiy qonunbuzarliklarga olib keladi.

Saksovullarni muhofaza qilish bo'yicha huquqiy chora-tadbirlarni kuchaytirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar

Saksovullarni muhofaza qilish samaradorligini oshirish va ekotizimning barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlash maqsadida quyidagi chora-tadbirlar taklif etiladi:

1. Yangi qonunchilik tashabbuslarini ishlab chiqish va amalga oshirish:

a) saksovullarni muhofaza qilishni yaxshilash uchun amaldagi qonun va me'yoriy hujjatlarga o'zgartirishlar kiritish.

b) saksovullar alohida muhofaza qilinadigan qo'shimcha himoya zonalarini va qo'riqxonalarini tashkil etish.

2. Yaxshilangan monitoring va nazorat:

a) Saksovullarning holati va qonunchilik normalariga rioya etilishini monitoring qilishning samarali tizimlarini ishlab chiqish va joriy etish.

b) qonun hujjatlariga rioya etilishi ustidan nazoratni kuchaytirish va buzilishlar uchun javobgarlikka tortish.

3. Ogohlantirish va jamoatchilik ishtirokini oshirish:

a) Saksovullarning ahamiyati va ularni muhofaza qilish zarurligi to'g'risida xabardorlikni oshirish uchun ma'rifiy kampaniyalarni o'tkazish.

b) jamoat tashkilotlari va mahalliy hamjamiyatlarni tabiatni muhofaza qilish tadbirlari va dasturlariga jalb qilish.

Xulosa

Janubiy Orol dengizida saksovullarni muhofaza qilish bo'yicha huquqiy chora-tadbirlarni kuchaytirish mintaqa ekotizimining barqarorligini ta'minlashda muhim qadamdir. Amaldagi huquqiy chora-tadbirlarni ekotizimning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va u duch keladigan tahdidlarni hisobga olgan holda takomillashtirish va real sharoitlarga moslashtirish zarur. Yangi qonunchilik tashabbuslarini ishlab chiqish va hayotga tatbiq etish, monitoring va nazoratni takomillashtirish, aholining xabardorligini oshirish hududda saksovulni samarali muhofaza qilish va ekologik muvozanatni saqlashning asosiy yo'nalishlaridandir.

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OMON MUXTOR - ROMANNAVIS

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi Omon Muxtorning romannavisligi va uning hayoti haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Omon Muxtor, roman, klassika.

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OMAN MUKHTAR-ROMANNAVIS

Annotation: this thesis provides information about the romanavism of the Omani Mukhtar and his life.

Keywords: Omon Mukhtar, novel, classics.

XX asr boshlarida tug'ilgan o'zbek romanchiligi bugungi kunda nafaqat milliy, balki rus va jahon klassik romanchiligining ajoyib an'alarini davom ettirgan holda inson hayotining yangi-yangi jabhalarini qamrab olmoqda. Insonning uning ichki ruhiyati, o'y-fikri, orzulari tasviriga yangicha usulda yondashayotgan, adabiyotda o'z ovozi, o'z uslubiga ega so'zini ayta olish baxtiga sazovor bo'lgan iste'dodli ijodkor Omon Muxtoridir. Adibning so'nggi yillarda chop etgan qator asarlari, umri davomida adabiy meros sifatida qoldirgan yigirmaga yaqin romani bizga yozuvchining iste'dodli, sarmahsul ijodkor sifatida tanitadi. Yozuvchi asarlarida biz yangi yo'llar, shakliy izlanishlarni ko'rishimiz mumkin. Tasvirlarda, xarakterlar mohiyatini ochib berishda adib jahon adabiyotining boy uslubiy an'alarini dadillik bilan milliy materialga singdira olishini, nafaqat jahon, balki milliy an'alarimizning folklor namunalaridan ham foydalanishi, uslubiy va shakliy izlanishlar qilishi, nasrda ham nazmni uyg'unlashtira olishi kabilarni ko'rishimiz mumkin. Dastlabki ikki romani ma'lum darajada an'anaviy uslubda bo'lsa, keyingi romanlar o'z shakli va yo'nalishi bilan butunlay yangichadir. Ular, asosan,

o‘zbek xalq ertaklari, qissalari, dostonlari va afsonalariga suyangan holda, bu kungi inson hayotini aks ettirish bilan birga, uning xayol olamiga, ruhiyatiga sayohatni eslatadi. Adib ijodiga xos bo‘lib kelgan falsafaga moyillik bu romanlarda bo‘rtib ko‘rinadi. Inson qismati ham, uning ruhiy olami ham naqadar murakkab ekanligini aks ettiradi.

Adib ko‘p qirrali, iste‘dodli ijodkor deb bejiz e‘tirof etilmaydi. Omon Muxtor shoir, yozuvchi, dramaturg. Nasrdagi ijodi hikoyalar yozishdan boshlagan adib “Yillar shamoli”(1976) keyingi nashrlarda “Buxorolik bir yigit”(1998) va “Egilgan bosh” (1989) kabi an’anaviy uslubda yozilgan asarlari bilan roman janrida o‘z mahoratini sinab ko‘rdi.

Uning oxirgi o‘n yillikda yaratgan qator romanlari yozuvchini elga tanitdi. “To‘rt tomon qibla” trilogiyasi (“Ming bir qiyofa”, “Ko‘zgu oldidagi odam”, “Tepalikdagi xaroba”), “Ayollar mamlakati va saltanati” (1997), “Aflotun” (1998), “Ffu” (1997), “Navoiy va rassom Abulxayr” dilogiyasi (“Buyuk farrosh”, “Ishq ahli”), “Maydon” (1999), “Xotin podshoh”, “Muhabbat o‘limdan kuchli”(2011) hamda “Odamlar kulishlari kerak” romanlari, avvalo, mazmun-mundariyasi, shakl-shamoyili, ifoda tarzining o‘ziga xosligi, shaklning turfaligi bilan alohida afzalliklarga ega.

Uning zamonaviy va tarixiy mavzudagi romanlari o‘zbek nasrining shaklan va mazmunan boyishida muhim o‘rin tutadi. Undagi yangicha tasvir usullari, tafakkur tarzi va roman – hangoma, roman – rivoyat, asr romani kabi roman janridagi shakliy izlanishlari e‘tiborga loyiq.

Buni adibning har bir romani adabiy jamoatchilik orasida turli bahslarga sabab bo‘lgani “Xotin podshoh”, “Maydon” hamda “Ishq ahli” romanlarining o‘zidayoq yaqqol ko‘rishimiz mumkin.

“Ko‘plab o‘zga adabiy janrlardan farqli ravishda romanning mavzu chegarasini belgilash deyarli mumkin emas. Roman hamma narsa haqida va har qanday hajmda bo‘lishi mumkin. Uni tarozida tortib yoxud bosma toboq bilan chegaralab bo‘lmaydi.”Romandan katta hikoyalar” (Shukur Xolmirzaev)

bo'lgani singari novelladan kichik romanlar ham bo'ladi. Qahramon yoxud muallif shaxsiyati qirralarining nechog'liq to'liq ochilganligi romanning romanligini o'lchaydigan birgina mezon, janrning muvaffaqiyatini belgilaydigan yagona omildir",-deydi adabiyotshunos olim Qozoqboy Yo'ldoshev.

Omon Muxtorning "Maydon" va "Aflotun" umuman olganda deyarli barcha romanlari talqin uslubi, voqelik talqini yechimi bilan bir-biridan farq qilsa-da, talqinga jalb etilgan manba va muammoni romanlar g'oyasiga singdirib yuborish jihatidan o'zaro mushtarak. "Ko'zgu oldidagi odam", "Aflotun", "Ffu" romanlarida falsafiy mushohada, "Ming bir qiyofa", "Tepalikdagi xaroba" da psixologik tahlilning yetakchilik qilishi va absurd g'oyalar bugungi kun misolida ochib berilishi romanchiligimizda noan'anaviy uslublarning yuzaga kelishida biz yashayotgan voqelik ham alohida o'rin tutishini ko'rsatadi.

"Har qanday asar kitobxon uchun yoziladi. Kitobxonni ko'p mamlakat baxtli, kitobxonni yo'q mamlakat baxtsizdir"-, degan edi yozuvchi Omon Muxtor haqli ravishda.

Texnika asri tobora rivojlanib borayotgan XXI asrning yigirma yilligida yashayotgan ekanmiz, internet, elektron kitob degan tushunchalar endi bizga yangilik bo'lmay qoldi. Munaqqid Qozoqboy Yo'ldoshev ta'biri bilan aytganda, kitobxon soni keskin kamaydi, lekin eng saralari xos kishilari qoldi.

Modern yo'nalishda ijod qiluvchi Omon Muxtor romanlarini tahlil qilish jarayonida quyidagi xulosalarga kelish mumkin.

Adib romanlarining soni o'n to'rttani tashkil etadi. Bu faqat roman janridagi asarlar soni. Demak, u mustaqillik davridagi eng sermahsul ijodkor sifatida e'tirof etish joiz. To'g'ri, har qanday yozuvchining iste'dodi uning qancha asar yozgani-yu, qancha ijod qilgani bilan emas, badiiy tafakkurga qanday o'zgarishlar olib kirib, adabiy jarayonga qanday ta'sir o'tkazgani bilan belgilanadi. Omon Muxtor adabiy jarayon faollaridan edi. Uning "Maydon" va "Xotin podshoh" asarlarini adibning eng sara, eng pishiq romanlari deb e'tirof etish mumkin.

Omon Muxtor tajribalar qilish, ayniqsa, shakliy izlanishlari yozuvchining yana bir o'ziga xos uslubini belgilaydi. U o'n to'rt romanida ham shakliy izlanishlar qilishi, shakl orqali mazmunning uyg'unligiga erishishi kuzatiladi. Kutilmagan tasvir yo'sinlari, badiiy ifodaning tutilmagan, yangi vositalardan foydalanish adib romanlarining yetakchi xususiyati ekanligi ko'rinadi. So'z san'atkorining barcha romanlarida azaliy tuyg'u muhabbat mavzusiga murojaat etadi. Asarlarida g'aroyib voqea-hodisalar, inson ishonishi qiyin, faqat tasavvur eta oladigan, tafakkur mahsuli bo'lgan hodisalarning kelishi tabiiy hol. Bu "Ming bir qiyofa", "Tepalikdagi xaroba" va "Muhabbat o'limdan kuchli" asarlarida uchraydi.

Romanlarda xalq og'zaki ijodi namunalari: Nasriddin Afandi latifalari, rivoyat, afsonalardan juda ko'p o'rinlarda foydalaniladi. Romanlarning hajm jihatidan qisqaligi bilan mini romanlarga yaqinlashadi. (An'anaviy qissalardan kichikroq, hikoyalardan kattaroq)

Insonning ichki olamida o'zgarishlarni ko'proq voqea-hodisalar asosida, badiiy tafakkur, ichki "ong oqimi" yordamida tasvirlash ustunligi; yozuvchining falsafiy mushohadaga o'chligi; romanda qalamga olingan voqea-hodisalarning sodir bo'lish davri nihoyatda kattaligi, xronotopning, makon va zamonning juda ham kengligi; romanlarda nasrning uyg'unlashib ketganligi, uning his-tuyg'ulari, hayot haqidagi falsafiy mushohadalari, o'y-xayollari lirizm bilan sug'orilganini ko'ramiz. Adib romanlarining deyarli barchasida, ba'zilarining har bir qism, bobida ham asar g'oyasini teran anglash, yozuvchi niyatini to'laqonli ochish, ifodalash uchun epigraf qo'llanishi, ularning asosiy qismi mumtoz adabiyotimizning nodir durdonalari tashkil etishi, adibning mumtoz adabiyotimiz bilimdoni ekanligi namoyon bo'ladi.

Adib romanlarida so'zlarning siniq mozaika tarzida berishi, ya'ni asardagi so'zlarning bo'g'inlarga ajratib berishi, hamda ma'lum so'zlarni imlo qoidalariga zid bo'lsa-da o'quvchini o'ylantirish, adib keltirayotgan so'zga

e'tiborni tortish uchun ko'p so'zlarni barcha tovushlarini katta harfda berish tabiiy hol ekanligini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Omon Muxtorni Oybekdan so'ng buyuk daho ijodkor Navoiyning to'laqonli siyimosini yaratgan mohir romannavis sifatida e'tirof etishimiz mumkin.

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USING PROFESSIONAL LANGUAGE OR SLANG IN MEDIA PRESS

Abstract: *The study of media language has much to offer to the different disciplines on whose territory it touches: linguistics, sociolinguistics, discourse analysis, semiotics, communication studies, sociology and social psychology and in this work we try to analyze its writing style: professional or enriched with slang words.*

Keywords: *Professional language, slang, quotes, news media.*

Davies' study found that using French vocabulary in select English newspaper stories might drive readers to read the articles because of the aesthetic effects generated by using French for an Anglophone audience. The newspaper articles are seen as having a professional touch, according to Davies, when the dominant words are effective and clear[2].

Rampton went on to say that the aesthetic impulse of words is immensely enticing and has a strong impact on the minds of readers. The diversity of instances examined demonstrates the numerous ways in which a foreign language can be present in an English journalistic section. He did a study on the use of English in Mexican, Spanish and Bulgarian magazine articles in the German magazine Der Spiegel[5].

Jackson, R.P in his article Searching for a Voice of Authority in Newspaper Writing reported that, readers repeated familiar laments about quality of writing: "Dull and uninspired ... too highbrow, nongraphic, unprofessional, wordy and undisruptive[3]. In other words, professional language is described as possessing some objectivity and meaningful terms.

As the newspaper also seeks to influence public opinion on various social, political or moral matters, its language frequently contains vocabulary with evaluative connotation, such as to allege (the person who allegedly committed

the crime), to claim (the defendant claims to know nothing about it). These cast some doubts on what is stated further and make it clear to the reader that those are not yet affirmed facts. A reporter's lack of confidence in the accuracy of the facts reported or desire to avoid responsibility can be seen in the choice and manner in which the news is presented, not only in the use of specific vocabulary but also in syntactic constructions.

Taken from <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Slang>, idioms and slang are similar. Slang in general refers to words that are trendy (in fashion) for a time, so slang changes as time passes. Also, slang may be different from region to region. For example, some slang words in California may be unknown to people in Florida, to say nothing of the difference in slang between England and the USA and other English speaking communities. Idioms often start as slang but get more ingrained into the language and as a matter of fact, many dictionaries now contain many idiomatic words and phrases, as they become a part of our everyday language.

Johnson and Fox quoted of saying that “slang is the poetry of everyday life”[4]. Other than that, Bullard mentioned that slang was the main reason for the development of prescriptive language in an attempt to slow down the rate of change in both spoken and written language[1]. Latin and French were the only two languages that maintained the use of prescriptive language in the 14th century. It was not until the early 15th century that scholars began pushing for a Standard English language.

In his publication *A Study of Slang and Informal Usage in a Newspaper*, Kenwood highlighted how the notion of standardization led to the formation of these non-standard usage groups in language (slang). In the seventeenth and eighteenth century's lexicographers and grammarians, especially men like Dr. Samuel Johnson proposed that the English language should be purified and “fixed”; that, in fact, it should be standardized for all time. But only dead languages remain lifeless; live languages branch infinitely in all directions.

Thus, these Renaissance pursuers of standardization in language ironically created, through 78 their efforts, the substandard - the slang, informal and other areas not relegated to the "cleansed" version. It was hoped that these vulgarities would thereby drop from use and cease to infiltrate the standard level of language.

Professional language is any content that contains complex terms that make it extremely difficult for others to enjoy and understand. Some journalists use slang language in their stories without even realizing it, or they do realize it but choose to use it nevertheless. The unenthused part is when writers use grandiloquent words for the sake of it, because sometimes as writers we have explanations for why we use certain words, but also, in my opinion, the use of professional language in newspapers needs to narrow a bit because not everyone can understand the same meaning as what the writer is trying to say.

Slang develops in social groups, which frequently recalls cliques of youths, minorities, and warriors. However, not all slang is unique to the group in which it originated; certain varieties of slang spread through generations and become recognized standard language because societal conditions make them popular or people have become accustomed to hearing and using them. Slang is

commonly used in the speech of teenagers. Across all races and regions, phrases like "dude, let's bounce, this party is totally bust" can be found rolling off the Special news topic Feature articles 79 tongues of many teenagers, and are often mimicked and made fun of by adults and the media as a sign of immaturity, irresponsibility and unintelligence. We cannot ignore slang, as much as we cannot ignore how we perceive slang. Linguist Michael Adams explains that "When we hear a word or sentence pattern, it undergoes scrutiny, whether we're conscious of it or not: we judge its acceptability according to a certain set of standards; the standards vary according to the vocabulary against which the newer item is measured. "The acceptability being spoken of is of the slang term as an easily accepted word or a comprehensible phrase. We are taught from an early age that slang is an inappropriate use of language, and many teachers and parents feel that it should never be used while teaching youngsters grammar and adult social skills.

According to Rousseau, even if all circles employ some form of slang, we still assess each other based on the slang we use. Some slang has grown more popular and consequently more acceptable in a variety of contexts. The words "cool" and "hot" have increased in popularity and become widely accepted in most social backgrounds; they are no longer considered as improper as newer slang like "that sucks," to express disappointment or "busted," to describe unattractiveness. Until that point where the majority of society has grown accustomed to hearing the word or phrase on a regular basis and has warmed to it, slang will continue to be viewed negatively, as an inferior part of language"[6].

This is an advantageous move, and it should be suggested to instructors and lecturers who want to use newspaper stories as teaching materials. The findings are comparable to Davies , who stated that newspaper stories are deemed to have a professional touch when the dominant terms are professional because it provides a clearer and more efficient end. According to Bullard, the

main reason for the formation of prescriptive language was to reduce the rate of change in both spoken and written language[1].

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WORDLY
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**OLIV TA'LIMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ZAMONAVIY
TENDENSIYALAR**

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada ta'lim tizimi boshqaruv jarayonining mohiyati va qonuniyatlarini aniqlash, bu jarayonda sodir bo'ladigan munosabatlarni ochib berish, baholash va boshqaruv sub'ektining asosiy tamoyillarni ishlab chiqish ta'limni boshqarish jarayonida muhim ahamiyati haqida ma'lumotlar joy olgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim tizimi, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyot, rivojlanish tendensiyalar, qonun-qonuniyat, boshqaruv.

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**MODERN TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER
EDUCATION**

Annotation: this article contains information about the important importance of the educational system in the process of managing education, identifying the essence and laws of the management process, revealing the relationship that occurs in this process, evaluating and developing the basic principles of the subject of management.

Keywords: educational system, socio-economic development, development trends, law and order, management.

O'zbekistonda ta'lim tizimi davlat tomonidan to'g'risidagi qonunlar, qarorlar va tadqiqotlar asosida amalga oshiriladi. Ta'lim tizimining nazariy qismi, oliy o'quv yurtlari, xususiy o'quv yurtlari, xalq ta'limi, maktab ta'limi va oliy o'quv yurtlari bo'yicha tartibga solingan.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi ta'limning bepul va har hafta 5 kun davomida olib borilishi zarurati bilan shaxsiy ta'limni ta'minlashni ta'minlaydi. Konstitutsiyada shuningdek, qiynaluvchan talabalarning o'qishiga

yordam berishga mo'ljallangan qonunchilik, o'qish uchun ma'yus uchun majburiyat stavkalari va xalqaro mazkur majburiyatni yozish inson huquqlarini himoya qilishni talab qiladi.

Ta'limning tamoyillarini tashkil etish asosida, qonunchilik boshqa bir qator qonunlari, farmonlar, qarorlar va institutlar moda modern fanlar va metodikalar, tajarbat va faol innovatsiyalar, elektron ta'lim asoslari va dizayn, o'quv, iste'molchi o'sish yillari va shuningdek cheklangan. Ular hisoblanadi.

O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimini mustaqil ijtimoiy faoliyatning eng muqim jizzalaridan biri deb qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan yoshlarning kasbiy yutuqlarini ta'minlashga yo'naladi. Ular ilg'or bir fikr muomsizligini, yoshlarning fikr to'pxonalari va xayoliy va fanlarga engil deb qaror qilish hamda odamlar uchun jihozlangan sharoitlarda mustaqil fuqarolar sifatida yashashi uchun zarur bo'lgan bilimlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Jahon iqtisodiyotining intensiv rivojlanishi va raqobatning tobora kuchayib borishi sharoitida ta'lim sohasining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotdagi strategik sohalardan biri sifatidagi ahamiyati tobora ortib bormoqda. "Hozirga kelib, ta'lim xizmatlari xalqaro bozorining hajmi 100 mlrd. AQSh dollarni tashkil etmoqda. «Inson kapitali» dunyo milliy boyligining 64 foizini tashkil etadi. Bu ko'rsatkich rivojlangan mamlakatlarda 70 foiz, o'rta daromadli mamlakatlarda 58 foiz, quyi daromadli mamlakatlarda 41 foizni tashkil etmoqda"¹⁸. Bugungi kunda oliy ta'limning innovatsion taraqqiyotning yetakchi omiliga aylanib borishi sharoitida ta'lim xizmatlari bozorini rivojlantirishga muhim vosita sifatida qaralmoqda.

Boshqaruv faoliyatining mohiyati to'g'risida g'oyalar, tushunchalar, mulohazalar, uni madaniy tarzda amalga oshirish tamoyillari, shakllari va usullari haqida tizim mavjuddir. Insoniyat tomonidan fan-texnika, iqtisodiyot va ijtimoiy muvaffaqiyatlar tobora oshirilib borishiga ko'ra

¹⁸<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/mirovoy-rynok-obrazovatelnyh-uslug-vysshey-shkoly>; <http://www.m-economy.ru/art.php?nArtId=3649>

boshqaruv faoliyatining ilmga bo'lgan talabi ham to'xtovsiz o'sib boradi. Bir tomondan, ta'lim boshqaruv faoliyatini konseptual boyitishdan manfaatdor bo'lsa, ikkinchi tomondan amaliyotchi boshqaruvchilar o'z faoliyatini ilmiy idrok etish, uni nazariy asoslashga intiladilar.

Shu o'rinda ta'lim faoliyatining jamiyat rivojlanishining muhim komponenti ekanligini ta'kidlab bu borada olimlarning qarashlariga e'tibor qaratamiz. Akademik S.S.G'ulomovning e'tirof etishicha¹⁹ "Ta'lim shunchaki jamiyat hayotining tomonlaridan birigina emas, balki umuman jamiyat rivojlanishining yetakchi, tizim hosil iluvchi omili bo'lmoqda".

Bu fikrni davom ettirgan iqtisochi olim Sh.R.Xolmuminov²⁰, "Zamonaviy sharoitlarda o'zbek ta'lim siyosatining asosiy vazifasi – ta'limning zamonaviy xususiyatlarini uning asosligi va davlat, jamiyat va shaxsning faol va istiqbolli ehtiyojlariga muvofiqligi asosida ta'minlash. Shunday qilib, ta'limni modernizatsiyalash - bu faqat mamlakat ta'lim majmuini rivojlantirishning muammolari majmui emas, balki ham siyosiy, ham umummilliy masaladir; u biror idoraga mansub loyiha bo'lishi mumkin emas. Respublika fuqarolari, davlat organlari institutlari, mahalliy o'zini boshqarish organlari, professional-pedagogik jamoatchilik, ilmiy, madaniy, tijorat va ijtimoiy institutlar ta'lim siyosatining faol sub'ektlari bo'lishlari lozim".

Hozirgi zamonda rivojlanish tendensiyalarini tushunish, ta'lim tizimini harakatlantiruvchi kuchlarni va omillarni tushunib yetish uchun ba'zi bir umumiy sharoitlarni va qonuniyatlarni o'rganib chiqish kerak. Bunday qonuniyatlarga quyidagilarni kiritish mumkin:

- Ilm talab ishlab chiqarish tarmoqlarining tobora rivojlanib, kengayib boryotganligi. Bunday tarmoqlar uchun xodimlarning 50 foiz va undan ortiq

¹⁹Gulyamov S.S. Obrazovanie v Uzbekistane: den segodnyashniy. M.// Alma mater. 2002. №7 8 S.

²⁰Xolmuminov Sh.R. O konsepsii modernizatsii obrazovaniya // Obrazovanie i sotsialno-ekonomicheskoe razvitie v nachale tretogo tysyacheletiya. Tez. dokl. konf. «XIX-Mejdunarodnye Plexanovskie chteniya», poryashennoy 10-letnemu yubileyu Filiala REA im. G.V. Plexanova v g. Tashkente. 2 fevralya 2006 goda. –T., 2006. – I. – S. 17-19

qismini oliy yoki o'rta-maxsus maxlumotli kishilar tashkil etishi zarur. Bu o'z navbatida oliy ta'lim rivojlanishini talab qiladi.

- Ilmiy va texnik ma'lumotlarning intensiv o'sishi, bu o'z navbatida bunday ma'lumotlarning o'rtacha har 7-10 yilda 2 karra ortishiga olib keladi. Bu soha mutaxassislari uzuluksiz ta'lim tizimiga qo'shilgan holda o'z-o'zini takomillashtirib, malakasini oshirib borishni taqoza etadi.

- Texnikaning tez-tez almashinib turishi, ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarining har 8-10 yilda ma'nan eskirishiga olib kelmoqda, bu o'z navbatida mutaxassislardan yaxshi fundamental tayyorgarlikni hamda tor mutaxassisliklarga xos bo'lgan tarzda yangi texnologiyalarni tezda samarali o'zlashtirib olishni ko'nikmalarini talab qiladi.

- Turli yo'nalishlardagi fanlar (biofizika, molekular genetika, nanoximiya va h.k.) tutashligini olib boriluvchi ilmiy tadqiqotlarning birinchi darajaga chiqib olishi. Bunday yo'nalishlarda yutuqqa faqat keng qamrovli va fundamental bilimlarga ega bo'lgan holda jamoa bilan ishlash qobiliyati ila erishish mumkin.

- O'ta kuchli ilmiy qobiliyatli tashqi muhitning mavjudligi nafaqat insonning jismoniy mehnatini, balkim hatto uning aqliy faoliyatini ham avtomatlashtirishga olib kelmoqda. Natijada ijodiy, algoritmlanmaydigan faoliyat turlarining qadri oshdi hamda shu faoliyatni amalga oshira oladigan mutaxassislarga talab otmoqda.

- Ilmiy va shunga o'xshash qiyin yo'nalishlardagi faoliyatga ko'plab kishilarning jalb qilinishing ortib borishi ayrim tadqiqotchilar tomonidan olimlarning o'rtacha evristik salohiyatining pasayishiga sabab bo'lishi sifatida ko'rsatilmoqda. Bunday pasayishni kompensatsiyalash uchun mutaxassislarni ilmiy va amaliy faoliyat metodologiyalari bilan qurollanirishni talab qiladi.

- Sanoat va qishloq xo'jaligida mehnat unumdorligining ortib borishi moddiy ishlab chiqarishdagi insonlar sonini qisqartiradi hamda aholining ko'proq madaniy, ma'rifiy va boshqa xizmat ko'rsatuvchi sohalarda bandligi

miqdorini ortishiga olib keladi. Bu o'z navbatida an'anaviy mutaxassisliklar o'rniga yangi zamonaviy sohalar, ayniqsa postindustrializm sohasi mutaxassislariga talabni oshiradi.

- Aholining daromadlari ortib turmush tarzi yaxshilanib borishi oliy ta'liga talabning ortishiga sabab bo'luvchi omillardan sanaladi. Vaqtning bunday talablarigi rivojlangan davlatlarning oliy ta'lim tizimi qanday javob qildi hamda shu orqali rivojlanib bordi. Shiddat bilan o'zgarib borayotgan, ko'p rejali jarayonlarda mutaxassislar jahon oliy ta'lim tizimining rivojlanishida quyidagi tendensiyalarni ajratib ko'rsatmoqdalar.²¹

1.Oliy ta'limning demokratlashuvi. Bu tendensiya oliy ta'limning umumiy ochiqligi, ta'lim olish shakli, turi, muhiti va mutaxassisliklarni tanlashning erkinligi, ta'lim jarayonlarinin boshqarishda avtoritarizm va ma'muriybuyruqbozlik usullaridan kechilayotgani kabi xususiyatlarni namoyon bo'layotganligi bilan xarakterlanadi.

2.Fan-ta'lim-ishlab chiqarish integratsiyasi va uning oqibatida ilmiy-o'quv-ishlab chiqarish komplekslarining yaratilayotganligi. Mazkur integratsiyada markaziy o'rinda, asosiy kuch sifatida ta'lim tizimi turibdi, uning bosh bo'g'ini esa universitetlardir. Universitetlar atrofida bu tizimda tayanch kollejlari, ixtisoslashgan maktablar, oliy ta'limdan keyingi ta'lim muassasalari birlashgan. Ilmiy tadqiqot markazlari ilmiy o'sishga asos sifatida, kompleks ishlanmalar, fanlararo ishlanmalar bilan ham o'qituvchilar ishtiroki ham talabalar ishtirokini ta'minlashni nazarda tutuvchi majmualar sifatida ishtirok etmoqda. Ishlab chiqarish sektori o'zlaridagi vaziyatdan shakllangan muammolarni oliy ta'lim va ilmiy tadqiqot muassasalariga yetkazish bilan ham o'zlaridagi konstruktorlik bo'limlari orqali ham yechishga ishtirok etib jarayonda qatnashishmoqda.

²¹ Zaynutdinov Sh.N., Ochilov A.O. Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini boshqarish samaradorligini baholash // Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim. – 2010. – 2. – 83-87-b.;

3. Oliy ta'limning fundamentallashuvi. Mutaxassisliklar doirasida umumiy va keng profilli, majburiy fanlar, yo'nalishlarni qisqartirish evaziga, mutaxassislik fanlari, fundamental, ixtiyoriy fanlarni ko'paytirish. Fundamentallashuvning o'ta chuqurlashuvi ham ko'pincha ta'limga bo'lgan qiziqishning so'nishiga olib keladi, tor ixtisoslik doirasida shakllanishni nazarda tutadi.

4. Ta'limning individuallashuvi. Bunda talabaning ta'lim olishi va mehnati individuallashuvi kuzatilmoqda. O'qish shakllari va muddatlarini, usullarini tanlashda talabaning individual yondoshuvlari, uning tahsil olishdagi rejalari individual tuzilishi, tahsil olishda talabaning individual psixofiziologik xususiyatlarining inobatga olib kurslarning tashkil qilinishi kabilarni ko'rsatish mumkin. Bu o'z navbatida fakultati va elektiv kurslarni tashkil etish, kuproq mustaqil shug'ullanish soatlari hisobidan shakllantirilmogda. Bu o'z navbatida auditoriya soatlarini kamaytirib, mustaqil ta'lim soatlarini oshirishga olib kelmoqda.

5. Ta'limning insonparvarlashuvi. Bunda tabiiy, texnik sohalardagi yo'nalishlardan ko'ra ijtimoiy, gumanitar, iqtisodiy yo'nalishlardagi fanlarni tarmoqlari kengaymoqda. Bundaylarning ulushi eng yetakchi OTMlarda hozirda 30-40 foizga yetadi. Talabaning madaniy dunyoqarashini kengaytirish, ijtimoiy munosabatlarni rivojlantirishni treninglar orqali kuchaytirish, turli diskussiyalar, rolli o'yinlar va boshqalar orqali ijtimoiy, madaniy munosabatlarni yaxshilashga yo'naltirish. Ta'limning insonparvarlashuvi o'qituvchining va talabaning shaxs sifatida o'z-o'zini namoyon qilishga qulay imkoniyatlarni yaratadi, insonlar bilan muloqot qilishda insoniylik xususiyatlarini oshiradi, boshqalar fikrini hurmat qilish, jamiyat oldida mas'uliyatni oshirish bo'yicha malakasini rivojlantiradi.

6. Oliy ta'limning kompyuterlashuvi. Ayrim yetakchi OTMlarda personal kompyuterlar soni talabalar sonidan oshib ketgan. Bunday ta'lim muassasalarida butun jarayonlar avtomatlashtirilgan. Ulardan avtomatlashgan

ta'lim resurslari sifatida ham axborot manbasi sifatida ham, texnik vositalar sifatida ham foydalaniladi. Ta'limni kompyuterlashtirilishi kasbiy faoliyatning xususiyatlarini o'zgartiradi. Bunda yangi kasbiy ko'nikmalar shakllanib boradi.

7.Oliy ta'limning ommaviylashuvi. Buni eng asosiy ikkita yo'nalishda yaqqol kuzatish mumkin, birinchisi, oliy ta'limga sarflanayotgan moliyaviy resurslarning oshib borayotganidan ko'rsak, ikkinchisi, talabalar sonining ortib borishida ko'rishimiz mumkin. 2009 yilda butun dunyo bo'yicha 153 mln. Talaba bo'lgan bo'lsa, 2016 yilda bu raqam 516,7 mln. kishini tashkil qildi. 2016 yilda oliy ta'lim jahon yalpi mahsulotida 1198,3 mlrd. AQSH dollariga teng miqdorni tashkil qildi.²² Bu miqdor 2015 yilga nisbatan 1 foiz ortganini ko'rish mumkin. YUNESKOning Ta'limni rejalashtirish Xalqaro instituti tayyorlagan "Har kimni oliy ta'lim bilan ta'minlashning olti usuli" yangi dokladi oliy ta'limni yanada ommaviy va moliyaviy jihatdan hammabop bo'lishiga olib kelishini nazarda tutadi. Bu dokladda talabalarning oylik o'qish summasi ularning oyltk daromadining 15 foizidan oshirmaslikni belgilab qo'yishgan. O'zbekistonda ham oliy ta'limning qamrovi so'nggi 3 yilda avvalgi 9 foizdan hozirda 12 foizga yetganini ko'ramiz. Bu raqam 2020 yilda 20 foiz, 2025 yilda 35 foiz, 2030 yilda 70 foizdan ortiqni tashkil etishi rejalashtirilgan.

8.OTMlarning mustaqilligining ortishi. Rivojlangan mamlakatlarda OTMlarning mustaqilligi so'nggi yillarda ortib bormoqda. Ular akademik, moliyaviy, siyosiy jihatdan mustaqilligini oshirib borishmoqda. Yevropa davlatlarida oliy ta'lim muassasalari avtonomlashuvi kuchayib bormoqda. Ular ma'muriy va moliyaviy o'z o'zini boshqarish, rahbarlarni o'zlari saylash kabi yo'nalishlarda mustaqil hisoblanishadi. Respublikamizda ham yangi O'zbekiston sharoitida oliy ta'lim muassaslarining mustaqilligi oshirib borish rejalashtirilgan. 2020 yildan dastlab 10 ta OTM moliyaviy jihatdan mustaqil bo'lib o'z resurslarini mustaqil idora qilishadi.

²² Aleks Muur. Ta'lim berish va ta'lim olish: pedagogika, ta'lim dasturi va tarbiya. - Rutledj. Ikkinchi nashr. 2012. 202-bet.

9. Professional o'qituvchiga talab ortishi. Jahon ta'lim va ilmiy sohasidagi qo'nggi yillar rivoji OTMlarda nafaqat o'qituvchini. Balki o'z kasbining professional darajadagi ustasi, mukammal soha vakilini talab qilmoqda. O'qituvchi ham ilmiy xodim, ham tadbirkor bo'lib ishlashi talab etilmoqda. Shuningdek, pedagogika va psixologiyaning o'rni ortib bormoqda, bunga sabab ta'lim jarayonlarining o'zgarishlaridagi xususiyatlar. Bundan tashqari professoro'qituvchilar mahalliy ijtimoiy muhitda ziyoli qatlam sifatida ijtimoiy faolligi ortishi ham tendensiya bo'lib bormoqda.

10. Oliy ta'lim tizimi faoliyatining jamoatchilik tomonidan doimiy baholanishi. Oliy ta'lim tizimi faoliyati raqobat jihatidan rivojlanib borar ekan, ular atrofdagilar tomonidan muntazam baholanib borishadi. Hozirda jahon OTMlari xalqaro agentliklar tomonidan turli ko'rsatkichlar asosida reyting baholanib bormoqda. Dunyoning yetakchi reyting agentliklari QS, THE, ARWU va boshqalar xalqaro oliy ta'limni ma'lum indikatorlar orqali baholab, ularning reytingini yuritishmoqda. Bu reyting o'z navbatida OTMlarni raqobatga chorlab, rivojlanishiga motivatsiya bermoqda. Bundan tashqari OTMlar jamoatchilikning boshqa institutlari tomonidan ham doimiy baholab, kuzatib boriladi.

11. OTMlarnig xalqarolashuvi. Dunyoning yetakchi OTmlari talabalarni o'zlariga jalb qilish bo'yicha turli yo'nalishlarda ishlarni olib borishadi. Bu bilan ular o'zlarinng asosiy faoliyatiga resurs yig'ishi bilan birga, dunyoning eng sara aqllarini yig'ib olishga harakat qiladi. Xorijda ta'lim olishning ortib borishi munosabati bilan mobil talabalarning ham soni ortib bormoqda. 2000 yilda xorijda tahsil olgan talabalarning soni 2 mln. bo'lgan bo'lsa, 2012 yilda ular 4 mln., 2018 yilda esa 7 mln. ni tashkil etdi. Bu raqamlar dunyo talabalari sonining o'rtacha 2-3 foizini tashkil etmoqda.²³

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018 yildagi "Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ta'lim sifatini oshirish va ularning mamlakatda amalga

²³ Saito, Y. (2008). Yaponiyada universitet-sanoat kooperativ tadqiqot dasturi: hozirgi holat va muammolar. Asia Pacific Journal of Cooperative Education, 9(2), 115-129.

oshirilayotgan keng qamrovli islohotlarda faol ishtirokini ta'minlash bo'yicha qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida"gi PQ-3775 sonli qarori qabul qilinishi bilan O'zbekistoda tahsil olishni xoxlovchi xorijiy fuqarolardan konsullik yig'implari undirish bekor qilindi, talabalarning o'zaro kelishuvlarga asosan qo'shma dasturlarda tahsil olishi hamda ularga O'zbekiston OTMlari hamda xorijiy ta'lim muassasalari o'rtasida o'zaro ikki tomonlama tan olinuvchi diplomlarni berish bo'yicha maqsadli ishlar boshlandi.

Oliy ta'limning yuqorida sanab o'tilgan xalqaro va mintaqaviy tendensiyalari albatta O'zbekistonda ham o'z ta'sirini o'tkazmoqda. Mamlakat OTMlari bu tendensiyalardan kelib chiqib, O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasiga asosan o'z strategiyalarini ishlab chiqqanlar.²⁴

O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim tizimini yaqin kelajakdagi istiqboli bugungi kunda oliy ta'lim tizimida malakali va raqobatbardosh kadrlarni tayyorlash dolzarb ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy masala bo'lib hisoblanadi. Oliy ta'lim tizimida mutaxassislarni tayyorlash jarayonida o'quv tarbiya faoliyatini tashkil etishning yangicha yondashuvlarini joriy etish, kadrlar tayyorlash va uzluksiz ta'lim tizimi davlat va nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarining rivojlanish dinamikasi va tarkibiy o'zgarishlarini davlat tomonidan tartibga solinishi amalga oshirilmoqda.

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**STRUCTURAL AND COMPOSITIONAL FEATURES OF
ADVERTISEMENT TEXTS IN VARIOUS FIELDS**

Annotation: Contrary to what some might believe, the advertising industry has a long history. Evidence of early advertising can be traced back to ancient Egypt, where a weaver handwrote an advertisement on papyrus. Similar findings have been unearthed in archaeological digs in ancient Greece and Rome.

Key words: text, Greece, Rome, human culture.

This suggests that advertising has been a part of human culture for most of our history. The components of an advertisement have been the subject of many studies, all aimed at determining the most effective styles and how to maximize their impact. These studies have delved into the elements of an advertisement to identify the most successful styles and how to optimize each one, thereby maximizing the advertisement's impact on the audience and ultimately increasing sales of the product or service. It's fair to say that over the past century, this field of study has essentially become a science.

Advertisement texts, regardless of the field, are meticulously crafted to achieve a specific purpose: to persuade the audience to take a particular action, such as purchasing a product or subscribing to a service. The structure and composition of these texts are influenced by various factors, including the nature of the product, the target audience, and the medium of communication.

The structure of an advertisement text typically includes the name of the product or service, its features, and a call to action. The name and brand of the product are usually prominently displayed to establish brand recognition. The features of the product are then detailed, often highlighting the benefits to the potential user. Finally, a call to action encourages the audience to make a purchase or seek more information.

The composition of advertisement texts involves the strategic use of language to create a persuasive narrative. This includes the use of stylistic devices, such as metaphors and similes, to create vivid imagery and appeal to the audience's emotions. The language used is often positive and emphasizes the superiority of the product or service. For instance, comparative and superlative adjectives may be used to highlight the product's advantages over competitors.

The structure and composition of advertisement texts can vary significantly across different fields. For example, a tech advertisement might focus on the innovative features of a product, using technical jargon to appeal to a tech-savvy audience. In contrast, a fashion advertisement might emphasize the aesthetic appeal of a product, using evocative language to create a sense of style and sophistication.

Moreover, the medium of communication also influences the structure and composition of advertisement texts. For instance, a billboard advertisement needs to convey its message quickly and effectively to passing motorists, so it might use large fonts, bold colors, and concise language. On the other hand, a magazine advertisement has more space to elaborate on the product's features and benefits, so it might use more detailed descriptions and persuasive narratives.

The Title (Headline)

The headline or title of an advertisement is a crucial component that carries the primary advertising message and argument. Historically, this headline was typically placed at the top of the page, but modern design practices allow for more flexibility in its placement. The success or failure of an ad can often hinge on the effectiveness of this headline.

The headline is a distinct part of the ad that is both separate and connected to the rest of the advertising message. Research has shown that 80% of readers do not read beyond the headline, underscoring its importance in capturing the audience's attention. The headline serves multiple functions, including attracting

the attention of potential consumers and sparking enough interest for them to read the main body of the ad.

The formulation of an effective headline requires careful consideration of various factors. It must be well-crafted and expressive, and its effectiveness largely depends on how well it aligns with other elements of the ad, such as graphics, images, and content. The creation of an effective headline also requires an understanding of consumer psychology, including their needs, cultural background, and interests.

The headline can have a significant psychological impact on the reader. If it provides valuable information about the product and successfully captures attention, it can greatly pique the interest of potential buyers. The headline presents the sales idea, and if this idea resonates with the reader, they are more likely to continue reading the ad text. Therefore, most ads include a headline, even if they may not incorporate all other elements of the advertising message.

Characteristics of the title:

1. The title should be capable of drawing public attention to the advertisement, enticing potential consumers of the advertised goods and services. This is achieved by using impactful phrases, words, and symbols that resonate with the target audience.
2. It should have an immediate and direct influence on the reader.
3. The words used in the title should be precise, potent, and easily comprehensible.
4. It should be able to guide the reader's focus towards the concepts presented in the advertisement, leading them to concentrate on its content.
5. The title should swiftly and effectively create a specific image or impression of the advertised product or service.
6. It should be capable of enticing potential consumers to read the entire advertising text.

7. The title should include information about the benefits that the consumer can gain from using the product or service.

2) The Subtitle (The Sub- Headline)

The subtitle, also known as the sub-headline, is a critical component in advertising text. It serves as a bridge between the headline and the main body of the advertisement, providing additional context and information.

The subtitle is typically smaller than the headline but larger than the body text, often bolded or in a contrasting color to stand out. While not always present in advertisements, it becomes essential when the headline alone cannot fully convey the intended message. In such cases, the subtitle elaborates on the promise made in the headline or emphasizes the unique features of the product or service.

The subtitle plays a significant role in retaining the reader's attention and encouraging them to read the entire advertisement¹. It is designed to keep the reader engaged, providing an additional opportunity to draw them in¹. This is particularly important in today's fast-paced world, where consumers often skim through content. A well-crafted subtitle can slow down the reader and draw them into the advertisement.

The content of the subtitle depends on various factors, including the product or service being advertised, the target audience, and the overall advertising strategy. For instance, a subtitle for a tech product might highlight its innovative features, while a subtitle for a fashion product might emphasize its style and sophistication.

Moreover, the subtitle can be used to target a specific demographic. For example, a subtitle like "Designed for the modern woman" immediately signals to female readers that the product is specifically for them.

3) Slogans, Logos, Signs, and Symbols

Slogans, logos, signs, and symbols are integral elements of advertising texts. They play a crucial role in creating brand identity, conveying key messages, and influencing consumer behavior.

- 1) Slogans: A slogan is a catchy phrase or sentence that encapsulates a brand's identity, mission, or unique selling proposition. It's designed to be memorable and resonate with the target audience. For instance, Nike's "Just Do It" slogan is a powerful call to action that aligns with the brand's focus on performance and determination. Similarly, McDonald's "I'm Lovin' It" slogan conveys a sense of enjoyment and satisfaction associated with their food.
- 2) Logos: A logo is a visual symbol or design used to identify a company or brand. It's often the first thing people associate with a brand, and it plays a crucial role in creating a strong first impression. For example, Apple's simple yet iconic apple logo, or McDonald's golden arches, are instantly recognizable worldwide. A well-designed logo can convey a brand's values, quality, and reliability.
- 3) Signs: In the context of advertising, signs are visual or auditory cues that represent specific information about the brand or product. They can be words, images, sounds, or even smells. For example, the "Intel Inside" jingle is a sign that has become synonymous with Intel's microprocessors. Similarly, the color red is often associated with Coca-Cola.
- 4) Symbols: Symbols are a type of sign that represent a particular idea or concept. They are often used in advertising to convey complex ideas quickly and effectively. For instance, a heart symbol is often used to represent love or care, while a green leaf might symbolize nature or sustainability. For example, Dove uses the dove bird, a symbol of peace and purity, in its logo to represent the brand's commitment to real beauty.

Slogans, logos, signs, and symbols are powerful tools in advertising. They help create a distinctive brand identity, convey key messages, and influence consumer perceptions and behaviors. Whether it's a catchy slogan, a memorable

logo, a recognizable sign, or a meaningful symbol, these elements work together to create effective and impactful advertising texts.

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WORDLY
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Farg'ona viloyati yuridik texnikumi davlat tilida

ish yuritish fani o'qituvchisi, 3-darajali yurist

ISH YURITISH VA HUJJATCHILIK TARIXI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi ish yuritish va hujjatchilikni rivojlantirishning asosiy bosqichlarini ko'rib chiqish, shuningdek ularning zamonaviy axborotni boshqarish jarayonlariga ta'sirini tahlil qilishdir. Maqolada ish yuritishning qadim zamonlardan hozirgi kungacha bo'lgan evolyutsiyasi yuzasidan fikr yuritilgan bo'lib, texnik yutuqlar va ijtimoiy-madaniy jihatlar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: boshqaruv faoliyati, hujjatlar, ish yuritish, hujjatchilik tarixi, ma'muriy faoliyat, gil planshetlar, ierogliflar, mixxat yozuvi, papirus, bambuk, yog'och lavhalar, ipak o'ramlari, hujjatlashtirish texnologiyalari, elektron katalog, zamonaviy ish yuritish, raqamlashtirish.

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HISTORY OF PROCEEDINGS AND DOCUMENTATION

Annotation: the purpose of this article is to consider the main stages of the development of proceedings and documentation, as well as to analyze their impact on modern information management processes. The article reflects on the evolution of business from ancient times to the present, highlighting technical achievements and socio-cultural aspects.

Keywords: management activities, documents, proceedings, documentation history, administrative activities, clay tablets, hieroglyphs, cuneiform, papyrus, bamboo, wooden tablets, silk scrolls, documentation technologies, electronic catalog, modern stationery, digitization.

Hujjatlarni yuritish va hujjatlashtirish insoniyat tarixi davomida davlatlar, korxonalar va tashkilotlarni boshqarishda asosiy rol o'ynaydi. Yozuvning birinchi shakllari paydo bo'lganidan beri odamlar muhim ma'lumotlarni yozib olishga intilishdi, bu ularga jamiyatning huquqiy, moliyaviy va madaniy asoslarini yaratishga imkon berdi. Yozuvlarni boshqarish tarixi insoniyat sivilizatsiyasi evolyutsiyasini aks ettiradi, boshqacha aytganda, loy planshetlar

va pergamentdan raqamli hujjatlar va axborotni boshqarish tizimlarigacha yoritib beradi.

Hujjatlarni boshqarish va hujjatlash tirish tarixini o'rganish nafaqat axborotni boshqarish tizimlarining qanday rivojlanganligini tushunish imkonini beradi, balki texnologik taraqqiyot va ijtimoiy o'zgarishlar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni ham ochib beradi. Hujjatlar bilan ishlashning an'anaviy usullari tez sur'atlar bilan sun'iy intellekt va blokcheyn kabi innovatsion texnologiyalar bilan almashtirilayotgan zamonaviy raqamlashtirish sharoitida bu mavzu ayniqsa dolzarbdir.

Ish yuritish va hujjatchilik tarixi qadimgi davrlarga borib taqaladi, birinchi sivilizatsiyalar boshqaruv, savdo va huquqiy munosabatlar uchun ma'lumotlarni yozib olish zarurligini anglay boshlagan. Hujjatlarning dastlabki shakllari insoniyat jamiyati rivojlanishining ajralmas qismi bo'lib, yozuv va boshqaruvning rivojlanishida muhim rol o'ynagan.

Ish yuritishni rivojlantirishning birinchi markazlaridan biri Mesopotamiya bo'lib, u erda miloddan avvalgi IV ming yillikda ma'lumotlarni yozib olish uchun gil planshetlardan foydalana boshlaganlar. Ular mixxatdan, ya'ni qamish tayoq yordamida nam loyga bosilgan xanjar shaklidagi belgilarga asoslangan yozuv tizimidan foydalanganlar. Ushbu planshetlarda turli xil yozuvlar mavjud edi: biznes hisobotlari va shartnomalardan tortib yuridik va ma'muriy matnlargacha. Bunday planshetlar saqlanadigan birinchi arxivlarning yaratilishi muhim yutuq bo'lib, buxgalteriya hisobi va boshqaruv tizimlarining rivojlanishidan dalolat beradi.

Miloddan avvalgi 3-ming yillikda Qadimgi Misrda hujjatlarning yana bir muhim shakli - papirus paydo bo'ldi. Qamishdan yasalgan papirus loy lavhalarga qaraganda yengilroq va bardoshli hujjatlarni yaratishga imkon beruvchi birinchi material edi. Hujjatlarda ierogliflar - obyektlar, g'oyalar yoki tovushlarni ifodalovchi belgilar ishlatilgan. Papiruslar ma'muriy buyruqlar, soliq hisoblari, huquqiy shartnomalar va boshqa rasmiy hujjatlarni yozib olish uchun

xizmat qilgan, keyinchalik ular maxsus omborlarda va davlat arxivlarida saqlangan.

Qadimgi Xitoyda foydalanilgan hujjatlarning dastlabki shakllariga bambuk va yog'och lavhalar, keyinchalik esa ipak o'ramlari kiradi. Miloddan avvalgi 2-ming yillikda xitoyliklar yozuv uchun cho'tka va siyohdan foydalana boshladilar, bu esa birinchi xattotlik yozuvlarini yaratishga olib keldi. Xitoyning byurokratik hisob-kitob tizimlari imperiyaning markazlashgan boshqaruviga hissa qo'shgan batafsil yozuvlar, ma'muriy qarorlar va huquqiy matnlarni o'z ichiga olgan eng murakkab tizimlardan biri edi.

Gretsiya va Rimda ish yuritish papirus va pergament yordamida rivojlangan. Yunon shahar-davlatlari va Rim provinsiyalarida hukumat qarorlari, sud qarorlari, soliq hujjatlari va shartnomalar yozuvlarini o'z ichiga olgan keng arxivlar mavjud edi. Birinchi tizimlashtirilgan davlat idorasi Rimda paydo bo'lib, unda buxgalteriya kitoblari va hujjatlari maxsus ajratilgan joylarda saqlangan.

Ish yuritish va hujjatlashtirishning dastlabki shakllari yozuvning rivojlanishi va birinchi davlat tuzilmalarining paydo bo'lishi bilan chambarchas bog'liq edi. Ular boshqaruv tizimlarining keyingi rivojlanishi uchun asos bo'ldi, shuningdek, avloddan-avlodga o'tadigan qimmatli bilimlarni to'plash imkonini berdi. Qadimgi sivilizatsiyalarda hujjatlarning shakllanishi va evolyutsiyasi boshqaruv va huquqni muhofaza qilishda yozma dalillarning ahamiyatini belgilab beruvchi zamonaviy hisob yuritish amaliyotiga asos soldi.

O'rta asrlar ish yuritish rivojlanishining muhim davri bo'lib, Yevropa va Sharqiy davlatlarning ma'muriy-huquqiy tizimlari sezilarli darajada murakkablashdi. Ish yuritish va hujjat yuritish davlat hokimiyatining asosi, shuningdek, cherkov va feodal hokimiyatining asosiy elementiga aylandi. Bu vaqtda markazlashtirilgan idoralar shakllana boshladi, hujjatlarning yangi shakllari ishlab chiqildi, pergament va qog'oz tashuvchilardan foydalanish

ma'lumotlarni yozib olish va saqlash imkoniyatlarini sezilarli darajada kengaytirdi.

O'rta asrlarda qirollik va knyazlik idoralari ish yuritishning asosiy markaziga aylandi. Ular davlat boshqaruvi uchun zarur bo'lgan hujjatlarni yaratish, nusxalash va saqlash bilan shug'ullangan. Idoralarda farmonlar, nizomlar, shartnomalar va boshqa rasmiy hujjatlar ishlab chiqildi.

14-asrda Yevropa arab davlatlaridan olib kelingan qog'ozdan keng foydalana boshladi, bu esa hujjatlar ishlab chiqarishni ancha soddalashtirdi va ularning tannarxini pasaytirdi. Qog'ozning paydo bo'lishi hujjatlarning jamiyatning keng qatlamlari orasida tarqalishiga yordam berdi va qog'ozbozlik hajmini oshirdi.

Uyg'onish davri (XV-XVI asrlar) turli xil hujjatlashtirish texnologiyalaridan faol foydalanish va ishlab chiqish davri edi. Asosiy yutuq 15-asr o'rtalarida Iogannes Gutenberg tomonidan bosmaxona ixtirosi bo'ldi. Matbaa texnologiyalari hujjatlarni yaratish jarayonini sezilarli darajada soddalashtirdi va ularning tez tarqalishiga yordam berdi. Bu qog'ozbozlik tizimida inqilob qildi: hujjatlar yanada qulayroq bo'ldi, ma'lumotlarning tarqalishi tezlashdi va qo'lda nusxa ko'chirishga xos bo'lgan xatolarning ta'siri kamaydi.

Uyg'onish va Reformatsiya davri ish yuritish va hujjatlashtirish evolyutsiyasida muhim rol o'ynadi, ularni yopiq, sekin va murakkab tizimlardan samaraliroq va foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan tizimlarga aylantirdi. Matbaa texnologiyasining joriy etilishi, byurokratik tuzilmalarning rivojlanishi, diniy va ijtimoiy sohalardagi o'zgarishlar Evropa va jahon boshqaruv va axborot madaniyatiga ta'sir ko'rsatgan ish yuritishni yanada isloh qilish va modernizatsiya qilish uchun asos yaratdi.

XVII-XIX asrlar markazlashgan davlatlarning rivojlanishi, byurokratiyaning kuchayishi va yangi texnologiyalarning joriy etilishi bilan bog'liq ish yuritishda jiddiy o'zgarishlar davri bo'ldi. Ma'rifat davri, sanoat

inqilobi va zamonaviy milliy davlatlarning shakllanishi boshqaruv va hujjat aylanishi tizimini tubdan o'zgartirdi. Ish yuritish ma'muriy nazorat va boshqaruvning muhim vositasiga aylandi va hujjatlarni standartlashtirish va yangi texnologiyalarni ishlab chiqish zamonaviy hujjatlashirish tizimining boshlanishini belgiladi.

XVIII asr oxiri va XIX asr boshlarida sodir bo'lgan sanoat inqilobi ish yuritishda jiddiy o'zgarishlar olib keldi. Telegraf, bug' mashinalari va yozuv mashinkalari kabi yangi texnologiyalarning paydo bo'lishi hujjatlarni uzatish va yaratish jarayonini sezilarli darajada tezlashtirdi. 19-asrning o'rtalarida ixtiro qilingan yozuv mashinkasi yangi davrning ramzi bo'ldi, chunki u hujjatlarni tayyorlashni standartlashtirish va ularni tayyorlash vaqtini qisqartirish imkonini berdi. Telegraf davlat idoralari, armiya va korxonalar o'rtasida tezkor aloqani ta'minladi, bu esa axborot almashinuvini yanada samarali qildi. Gazeta va ommaviy matbuotning paydo bo'lishi ham hujjatli makonning kengayishiga yordam berdi: ma'muriy-huquqiy hujjatlar rasmiy nashrlarda e'lon qilina boshladi, bu esa boshqaruvning shaffofligini oshirishga yordam berdi.

Yangi vaqtlar ish yuritishda standartlarni faol joriy etish davriga aylandi. Birinchi marta buxgalteriya daftarlari, buxgalteriya registrlari, pasport va ruxsatnomalar kabi hujjatlarning yagona shakllari qo'llanila boshlandi. 18-asrda fransuz inqilobi yanada standartlashtirishga yordam berdi, chunki yangi hukumat barcha ma'muriy jarayonlarni birlashtirishga harakat qildi.

Jahon urushlari ish yuritishning rivojlanishiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatdi, chunki ular keng ko'lamli axborotni boshqarish, rejalashtirish va muvofiqlashtirishni talab qildi. Harbiy bo'limlar qo'shinlarni boshqarish, moddiy-texnik ta'minot va ta'minot uchun murakkab hisob, aloqa va hujjatlar tizimlarini ishlab chiqdilar. Birinchi avtomatlashtirilgan boshqaruv tizimlari, masalan, IBM tabulatorlari paydo bo'ldi va ular katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash uchun ishlatilgan.

XX asr ish yuritishning muhim bosqichi ma'lumotlarni saqlash va arxivlash tizimlarining rivojlanishi edi. Magnit tashuvchilar, masalan, lentalar va floppi disklar katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarni raqamli saqlash, hujjatlarni qidirish uchun joy va vaqtni sezilarli darajada tejash imkonini berdi. 1980-yillarda shaxsiy kompyuterlar va serverlarning keng tarqalishi arxivlarni boshqarish, elektron kataloglarni joriy etish va hujjatlarga kirishni avtomatlashtirish uchun yangi imkoniyatlar ochdi.

Ushbu o'zgarishlar elektron arxivlar va ma'lumotlar bazalarini rivojlantirishni rag'batlantirdi, bu esa qog'ozni og'ir saqlashni bartaraf etdi va axborotning ishonchli saqlanishini ta'minladi.

XX asrning oxirida raqamli texnologiyalar va dasturiy ta'minotning rivojlanishi bilan "qog'ozsiz ofis" tushunchasi paydo bo'ldi. Qog'oz hujjatlarni chop etish, saqlash va yo'q qilish xarajatlarini kamaytirish istagi elektron hujjat aylanish tizimlarini ishlab chiqish va joriy etishga olib keldi.

Bugungi dunyoda Elektron hujjat boshqaruvi (ESM) tizimlari aksariyat tashkilotlar uchun standartga aylandi. Bunday tizimlar nafaqat hujjatlarni raqamli saqlash imkonini beradi, balki ularni yaratish, muvofiqlashtirish, tarqatish va versiyalarni boshqarishni ham ta'minlaydi. Bu xatolarni kamaytiradi va xodimlar va bo'limlar o'rtasidagi aloqani yaxshilaydi.

Zamonaviy ish yuritish va raqamlashtirish axborot va hujjat aylanishiga yondashuvlarni tubdan o'zgartirdi. Avtomatlashtirish, bulutli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish jarayonlarni yanada samarali va xavfsiz qildi, elektron imzo va raqamli arxivlarning joriy etilishi esa tashkilotlar ichida ham, o'rtasida ham o'zaro aloqalarni sezilarli darajada tezlashtirdi va soddalashtirdi. Bu o'zgarishlar nafaqat samaradorlikni oshirish, balki global raqamli iqtisodiyotning yangi muammolariga moslashishga yordam beradi, ofis ishlarini yanada moslashuvchan, shaffof va ishonchli qiladi.

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ISSIQLIK O`TKAZUVCHANLIK TENGLAMASINI

INTEGRO-INTERPOLATSIYALASH METODI YORDAMIDA

HISOBLASH EXPERIMENTINI YARATISH NATIJALAR TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Bu maqolada bir jinsli konservativ sxemalar berilgan va bu sxemalar asosida qurilishi kerak bo`lgan masalalar qo`yilgan. Issiqlik o`tkazuvchanlik tenglamasi keltirilgan bu masalaga mos bo`lgan chegaraviy shartlar qo`yilgan va shartlar asosida masalani yechish algoritmi va kompyuter dasturi ham keltirilgan. C++ builder dasturlash tilida dasturi tuzilgan. Ayirmali sxemaga keltirilgan va bu natija boshqa usul yechimi bilan taqqoslangan.

Kalit so`zlar: bir jinsli sxemalar, ayirmali sxema, approksimatsiya, chegaraviy shart, C++ dastur kodi.

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THE EQUATION OF HEAT CONDUCTIVITY

USING THE INTEGRO-INTERPOLATION METHOD

CREATION OF CALCULATION EXPERIMENT RESULTS

ANALYSIS

ANNOTATION

In this article, homogeneous conservative schemes are given and the issues that should be built on the basis of these schemes are set. The equation of heat transfer is presented, the boundary conditions suitable for this problem are set, and the algorithm and computer program for solving the problem based on the conditions are also presented. The program is built in the C++ builder programming language. A differential scheme is presented and this result is compared with the solution of another method.

Key words: homogeneous schemes, differential scheme, approximation, boundary condition, C++ builder program code.

Zamonaviy kompyuterlarning keng miqyosda qo`llanilayotganligi sababli, amaliy masalalarni yechishda xususiy ko`rinishdagi ayrim masalalarni

yechishga mo'ljallangan ayirmali sxemalardan foydalanish va ular uchun dasturlar tuzish maqsadga muvofiq emasligi tobora yaqqol sezilmoqda. Shunday ayirmali sxemalarga ega bo'lishimiz lozimki, ular differensial tenglamalar tipi, boshlang'ich va chegaraviy shartlar sinfi, differensial tenglama koeffitsientlari tegishli bo'lgan funksional fazoning berilishi orqali aniqlanadigan butun bir sinfdagi masalalarni yechishga yaroqli bo'lsin. Bunday universal ayirmali sxemalar, tabiiyki, ixtiyoriy to'rlar ketma-ketligida va qaralayotgan masalalar sinfidagi ixtiyoriy dastlabki masala uchun yaqinlashish va turg'unlik shartlarini qanoatlantirsin. Butun bir masalalar sinfi uchun hisoblash algoritmlarining aynan bir xil bo'lishi talabi birjinsli ayirmali sxemalar tushunchasiga olib keladi.

Ayirmali masalaning qo'yilishi. Masalaning yechish algoritmi.

Kompyuter dasturi.

Quyidagi masalani ko'rib chiqamiz.

$$\begin{cases} (k(x)u'(x))' - q(x)u(x) = -f(x), & 0 < x < 1, \\ u(0) = \mu_1, \quad u(1) = \mu_2, \quad k(x) \geq c_1 > 0, \quad q(x) \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Kesma $0 \leq x \leq 1$ da teng oraliqli to'ra kiritamiz:

$$\bar{\omega}_h = \{x_i = ih, i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad hN = 1\}.$$

$h_i = x_i - x_{i-1}, i = 1; 2; 3; \dots; N$ kiritamiz va (1) tenglamani quyidagi ayirmali tenglama bilan almashtiramiz.

$$\begin{cases} (ay_{\bar{x}})_{\bar{x},i} - d_i y_i = -\varphi_i, & 1 \leq i \leq N - 1 \\ y_0 = \mu_1, \quad y_N = \mu_2 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

bu yerda $d_i = q(x_i), \varphi_i = f(x_i), a_i$ ni $k(x)$ funksiyaning koeffitsientining approksimatsiyasidan foydalangan holda quyidagicha topamiz $a_i = k(x_i - 0.5h_i)$. (2) ayirmali hosiladagi $(ay_{\bar{x}})_{\bar{x},i}$ ni quyigadicha yozish mumkin.

$$(ay_{\bar{x}})_{\bar{x},i} = \frac{1}{\tilde{h}_i} \left(a_{i+1} \frac{y_{i+1} - y_i}{h_{i+1}} - a_i \frac{y_i - y_{i-1}}{h_i} \right),$$

So'ng (3.2) sxemaga qo'ysak quyidagiga teng bo'ladi

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{1}{\tilde{h}_i} \left(a_{i+1} \frac{y_{i+1} - y_i}{h_{i+1}} - a_i \frac{y_i - y_{i-1}}{h_i} \right) - d_i y_i = -\varphi_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq N - 1 \\ y_0 = \mu_1, \quad y_N = \mu_2 \end{array} \right.$$

bu yerda $\tilde{h}_i = 0.5(h_i + h_{i+1})$ x nuqtadagi o`rtacha qadam bo`lsa, (2) masala uchun sistemani quyidagicha keltiramiz.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} C_0 y_0 - B_0 = F_0, \quad i = 0, \\ -A_i y_{i-1} + C_i y_i - B_i y_{i+1} = F_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq N - 1, \\ -A_N y_{N-1} + C_N y_N = F_N, \quad i = N \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

Bu yerda

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} B_0 = A_N = 0, \quad C_0 = C_N = 1, \quad F_0 = \mu_1, \quad F_N = \mu_2, \quad F_i = \varphi_i \\ A_i = \frac{a_i}{\tilde{h}_i h_i}, \quad B_i = \frac{a_{i+1}}{\tilde{h}_i h_{i+1}}, \quad C_i = A_i + B_i + d_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq N - 1 \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

Demak (1) differensial tenglamani yechish uchun yetarlicha silliq bo`lgan $k(x)$, $q(x)$, $\varphi(x)$ funksiyalarni tanlab olamiz:

$$k(x) = x^2 + 1, \quad q(x) = 3x^2 + 4, \quad f(x) = 2x^3 + 1$$

Bundan tanlab olingan funksiyalarni (3.1) tenglamaga oborib qo`ysak quyidagi differensial tenglamaga ega bo`lamiz.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} ((x^2 + 1)u'(x))' - (3x^2 + 4)u(x) = -2x^3 - 1 \\ \mu_1 = 0.5; \quad \mu_2 = 1.7 \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

(4) tenglama (2) ayirmali sxemaga yuqorida olib kelingan va shu belgilashlar asosida masalaning yechish algoritmi Pragonka metodi yordamida hisoblanadi.

Masalani $[0; 1]$ segmentda yechamiz. Bu kesmani N qismga bo`lib to`r kiritamiz.

Masalani hisoblash dasturini c++ builder muhitida yaratamiz. Dastur kodi quyidagicha:

C++ Builder dasturi

```
//-----
#include <vcl.h>
#pragma hdrstop
```

```

#include <math.h>
#include "Unit1.h"
//-----
#pragma package(smart_init)
#pragma resource "*.dfm"
TForm1 *Form1;
//-----
__fastcall TForm1::TForm1(TComponent* Owner) : TForm(Owner)
{}
//-----
void __fastcall TForm1::Button1Click(TObject *Sender)
{Memo1->Clear();
int i,n;
n=StrToInt(Edit1->Text);
float a[100],k, x[100], h[100], d[100], fi[100], y[100], z[100], A[100],
B[100], C[100], F[100], alfa[100], betta[100], M1, M2, kapa1, kapa2;
M1=StrToFloat(Edit2->Text);
M2=StrToFloat(Edit3->Text);
k=1/float(n);
for(i=1; i<=n; i++)
{ x[0]=0;
x[i]=x[i-1]+k;
h[i]=x[i]-x[i-1];
a[i]=pow((x[i]-0.5*h[i]),2)+1;
d[i]=3*pow(x[i],2)+4;
fi[i]=2*pow(x[i],3)+1; }
for(i=1; i<=n; i++) {
z[i]=0.5*(h[i]+h[i+1]);
B[0]=0; A[n]=0; C[0]=1; C[n]=1; F[0]=M1; F[n]=M2;

```

```
F[i]=fi[i];
A[i]=a[i]/(z[i]*h[i]);
B[i]=a[i+1]/(z[i]*h[i+1]);
C[i]=A[i]+B[i]+d[i];    }
for(i=1; i<=n; i++)
{   alfa[1]=0; betta[1]=M1;
    alfa[i+1]=B[i]/(C[i]-A[i]*alfa[i]);
    betta[i+1]=(F[i]+A[i]*betta[i])/C[i]-A[i]*alfa[i]; }
for(i=n-1; i>0; i--) {
    y[n]=M2;
    y[i]=alfa[i+1]*y[i+1]+betta[i+1];}
for (i=1; i<=n; i++){
    Memo1->Lines->Add(" "+FloatToStr(y[i]));}
//-----
void __fastcall TForm1::Button2Click(TObject *Sender){Close();    }
//-----
```

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TATU Qarshi filiali erkin tadqiqotchisi

**XX ASR BOSHLARIDA TURKISTON VA USMONIYLAR
O'RTASIDAGI ALOQALAR**

Annotatsiya

Ushbu tezisdagi birinchi jahon urushi davrida Turkiston o'lkasining Usmoniylar davlati (bugungi O'zbekistonning Turkiya davlati bilan) bilan o'rnatgan aloqalari tarixiy manbalar va tarixiy asarlarga tayangan holatda yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Birinchi jahon urushi, asirga olingan turk askarlari, asirlar lageri, moddiy va ma'naviy yordam, elchilik aloqalari.

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**RELATIONS BETWEEN TURKESTAN AND THE OTTOMANS
IN THE EARLY 20TH CENTURY**

Annotation

This thesis, based on historical sources and historical works, illuminates the relations established by the Turkestan region with the Ottoman Empire (present-day Uzbekistan with the Turkish state) during the First World War.

Key words. World War I, captured Turkish soldiers, prisoner camp, material and moral assistance, and diplomatic relations.

Kirish. Turkiy davlatlar xalqlarining hayoti bir-biri bilan doimo uzviy bog'liqlikda rivojlanib borgan. Ular o'rtasidagi siyosiy, iqtisodiy va madaniy aloqalar doimo mavjud bo'lganligini tarixiy manbalar ham isbotlaydi. O'zbekiston va Turkiya davlatining vakillari yillar mobaynida ushbu ikki xalq taqdiri, turkiy xalqlar hayoti bir-biri bilan uzviy bog'langanligi va boy tarixga ega ekanliklari nuqtayi nazaridan bir-birlarining tarixlariga qiziqib, ikki davlat orasida ta'lim, madaniy aloqalarni yo'lga qo'yish maqsadida mutaxassis olimlar almashinib o'z tadqiqotlarini amalga oshirganlar. Bundan tashqari birinchi jahon urushi davrida Turkiston o'lkasi va aholisi Turkiyaga ma'naviy dastak bo'lishga intilishlari bilan bir qatorda Turkiston musulmonlari Turkiya aholisini moddiy jihatdan qo'llab quvvatlashga ham harakat qilganlar. Ushbu fikrlarimizni

quyidagi ba'zi tarixiy ma'lumotlar va manbalar bilan yanada aniqroq aks ettirishimiz mumkin.

1917-1923-yillarda Rossiyaning katta shaharlarida turk askarlarini uchratish mumkin edi. 1917-yil may oyida Butun Rossiya Musulmonlarining Birinchi Kongresi bo'lib o'tadi. 1912-yilning iyun oyida Nijniy Novgorod musulmonlari Butun Rossiya musulmonlari Ijroiya tashkilotiga asirga tushgan turk askarlarining yomon ahvoli haqida maktub yozadi. Maktubda Rossiya tomonidan Kavkaz frontida asir olingan turk askarlari juda qiyin sharoitda asirlar lagerida saqlanayotgani haqida yozilgan edi. Nijniy Novgorod asirlar lagerida 500 ga yaqin asir bo'lgan. Bu yerdagi asirlarning 200 ga yaqini kasalliklar va og'ir shart-sharoit natijasida vafot etgan. Nijniy Novgoroddagi musulmonlar o'zlari qiyin sharoitda yashasalar ham turk asirlariga yordam berishga harakat qilishadi. Asirlar orasida 90 yoshli bir keksa askar ham bor ekanligi manbalarda uchraydi [1;181-187]. Nijniy Novgorod Musulmonlar tashkiloti Usmoniylar hukumati bilan ko'rishib bu askarlarni almashtirish xususida muzokara olib borishadi. Bu askarlar bu hududdagi sovuq havо iqlimiga moslasha olmasligi, ularni havosi issiqroq shaharlarga joylashtirish kerakligi taklifi beriladi. Bu kabi takliflarni amalga oshishi turk askarlari uchun juda muhim edi. Bu harakatlar insoniylik jihatidan ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etardi. Birinchi jahon urushida Rossiya tomonidan asir olingan turk askarlari Turkiston ijtimoiy, siyosiy va madaniy hayotidagi faoliyatlari bilan alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Turk askarlari Turkistonliklar tomonidan iliq kutib olinadi va bu tabiiy bir munosabat sifatida qabul qilinadi. Markaziy kuchlar urushda mag'lub bo'lganliklarini qabul qildilar va ittifoqchi kuchlardan sulh so'rashdi. Urushda mag'lub bo'lgan hukumat va Sadr Tal'at Posho iste'foga chiqdi va ittifoqchi siyosiy liderlar Turkiyani tark etishdi. 1920-yilning 16-martda inglizlar Istanbulni ishg'ol etdi. Usmoniylar poytaxti ittifoqchilarning harbiy boshqaruvi qo'lga o'tdi. Inglizlar "Mejlesi Mebusan" deb nomlangan turk Milliy Majlisiga bostirib kirdi. Bir qancha millat vakillari Anqarada yig'ildilar.

1920-yil 23-aprelda Anqarada “ Turkiya Millat Majlisi” nomli majlisda yig‘ilib Mustafu Kamol Poshoni prezident etib tayinlaydilar. 1920-yilning may oyida Samarqandda bosilib chiqqan “ Mehnatkashlar ovozi” gazetasida Angliya tomonidan Istanbulni egallanishi Turkiston xalqlarining noroziligiga sabab bo‘lgani va hukumatning turk qardoshlariga yordam berishi to‘g‘risida xabar berganligi haqida maqola e‘lon qilingan edi. Turkiston Xalq universitetida tashkil etilgan mitingda Turkiyani qo‘llab quvvatlovchi va Istanbulning ishg‘ol etilishiga qarshi fikrlar bildiriladi. Shuningdek mitingda Turkiyaga moddiy yordam uchun pul yig‘ish maqsadida besh kishidan iborat vakillar ma’sul etib tayinlanadi [2;26] 1921-yilning 20-iyunida (ba’zi manbalarda 15-iyunda deb keltiriladi) [3.137]. Buxoro Xalq Sovet Respublikasi Nozirlar Kengashi va Tashqi ishlar vazirligi tomonidan Turkiya Tashqi ishlari vazirligiga maktub yoziladi. Maktubda Anadolu hukumati va Buxoro Xalq Sovet Respublikasi orasidagi elchilik aloqalarining yaxshilanishiga xizmat qiluvchi elchilarni tayinlash haqida kelishuvni imzolash taklif etiladi. Maktubda: “Buxoro xalqi va hukumati jasoratli, millatparvar turk xalqini olqishlaydi va sizlarni Buxoroda ko‘rishdan mamnun bo‘lamiz” deb yozilgan edi. Bu maktubga javob sifatida 1922-yil 4-yanvarda Turkiya Buyuk Millat Majlisi tomonidan Buxoroga Fahri Posho vakil etib tayinlanadi[4;3]. Bunga javob sifatida Buxoro Xalq Sovet Respublikasi hukumati tomonidan Turkiyaga vakillar yuborilgani haqida “Buxoro xabarlar” gazetasining 1922-yilgi 4-apreldagi sonida xabar bosib chiqiladi. Buxoro vakillari Turkiya Buyuk Millat Majlisi rahbari Mustafu Kamol tomonidan qabul qilinadi. Buxoro vakillari hadya sifatida 2 dona qilich va boshqa sovg‘alar bilan kelishgan edi. Qilichlardan biri Mustafu Kamolga, ikkinchisi Izmirni qaytarib olgan armiya qo‘mondoni uchun bo‘lgan. Mustafu Kamol sovg‘alar uchun minnatdorchilik bildiradi va mustaqillik kurashida zafarli qo‘shinimiz bu qilichlar bilan yana zafar qozonadi deb aytgan edi” [2;27] Turkiyaning mustaqillik uchun kurashi davrida Rossiya hukumati O‘rta Osiyo mamlakatlari va Turkiya orasidagi aloqalarga to‘sqinlik qilmadi. Chunki

sovetlar bu davrda Turkiya bilan ijobiy aloqalar o'rnatgan edi. Rossiya Sovet Sotsialistik Respublikasidan ilk yordam partiyasi 1920-yil 22-sentabrda Trabzonga yetib boradi [5;386]. 1921-yil 16-martda Moskva shartnomasi imzolandi va Turkiyaning elchisi sifatida Ali Fuad Posho, Rossiya Sovet federativ sotsialistik Respublikasi elchisi etib Nasarenu tayinlanadi. 1921-yil 26-sentyabrda Rossiya vositachiligida "Turkiya va Kavkaz respublikalari orasida do'stlik haqida kelishuv" imzolanadi. 1922-yil 4-yanvarda Ukraina bilan shartnoma imzolanadi. M. Frunze Ukrainaning Turkiyadagi elchisi etib tayinlanadi. Bu kelishuv imzolanganidan so'ng Turkiya Ukrainadan 100 ming miltiq, 100 ming quti patron, 3500 miltiq, 500 ming o'q so'raydi [6;73]. Turkiston xalqlari tomonidan yig'ilgan oltinlar Moskvada rubl qilib bosib chiqiladi va 1920-yil sentabridan 1922-yilga qadar 11 million rubl yuboriladi (Tohir Qahhor buni 11mln emas 100 mln bo'lganini aytib o'tadi. Uning keltirishicha 89mln rubl yuborilmasdan Moskvada qolgan) [7;112]. Turkistondan yig'ilgan mablag'lar Moskva vositachiligida Turkiyaga olib borilgan. Sovetlar davri tarixchilari "Rossiya hukumati Turkiyaga 10 mln rubl miqdorida oltin va to'p, patron kabi qurollar yuborgani haqida yozilgan ma'lumotlar mavjud [8;94].

1922-yil 9-sentabrda Izmir Turkiya askarlari tomonidan ozod etiladi. 1922-yil 6-oktabrda Turkiston Muxtoriyati, 1922-yil 12-oktyabrda Buxoro Xalq Sovet Respublikasi, 16-oktyabrda Xorazm Xalq Sovet Respublikasi tomonidan turk armiyasining zafarlarini qutlash uchun maktablar yuboradi va mitinglar tashkil etadi. 1922-yil 11-oktyabrda Mudanya sulh shartnomasi urushga chek qo'ydi va bir necha oy davom etgan muzokaralardan so'ng Turkiya bilan urushayotgan davlatlar o'rtasida 1923-yil 24-iyulda Lozanna shartnomasi imzolandi.

Buxoro Xalq Sovet Respublikasi Nozirlar Kengashi raisi Otaxo'jayev tomonidan Turkiya Buyuk Millat Majlisi Rahbari Mustafo Kamolga yozgan tabrik maktubida: "Buxoro Hukumatining 5mln xalqi nomidan ikki yildirki

davom etayotgan milliy mustaqillik uchun kurashdagi g'alabasi bilan turk armiyasini chin yurakdan qutlaymiz. 1922-yil 12-oktyabrda Buxoro xalqi va hukumati tomonidan turk armiyasi zafarlarini qutlash uchun miting tashkil etildi. Minorayi Kalon masjidida mustaqillik kurashida vafot etgan insonlar xotirasiga duo qilinadi. Buxoro xalqi urushning tezroq yakunlanishini juda xohlagandi va turk armiyasini zafar qozonishiga ishongandi" deyilgan edi[4;248]. Bu telegramma Turkiya Buyuk Millat Majlisi vakillari tomonidan o'qiladi va juda iliq qabul qilinadi. Doktor Adnan tomonidan javob maktubi tayyorlanadi va Buxoro Xalq Sovet Respublikasi hukumati va xalqiga ma'naviy dastak uchun tashakkur bildiriladi. "Buxoro xabarleri" gazetasida bu mavzuda xabar bosilib chiqilgan edi. Turklarning milliy mustaqillik uchun kurashi yakunlanganidan Turkiston xalqlari juda xursand bo'lgandi.

Xulosa. Birinchi jahon urushida Turkiston xalqi Turkiyaga moddiy va ma'naviy dastak berdi, uni qo'llab-quvvatladi. Turkiston ziyolilarining bu kabi keng ko'lamli, qizg'in faoliyatlari ikki davlat o'rtasidagi aloqalarning rivojlanishida muhim rol o'ynadi va bu kabi faoliyatlar xalq tomonidan ham ijobiy qarshilandi, ular ham bu kabi ishlarni amalga oshirishda ko'makchi bo'ldilar. Birinchi jahon urushida Rossiya tomonidan asir olingan turk askarlari ham Turkiston xalqi tomonidan juda iliq qarshilandi. Turkiya milliy mustaqillik uchun kurashi davrida ham Turkiston, Buxoro va Xorazm Xalq Sovet Respublikasi hukumatlari va xalqi tomonidan moddiy va ma'naviy jihatdan qo'llab quvvatlandi.

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WORDLY
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ASSESSMENT OF COSTS FOR THE QUALITY OF LOGISTICS ACTIVITIES

Annotation: An overview of existing approaches to accounting for quality costs and their management in logistics activities is given, an approximate list of quality costs in this area is proposed, divided into categories. To manage quality costs, it is proposed to determine the value of optimal costs at which the difference between income and quality costs will be maximum.

KEY WORDS : quality cost accounting, quality cost management, optimal costs, competitiveness.

The well-known American specialist in the field of quality management Philip Crosby asked a rhetorical question: "Think about where your company could be if you completely eliminated the cost of errors?" [one]. This question is not without meaning, because the costs associated with errors, that is, with poor quality, "pull" the company down from the heights of competitiveness.

The riya shows that in order to increase the competitiveness of a company, it is necessary to strive to increase the volume of output of products or the provision of services and reduce the cost of production. Another indicator of competitiveness is the level of quality of the offered products or services. Between these two criteria, unity and opposition are observed.

As a first approximation, we can assume that the money spent on quality should increase sales volumes, and, consequently, profits. On the other hand, additional costs for quality increase the cost, that is, reduce profit. According to Edwards Deming, the costs of not meeting quality requirements and the resulting loss of reputation with customers are so high that they need to be assessed. At the same time, he argued that attention to measuring the cost of quality and finding the optimal.

The greatest contribution to solving the problems of the economics of quality was made by American specialists, the most famous of them is Joseph

Juran. He divided the cost of quality into four categories: the cost of preventing defects, evaluation, internal rejects and external rejects. Schematically, the general structure of quality costs is shown in fig 1.

According to J. Juran, as quality improves, the costs of preventing nonconformities increase, while the costs of marriage (internal and external) decrease.

A more detailed classification of quality assurance costs was presented by another American expert, Armand Feigenbaum. He divided all the costs of quality assurance into three groups: defect prevention, quality assessment, and scrap losses. Further, he detailed each group of costs in the form of its components. This classification of costs is shown in fig 2.

Summing up the costs associated with the prevention of defects, quality assessment and the appearance of defects, we obtain a general dependence of quality costs on its level. The graph of this dependence has the shape of a “U” shaped curve, as shown in Fig. 3. From the figure it follows that as the quality improves, characterized by the absence of defects, the costs associated with their elimination tend to zero. At the same time, achieving this level of quality is associated with a rapid increase in the cost of preventive measures. At the same time, the costs of assessing (controlling) quality are reduced insignificantly.

This situation leads to the idea that the task of quality management should be to find an appropriate level of quality (the number of defects) that minimizes the total cost of it.

Rice. 1. General structure Marriage loss according to A. Feigenbaum [The structure of quality assurance costs according to A. Feigenbaum quality costs according to J. Juran [General structure of quality costs according to J. Juran]

To account for the costs of the quality of logistics activities, they can be divided into several categories. 1. Costs due to internal inconsistencies:

- irreparable marriage (complete loss of goods) due to violation of the rules of storage and transportation: the cost of labor; compensation for the cost of the lost goods; overheads;

- reparable marriage (recovery of goods): restoration costs; unscheduled control and assessment of the quality of goods;

- nonconformity analysis: the cost of conducting a nonconformity analysis in order to identify the causes;

- the cost of disposal of damaged goods;

- the cost of sorting control and selection upon detection of damage to goods in batches of products;

- Losses from grade reduction due to violation of storage and transportation rules;

- Losses during storage, including from natural wastage;

Rice. 2. Cost structure for quality assurance according to A. Feigenbaum
[The structure of quality assurance costs according to A. Feigenbaum].

Rice. 3. Dependence of costs on quality assurance on the level of quality
[Dependence of quality assurance costs on the quality level].

- losses associated with failures of information and communication systems of logistics;
- costs for the assessment and management of logistical risks;
- logistics insurance costs sky risks.

Costs associated with the problems of external counterparties due to their

Table
Quality management maturity grid

Measured category [Measured category]	Stage I: Uncertainty [Stage I: uncertainty]	Stage II: Awareness [Stage II: awareness]	Stage III: enlightenment [Stage III: Enlightenment]	Stage IV: Wisdom [Stage IV: Wisdom]	Stage V: Confidence [Stage V: confidence]
Understanding leadership and position	Missing quality understanding as a management tool	Awareness of the need for the management company, but the lack of its funding	Increasing awareness of and support for QM A quality department has been established and the	Understanding the need for the Criminal Code and participation in its implementation	A look at the management company as the main part of the company's management system
Organizational quality status	Quality is hidden in different departments	The head of the Criminal Code has been appointed, but there is no system yet	role of the QM manager has been strengthened QM issues are recognized openly	The quality manager is the most important person in management	The head of the management company is a member of the Board of Directors
Approach to quality problems	bureaucratic approach	Teams are formed to attack quality problems	and dealt with in an organized manner	QC problems are detected at an early stage. All features are open for improvements	All problems of the Criminal Code are prevented in a timely manner
The cost of quality as percentage of implementation	According to reports - unknown real - 20% No	According to reports - 3%, real - 18%	According to reports - 8%, real - 12%	According to reports - 6.5%, real - 8%	According to reports - 2.5%, real - 2.5%
Measures for improvement quality	organized activity	Attempt take short-term actions on the CC	Application of the program 14 steps with complete everyone's understanding step	Continuation of the 14-step program and the beginning of the "transition to confidence"	Quality improvement becomes normal and permanent activities
The final position with quality in the company	"We don't know why we have quality problems"	"Is it absolutely necessary to have quality issues?"	"With the help of QM managers, we identify and resolve our problems"	"Marriage prevention is a routine part of our work"	"We know why we don't have quality problems"

failure to meet the requirements for logistics services:

The above types of quality costs can be considered the most common for logistics activities, but this list is not exhaustive. The presence of certain costs depends on the field of activity of a particular company and the processes it implements. The classification of costs should be formed in accordance with the specific needs of the enterprise. How to build a quality cost management system? To begin with, it is necessary to "clean up" the terminology so that everyone "speaks" the same language. The names of the costs should sound like it is customary in the company. The selected list of costs should be discussed with various specialists, primarily with accountants, lives in relation to the term "quality costs". There is a different understanding of this term: the costs of achieving the required quality; the cost of the quality service; poor quality cost.

Keep in mind that all these elements are related to quality costs! This is the sum of the costs incurred by many divisions of the company.

Specific costs routinely charged by the company may be accepted as inevitable, but they do not cease to be part of the bad quality.

Practice shows that the costs associated with quality are significantly At the same time, it is necessary to decide reducing non-production costs. Method Improvement Programs: identify opportunities to reduce higher than indicated in the accounting documents. They, as a rule, provide data only for the main processes (business processes), not taking into account that the costs associated with quality are the result of poor performance in auxiliary operations.

The costs associated with poor quality can be "hidden" in company standards. As a rule, when developing these documents, they lay down an ideal model for the operation of processes. With the introduction of standards into the activities of the enterprise, a lot of imperfections "emerge". But developers of standards, for various reasons, are in no hurry to improve them, although they are amenable to improvement.

What can be recommended for organizing work on quality cost management? First, to determine the scale of the problems, it is necessary to translate all the data into the "language of money" - a language accessible to managers at all levels of management.

At the same time, it is necessary to decide tasks:

1. estimate the costs associated with poor quality by a one-time calculation;
2. organize accounting reports in such a way that the costs can be calculated and the result can be demonstrated;
3. identify opportunities to reduce spending on quality, using modern management tools (for example, SWOT analysis), including taking into account the possibility of reducing customer dissatisfaction, as well as budgetary and cost regulation (transferring part of the costs to relations between departments);

4. stimulate quality improvement through bringing the results to employees, their motivation;

Method Improvement Programs:

- wages;
- automation;
- implementation of new processes;
- reducing non-production costs.

I analyzed and presented the existing approaches to accounting for quality costs and their management in logistics activities. The article contains an approximate list of costs for the quality of logistics activities, divided into categories: costs due to internal inconsistencies, costs associated with problems of external counterparties, estimated costs, costs of prevention, etc. This list can be considered general, but not exhaustive.

The classification of costs should be formed in accordance with the specific needs of the enterprise. Practice shows that the effect of investing in quality improvement is not proportional to the size of these funds. It will continue to grow until internal and external factors of influence begin to limit the opportunities for generating income.

I believe that quality cost management should be based on finding the optimal cost value, at which the effect in the form of the difference between income and quality costs will be maximum. To do this, it is necessary to take into account all the costs of quality: for the prevention of nonconformities, for the evaluation and for the elimination of defects in all their manifestations.

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**THE IMPORTANCE TYPES OF VOCABULARY IN MAKING
ACADEMIC DICTIONARY**

Annotation: The article deals with the importance of the types of vocabulary in making academic dictionary according to their grade.

Key words: language, listening ,speaking.

Children start to learn language from the day they are born. As they grow and develop, their speech and language skills become increasingly more complex. They learn to understand and use language to express their ideas, thoughts, and feelings, and to communicate with others. During early speech and language development, children learn skills that are important to the development of literacy (reading and writing).

Professor from ASHA Judy Montgomery's book *The Bridge of Vocabulary* showed there are four types of vocabulary. They are Writing, Listening, Speaking, Reading. As we know the first two constitute spoken vocabulary and the last two, written vocabulary. In all cases learners begin to acquire listening and speaking vocabularies many years before they start to build reading and writing vocabularies.

From method of teaching English we are informed that spoken language forms the basis for written language. Each type has a different purpose and, luckily, vocabulary development in one type facilitates growth in another and they fill each other[1].

If we learn Listening Vocabulary so in this field the words we hear and understand. By modern psychologists say the baby learn the words starting in the womb, fetuses can detect sounds as early as 16 weeks. Furthermore, babies are listening during all their waking hours – and we continue to learn new words this way all of our lives. By the time people reach adulthood, most of them will

recognize and understand close to 50,000 words. But what about the children who are completely deaf. So they do not get exposed to a listening vocabulary. Instead, if they have signing models at home or school, they will be exposed to a “visual” listening vocabulary. The amount of words modeled is much less than a hearing child’s incidental listening vocabulary.

The second is Speaking Vocabulary in which the words we use when we speak and relatively limited. Most adults use a mere 5,000 to 10,000 words for all their conversations and instructions. This number is much less than our listening

vocabulary most likely due to ease of use. Actually we don’t use all material that we accept by listening and in order to activate them the enough time required.

The third is Reading Vocabulary, they are the words we understand when we read text. When we read the text our brain assume the information and it is kept in visual passive memory. We can read and understand many words that we do not use in our speaking vocabulary. This is the 2nd largest vocabulary which is necessary if you are a reader. Otherwise if you are not a reader, you can not “grow” your vocabulary and never enhance your vocabulary [2].

The fourth is Writing Vocabulary in which the words we can retrieve when we write to express ourselves. We generally find it easier to explain ourselves orally, using facial expression and intonation to help get our ideas across, then to find just the right words to communicate the same ideas in writing. Our writing vocabulary is strongly influenced by the words we can spell. Think about it: When reading, a child with hearing will say all the phonemes related to a word to sound it out. They will then guess a word they know. Children would not guess a word they didn’t know. That’s why the level of using words is important. Children whose knowledge of English A2 level can not understand the words which is not authentic for them.

For the learners with A1 and A2 levels we should prepare the imagination of words which they are going to learn. Developing language skills through hearing and admitting the world by their auditory system is primary. Every baby perceives the sounds of outer world and try to imitate the sounds. That's why in learning language it is very important to develop listening skills. As a child even adults learn foreign languages by listening their favorite films' action, television shows and others.

The words in Writing Vocabulary are not enough for those children in activating them in their speech. To assume and to maintain them in speech the children should have imagination of words and their place in social life. So modern dictionary makes allow for this fact and make picture dictionary.

But the pronunciation and spelling also should be in our attention. The Listening Vocabulary are saved by accepted information as well as we should be sure the correctness of pronunciation by checking them audio dictionaries. In addition young learners should be taught the phonetic symbols. In this situation we shouldn't forget the learners belong to different learning styles.

In conclusion, we can say the learners in their early age should obtain all four Vocabulary at the same time. Academic vocabulary should be mixed with daily routine conversation taking the vocabulary from their leisure time. The appropriation of academic dictionaries with students' grade the four types of vocabulary play the equal role.

The used literature:

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THE ADVANTAGES OF CORPUS BASED APPROACH IN TEACHING LANGUAGE

Annotation: This article is about Corpus Based Study and its challenge and beneficial sides in teaching language. Implementation this new approach in Uzbek EFL learners.

Key word: Corpus Linguistics, Corpora learning, Concordance, Data Driven Learning

In order to reach good effect in teaching Vocabulary and Grammar the teacher should use different methods in integrating skills. Developing the computer technology gives the teachers a wide range opportunities in teaching students foreign languages. Since last 30 years corpus based study in teaching foreign languages has become useful tools in language teaching. However, because of lack internet access classes using corpus based activities are neglected by the teachers in Uzbekistan.

To understand what is corpus based study one should learn the Corpus linguistics the first. Corpus linguistics is a methodology within the field of linguistics that has been developing rapidly since the year 1964 when the first computerized corpus, The Brown Corpus, was completed. Corpus linguistics are mainly interested in descriptive or functional interpretations of language [1] and study linguistic phenomena through the empirical analysis of large computerized databases of language called corpora. A corpus is a collection of texts, written or spoken, which is stored on a computer. In the past the term was more associated with a body of work, for example all of the writings of one author. However, since the advent of computers large amounts of texts can be stored and analysed using analytical software.

According to Leech computerized corpora have been mainly used for further research and for finding out about language and texts. The fact that corpora have been used by linguists for research purposes but the researchers who are also language instructors begin to have interest in exploiting corpora for the teaching of second and foreign languages. Leech claims corpora have a direct or indirect effect on the language classroom. Reference materials as dictionaries, grammars and thesauri and textbooks contain impacting materials in language classroom which is indirect corpora. Furthermore corpora have been used to make general academic and discipline specific wordlist.

Use of authentic and real life material gives more advantage than the samples made by teachers which do not refer to real life. Moreover corpora gives the learners the chance to actually work with language and analyze it. In corpora learning the learners should learn not only word meaning, form and usage but also real language use. If students learn the language by corpora the outcome of students vocabulary development is riser than usual.

Though the classes should be student-centered the role of the teacher is crucial in corpora learning. To have advantage in corpora for learners firstly the teachers should be trained how to use the corpora. However the teacher could take benefit from corpora and at the same time the challenges are also faced during the process. Corpora gives the teacher and students different beneficial motivation. The teacher use it in order to understand the interaction of the classroom. Teacher use it to discover recurrent patterns of interaction between teachers and students. Especially corpus writing gives a chance where the students errors in grammar and choosing vocabulary in situations. [2.]For students it should be a part of process of learning about particular structure. Learners can enhance their vocabulary through corpus dictionaries.

According to Tim Johns learners could benefit more than corpora by becoming language researchers themselves and analyzing the language data from a corpus first hand . this technique is called “Data –driven learning” (DDL). As we know

Data- driven learning (DDL) is the use in the classroom of computer-generated concordances to help students explore patterns in the target language, and the creation of activities and exercises based on concordance output. The main reason being that DDL creates learning conditions which have been found to facilitate second language acquisition processes.

As Tomlinson mentioned that The choice of the concordancer can have a significant impact on the process of language learning, stimulating enquiry and speculation on the part of the learner, and creating the student also to develop the ability to see patterning in the target language and to form generalisations to account for that patterning.

To sum up all evidences according to corpus based study and DDL we can say that in spite of challenge during corpora learning process, it has a big potential in EFL and ESP classrooms. If teachers are trained on how to design appropriate corpus -based tasks, they can help their students get exposed to a broader framework of how English is used for communication by native speakers. Designing corpus based tasks consists of the students ability level, their cultural and educational background and their age group. It is also recommended to use online corpora as they are available for anybody at any given time.

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ANTIPATIYA VA SIMPATIYA

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi antipatiyaning kontseptual holatini va uning atrof-muhit bilan jismoniy va ijtimoiy munosabatlarni shakllantirishdagi rolini aniqlashdan iborat. Hayotiy jarayonlarda assimilyatsiya, dissimilatsiya faoliyati kuzatilgan. Shuningdek, dunyo olimlarining simpatiya va antipatiyaga nisbatan bildirilgan fikrlaridan misollar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Antipatiya, ekskrement, simpatiya, empatiya, antisemitizm.

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ANTIPATHY AND SYMPATHY

Annotation. The purpose of this article is to determine the conceptual state of antipathy and its role in the formation of physical and social relations with the environment. In vital processes, assimilation, dissimilatory activity are observed. Examples are also given from the opinions expressed by scholars of the world regarding sympathy and antipathy.

Keywords. Antipathy, excrement, sympathy, empathy, antisemitism.

Ingliz shoiri Jorj Bayron shunday deb yozgan edi: "Xushyoqishning to'satdan tug'ilishining o'ziga xos qonuni bor". Biroq, Bayron tug'ilishidan ancha oldin, taniqli shotlandiyalik iqtisodchi Adam Smit ushbu "qonun"ni shakllantirishga harakat qildi. 1754 yilda u "axloqiy tuyg'ular nazariyasi" nomli kitobini nashr etdi. Smit bu kitobni hamdardlik hissi va uning odamlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarga ta'sirini aniqlashdan boshlaydi. Smitga ko'ra, xushyoqish-bu boshqa odamlarning har qanday kayfiyati va his-tuyg'ularini baham ko'rish qobiliyatidir. Zamonaviy psixologiya bu qobiliyatni "empatiya" so'zi deb ataydi. "Xushyoqish" so'zi (yunoncha *sympatheia* - diqqatga sazovor joy, joylashuv) kimgadir nisbatan xushmuomalalik, xayrixohlik va

boshqa ijobiy his-tuyg'ularda namoyon bo'ladigan barqaror ma'qullash munosabatini anglatadi.

Ba'zida hatto yoqtirish yoki yoqmaslik hissi juda qimmatga tushishi mumkin. Masalan, "Barcha zamon va xalqlarning buyuk odamxo'ri" jurnalist Mixail Koltsovni qiynoqqa solgan, va shu bilan birga yozuvchilar Ilya Erenburg va Boris Pasternakni ogohlantirgan va tegmagan. Chunki ular Stalinga yoqqan edilar.

Xushyoqish-bu shaxslararo jozibadorlikning eng oddiy turi. U bizga chuqur ta'sir qilmaydi. Aytish mumkinki, bu tuyg'u yuzaki. Agar biz ilgari yoqimli bo'lgan odamdan hafsalamiz pir bo'lsa, bu bizga ko'p og'riq keltirmaydi. Biz har qanday jins va yoshdagi ko'plab odamlarni yoqimli deb bilishimiz mumkin. Shuning uchun yoqimlilik hissi aniq jinsiy rangga ega emas. Ko'p hollarda simpatiya o'zaro simpatiyani keltirib chiqaradi. Agar kimdir bizga qiziqish bildirsa va bizning "ajoyib" fazilatlarimizga qoyil qolsa, biz o'z navbatida bu odamga yoqimli bo'lishni boshlaymiz. Va deyarli simpatiya javob simpatiyasini keltirib chiqaradi.

Simpatiya paydo bo'lishining dastlabki bosqichida insonning tashqi ko'rinishi va uning xulq-atvori eng muhim hisoblanadi, keyin aloqa jarayonida uning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari yanada muhimroq bo'ladi. G'alati tuyulishi mumkin bo'lganidek, ijobiy fazilatlarining juda yuqori darajasi jozibadorlikni pasaytiradi, chunki bunday odam juda yiroq va erishib bo'lmaydigan deb qabul qilinadi. Uning doimiy "to'g'riligi" asabingizga tegadi. Simpatiyaning kelib chiqishi sheriklarning bir-biriga bo'lgan ishonchiga sezilarli bog'liq bo'ladi. Shu bilan birga, nafaqat hayotiy munosabatlarning o'xshashligi, balki shaxsiy xususiyatlarning bir-birini to'ldirishi, shuningdek raqobatga aylanmaydigan hamkorlik juda muhimdir.

Zamonaviy romanlardan birida bir yildan ko'proq vaqt davomida birga ishlagan ikki kishi - xo'jayin va ishchi o'rtasida o'zaro simpatiya hissi qanday paydo bo'lganligi tasvirlangan: "o'sha paytda nimadir o'zgardi: ular

munosabatlarni rivojlantirdilar va ikkalasi ham buni aniq his qilishdi. Ehtimol, ilgari ularning ongida nimadir sodir bo'lgan. Va, ehtimol, qo'qisdan o'z-o'zidan paydo bo'lgan. Psixologiya sirlarini kim tushunadi..."

Agar biz psixologiya sirlari haqida gapiradigan bo'lsak, unda fan ikki kishi o'rtasida qanday va nima uchun yoqimlilik hissi paydo bo'lishini tushuntirishga harakat qiladi. Ba'zi tadqiqotchilar, agar ular bir-biridan ikki metrdan oshmasa, ikki kishi o'rtasida simpatiya paydo bo'lishi mumkinligini aniqladilar. Ko'ryapsizmi, tanada ajralib chiqadigan va feromonlar deb ataladigan moddalarni uzoq masofada his qilish juda qiyin. Xohlaysizmi-ishoning yoki ishonmang-tekshiring. Ammo 2008 yil oxirida "Welt am Sonntag" gazetasida "Gentest statt Gespräch" ("Suhbat o'rniga genetik test") nomli maqola chop etildi. Maqolada aytilishicha, olimlar simpatiya hissi genetik darajada amalga oshirilganligini aniqladilar va tegishli tadqiqotlar olib borilgandan so'ng, ikkita aniq odam bir-biriga yoqadimi yoki yoqmaydimi, aniqlanishi mumkin deyilgan. Bundan tashqari, er-xotinlar bilan tanishish va tanlash bilan shug'ullanadigan ba'zi agentliklar ushbu nazariyani qabul qilib, uni amaliyotga tatbiq etishgan.

Ko'rinishidan, bu tadqiqotlarda qandaydir ma'no bordek. Tasdiqlash sifatida Maksim Gorkiyning mashhur bayonotini keltirish mumkin. Yozuvchi Leonid Andreyevning (Gorkiy) antisemitizmga qarshi samarasiz kurashga vaqt sarflashiga nima sabab bo'lganligi haqidagi savoliga, Gorkiy shunday javob berdi: "Yahudiy menga umuman yoqadi, simpatiya esa biokimyoviy hodisa va tushuntirishga imkon bermaydi".

Umuman olganda, antisemitizm deb ataladigan yahudiylarga nisbatan antipatiya (va ba'zi bir yahudiylarga emas) biokimyoviy darajada amalga oshiriladi deb taxmin qilish mumkin. Agar biz ushbu nuqtai nazardan kelib chiqsak, unda ba'zi bir odamning antisemitizmini (yoki umuman aytganda, ksenofobiyani) yo'q qilish qiyin, chunki uning biokimyoviy tabiatini o'zgartirish mumkin emas.

Mashhur amerikalik psixoterapevt Janet Reynuoter bunday e'tiqod (aniqrog'i, noto'g'ri qarashlar) haqida shunday yozgan edi: "Men yoshligimda irqchi e'tiqodga ega bo'lgan do'stlarim bilan bahslashdim, noto'g'ri missionerlik g'oyalariga asoslanib, g'azablandim va va'z qildim. Ularning nuqtai nazarini o'zgartirishga harakat qildim. Albatta, buni amalga oshirish mumkin emas edi."

Har bir kishi, o'zini kuzatib, ba'zi odamlarni yoqtirishini, boshqalarga nisbatan befarqligini, uchinchisiga esa antipatiyani his qilishi mumkinligini sezadi. Shu bilan birga, ba'zida biz bu odamlarni hech qachon uchratmagan, faqat televizorda ko'rgan bo'lamiz. Demak, agar kimdir menda nafratlanish, yoqtirmaslik va hatto g'azablanish xissini keltirib chiqarsa, demak, men ham ba'zi odamlarda shu tuyg'uni keltirib chiqarishim mumkin.

Psixologlarning fikriga ko'ra, ancha murakkab his-tuyg'ular sevgi va jinsiy jalb qilishdir. Ko'pincha sevgi yoqtirish tuyg'usidan boshlanadi. Agar xushyoqishning paydo bo'lishidan muhabbat tug'ilishigacha bo'lgan vaqt juda qisqa bo'lsa, unda birinchi qarashda sevgi haqida gapirish odatiy holdir. Stendal o'zining mashhur "sevgi to'g'risida" risolasida shunday deb yozgan edi: "xushyoqish va tabiatimizning boshqa qonunlari tufayli sevgi shunchaki bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan eng katta baxtdir". Jinsiy jozibadorlik haqida fikr yuritar ekan, Stendal yana shunday yozadi: "ikki kishi o'rtasidagi yaqinlikdan so'ng, hatto sevgini emas, balki faqat xushyoqis tuyg'usini boshdan kechirgandan so'ng, bunday ishonch, muloqotning bunday qulayligi, bir-biriga shunchalik yumshoq e'tibor paydo bo'ladiki, ular o'n yillik simpatiya va mustahkam do'stlikdan keyin ham paydo bo'lmaydi".

Stendaldan iqtibos keltirgan holda aytish mumkinki 19-asr va asosan 20-asrga xos bo'lgan bu "lirika" 21-asrga kelib umuman boshqacha tus olgandek. Masalan, rus kinematograflari tomonidan olingan "Maktab" teleserialini tomosha qilib, albatta, xuddi shunday xulosaga kelasiz, chunki odamlar o'rtasidagi yaqin munosabatlar ma'naviy yetuklikka emas, balki jismoniy yetuklikka erishganlarida, juda erta yoshda boshlanganini ko'ramiz.

Agar xushyoqishning ildizlari ongimizda yashiringan bo'lsa, unda antipatiyaning sabablari nimada bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu sabablar har xil bo'lishi mumkin va ko'pincha bir-birini istisno qiladi. Ko'pincha biz boshqa odamda o'zimizga yoqmaydigan narsalarni yoqtirmaymiz. Masalan, biz ortiqcha vazn yoki ajinlar bilan kurashamiz. Va boshqa odam bizning kamchiliklarimizni eslatadigan oyna bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Shuning uchun biz bunday odamni xush yoqtirmaymiz va undan qochishga harakat qilamiz.

Mumkin bo'lgan sabablarning ikkinchisi to'g'ridan-to'g'ri qarama-qarshilik tuyg'usi: biz boshqalarda biz xohlagan narsani ularda ko'rganimiz uchun ham uni yoqtirmaymiz. Masalan, iste'dodsiz odam iste'dodli hamkasbini yoqtirmaydi. Yoki kimdir oilaviy hayotda baxtli, uning oilasidagi "ob-havo" juda yomon bo'lsa ham shunday holat bo'ladi. Va o'zi bilmagan holda, bu odamga nisbatan hasad va norozilik tuyg'usini boshidan kechiradi.

Biror kishini yoqtirmaslikning yana bir mumkin bo'lgan sababi shundaki, ular bizning boshqa odamlar bilan o'tmishdagi munosabatlarimizdagi muvaffaqiyatsizliklarimizga sabab bo'lgan insonlarga o'xshaydi. Aytaylik, ma'lum bir ovoz modulyatsiyasiga ega bo'lgan kishi bir vaqtning o'zida bizda yoqimsiz taassurot qoldiradi. Xuddi shu modulyatsiyaga ega bo'lgan boshqa odamning bizga yoqishi ehtimoli kam.

Keyingi sabab shundaki, boshqa odam bizga o'xshamaydi. Masalan, ziqna odam keng tabiatlini rad etadi, va aksincha, saxiy odam ziqna yoqtirmaydi va o'zini tutib tura oladigan vazmin odamda beadablik jirkanchlik va nffratni keltirib chiqaradi.²⁵

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WORDLY
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DETEKTIV JANRI JAHON ADABIYOTIDAGI FENOMEN SIFATIDA

Annotatsiya: Detektiv asarlar adabiyotning muhim janrlaridan biridir. Ular nafaqat qiziqarli hikoyalar va sirli vaziyatlar bilan o'ralgan, balki inson tabiati, axloqiy savollar va ijtimoiy muammolarni o'rganishga ham imkon beradi. Ushbu maqolada detektiv asarlarning adabiyotdagi o'rni, tarixiy rivoji va zamonaviy ta'siri haqida so'z yuritamiz. Detektiv janrining tarixi XVIII asrga borib taqaladi. Birinchi marta detektiv hikoyalar Edgar Allan Poe tomonidan yaratildi. "Murders in the Rue Morgue" (1841) asari, ko'pincha birinchi detektiv hikoya sifatida qabul qilinadi. Poe ning asarlari sirni ochish jarayonida analitik fikrlash va kuzatish qobiliyatining muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Arthur Conan Doyle, fenomen

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THE DETECTIVE GENRE AS A PHENOMENON IN WORLD

LITERATURE

Annotation: detective works are one of the most important genres of literature. They are not only surrounded by interesting stories and mysterious situations, but also allow you to explore human nature, moral questions and social problems. In this article we will talk about the role of detective works in literature, historical development and modern influence. The detective genre can be traced back to the 18th century. For the first time, detective stories were created by Edgar Allan Poe. "Murders in the Rue Morgue" (1841), is often regarded as the first detective story. Poe's works highlight the importance of analytical thinking and the ability to observe in the process of uncovering mystery.

Keywords: Arthur Conan Doyle, phenomenon

XIX asrning oxirida, Arthur Conan Doyle tomonidan yaratilgan Sherlok Holms obrazining paydo bo'lishi detektiv janrining yanada rivojlanishiga olib keldi. Holmsning mantiqiy fikrlash uslubi va o'ziga xos uslubi, asarlarni o'qish jarayonini qiziqarli va hayajonli holga keltirdi. Bu davrda detektiv asarlarning asosiy temasi jinoyatni o'rganish va jinoyatchini aniqlash bo'lib, o'quvchilarni muammolarni hal qilishga jalb etdi. Detektiv asarlarning adabiyotdagi o'rni faqatgina o'qish qiziqishini oshirish bilan cheklanmaydi. Ular inson tabiati,

axloqiy dilemmalar va ijtimoiy muammolarni ochishga yordam beradi. Masalan, Agatha Christie asarlarida ko'pincha ijtimoiy tabaqalarning o'zaro munosabatlari va jinoyatlarning ko'rinishida ijtimoiy adolatsizlik ko'rsatib beriladi. Detektiv hikoyalar orqali mualliflar o'quvchilarni o'z fikrlarini shakllantirishga undaydi. Zamonaviy detektiv asarlar, masalan, Stieg Larssonning "Qizning ajdarhasi" seriyasi, ijtimoiy masalalarni chuqurroq o'rganadi, qiyinchiliklarga duch kelayotgan shaxslarning ichki kurashlarini aks ettiradi. Bularning barchasi detektiv janrining rivojlanishi va o'zgaruvchanligini ko'rsatadi. Ular detektivning universal formulasini ushbu janrning har qanday namunasiga xos bo'lgan san'at asari sifatida belgilaydilar.

Detektiv ("detego"dan - ochaman, fosh qilaman) atamasi birinchi marta edi amerikalik yozuvchi Anna Ketrin Grin (1846-1935) tomonidan kiritilgan, u juda haqli ravishda " detektivning onasi " deb hisoblanadi . Uning birinchi detektiv romani " Leavenworth ishi ", 1878 yil katta muvaffaqiyatga erishdi. Advokatning qizi bo'lgan muallif tergov va sud tergovining nozik tomonlarini bilgan va uning boy tasavvuri unga dahshatli sirlar va murakkab jinoyatlarni ochishga imkon bergan. Agata Kristi tan oldi. E. A. Po ham janr asoschilariga mansub. 1840-yillarning qisqa hikoyalarida u Buyuk Detektiv, eksentrik detektiv turini yaratdi, deduktiv jinoyatni aniqlash texnikasini, ko'plab syujet harakatlarini (yolg'on maslahatlar, eng kam gumon qilingan jinoyatchi, qulflangan xonaning siri) tasvirlab berdi.

Adabiy formula ma'lum bir aniq ob'ektlar yoki odamlarni tasvirlashning an'anaviy usullarini, an'anaviy epithetlarni, tasvirlarni, personajlarning stereotipik tasvirlarini va umumiy syujet sxemasini o'z ichiga oladi. Bunday formulalar ommaviy adabiyot asarlarining asosini tashkil etib, janrni eng to'liq amalga oshirish imkonini beradi. Detektiv formula har bir aniq muallifning har bir o'ziga xos asarida o'ziga xos mazmunga ega bo'ladi. Detektiv asarning tuzilishida an'anaviy ravishda uch bosqich ajratiladi: sir (odatda jinoyat), tergovning borishi va fosh qilish (ya'ni jinoyatni ochish). Bu elementlar har

qanday san'at asariga xos bo'lgan boshlanish, avj va denoumentga mos keladi. Ularning ketma-ketligi, xuddi detektiv-shiftchilarda bo'lgani kabi, buzilishi mumkin.

Zamonaviy davrda detektiv asarlar turli xil formatlarda, jumladan, filmlar, seriallar va o'yinlarda namoyon bo'lmoqda. Bu janrning global mashhurligi o'quvchilar va tomoshabinlarga yangi hikoyalar va tajribalar taklif etadi. Buning natijasida detektiv janrida yaratilayotgan asarlar doimo yangilanib, o'zgarib bormoqda. Detektiv asarlar adabiyotda o'ziga xos o'rni bor. Ular nafaqat qiziqarli va sirli hikoyalar yaratadi, balki insoniyatning murakkab tabiati, axloqiy dilemmalari va ijtimoiy masalalarini o'rganish imkonini beradi. Ushbu janr adabiyotning ko'plab sohalariga ta'sir ko'rsatib, zamonaviy madaniyatda o'z o'rnini egallab kelmoqda. Detektiv asarlar inson tafakkurini rivojlantirish va fikrlarni ochish uchun muhim vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

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**MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA IJODIY O'YINLARNING
AHAMIYATI**

Annotatsiya: Bolalarda intellektual rivojlanish, ularning xotiragi, muammolarni hal qilish va til ko'nikmalariga ta'sir qilish xususiyatlari haqida intellektual rivojlanishi, bolaning jamoaviy va hissiy ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda ham ahamiyatga egaligi haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Misol uchun, empatiya, o'z-o'zini tartibga solish va insonlararo aloqalarni.

Kalit so'zlar: Empatiya, til ko'nikmalari, intellektual, ko'nikmalar, kommunikatsiya, intellektual-anglash, ijodiy o'yinlar, ijtimoiy aloqalar, "20 Savol", ta'limiy.

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**THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVE GAMES IN PRESCHOOL
CHILDREN**

Annotation: information about intellectual development in children, their memory, intellectual development about the features of solving problems and influencing language skills, as well as their importance in the formation of the collective and emotional skills of the child. Examples include empathy, self-regulation, and interpersonal communication.

Keywords: empathy, language skills, intellectual, skills, communication, intellectual-awareness, creative games, social interaction, "20 questions", educational.

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda intellektual-anglash malakalarini shakllantirishdagi kommunikatsiya ko'nikmalarining ahamiyati hamda kommunikativ o'yinlardan foydalangan holda bolalar bilan faoliyat olib boriladi. Samarali kommunikatsiya ko'nikmalari bolalarga aloqalar qurish, fikrlarini ifoda qilish va boshqalarining qarashlarini tushunishga yordam beradi, ya'ni yaqinlari va o'qituvchilar bilan aloqalar orqali. Kuchli kommunikatsiya

ko'nikmalari bolalarga o'z fikrlarini ifoda qilish, darsda muzokaralarga qo'shilish va buyruqlarni tushunishga imkonini beradi, ya'ni o'qishda muvaffaqiyatni oshiradi. Yoshdagi bolalar bosqichida mutaxassis kommunikatsiya ko'nikmalari kelajakdagi suhbatlar, prezidentatsiyalar va professional aloqalar uchun asos yaratadi. Ijodiy o'yinlar bolalarni muammolarni hal qilish va kritik fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda yordam beradi, masalan, jigsaw va strategiya o'yinlari. Ijodiy o'yinlar bilan shug'ullanish jamoatda hamkorlik, hamjamiyat va o'zaro kommunikatsiyani rag'batlantiradi, shuningdek, ijodiy o'yinlar empatiya va ijtimoiy aloqalarni rivojlantiradi. Hayoliy o'yinlarga qatnashish bolalarga o'z hissiyotlarini ifodalash va o'z-o'zini tartibga solish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi, shuningdek, ruh va hissiyotlar yaxshilikka yordam beradi.

Intellektual rivojlanish uchun ijodiy o'yinlarni aniqlash bo'yicha bir necha misollar mavjud.

Kichik bolalar intellektual rivojlanishining ahamiyati. Xotirjamlik, mo'ljaldagi musteriler va jadvallar kabi o'yinlar orqali tushunchalarni shakllantirish, murakkablikni tan olish, va masalalar hal qilish, kichik bolalar uchun intellektual rivojlanish uchun ahamiyatli hisoblanadi.

Intellektual rivojlanish uchun ijodiy o'yinlar misollari:

Scrabble, shatranj, va Sudoku kabi o'yinlar bolalar uchun kritik fikrlash, muammolarni hal qilish, va qaror qabul qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun ajoyibdir. Intellektual rivojlanish uchun mos o'yinlarni tanlash uchun qo'llanma. O'yinlarning yoshiga muvofiqligi, tushunchaviy murakkablik, va ta'limiy qiymati hisobga olgan holda, o'yinlarning bolalar intellektual rivojlanishiga samarali hissa qo'shishini ta'minlash uchun o'rganish zarurdir.

Maktabdagi sinflarda ijodiy o'yinlarni amalga oshirish Ijodiy o'yinlarni qo'llashning foydasi So'z qimirlari va hikoyalar kabi o'yinlardan foydalanish, yosh o'quvchilarda kritik fikrlashni, muammolarni hal qilishni va til rivojlanishini rag'batlantiradi. Samarali ijodiy o'yinlarning misollar "Simon deydi" deb nomlangan o'yin, buyruqlarni qabul qilish uchun, "Pictionary" -

lug'atni rivojlantirish uchun va "20 Savol" - kritik fikrlash uchun sinflarda samarali o'quv o'yinlari.

Ijodiy o'yinlarni integratsiya qilish strategiyalari. O'qituvchilar o'yinlarni dars rejalariga integratsiya qilishlari, ularni o'rganish maqsadlari bilan moslashtirish, aniq buyruqlar berish va o'yinlar so'nggi ko'rib chiqish va muzokalariga imkon berish orqali amalga oshirishlari mumkin.

Intellectual rivojlanish uchun qiziqarli o'yinlar yaratish.

Kritik fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish

Bolalarni muammolarni hal qilish, tezlik, va o'ylash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun mantiqiy o'yinlar, taskiyalar, va boshqalar kabi faoliyatlar bilan shug'ullanishga yo'l qo'yish.

Ijodiylik va tasavvurlarini rivojlantirish. Rassomlik, hikoya yozish, va rolyo'nalish kabi faoliyatlar orqali san'at ifodasini rag'batlantirish, bolalarda ijodiylik va tasavvurlarini rivojlantirishga yo'l qo'yish.

O'yin orqali kognitiv rivojlanishni rag'batlantirish

Ma'lumotli o'yinlar, xotira muammozlar, va interaktiv hikoyalar bilan kognitiv rivojlanishni rag'batlantirish va xotira, e'tibor, va til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish.

O'yinlar orqali hamkorlik va kommunikatsiyani o'stirish foydasi

O'yinlardan foydalanishning intellektual rivojlanishga foydasi So'z bog'lash, xotira o'yini va rolli o'yin kabi o'yinlar kognitiv ko'nikmalarni yaxshilaydi va jamoat bilan ishlashni rag'batlantiradi. Intellectual rivojlanish uchun hamkorlik o'yinlarining misollar. Pictionary, Charades va Escape Rooms kabi o'yinlar muammolarni hal qilish va maqsadlarni erishish uchun kommunikatsiya va jamoat bilan ishlashni talab qiladi.

O'yinlar asosida o'qitishni ta'lim muhitida tatbiq etish. O'qituvchilar o'yinlar asosida faoliyatlarini dars rejalariga integratsiya qilishlari bilan talabalar o'rtasida hamkorlik, nazariy tafakkur va kommunikatsiya ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishlari mumkin. O'yin asosida o'rganish samaradorligini baholash. O'yin

asosida o'rganish talabalarda kritik fikrlash qobiliyatlari, muammolarni hal qilish ko'nikmalarini va bilimni saqlashda yaxshilashga yordam berishi mumkin. Muvaffaqiyatli o'yin asosida o'rganish misollari ta'limiy video o'yinlar tarkibiga "Minecraft" kabi. O'yin asosida o'rganishning samaradorligi talaba qatnashishi, akademik natijalari va bilimni amaliy hayotda qo'llab-quvvatlash kabi metrikalar orqali baholanadi. O'yin asosida o'rganish samaradorligini baholashda standartlashtirilgan metrikalar, baholashda potentsial ta'sir va talabalarning o'rganish natijalariga uzun muddatli ta'sirni o'lchashda qiyinliklar mavjud. Bolalar o'quv o'yinlari bilan bog'liq qurilmalarga va internetga kirishga ega bo'lishi muhimdir, bu amalga oshirishda muvaffaqiyatli bo'ladi.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, o'yinlar asosida o'rganish kritik fikrlash, muammolarni echish ko'nikmalarini va matematika va tabiiy fanlarda talaba motivatsiyasini oshirishganligi ko'rsatilgan. O'yinlar asosida o'rganishning kelajagi virtual realiti va o'zgaruvchan realiti kabi chet el texnologiyalarini integratsiyasi orqali ta'limda immersiv va interaktiv o'rganish tajribalarini yaratishni o'z ichiga oladi. O'yinlar asosida o'rganishning kelajagi virtual realiti va o'zgaruvchan realiti kabi chet el texnologiyalarini integratsiyasi orqali ta'limda immersiv va interaktiv o'rganish tajribalarini yaratishni o'z ichiga oladi.

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**TA'LIMDA “BUMERANG” VA “FSMU” TA'LIM METODLARINI
QO'LLASHNING MAZMUNI VA MOHIYATI**

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada dars jarayonini tashkil etishga qo'llanadigan metodlarni tanlash, ta'limning maqsadini amalga oshirishda interfaol metodlarni samarali qo'llash, ayniqsa, oliy ta'limda o'quv jarayonida “Bumerang” hamda “FSMU” metodlarini qo'llash, dars bosqichlarini rejalashtirish, dars jarayonida mazvuning maqsadi, mazmuni, bosqichlarini tizimli tashkil qila olish ko'nikmalaruiga ega bo'lish, “Bumerang” hamda “FSMU” metodlarini qo'llash orqali ta'lim samaradorligiga erishish kabi masalalarda fikr yuritilgan.

Tayanch iboralar: o'quv jarayoni, ta'lim, metod, “Bumerang” metodi, “FSMU” metodi, talaba, dars bosqishlari.

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**THE CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF THE APPLICATION OF THE
METHODS OF EDUCATION “BOOMERANG” AND “FSMU” IN
EDUCATION**

Annotation. This article reflects on such issues as the selection of methods that apply to the organization of the course process, the effective application of interactive methods in the implementation of the educational goal, especially the application of Boomerang and FSMU methods in higher education, planning the lesson stages, the ability to systematically organize the purpose, content, stages of the course, achieving educational efficiency by applying Boomerang and FSMU methods.

Base phrases: educational process, education, method, “Boomerang” method, “FSMU” method, student, lesson raids.

O'qitish usullarini tanlashda asosiy e'tiborni ta'lim maqsadi va vazifalariga qaratilmog'i lozim. Chunki, o'qitish usullari bilan ta'lim maqsadi

o‘zaro bog‘liqlik mavjuddir va ta‘lim maqsadi o‘rtasida yaqin o‘zaro bog‘liqlik mavjud.

Har qanday ta‘limning maqsadi – bilimni hamda uni amalda qo‘llay bilish ko‘nikmalari va malakalarini shakllantirish, shunga zarur shaxs sifatleri va ko‘rsatmalarini ishlab chiqishdan iboratdir. O‘quv faoliyati harakatida maqsadning barcha komponentlari amalga oshar ekan, turli usullarni birgalikda qo‘llash zarur. Shuning uchun, ta‘lim metodlarini tanlashda eng asosiy omil bo‘lib aniq o‘quv mashg‘ulotining didaktik vazifasi xizmat qiladi.

Quyida oliy ta‘lim muassasalarida amaliy mashg‘ulotlarda “Bumerang” metodini qo‘llashning mazmuni va bosqichlarini ko‘rib o‘tamiz.

“Bumerang” metodi tahsil oluvchilarni mashg‘ulot jarayonida, mashg‘ulotdan tashqarida turli adabiyotlar, matnlar bilan ishlash, o‘rganilgan materialni yodda saqlab qolish, so‘zlab bera olish, fikrini erkin holda bayon eta olish hamda bir mashg‘ulot davomida barcha ishtirokchilarni baholay olishga qaratilgan. Ushbu texnologiyada tarqatma materiallar ishtirokchilar tomonidan yakka va guruh holatida o‘zlashtiriladi hamda o‘zaro suhbat, bahs- munozara, turli savollar orqali ularning matnni qay darajada o‘zlashtirilganligi nazorat qilinadi va kichik guruhlarning faolliklari va o‘zlashtirish darajalari tezkor baholanadi.

“Bumerang” metodi bir necha bosqichda o‘tkaziladi:

1-bosqich. 4-5 kishidan iborat kichik guruhlarni tashkil etish va o‘rganiladigan mavzu matnini guruhlar soniga mos holda alohida bo‘laklarga ajratgan holda guruhlarga tarqatish.

Har bir guruhga alohida topshiriq beriladi, tarqatma matnlar ham har bir ishtirokchiga berilishi lozim.

2-bosqich. Guruh a‘zolariga berilgan matnlar ishtirokchilar tomonidan yakka tartibda, so‘ng guruh bilan mustaqil o‘rganiladi.

3-bosqich. Raqamlar yozilgan qog'ozchalar (raqamlar kichik guruh ishtirokchilarining soniga mos bo'lishi kerak) kichik guruh ishtirokchilari tomonidan tortiladi.

4-bosqich. Har bir kichik guruhlardagi bir xil raqamli ishtirokchilar alohida stol atrofida birlashadilar. Bu bosqichda har bir ishtirokchi ham ta'lim beruvchi, ham talaba roliga ishtirok etadilar (1-rasm).

1-rasm. “Bumerang” metodi bosqichlarini amalga oshirish

Ta'lim beruvchi sifatida o'rganib kelgan materialini sheriklariga tushuntiradi. Talaba sifatida sheriklari tushuntirgan matnlarni o'rganadi. Guruh ishtirokchilari savollar asosida bir-birlarini tekshirib ko'radilar.

Baholash esa guruhlarining bir-birlariga savol berishi yoki test savollari yoki shu ishlarning taqdimoti ko'rinishida olib borilishi mumkin.

Shuningdek, oliy ta'limda nazariy va amaliy mashg'ulotlarni samarali ta'sirchan tashkil qilishda ta'lim natijasiga ijobiy ta'sir etishi amalda isbotlangan va keng qo'llaniladigan “FSMU” metodi haqida to'xtalib o'tamiz.

“FSMU” metodi munozarali masalalarni hal etishda, bahs-munozara o'tkazishda yoki o'quv reja asosida biron bo'lim o'rganib bo'lingach qo'llanilishi mumkin, chunki bu metod talabalarning o'z fikrini himoya qilishga,

erkin fikrlash va o‘z fikrini boshqalarga o‘tkazishga, ochiq holda bahslashishga, shu bilan bir qatorda talabalarning ta‘lim jarayonida egallagan bilimlarini tahlil etishga, qay darajada egallaganliklarini baholashga hamda tinglavchilarni bahslashish madaniyatiga o‘rgatadi.

Ushbu metod tarqatilgan oddiy qog‘ozga o‘z fikrlarini aniq, qisqa xolatda ifoda etib, tasdiqlovchi dalillar yoki inkor etuvchi fikrlarni bayon etishga yordam beradi. Bu metod quyidagicha amalga oshiriladi: mashg‘ulotda avval har bir talaba yakka tartibda berilgan vazifani bajaradi, keyin esa kichik guruhlarda ish olib boradi va dars ohirida jamoa bo‘lib ishlaydilar.

Har bir

F – fikringizni bayon eting

S – fikringizning bayoniga sabab ko‘rsating.

M – ko‘rsatilgan sababingizni isbotlab misol (dalil) keltiring.

U – fikringizni umumlashtiring (2-rasm).

Har bir talaba yakka tartibda tarqatilgan qog‘ozdagi “FSMU” metodining 4 bosqichini o‘z fikrlarini yozma bayon etgan holda to‘latadi. O‘z qog‘ozlarini to‘latib bo‘lganidan keyin, talabalar kichik guruhlarga ajratiladi va guruhlarga “FSMU” yozilgan flipchart qog‘ozi beriladi. Kichik guruhda har bir talaba o‘zining yozgan javobini o‘qib tanishtiradi, so‘ngra guruh a‘zolari birgalashib muhokama qilib, umumiy javoblarini yozadilar va uni himoya qiladilar (3-rasm).

“FSMU” metodining afzalliklari quyidagilardan iborat:

- ✓ dars jarayoni mazmunini yaxshi o‘zlashtirishga olib keladi;
- ✓ muloqotga kirishish ko‘nikmasining takomillashishiga olib keladi;
- ✓ vaqtni tejash imkoniyati mavjud;
- ✓ barcha talabalar jalb etiladi;
- ✓ tahlil qilish va fikrlarni asoslash malakasini rivojlanishiga yordam beradi.

Demak, aytish mumkinki, ta’lim beruvchi to‘g‘ri savol berish hamda dars jarayoni mavzusidan kelib chiqib, ta’lim metodini to‘g‘ri tanlay olishi, mazkur metodni maqsadli va o‘rinli qo‘llash malakasiga ega bo‘lishi, ushbu metodlar doirasida savol-javob texnikasini egallagan bo‘lishi lozim. Bundan tashqari, ta’lim beruvchi interfaol metodlarni qo‘llaganda, fikr-mulohazalarni umumlashtirishni va xulosalar chiqarishni bilishi hamda guruhni boshqarish qobiliyatiga ham ega bo‘lishi kerak. Ayniqsa, “Bumerang” hamda “FSMU” metodlarini qo‘llaganda, ta’lim beruvchi dars bosqichlarini rejalashtira olishi,

vaziyat mazmunini va ishtirokchilarning vazifalarini ishlab chiqishni bilishi lozim. Shundagina, “Bumerang” hamda “FSMU” metodlari o‘zining ijobiy samarasini bera oladi.

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**9-12 VA 15 ASR BUXORO SHASHMAQOMINING ILMIY
FALSAFIY(KOINOTVIY) VA AMALIY USLUBIYNAZARIYASI
ASOSLARI**

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Ota Jalol Nosirov shubhasiz, XX-asr Buxoro Shashmaqomi tarixidagi muhim shaxsdir. U Buxoro Shashmaqomining eng ko'zga ko'ringan san'atkorlaridan biri edi. Ijrochi, saroy sozandasi, oxirgi uch amir davrida saroy musiqachilarining boshlig'i: Afsuski, Ota Jalolning qo'shiqchi sifatida kuylagan yozuvlari bizgacha yetib kelmagan. Uning shogirdlari orasida domla Halim Ibodov, domla Savthon, Shodi Azizov, Hoji Abdulaziz Rasulov, Levicha Babaxonov, Shonazar Sohibov, Boboqul Fayzullaev kabi mashhur ijrochilar va boshqa ko'plab nomlar keltirilgan

Kalit so'zlar: Shashmaqom, bayaz, shiru-shakar, fors, diapazon, mumtoz.

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**FUNDAMENTALS OF SCIENTIFIC PHILOSOPHICAL
(COSMOLOGICAL) AND PRACTICAL METHODOLOGICAL THEORY OF
BUKHARA SHASHMAKOMI OF THE 9TH-12TH AND 15TH
CENTURIES**

Annotation: in this article, father Jalal Nasirov is undoubtedly an important figure in the history of Bukhara Shashmakomi of the 20th century. He was one of the most prominent artists of Bukhara Shashmakomi. The performer, the court musician, the head of the court musicians during the last three Emirates: unfortunately, the recordings of father Jalal singing as a singer have not reached US. Among his pupils are famous performers such as domla Halim Ibadov, domla Savthon, Shudi Azizov, Haji Abdulaziz Rasulov, Levicha Babakhanov, Shonazar Sahibov, Bobokul Fayzullaev and many others

Keywords: Shashmakom, bayaz, shiru-sugar, Persian, range, classical.

O'rta asr Yaqin va O'rta Sharq xalqlari musiqa ilmida maqom, asosan, parda tuzilmalari tushunchasini hamda ularga mos holda yaratilgan quy va

ashulalarni ifodaladi. Maqomlar dastlabki davrda tarqoq shakllarda rivojlandi, 13-asrda esa Safiuddin al-Urmaviy ularni o'n ikki asosiy maqomdan iborat nazariy tizim shakliga keltirdi. 17-asrdan so'ng O'n ikki maqom tizimi inqirozga uchrab, uning negizida Sharq xalqlari orasida maqomlarning yangicha milliy va mahalliy shakllari vujudga kela boshladi. Xususan, 18-asrning o'rtalarida O'rta Osiyoning yirik madaniy markazlaridan biri Buxoro shahrida saroy sozanda, xonanda va bastakorlari ijodiy ijrochilik faoliyatida Shashmaqom uzilkesil shakllanib, Buxoro maqomlari, Buxoro Shashmaqomi nomlarida ham yuritildi. O'zbek maqom turlaridan Xorazm maqomlari, Farg'ona-Toshkent maqom yo'llari, shuningdek, yovvoyi (erkin ko'rinishdagi) maqomlar, surnay, dutor yo'llari va boshqalar Shashmaqom ta'sirida rivojlandi. O'tgan zamon bastakorligida keng qo'llanilgan amal, kor, naqsh, peshrav, savt, tarona, qavl kabi janrlarning noyob namunalari Shashmaqom tarkibida bizgacha yetib keldi.

Sh. Buzruk, Rost, Navo, Dugoh, Segoh va Iroq maqomlaridan tashkil topgan bo'lib, jami 250 dan ortiq har xil shakldagi kuy va ashula namunalari iborat. Shu qunga qadar sozanda, hofiz va bastakorlar maqom yo'llarining qo'plab ijroviy talqinlarini kashf etdilar, ovoz, tanbur, surnay, dutor va boshqalar maqom yo'llarida bir qismli va turkumli asarlar ijod qildilar, ular asosida yangi kuy va ashulalar yaratdilar.

Maqomlar sozanda va xonandalar tomonidan yakka tarzda, shuningdek, jo'rovoqlik va jo'rnavozlikda ijro etib kelingan. Xususan, Buxoro amirlari saroyida eng so'nggi davrda jo'rnavozlik asosan, 2 tanbur, 2 doira (doirachilar xonanda ham bo'lgan), afg'on rubobi, sato yoki qo'biz, imkongga ko'ra bo'lamon cholg'ularidan iborat bo'lgan. Maqom ijrochiligida tanbur yetakchi soz hisoblanadi. Chunki u torlarini maqom pardalariga moslab sozlashda va maqom yo'llarini mukammal yangratishda birmuncha qulayliklarga ega. Doira esa sozanda va xonandalarning Shashmaqom qismlarini belgilangan usul negizida ijro etishlari uchun zarur vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Har bir maqomning bosh tovushqatori o'ziga xos va nisbatan barqaror bo'lib, turkumning to'liq musiqiy ijro jarayonida uning pardalarida ayrim o'zgarishlar ham sodir bo'lib turadi. Chunki Shashmaqom shakllanishida maqomlar tarkibiga 12 maqomdan mazkur maqom pardalariga yaqin, kuy mavzui tabiatiga ohangdosh o'zga sho'ba va maqom yo'llari ham kiritilgan. Ularning ladtonalligi asosiy maqom yo'llariga ba'zan mos kelmasligi ham mumkin.

Shashmaqomni tashkil etgan maqomlarning har biri ikki — cholg'u (mushkilot) va ashula (nasr) yirik bo'limlaridan iborat. Cholg'u bo'limlarida bir xil nom bilan ataluvchi cholg'u qismlari mavjud bo'lib, ohanglari o'zlari mansub bo'lgan maqom kuyiga xos, doira usullari esa bir xildir. Ulardan asosiylari Tasnif, Tarje, Gardun, Muxammas va Saqil deb ataladi. Bu kismlar maqom nomlariga qo'shib (mas, Tasnifi Buzruk, Tarjei Dugoh, Garduni Segoh kabi), ayrimlari esa bastakorlar nomi bilan birga (mas, Muxammasi Nasrullovi, Saqili Islimxon) ataladi. Ba'zi cholg'u qismlari alohida nomga ega (mas, Nag'mai Orazi Navo), Dugoh va Segoxda esa maqom nomi bilan qo'shib aytiladi (mas, Peshravi Dugoh, Samoii Dugoh, Xafifi Segoh). Shashmaqomning cholg'u qismlari xona va bozgo'y kuy tuzilmalaridan tashkil topadi. Bunda muntazam ravishda o'zgaruvchi xonalarning rivojlanishi uchun qo'llanadigan peshrav uslubi alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Tasnif, Tarje, Nag'mai Oraz, Samoii, Xafif kabi cholg'u qismlari bir-biriga o'xshash, kichik hajmli; Gardun va Peshrav birmuncha rivojlangan; Muxammas va Saqil yo'llari uzun va murakkab doira usullari negizida ijod etilgan. Shashmaqom cholg'u yo'llarining ichki tuzilishi murakkab bo'lsada, o'zining ravon ohangdorligi va rangbarangligi bilan shu maqom quy mavzulari bilan bevosita bog'likdir. Bu asarlar teran falsafiy va turfa lirik kayfiyatlarni ifodalaydi, tinglovchilardan esa eshitish ko'nikmalariga ega bo'lishni talab etadi.

Halim Ibatov ta'kidlashicha: domlasini kuylash chog'ida musiqali iborani bir nafasda 22-25 soniya davomida qattiq nafas bilan kuylashi aniqlandi. Evropa

maktabida qo‘shiqchi uchun bunday nafas olish, odatda, kamdan-kam uchraydigan hodisa. Bunday xonandalardan faqat uchitasi: Ota Jalol Nosirov (Buxoro), Xoji Abdulaziz Rasulov (Samarqand) va Halim Ibodov (Buxoro). Ularning barchasida juda katta ovoz diapazoni bor edi. Ajoyib rivojlangan nafas olish uslubi Buxoro vokal maktabiga mansubdir. Ota Jalol Nosirovning mashhur shogirdi Levi Boboxonov kuchli ovoz, baland tenor, keng diapazonni egallagan san’atkor bo‘lgan.

Shu o‘rinda shuni aytishim kerak: Levi Boboxonovlar sulolasidan meros bo‘lib qolgan musiqachilar – uning o‘g‘li Masha Babaxonov O‘zbekiston xalq hofizi edi; Ari Boboxonovning nabirasi esa buyuk cholg‘uchi, Buxoro Shashmaqom an‘anasini saqlovchisi u “Buxoro Shashmaqom”ining asl holatini nashr ettirgan. Bu kitob Angelka Jung tahririyati ko‘magi tufayli Germaniyada nashrdan chiqdi. Bu uning ko‘p yillik mehnati, buni ta’kidlab keladi va o‘z ijodini Ota Jalol Nasirovga bag‘ishlaydi.

Bu shaxs, XX asr Shashmaqom tarixida alohida o‘rin tutgan shaxs. Shu bois Boboxonovning o‘zi ham shunday degan edi: “O‘zi chuqur hurmat qiladigan, tushunishga, o‘rganishga harakat qiladigan yagona maqomchi Shashmaqomning atoqli bilguvchisi, xonanda Ota Jaloldir, men faqat unga ta’zim qilaman, men uchun u buyuk siymo hisoblanadi. Kechayu kunduz, bo‘sh vaqt topsam, darhol Uspenskiyning kitobini olaman». Shu tariqa biz Buxoro Shashmaqomining o‘ziga xos tushunchasini tartibga solamiz, bu esa keksa ustalar san’ati bilan bog‘liqdir. Bular o‘nlab ismlar: IX-asr oxiri va XX-asrning birinchi ikki o‘n yilligi boshlari qo‘shiqchilari. Shashmaqomning vokal qismlari bilan keyinchalik, afsuski, 60 yillarning oxiri va 70 yillarning boshidan boshlangan bu an‘ana, birinchi navbatda, vokal an‘anasi, Shashmaqomning cholg‘u an‘anasi - inqirozga uchrasada, lekin bu birinchi navbatda, albatta, Buxoroda kuzatiladi. Ushbu inqiroz hodisasi 70 yillarda ko‘plab tadqiqotchilar tomonidan qayd etilgan, allaqachon Buxoroda Shashmaqom san’ati o‘zining inqirozini boshdan kechirayotganini ta’kidlagan. Avvalo, vokal maktabi, bu

san'atning genezisi ildizlarga borib taqaladi va bu, albatta, fors madaniyatida barcha mas'uliyat bilan tan olinishi kerak. O'tgan asrlarda ko'plab hujjatli materiallar, birinchi navbatda, Shashmaqom uchun "Bayaz" deb nomlangan she'rlar to'plami, Shashmaqom fors-tojik matnida kuylangan.

Ammo, umuman olganda, Shashmaqom doim til ma'nosida ham, shakl va janr jihatidan ham qadimgi fors madaniyati hodisalariga nisbat berilgan, deyishimiz mumkin. Bu hodisadagi bir qator shakl va janrlar shartsiz, bunda o'rta asrlar fani va musiqasida keng yoritilgan eski klassik, fors shakllariga ko'tariladi. Shashmaqom tarixida esa ko'p narsa haligacha o'rganilmagan. Va, albatta, o'sha paytda asosan, elita qismiga tegishli aytaylik, Shashmaqom boshqa maqomot turlari uchun klassik asos bo'lgan.

Shunday qilib, biz ushbu hodisaning taqdiri paradoksal ekanligini ko'ramiz. Bir tomondan, uning bosqichma-bosqich integratsiyalashuvi yuz bergagini, uning negizida yangi Shashmaqom paydo bo'ldi. Ammo original modelni izlashda ular hozirgi bosqichda asosiy nuqtaga aylandi. Aytishimiz kerakki, mumtoz Buxoro uslubida tanazzul kuzatilgan bo'lsa-da, Buxoroda sanoqli sozandalar paydo bo'ldi. Xususan, bular Buxorolik yahudiylardir.

Bu an'anani, qadimgi Buxoro vokal maktabini saqlab qolgan o'nlab nomlar shu Shashmaqomni ijro eta boshlagan. Bu o'nlab ismlar:, Yuriy Boboxonovdan boshlab, Masha Babaxonova, Barno Isqarov – taniqli xonanda, Nariyo Aminov, Gavriel Mullaqandov, Abram Talmasov, Berta Davidova va boshqalar Buxoro va Samarqandda, ayniqsa, Dushanbeda Shashmaqom ijro etganlar. Bu borada Ari Babaxonov - Levichaning nabirasi, ko'p ishlarni amlga oshirdi. Shashmaqomning qayta tiklanishi o'zining dadasi haqida eslaganidek, va boshqa musiqachilarning hikoyalariga ko'ra, xususan, Ari Boboxonov bir qator yo'qolgan kuylarni qayta tikladi.

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VAGON OQIMLARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI

Kalit so'zlar: Vagon oqimi, yuk aylanmasi, rivojlanish bosqichlari, vagonlar yig'ilishi, poyezd tuzish, optimal reja, hisoblash usuli.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada yuklarni yetkazib berish jarayonida vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish, ularning mavjud holati va mahsulotlarni qabul qilib olgandan keyin yetkazib berish jarayonida sifatli xizmat ko'rsatish usullarining optimal variantlarini tanlash ko'rsatib berilgan. Vagon oqimlarini tashkil qilish jarayonida uzoq muddat turib qolishiga sabab bo'luvchi omillarni aniqlab, ularni bartaraf etish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar va takliflar ishlab chiqilgan. Bundan tashqari, yuklarni yetkazib berish jarayoni tahlil qilinib, mavjud tizimdagi kamchiliklarni bartaraf etishda vagon oqimlarini tashkil qilish bo'yicha takliflar berilgan.

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STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE ORGANIZATION OF WAGON FLOWS

Keywords: wagon flow, freight turnover, stages of development, wagon Assembly, train formation, optimal plan, calculation method.

Annotation: the article shows the organization of Wagon flows during the delivery of goods, their current state and the selection of optimal options for quality service methods in the delivery process after receiving the products. In the process of organizing wagon flows, measures and proposals have been developed to identify the factors that cause them to stand in the long term and eliminate them. In addition, the delivery process was analyzed and proposals were made for the organization of Wagon flows in the elimination of shortcomings in the existing system.

Kirish. Temir yo‘l transportida vagon oqimlarini tashkil qilish bo‘yicha ilmiy izlanishlar bugungi kungacha o‘zining dolzarbligini yo‘qotgani yo‘q. Dunyo mamlakatlari temir yo‘llarida vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish usullarining rivojlanish bochqichlarini tadqiq etish kelgusida ushbu sohani rivojlantirishga o‘zining hissasini qo‘shadi. Ushbu maqolada vagon oqimlari, poyezdlar tuzish rejasi va me‘yorlashtirish bo‘yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlarning rivojlanish bosqichlari tadqiqi amalga oshirildi.

Asosiy qism. Temir yo‘l transportida vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish bo‘yicha turli yillar davomida bir qator tadqiqotlar olib borilgan. Dastlabki davrda ishlab chiqilgan tadqiqotlar asosan alohida stansiyalarda vagonlarning yig‘ilish jarayonida turib qolishini meyorlashtirish maqsadlari uchun tavsiya etilgan. Ularni amaliy qo‘llash murakkabligi unda qiymatlari poyezdlarni tuzish rejasini ishlab chiqishga qadar noma‘lum bo‘lgan e va γ parametrlari mavjudligi bilan bog‘liq.

Ushbu muammoni hal qilish maqsadida A.P. Petrov ishda vagonlar yig‘ilish koeffitsiyenti tushunchasini yig‘ilish parametri bilan almashtirish va uni stansiyada tuziladigan poyezdlar yo‘nalishlari k lari soniga bog‘liq ravishda aniqlashni taklif etdi:

$$C = 12 \left(1 - \frac{2}{k+5} \right) \quad (1)$$

Keltirilgan formula quyidagi ko‘rinishda hozirgi kungacha amaliy hisob-kitoblar uchun ishlatiladi:

$$C = 12 \left(1 - \frac{2}{k+A} \right) \quad (2)$$

Vagonlar oqimlarini tashkil etishga oid asosiy vazifalardan biri bir guruhli poyezdlarni tuzishning optimal rejasini ishlab chiqish bilan bog‘liq. Bu masala kombinator ko‘rinishga ega. Poyezdlar tuzish rejasining amaliy jihatdan qo‘llanishi mumkin bo‘lgan variantlariga muvofiq ravishda quyidagi ifoda bilan aniqlanadi:

$$K_{PTR} = 2^{\frac{k_{st}(k_{st}-1)(k_{st}-2)}{2}} \quad (3)$$

bu yerda, k_{st} – poyezd tuzish rejasi hisoblab chiqiladigan, yo‘nalishdagi stansiyalar soni.

Ushbu formula tahlili ko‘rsatishicha, stansiyalar soni k_{st} ortishi bilan poyezdlarni tuzish rejasi variantlari soni ham keskin ko‘payib ketadi. Masalaning murakkablashib ketishiga ham aynan shu sabab bo‘ladi.

Boshlang‘ich bosqichda vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish masalasini ayrim stansiyalar orasidagi saralash ishlarini qayta taqsimlash nuqtai nazaridan ko‘rib chiqilgan. 1921-yilda A.N. Frolov ilk marotaba ikki stansiya orasida saralash ishlarini taqsimlash variantlarini qiyoslash ishini bajardi. Variantlarni baholash ko‘rsatkichlari sifatida vagon va poyezd-sutkalar xarajatlari qo‘llandi. Bunda vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish variantlarini bir sutkadagi vagon va poyezd-sutkalar sarf-xarajat stavkalari asosida pul ko‘rinishida baholash taklif etilgan.

Poyezdlar ixtisoslashuvining optimal variantini aniqlash uchun mo‘ljallangan, izchil analitik qiyoslashlar usluli deb nom olgan birinchi variantini I.I. Vasilyev taklif qilgan. Bunda dastlab vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish masalasini I.I. Vasilyev vagon-soatlar va manyovr ishlari xarajatlarini hisobga olmagan holda faqat yuklarni yetkazib berish muddatlariga rioya qilish shartidan kelib chiqqan holda hal qildi. Biroq keyinchalik poyezdlarni tuzish rejasi variantlarini baholash uchun mezon sifatida keltirilgan vagon-soatlar tanlab olindi. Poyezdlarni tuzish rejasi variantlari samaradorligini baholash ushbu usulda tuzish stansiyalaridagi vagon-soatlarni yo‘l yo‘lakay stansiyalardagi vagon oqimlarining kichik oqimlariga ishlov berishdan tejalgan mablag‘ni qiyoslash asosida bajarilgan. Hisob-kitoblar uchun ikki asosiy shartdan foydalanildi: zarur va yetarli. Bu usulning kamchiligi shu bilan bog‘liqki, u tuzish rejasining qat’iy optimal varianti olinishini kafolatlamagan. Bundan tashqari, masalaning hal qilinish natijasi vagonlar oqimlarini tashkil etishning birgina varianti bo‘lib kelgan. Biroq, ma’lumki, masala maqsadli funksiyaning bir xil yoki o‘zaro yaqin qiymatiga ega bo‘lgan, qo‘shimcha parametr bilan solishtirilishi talab etilgan bir necha yechimlarga ega bo‘ladi.

Ushbu kamchiliklarga qaramay, I.I. Vasilyev tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan analitik qiyoslashlar usuli vagonlar oqimlari katta guruhlarini alohida tayinlanma sifatida ajratib olish sharti kabi poyezdlarni tuzish rejasini hisob-kitob qilishning bir qator turli usullari uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

$$Cm \leq n_i \sum t_j \quad (4)$$

bu yerda, n_i – i-nchi vagon oqimlari soni.

1944-yilda A.P. Petrov poyezdlarni tuzish rejasining tubdan yangicha hisobkitobini taklif qilib, u barcha mumkin bo'lgan yoki muayyan tarzda tanlab olingan variantlar ko'rsatkichlarini qiyoslashga asoslangan edi. Bu usul keyinchalik mutloq hisoblash usuli deb nom oldi.

A.P. Petrovning mutloq hisoblash usuli asosida poyezdlarni tuzish rejasining barcha mumkin bo'lgan variantlarini to'liq ko'rib chiqish yotadi. Bu kabi yondashuv aniq optimal yechimga ega bo'lish imkonini berishiga qaramay, biroq vagon oqimlarining ko'p sonli kichik oqimlarini hisobga olib, bu ish qo'lda to'liq holda yo'nalishning ko'pi bilan beshta stansiyasi uchun bajarilgan. Stansiyalar soni ko'proq bo'lganida esa vazifani ikki bosqichda amalga oshirish taklif etilgan: birinchisida ikkita asosiy tayanch saralash stansiyasi uchun tuzish rejasi hisoblab chiqilgan, ikkinchisida tayanch va tayanch bo'lmagan stansiyalar orasida saralash ishining eng maqbul taqsimlanish variantlari aniqlangan. Hisob-kitob jarayonini yengillashtirish uchun A.P.Petrov maxsus jadvallarni ishlab chiqdi. Masalani ikki bosqichda hal qilish tahlil qilinayotgan variantlar sonini qisqartirish imkonini berib, biroq bu holda optimal variantga ega bo'lish kafolatlanmaydi. Shuningdek ilmiy ishda yuklarni yetkazib berish muddatini ta'minlash shartiga ko'ra poyezdlarni tuzish rejasi variantlarini tekshirish o'z dolzarbligini yo'qotganligi to'g'risidagi qilingan xulosani ko'rsatib o'tish maqsadga muvofiq. Shundan keyin bir necha yillar davomida poyezdlarni tuzish rejasi bo'yicha ishlarda bu masala ko'tarilmagan. 1950-yilga kelib A.P. Petrov poyezdlarni tuzishning optimal rejasini izlab topish uchun birinchi navbatda, EHM vositalari yordamida hal qilinishi talab etilgan dolzarb transport

muammosi sifatida ko'rsatib berdi. 1958-yil EHM yordamida, poyezdlar tuzish rejasining optimal variantini aniqlash imkonini beradigan dastur ishlab chiqilgan. Hisob-kitoblar A.P. Petrovning stansiyalari soni to'rttagacha bo'lgan chiziqli poligon uchun mo'ljallangan mutloq hisob-kitob usuli uchun bajarilgan. Vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish va boshqarish bo'yicha A.P. Petrovdan keyin ko'plab olimlar EHM yordamida dasturiy ta'minotlar ishlab chiqqan, jumladan A.T. Osminin (2000-yillarda) tomonidan bir guruhli va ko'p guruhli poyezdlar tuzish rejasi usuli hozirgi kungacha MDH davlatlari temir yo'l tarmog'ida keng foydalanilmoqda.

Xulosa. Hozirgi rivojlanayotgan bozor munosabatlari sharoitida yuklarni temir yo'l transportida transportirovka qilish uchun vagon oqimlarini to'g'ri tashkil qilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Temir yo'l transportining xalqaro yuk tashish bozoridagi ulushi beqiyosdir. Biroq mamlakatimizda vagon oqimlarini tashkil qilishda jahon tajribasidan unumli foydalanish va transport oqimlarining temir yo'l transportidagi ulushini yaxshilash bo'yicha olib boriladigan ishlar mavjud.

Mazkur ishning asosiy qismida temir yo'l transportida vagon oqimlari, ularning ahamiyati, hamda vagonlarni qayta ishlash uchun zaruriy texnik vositalarning hisob ishlari asosida bajarilgan barcha amallar tashishlarni tashishni tashkil etishga asos bo'ladi. Yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tilgan muammolarni bartaraf etish va vagon oqimlaridan samarali foydalanishni ta'minlash asosida ulardan yanada effektiv foydalanish mumkin.

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TEMIR YO'L TRANSPORTIDA VAGON OQIMLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA JAHON TAJRIBASI

Kalit so'zlar: Vagon oqimi, yuk aylanmasi, rivojlanish bosqichlari, vagonlar yig'ilishi, poyezd tuzish, optimal reja, hisoblash usuli.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada yuklarni yetkazib berish jarayonida vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish, ularning mavjud holati va mahsulotlarni qabul qilib olgandan keyin yetkazib berish jarayonida sifatli xizmat ko'rsatish usullarining optimal variantlarini tanlash ko'rsatib berilgan. Vagon oqimlarini tashkil qilish jarayonida uzoq muddat turib qolishiga sabab bo'luvchi omillarni aniqlab, ularni bartaraf etish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar va takliflar ishlab chiqilgan. Bundan tashqari, yuklarni yetkazib berish jarayoni tahlil qilinib, mavjud tizimdagi kamchiliklarni bartaraf etishda vagon oqimlarini tashkil qilish bo'yicha takliflar berilgan.

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WORLD EXPERIENCE IN THE ORGANIZATION OF WAGON FLOWS IN RAIL TRANSPORT

Keywords: wagon flow, freight turnover, stages of development, wagon Assembly, train formation, optimal plan, calculation method.

Annotation: the article shows the organization of Wagon flows during the delivery of goods, their current state and the selection of optimal options for quality service methods in the delivery process after receiving the products. In the process of organizing wagon flows, measures and proposals have been developed to identify the factors that cause them to stand in the long term and eliminate them. In addition, the delivery process was analyzed and proposals

were made for the organization of Wagon flows in the elimination of shortcomings in the existing system.

Kirish. Temir yo‘l transportida vagon oqimlarini tashkil qilish bo‘yicha ilmiy izlanishlar bugungi kungacha o‘zining dolzarbligini yo‘qotgani yo‘q. Dunyo mamlakatlari temir yo‘llarida vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish usullarining rivojlanish bochqichlarini tadqiq etish kelgusida ushbu sohani rivojlantirishga o‘zining hissasini qo‘shadi. Ushbu maqolada vagon oqimlari, poyezdlar tuzish rejasi va me‘yorlashtirish bo‘yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlarning rivojlanish bosqichlari tadqiqi amalga oshirildi.

Asosiy qism. Dunyo mamlakatlari temir yo‘llarida vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish usullarining rivojlanish bochqichlarini tadqiq etish kelgusida ushbu sohani rivojlantirishga o‘zining hissasini qo‘shadi. Vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish usullari temir yo‘l transporti ish sharoitlari o‘zgarishi ta‘sirida kattagina taraqqiyot yo‘lini bosib o‘tgan. Poyezdlar tuzish rejasiga asoslangan, vagon oqimlarini tashkil etishga bo‘lgan zamonaviy yondashuvlar nazariyasi MDHda asosan 1931–1952 yillar davomida va amaliy jihatdan 1970–1980-yillarda EHM yordamida rivojlanganligi aniqlandi. O‘tkazilgan tadqiqot natijalariga ko‘ra MDH mamlakatlarida vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish tizimini temir yo‘l transportining hozirgi ishlash sharoitlariga va temir yo‘llar orqali tashish bozorini isloh qilishning tanlab olingan yo‘nalishlariga muvofiq o‘zgartirish zarurligi aniqlandi.

Temir yo‘l transporti har qanday davlat iqtisodiyotining bazaviy tarmoqlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Temir yo‘l transporti davlatning ichki va tashqi transport-iqtisodiy aloqalarini ta‘minlashda, shuningdek aholining tashishlarga bo‘lgan ehtiyojini qondirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Temir yo‘l transportining ustun jihatlaridan biri tashishlar tannarxining pastligi va infratuzilmaning yuqori darajali o‘tkazish va tashish imkoniyatiga ega ekanligi hisoblanadi. Temir yo‘l orqali tashishlar tannarxini belgilab beradigan asosiy

omillardan biri poyezdlarni tuzish rejasida belgilab beriladigan vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish tartibi bo‘lib MDH mamlakatlari temir yo‘llarida vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish bo‘yicha qo‘llanadigan asosiy usullarga Rossiya imperiyasi davridayoq asos solingan.

Vagon oqimlarini yuk poyezdlari va muayyan marshrutlar bo‘yicha ularning yo‘nalishlari tarzida tashkil etish tizimi temir yo‘llarning transport xizmatlari bozorida barqaror ishlashini, tashishga minimal xarajat sarflanishini, yuklarni tashish muddatlariga aniq rioya qilinishini, shuningdek yuk jo‘natuvchilar va qabul qiluvchilar talab va ehtiyojlarining qondirilishini ta‘minlashi kerak. Vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish asosida stansiyalarda tuziladigan poyezdlar va vagonlar guruhlarining borish joylarini va toifasini belgilab beradigan, ularni yo‘naltirish tartibi va yuk poyezdlarni tuzish rejasi tartibi yotadi. Vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish usuli temir yo‘l orqali tashish tannarxiga jiddiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatib, temir yo‘l transporti texnik vositalarining yuklanganlik darajasini, shu bilan birga yuk poyezdlari jo‘natilish stansiyalari va punktlari hamda borish joylari orasida saralash va manyovr ishlarining taqsimlanishini ta‘minlab beradi. Shuni ham qayd etish lozimki, vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish muammosini o‘rganish 100-yildan uzoqroq tarixga ega bo‘lib, ana shu davr mobaynida uni hal qilish usullarini rivojlantirish tarixi bo‘yicha ko‘plab ilmiy ishlar yaratilgan. Bular qatorida, birinchi navbatda ishlarni, shuningdek amaliy ishlarida masala mohiyatiga doir qo‘shimcha ma‘lumotlar mavjud bo‘lgan ayrim olimlarning faoliyatini ko‘rsatib o‘tish mumkin.

XIX asr oxiri XX asr boshida MDH mamlakatlarida chop etilgan maqolalar temir yo‘llarning, xususan vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish sohasidagi ekspluatatsiya ishiga oid amaliy tajribani umumlashtirishga va bu faoliyatni takomillashtirish bo‘yicha yangi g‘oyalarni taqdim etishga qaratilgan edi.

Vagon oqimlarini tashkil etish muammosi bo‘yicha dastlabki ilmiy tadqiqotlar va maqolalar professor A.N. Frolov tomonidan chop etilgan. Vagon

oqimlarini tashkil etish va temir yo‘llar texnik stansiyalari orasida saralash ishlarining taqsimlanishiga oid muammolarning nazariy tadqiqot natijalari chop etilgan. Ushbu ilmiy ishlarda saralash parkida vagonlarning yig‘ilish vaqti T , poyezdlarning tuzilayotgan tayinlanmalari k va ishlov beriladigan vagonlar soni N orasidagi bog‘liqlik belgilab berilgan.

$$T = \frac{12k}{N}, \quad (1)$$

Shuningdek, alohida tayinlanmaga doirlar vagonlar yig‘ilish vaqti quyidagi formula orqali aniqlanadi:

$$t_{yig'}^x = \frac{12}{N_{jo'n}^x}, \quad (2)$$

bu yerda, $N_{jo'n}^x$ – bir sutka davomida tuzilgan x tayinlanma poyezdlar soni.

1910-yilda D.M. Karamishev grafik modellashtirish asosidagi stansiyalarda vagonlar yig‘ilish jarayonining tadqiqot natijalari chop etilgan. Bunda poyezdlarning stansiyaga kelish va jo‘nash grafiklari, hamda vagonlarning turib qolishi orasidagi bog‘liqlik aniqlab olingan. Grafik modellashtirish temir yo‘l stansiyalarda vagonlarning yig‘ilish jarayonini tadqiq etish maqsadida hozirgi kunga qadar qo‘llanib keladi.

Shuningdek, V.A. Sokovich vagonlarning yig‘ilish jarayoni vaqtini quyidagi formulaga binoan aniqlashni taklif qilingan:

$$T = \frac{12(k-1)m}{N}, \quad (3)$$

bu yerda, m – poyezd tarkibidagi vagonlar soni; n – sutkalik vagon oqimlari.

Vagonlar yig‘ilish vaqtini baholash uchun XX asrning 20-yillarida A.N. Frolov, V.A. Sokovich va I.I. Vasilyevlar tadqiqotlar olib borgan. Jumladan, I.I. Vasilyev vagonlar saralash parkida o‘rtacha turib qolish vaqtini baholash uchun quyidagi formulani tavsiya etgan:

$$T_{yig'} = \frac{12m-1}{N}, \quad (4)$$

Ishda V.S. Larionov vagon oqimlarini yanada samarali tashkil etish uchun saralash stansiyasida vagonlar yig'ilish vaqtini hisoblashning formulasini taklif qildi,

$$T_{yig'} = 10 \quad (5)$$

Bunda 10 koeffitsiyenti amaliy tajriba asosida qabul qilingan.

1941-yili prof. I.I. Vasilyev alohida tayinlanmaga oid vagonlarning yig'ilishda o'rtacha turib qolish vaqtini baholash uchun mo'ljallangan formulani qayta ko'rib chiqdi va uni quyidagi ko'rinishda taqdim etdi

$$T_{yig'} = 12 \left(\frac{m}{N} - \frac{1}{n_{qayta}} \right) \quad (6)$$

bu yerda, n_{qayta} – qayta ishlovga keluvchi sutkalik poyezdlar soni.

1946-yil ishda K.A. Bergard vagonlar sutka davomida guruhlar bo'lib bir tayinlanmaga bir tekis kelib tushganida va alohida yakunlovchi guruhlar kelib tushganidan so'ng yig'ilishda tanaffuslar yuzaga kelganida yig'ilishga vagon-soatlar sarfini aniqlash uchun quyidagi formula tavsiya qilgan:

$$T_{yig'} = 12 \left(1 - \frac{1}{e\gamma} \right) \quad (7)$$

bu yerda, m – poyezd tarkibidagi vagonlar soni; e – ulardan bir tarkib yig'iladigan guruhlar soni; γ – tarkib va guruh karraliligi koeffitsiyenti.

Yuqoridagi formulani, shuningdek quyidagicha ham taqdim etish mumkin

$$T_{yig'} = C \quad (8)$$

bu yerda, C – hisobiy yig'ilish koeffitsiyenti:

$$C = 12 \left(1 - \frac{1}{e\gamma} \right) \quad (9)$$

Bu formulalar alohida stansiyalarda vagonlarning yig'ilish jarayonida turib qolishini meyorlashtirish maqsadlari uchun tavsiya etilgan. Ularni amaliy qo'llash murakkabligi unda qiymatlari poyezdlarni tuzish rejasini ishlab chiqishga qadar noma'lum bo'lgan e va γ parametrlari mavjudligi bilan bog'liq.

Xulosa. Hozirgi rivojlanayotgan bozor munosabatlari sharoitida yuklarni temir yo'l transportida transportirovka qilish uchun vagon oqimlarini to'g'ri

tashkil qilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Temir yo‘l transportining xalqaro yuk tashish bozoridagi ulushi beqiyosdir. Biroq mamlakatimizda vagon oqimlarini tashkil qilishda jahon tajribasidan unumli foydalanish va transport oqimlarining temir yo‘l transportidagi ulushini yaxshilash bo‘yicha olib boriladigan ishlar mavjud.

Mazkur ishning asosiy qismida temir yo'l transportida vagon oqimlari, ularning ahamiyati, hamda vagonlarni qayta ishlash uchun zaruriy texnik vositalarning hisob ishlari asosida bajarilgan barcha amallar tashishlarni tashishni tashkil etishga asos bo'ladi. Yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tilgan muammolarni bartaraf etish va vagon oqimlaridan samarali foydalanishni ta'minlash asosida ulardan yanada effektiv foydalanish mumkin.

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**XORAZM DOSTONLARIDA QO'LLANILGAN O'ZLASHGAN
QATLAMGA OID BIRLIKLAR**

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Xorazm dostonlaridagi o'zlashgan qatlamga oid birliklar, antroponimlar tarkibidagi arab, fors tillaridan kirib kelgan affiksoidlar haqida fikrlar bayon qilingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Antroponim, affiksoid, sodda tuzilishga ega affiksoidlar, murakkab tuzilishga ega affiksoidlar, onomastika, lingvopoetika.*

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**ADAPTED LAYER-SPECIFIC UNITS USED IN THE
KHWAREZMIAN EPICS**

Abstract: *In this article, thoughts are reflected about the affixoids acquired from foreign languages in the epics of Khorezm, and the affixoids introduced from Arabic and Persian languages in anthroponyms.*

Key words: *Anthroponym, affixoid, affixoids with a simple structure, affixoids with a complex structure, onomastics, linguopoetical science.*

Xorazm dostonlari tilidagi arabiy tillarga oid kishi ismlarini tuzilishi, tarkibidagi elementlari nuqtayi nazaridan ham tahlilga tortish mumkin. Bunday nomlarning ko'pchiligini hozirgi kunda kishilar bir necha qismlardan iborat ekanligini sezmasligi mumkin. Ana shuning uchun ham dostonlarimiz matnlarida uchraydigan arabiy qatlamga xos kishi ismlarini komponent tahlil qilish orqali ularning strukturasiga aloqador qo'shimcha unsurlarni tekshirish maqsadga muvofiq deb hisoblaymiz.

Xorazm dostonlari atoqli otlar tizimidagi arabiy asosga ega bo'lgan onomastik birliklar orasida sodda tarkibli nomlar foiz jihatidan ozchilikni tashkil qilsa ham, ma'lum darajada o'ziga xosliklari bilan ajralib turadi. Nomlarning sodda yoki qo'shma (ba'zan murakkab) tarkibga egaligini baholashda muayyan qiyinchiliklarga duch kelinadi. Murakkablik shundan iborat bo'ladiki, birinchidan, nomning tarkibini yuzaga keltirayotgan birliklarning tarkiblarga

ajralishi masalasi qaysi nuqtayi nazardan belgilanishiga bog‘liq holatlar talaygina. Ikkinchidan, nomning tarkiblarga ajralishi yoki ajralmasligi qaysi qatlam nuqtayi nazaridan baholanishi kabilarda tekshiruvchi uchun ma‘lum bir prinsiplarni belgilab olish talab etiladi. Quyidagi nomlar maqbul prinsiplar asosida tahlil qilingan:

Luqmon. “Oshiq Alband” dostonida Hazrati Luqmon shaklida qo‘llaniladi: *...Dardga davo etgan hazrati Luqmon,*

Dod etarman parizodning alinnan... (“Oshiqnoma” 2-kitob, “Oshiq G‘arib va Shohsanam” dostoni, 183-b).

Qadimgi arab mifologiyasida Luqmon nomi bilan mashhur bo‘lgan ikkita shaxs tilga olinadi. Ulardan biri Luqmon ibn Od deb yuritilgan. Afsonaga ko‘ra, qadimiy Arabistonda yashagan Od xalqi Ollohning g‘azabiga uchrab, qurg‘oqchilikka duchor bo‘ladi. Xalq bu ofatdan qutilish uchun o‘z vakillarini Makkaga yomg‘ir so‘rab duo o‘qish uchun yuboradi. Ularga Luqmon boshchilik qiladi va Ollohdan o‘ziga uzoq umr tilaydi. Olloh unga yetti burgut umriga teng uzoq umr ato etgan. Ikkinchi Luqmon Qur‘onda tilga olinadi (31-Luqmon surasi). Luqmon al-Hakim sifatida qayd etilgan bo‘lib, donishmand va yakkaxudolikning targ‘ibotchisi sifatida tavsiflanadi. Islom afsonalaridagi ko‘pgina aforizm, maqollar, hamda masallar, shuningdek, musulmon xalqlarining folklor asarlarida Luqmon nomi juda mashhur bo‘lgan. O‘rta Osiyo xalqlari orasida Luqmon buyuk hakim va hakimlarning piri deb tan olinadi. Shuningdek, Luqmon so‘zi dono, bilimdon shaxs ma‘nosini ham anglatadi. Luqmon so‘zi arabcha (halol luqma) “boquvchi” degan ma‘noni bildiradi.

Bahovuddin. “Oshiqnoma” turkumiga kiruvchi “Oshiq Alband” dostonida uchraydi.

...Bag‘rim uzra bordur maning bir nishon,

Duo qilsin dedi ul Shohimardon,

Abu Bakr, Siddiq ul Umar, Usmon,

*Bahovuddin sarmast buzrug ko'rindi*²⁶... (“Oshiqnoma” 2-kitob, “Oshiq Alband” dostoni, 172-b).

To'liq ismi Said Muhammad ibn Jaloliddin (1318 – 1389) bo'lib, naqshbandiylik tariqatining asoschisidir. Buxoro yaqinidagi Hinduvon (hozir Qasri Orifon)²⁷ qishlog'ida tug'ilgan va shu yerda vafot etgan. U yog'och va metallarga naqsh berish kasbi bilan shug'ullangani sababli unga Naqshbandiy taxallusi berilgan. Bahovuddin yoshligidayoq so'fiylik yo'liga kirgan. Ustozi Mir Said Kulol ta'sirida o'z tariqatini yaratdi. U islomni tozalash, ilk holiga qaytarish g'oyasini ilgari surgan. U o'zini Muhammad payg'ambar avlodidan bo'lgan mashhur Murshid deb tanitgan. Bahovuddinning ayrim qarashlari so'fiylikning boshqa vakillari, xususan, Ahmad Yassaviy qarashlaridan farq qiladi. U ham Yassaviy singari faqirlikka, kambag'allikka undaydi, lekin xayrehson hisobiga emas, balki faqat o'z mehnati evaziga kun kechirish g'oyasini yoqlaydi. “Dil ba yoru, dast ba kor” ya'ni, dil, qalb yor (xudo) bilan, qo'l mehnat bilan band bo'lishi g'oyasini ilgari suradi.

Bahovuddin so'fiylikni targ'ib qilib Arabiston, Eron va O'rta Osiyoning ko'p shaharlarida bo'lgan. Uning nomi ilohiylashtirilib, u haqda turli rivoyat-u afsonalar to'qilgan. Ularga ko'ra, go'yo uning qabrini ziyorat qilgan kishi haj qilganlik savobini olar ekan. Hozirgi kunda ham bu tasavurning ta'siri saqlangan. Dindorlar uni “balogardon”, ya'ni “balolarni daf qiluvchi” deb biladilar. Xalq dostonlarida ham uning obrazi shu tariqa talqin qilinadi.

Shunday nomlardan yana biri “*Ali*” nomi hisoblanadi. Ali tarixda yashagan mashhur kishilardan biri bo'lib, u payg'ambarimizning kuyovi bo'lgani va islom olamida o'ziga xos martabaga ega bo'lganligi haqida ko'pgina ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan.

Alining to'liq ismi Ali ibn Abu Tolib bo'lib, u haqida xalq orasida juda ko'plab rivoyatlar va afsonalar to'qilgan, bu esa o'z navbatida xalq og'zaki

²⁶ Ro'zimbayev S. Oshiqnoma. 1-kitob, Xorazm nashriyoti. 2006. –B. 172.

²⁷ Nasafiy (E.E.Berezikov). Hazrat Bahovuddin Naqshbandiy. Tarjimon Mahkam Andijoniy –T: Meros, 1992. – B.100.

ijodiga mansub ko‘plab asarlarda o‘z izini qoldirmasdan iloji yo‘q edi. Uning *Hasan* va *Husan* nomli egizak o‘g‘illari – payg‘ambarimizning sevimli nevaralari hisoblanadi²⁸.

“Oshiqnoma” turkum dostonlaridagi atoqli otlarning qo‘shma tarkibli turlari ichida ko‘pchiligi erkak jinsli kishilarga qo‘yilgan nomlar bo‘lishi bilan birga, ayrim nomlar xotin-qizlar, payg‘ambarlarning rafiqalari, afsonaviy parilar, devlar kabilarga tegishlidir. Masalan, “*Hashtiruh*” nomi “Oshiqnoma” turkumidagi “Hurliqo va Hamro” dostonida uchraydi. Tarkib jihatidan ikki qismdan iborat bo‘lgan bu nom dev nomi sifatida talqin qilinishi quyidagi misoldan ham sezilib turibdi:

... *anda **Hashtiruh** dev bayakbor devning orqasidin havog‘a chiqib, Amud urdi ikki dev urushg‘a mashg‘ul bo‘ldi...*(“Oshiqnoma” 2-kitob, “Hurliqo va Hamro” dostoni, 121-b).

Yuqoridagilardan xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, Xorazm dostonlarida uchraydigan sodda va qo‘shma tuzilishga ega bo‘lgan nomlarning tarkibiy jihatlarini tahlil qilish o‘zbek tili va uning onomastika sohasini yanada qiziqarli ma’lumotlar bilan boyitishi mumkin.

²⁸ Irisov A.Chahoryorlar. Toshkent. Fan.1993-yil. –B. 48.

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**MAHALLA BOSHQARUV TIZIMINING TARIXIY SHAKLLANISHI
VA UNING HUQUQIY-TASHKILIY ASOSLARINING YARATILISHI**

Anotatsiya. Mahalla O'rta Osiyoda qadimdan hududiy-ma'muriy birlik hisoblanadi. Bu yerda har bir yashovchi taqdiri, orzu-umidi, hayotga va odamlarga munosabati qat'iy bir biriga bog'liq bo'lgan. Bir-biri bilan hisoblashib yashagan. Shu bilan birga mahallachilik uzoq an'analarga va xalqimiz tarixiga, uning boy ma'naviy-axloqiy udumlariga bog'liq bo'lgan ulkan hayot maktabi. Ma'lumki, jamiyatni demokratlashtirishning yana bir muhim sharti mahalla tizimini huquqiy asoslar bilan shakllantirishdir. Maqolada mahalla boshqaruv tizimining tarixiy shakllanishi va uning qanday qilib huquqiy-tashkiliy asoslarining yaratilganligi va bu soxada yana qanday ishlarning amalga oshirilishi kerakligi to'g'risida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar. Tarix, oila jamiyat, davlat, hududiy birlik, xalq, urf odat, taraqqiyot.

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**HISTORICAL FORMATION OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD
MANAGEMENT SYSTEM AND CREATION OF ITS LEGAL AND
ORGANIZATIONAL BASIS**

Annotation.

Mahalla has long been considered a territorial-administrative unit in Central Asia. The fate, dreams and hopes of every resident here are under strict control. They lived with each other. At the same time, neighborhood is a huge school of life, which depends on long traditions and the history of our nation, its rich spiritual and moral achievements. It is known that another important condition for the democratization of the society is the formation of the neighborhood system with legal foundations. The article describes the historical formation of the neighborhood management system, how its legal and organizational foundations were created, and what other work should be done in this area. it's about.

Key words. History, family, society, state, territorial unit, nation, tradition, development.

Kirish (Introduction).

Mahalla tarixi qadim zamonlarga borib taqaladi. Mahalla boshqaruv tizimining tarixiy shakllanishi haqida soʻz borganda avvalambor Surxondaryoda joylashgan Sopollitepa qadimiy yodgorligidagi oilalarning bir maqsad sari uyushib yashab, bugungi tuzilma tushunilgan. Albatta ularning faoliyatida urugʻchilik munosabatlari ustunlik qilib turgan. Bu davrda jamoalarning manfaatlari birinchi oʻringa qoʻyilib, bevosita ularning manfaatlari oqsoqollar Boshqarmai tomonidan himoya qilingan va ular mahalliy ahamiyatga molik masalalarni hal etishda mustaqil boʻlgan. Bu esa oʻz navbatida, butun tarix davomida mahalla insonlar bilan birga, ularning yaxshi va yomon kunlarida hamnafas boʻlib, muhtojlar, zaiflarga yordam qoʻlini choʻzib kelish vakolatlariga ega boʻlganligidan dalolat beradi.

Ularni faqat urugʻ jamoasigina emas, balki ishlab chiqarish manfaatlari ham birlashtirib turgan. Keyinchalik ularning safiga patriarxal tizim asosida 100 dan ortiq oilalar kelib qoʻshilgan. Katta oilalar jamoasini ular orasidan saylangan oqsoqol boshqargan. Oqsoqollar oʻz navbatida oliy oqsoqollar kengashiga birlashgan. Oqsoqollar, odatda, jamoa — qishloq hayoti bilan bogʻliq barcha masalalarni oliy kengash orqali hal qilishgan. Miloddan avvalgi 3-asrdan milodiy 5-asrning boshlarigacha Fargʻona (Parkana) davlatida ham oqsoqollar kengashi muhim vazifalarni hal etgan. Kengash, asosan, sulh tuzish, vazirlar tarkibi va soliqlarni tayinlash, urush eʼlon qilish, jamoa ishlariga safarbar etish kabi masalalar bilan shugʻullangan. Mahalla mintaqalarda mahallot (joy), guzar, jamoa, elat, elod nomlarda atalib kelingan. Adabiyotlarda Mahallarning tashkil topishi ularlarning koʻp ming yillik tarixga ega ekanligi haqida maʼlumotlar uchraydi. Buxoroda bundan 1100-yil ilgari bir qancha mahallalar boʻlgan. Alisher Navoiy oʻzining „Hayrat ul-abror“ asarida mahallani „mahalla shahar

ichidagi shaharcha“dir deb ta’riflaydi, Hirot shahri yuz shaharcha ahamiyatiga ega bo‘lgan mahallalardan tashkil topganini aytib o‘tadi. Boshqaruv tizimiga ko‘ra, jamoa tomonidan oqsoqol ayni paytda, o‘z oila jamoasi uchun diniy va dunyoviy boshliq bo‘lgan. Urug‘-qishloq oqsoqoli esa, Oqsoqollar Boshqarmaining boshlig‘i bo‘lishi bilan bir qatorda butun qishloq aholisining ham boshlig‘i hisoblangan va o‘z navbatida, Oqsoqollar Boshqarmasining boshlig‘i qishloqda istiqomat qiladigan jamoaning manfaatlarini himoya qilishga qaratilgan bir qator vakolatlarni amalga oshirgan. Boshqacha aytganda, bu davrda davlatning shakllanishida mahalla hal qiluvchi omil bo‘lib xizmat qilgan. Bundan tashqari, miloddan avvalgi III asrdan to milodiy V asr boshlarigacha qadimgi Parkana (Fag‘ona) davlatida ham jamoalar hayoti bilan bog‘liq masalalar ham oqsoqollar Boshqarmasi orqali hal etilgan.

Mahallalar, ayniqsa, Amir Temur davrida ravnaq topgan. Bu davrda mahallalar fuqarolarning kasbkori asosida shakllangan va shunga qarab nomlangan. Ta’kidlash kerakki, O‘zbekiston hududida X asrdayoq «mahalla» atamasi savdo-hunarmandchilik kasblarini belgilovchi atama sifatida uchraydi. Bu davrlarda mahalla uch asosiy yo‘nalishda o‘z vakolatiga ega bo‘lgan. Xususan, shahar hududini orasta saqlash, tegishli hududda istiqomat qiluvchi aholi joyi hamda mahalliy aholining turmush tarzini to‘g‘ri tashkil etilishini ta’minlash, davlat va mahalliy tadbirlarni o‘tkazishda ularga rahbarlik qilish borasidagi vakolatlarni amalga oshirgan. 20-asrning boshlaridayoq Mahallalar daha boshliqlari — mingboshilar saylaydigan yuzboshi (oqsoqollar) tomonidan boshqarilgan. Yuzboshi va uning yordamchilari Mahalladagi barcha jamoat ishlari va marosimlarni boshqargan. Shuningdek, fuqarolarning shahar yig‘inlari va shahar muassasalarida mahallaning manfaatlarini himoya qilgan. Mahalla jamiyatning tuzilmasi sifatida tarixan bir qancha rivojlanish bosqichlarini bosib o‘tdi. U 20-asrning 1-choragida o‘zining an’anaviy shaklini oldi.

Sovet hukumati mahallalarga o‘z umrini yashab bo‘lgan o‘tmish sarqiti sifatida qaradi. Shundan kelib chiqib, u an’anaviy milliy boshqaruvlarni bekor qilish

yo‘li bilan bu yerda sanoatlashgan jamiyatni qaror toptirish siyosatini joriy etishga kirishdi. 20-yillar boshlaridan sovet hukumati mahallalar vazifasini cheklash, o‘ziga bo‘ysundirishga intildi. Biroq mahallalar o‘zining yashovchanligini namoyon etib, an’anaviy xayot va aloqa tarziga qarshi har qanday hujumlarga va ularni yo‘qotish yo‘lidagi urinishlarga dosh berdi. U ilgari hayot tarzi, urf-odat va rasm rusumlarni saqlab qoldi. 1932-yil 17-aprelda O‘zbekistonda birinchi marotaba shaharlardagi „Mahalla qo‘mitalari to‘g‘risida“ Nizom qabul qilindi. 1935—1936 yillarda mahallalarda oqsoqol boshchiligida Mahalla qo‘mitalari tashkil etilib, aholi o‘rtasida olib boriladigan barcha ishlarni rais boshqargan.

1961-yil avgustda O‘zbekiston Oliy Kengashi tomonidan chiqarilgan „Respublika shahar, qishloq, posyolkalaridagi va ovullaridagi mahalla qo‘mitalari to‘g‘risida“gi Nizomda ham mahallaga yuridik shaxs maqomi berilmagan edi. Mahalla qo‘mitalari biron-bir moliyaviy xo‘jalik faoliyati bilan shug‘ullanishi mumkin emas, ular oldi sotdi, ijaraga berish ishlarini bajarishda qatnashishlari mumkin bo‘lmagan. Mahallaning huquq va vakolatlari cheklangan edi.

Natijalar va ularning muhokamasi (Results and its discussion).

Bu davrda **mahalla**, (mahallat, yer, daha, jamoa, el, yurt kabi) bir qancha nomlar bilan yuritilgan hamda shahar jamiyatining nafaqat hududiy, shu bilan birga, eng quyi birligi hisoblanib, o‘z vakolatlarni amalga oshirishda odamlarning avloddan-avlodga o‘tib kelayotgan o‘zlarining qon-qarindoshlik va ruhiy yaqinlik haqidagi tasavvurlariga tayangan. Har bir dahaning o‘z oqsoqollari, qozilari va ma‘muriy boshqaruvidagi boshqa alohida mansablari bo‘lgan. Dahalar Qo‘qon xonligi davrida shaharning obro‘li xonadon vakillaridan tayinlangan oqsoqollar tomonidan boshqarilgan bo‘lsa, Rossiya imperiyasi istilosidan so‘ng mingboshilar tomonidan idora qilingan. Ayrim hollarda esa bir necha mahallalarga tavochilar biriktirilgan. Dahalar tarkibidagi mahallalar boshqaruvi esa ellikboshilar qo‘lida bo‘lgan.

Mahallaga boshchilik qilgan shaxslar mahalladagi barcha jamoat ishlari va marosimlarini boshqarganlar, shuningdek, fuqarolarning shahar yig'inlari va muassasalarida mahalla manfaatlarini himoya qilish vakolatiga ega bo'lganlar. Mahallaning jamoa tartibi o'zini o'zi boshqarish tizimi bilan belgilangan, uni boshqaruvchi vakillar umumiy yig'inlarda saylanganlar. Jamoa boshlig'i qilib, ko'pincha boy bo'lmagan, o'rta hol, katta hayotiy tajribaga ega bo'lgan hurmatli kishini saylaganlar. U fuqarolar o'rtasida hurmat e'tiborga ega bo'lishi va shahar yig'inida, daha sudida mahalla manfaatlarini munosib himoya qila olishi lozim bo'lgan. Shuningdek, bu davrda ayollarning ijtimoiy hayotiga oqsoqollar tomonidan saylab qo'yilgan kayvoni rahbarlik qilgan. Kayvoni lavozimiga mahallada katta hurmat qozongan va o'zbek turmush tarzini, urf-odat va an'alarini butun nozikligi bilan biladigan, serg'ayrat, faol, tashkilotchilik qobiliyatiga ega, odob-ahloqi bilan obro'-e'tibor qozongan ayol loyiq ko'rilgan. Unga xodima yoki dasturxonchi ko'maklashgan. Bu vazifaga ko'pincha beva xotinlarni saylaganlar, chunki ularning bo'sh vaqti ko'p bo'lgan hamda bu ish ularga qo'shimcha daromad keltirgan.

Mahallalar 1917 yilgacha bo'lgan davrda juda keng ish olib borib, mahalliy aholini birlashtiruvchi tashkiliy tuzilma bo'lgan. Sobiq sho'rolar hokimiyati mahallalarni tuman, shahar, qishloq Boshqarmalari rahbarligida boshqargan. Lekin u davrda mahallalar boshqaruv tizimi sifatida «chalajon» holatga keltirib qo'yilgan. Ular xalqning dastlabki jamoat tashkiloti sifatida faoliyat ko'rsatishi uchun hech qanday huquq, vakolat, imkoniyatga ega bo'lmagan hamda mahalliy hokimiyat organlarining quyi bo'g'ini sifatida qaralgan. Ammo shunga qaramay, sho'rolar davrida hukmron tuzum va mafkura mahallalarni rasman tan olmasada, biroq aholining chuqur noroziligiga sabab bo'lmaslik uchun mahallalarni taqiqlay ham olmagan, uni jamiyatni boshqarish tizimiga kiritmagan.

Bir so'z bilan aytganda, sovet hukumati mahallaga o'z umrini yashab bo'lgan o'tmish sarqiti sifatida qaragan. 20-yillar boshlaridan sovet hukumating uni vazifa va vakolatlarini cheklash, o'ziga bo'ysundirishga intildi. Bu esa o'z

navbatida mahalla faoliyatiga o'z ta'sirini o'tkazdi. Biroq, mahalla o'zining yashovchanligini namoyon etib, an'anaviy hayot va aloqa tarziga qarshi har qanday hujumlarga va ularni yo'qotish yo'lidagi urinishlarga dosh berdi.

1935-1936 yillarda mahallalar (oqsoqol) boshchiligida mahalla komitetlari tashkil etilib, aholi o'rtasida olib boriladigan barcha ishlarni rais boshqargan. Rasmiy doiralar mahalla idoralariga aholini hisobga olish va ma'lumotnomalar berish 1941 yilda O'zbekiston SSR xalq komissarlari soveti «O'zbekiston SSR shaharlaridagi mahalla (kvartal) qo'mitalari to'g'risida»gi nizomning yangi tahririni qabul qildi. Unga binoan, mahalla komitetlari a'zolari mehnatlariga hech qanday haq olmas edi. Mahalla komitetlari moliyaviy-xo'jalik ishlari (oshxonalar, qizil choyxona, sartaroshxonalar ochish va ularni ishlatish) bilan shug'ullanishi mumkin emas edi, ular yuridik shaxs maqomiga ega bo'lmagan. Uning asosiy vakolatlari mahalla hududidagi sovet, partiya va jamoat tashkilotlariga madaniy-ommaviy ishlarda yordam berish, ko'chalar, maydonlar, hovlilarni obodonlashtirish hamda tabiiy jihatdan ularni nazorat qilishdan iborat bo'lgan. 1953 yil 3 aprelda O'zbekiston SSR Ministrlar Boshqarmasining «O'zbekiston SSR shaharlaridagi mahalla (kvartal) qo'mitalari to'g'risida»gi Qarori qabul qilinib, unda mahallalarning soliq yig'ishdagi amaliy vazifasi o'z dolzarbligini yo'qotdi. Asosiy e'tibor esa, g'oyaviy va tashviqot hamda targ'ibot ishlariga qaratildi. Shu bilan birga, mahallalarga mustaqil birlashma deb emas, balki sovet organlari qarorlarining tarqatuvchilari va yordamchilari sifatida qaraldi. Mahalla komitetlarining faoliyati sotsialistik shiorlar ostida olib borildi. Boshqacha aytganda, sobiq Ittifoq mafkurasi mahallalarni rasman tan olmadi, ularni jamiyatni boshqarish tizimiga kiritmadi. Mahallalar faoliyati milliy qadriyatlarni e'zozlash va targ'ib qilishga emas, balki faqat sobiq mustabid tuzum g'oyalariga qaratildi, uning tuzilishi ma'muriy-buyruqbozlik tizimiga xos belgilar bilan shakllantirildi. Ma'naviyat, ta'lim-tarbiya sohasida mahallaning ahamiyati yo'qqa chiqarilgan, yuridik shaxs huquqlaridan foydalanish man etilgan edi.

Yuqoridagi Qaror bo'yicha mahallalar faqatgina fuqarolarga mulk huquqi asosida tegishli bo'lgan uylar ko'pchilikni tashkil qiladigan ko'cha va mavzeldagi hududlarda tashkil etilishi belgilandi. Bu davlat mulki bo'lgan uy-joylar hududida mahalla qo'mitalari tashkil etilmasligini anglatar edi. Qarorga ko'ra, mahalla qo'mitalari aholining jamoatchilik asosidagi o'zini o'zi tashkil etish bo'yicha tashkiloti bo'lib, hech qanday ma'muriy vakolatlarga ega bo'lmagan. Ular buyruq va farmoyishlar chiqara olmaganlar, jarima yoki to'lovlar undirishlari mumkin bo'lmagan, guvohnoma, ma'lumotnoma va boshqa rasmiy hujjatlar ham bera olmagan, shuningdek, o'z muhriga ega bo'lishi ham mumkin bo'lmagan.

Guvohi bo'lganimizdek, ushbu davrda chiqarilgan barcha huquqiy hujjatlarda mahallalarning huquqlari va vakolatlari qat'iy cheklangan bo'lib, yuqorida ta'kidlaganimizdek ularga yuridik shaxs maqomi berilmagan edi. Shu bilan birga 1958 yil 30 iyulda O'zbekiston SSR Ministrlar Boshqarmasi «Mahalla (kvartal) qo'mitalariga o'z muhriga ega bo'lish huquqini taqdim etish to'g'risida»gi Qaror qabul qilib, unda ushbu tuzilmalarga tegishli mahalla (kvartal) qo'mita nomi tushurilgan uchburchak shakldagi muhrga ega bo'lish vakolatini berdi. Ushbu Qaror asosida «O'zbekiston SSR shaharlaridagi mahalla (kvartal) qo'mitalari to'g'risida»gi Nizomning bandiga o'zgartirish va qo'shimchalar kiritilib, mahalla (kvartal) qo'mitalariga ko'p bolali oilalar va yolg'iz onalarga davlat nafaqasini olish uchun bolalar soni to'g'risida turar-joydan ma'lumotnomani, ish joyiga taqdim etish uchun qaramog'idagi boqiluvchilar soni to'g'risidagi ma'lumotnomani, propiska uchun kelish va ketish varaqasini, pasportni olish va almashti-rishni muhr bilan tasdiqlash vakolati berildi.

Shunday bo'lsada, ushbu davrda mahalla vakolatlari faqatgina mahalliy ahamiyatdagi masalalar yuzasidan rasmiy ma'lumotlarni tasdiqlashdan iborat bo'lgan, xolos. Ular mustaqil moliyaviy-xo'jalik yoki tashkiliy-boshqaruv vakolatlariga ega bo'lmagan. Masalan, 1961 yil 30 avgustda O'zbekiston SSR Oliy Soveti tomonidan qabul qilingan «O'zbekiston SSR shahar, posyolka,

qishloq va ovullaridagi mahalla qo‘mitalari to‘g‘risida»gi Nizomga ko‘ra ham mahalla komitetlari biron moliyaviy xo‘jalik faoliyati bilan shug‘ullanishlari (oshxonalar, sartaroshxonalar va shu kabilarni tashkil qilishlari va ulardan foydalanishlari) mumkin emas edi. Shuningdek, ular oldi-sotdi, ijaraga berish ishlarini amalga oshirishda qatnashishlari mumkin emas, degan norma mustahkamlanganligi ham mahallalarning huquq va vakolatlarini sezilarli darajada cheklar edi, ularning huquqlarini kengaytirish o‘rniga kun tartibiga ularni cheklash haqidagi masalalar doimiy ravishda qo‘yilib kelar edi.

Xulosa.

Xulosa o‘rnida shuni alohida ta’kidlash lozimki, xalqimizning milliy tabiati, azaliy an’analari va qadriyatlariga asoslangan mahalla o‘zining uzoq tarixida hech qachon O‘zbekiston davlat mustaqilligi davridagidek alohida e’tiborga sazovor bo‘lgan emas. Davlat mustaqilligi sharofati bilan O‘zbekistonda mahallalarga e’tibor berish, ularning ta’lim-tarbiyaviy huquqiy maqomini oshirish, o‘zini o‘zi boshqarish, beva-bechoralar, nogironlarning biron bir sababga ko‘ra omadi yurishmagan oilalar va odamlarning issiq-sovug‘idan, g‘am-tashvishlaridan xabardor bo‘lib, moddiy va ma’naviy yordam ko‘rsatish singari masalalar bo‘yicha, shuningdek yanada obod va go‘zal, ko‘rkam va chiroyli bo‘lishi, el-ulus mehr-muhabbatini qozonishida yangi davr boshlandi. O‘zbekiston mustaqillikka erishgach, mahallalarga bo‘lgan munosabat tubdan o‘zgardi. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasining 1992 yilda qabul qilingan konstitutsiyasining 105-moddasiga va 1993-yil sentabrda qabul qilingan „Fuqarolarning o‘zini-o‘zi boshqarish organlari to‘g‘risida“gi qonunga binoan, mahallalar o‘z huquqiy maqomiga ega bo‘lib, mahalliy hokimiyat tarkibiga kirgan. Mahallalar davlatning joylardagi muhim tayanchi, yuridik shaxs sifatida o‘z mol-mulkiga, moliyaviy byudjetiga, bankdagi hisob kitob raqamiga — jamg‘armasiga ega bo‘lganligi mustaqillik tufayli mahallalar ancha rivojlanganligining isbotidir

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**MUSTAQILLIK YILLARIDA MAHALLALARDAGI IJTIMOYIY
IQTISODIY TURMUSHNING BARQARORLISHUVI**

Anotatsiya. O'zbekiston mustaqillikning ilk kunlaridanoq islohotlarning bosqichma-bosqich amalga oshirilishida yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy buhronlarning oldini olib, islohotlar samaradorligini ta'minlashga kirishdi. Fuqarolarning o'zini o'zi boshqarish organlari hududlardagi muhim masalalarni hal etishga kirishdi.[1] Mahalliy boshqaruv organlari faoliyati ustidan jamoatchilik nazorati olib borilishining o'zi Mahallalarda tom ma'nodagi demokratik qadriyatlar rivojlanishi, iqtisodiy ijtimoiy turmushning yaxshilanishiga zamin bo'la oladi. Maqolada O'zbekistonning mustaqillik yillarida ijtimoiy iqtisodiy turmushida ro'y bergan o'zgarishlar haqida tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijtimoiy hayot, qishloq xo'jaligi, demokratik qadriyatlar, "Yagona ijtimoiy reysr" islohot, barqaror iqtisodiyot.

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**SUSTAINABILITY OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC LIFE IN
NEIGHBORHOODS IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE**

Annotation. From the first days of independence, Uzbekistan started to ensure the effectiveness of reforms by preventing economic and social crises that may arise in the gradual implementation of reforms. Self-government bodies of citizens began to solve important issues in the regions. Public control over the activities of local government bodies can be the basis for the development of democratic values in the literal sense of the neighborhood and the improvement of economic and social life. The article analyzes the changes that took place in the social and economic life of Uzbekistan during the years of independence. .

Kirish (Introduction).

Avvalo, shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, mamlakatimiz yangilanish davriga qadam qo'ygan birinchi kunlardan boshlab ochiq, pragmatik va amaliy tashqi siyosat

yuritish, dunyodagi barcha taraqqiyparvar mamlakatlar, ayniqsa, qo'shni davlatlar bilan yaqin do'stlik va hamkorlik munosabatlarini mustahkamlashga ustuvor ahamiyat qaratib, fuqarolarning ijtimoiy iqtisodiy hayotini farovonlashtirishga harakat qilib kelmoqdamiz.[2] Mustaqillik yillarida respublikaning aholi harid qobiliyati bo'yicha 3,4marta 27,1milliard 92.3 Aqsh dollariga sanoat mahsulot hajmi 3 martaga oshdi. 2004 yildan buyon Respublikadagi mahallalardagi iqtisodiyot yiliga 7-9 foizga darajasidagi yuqori va barqaror iqtisodiy o'sish suratda namoyon etmoqda. Mustaqillik yillarida yalpi ichki mahsulot sanoatning hissasi 17,6 foizgacha xizmatlar ulushi 33,6 foizdan 49 foizgacha o'sdi. Mamlakatda olib borilayotgan islohotlarning barchasi mahallalardagi aholining ijtimoiy hayot farovonli uchun xizmat qiladi.[3]

Material va tadqiqot usullari (Materials and methods).

Tadqiqot olib borish jarayonida ilmiy muammoga sivilizatsion yondashuv asosida tarixiy-qiyosiy, muammoli-xronologik, ob'ektivlik, tizimli tahlil, manbaviy, qiyosiy-mantiqiy tahlil, xolislik, og'zaki so'rov kabi usullar yordamida mustaqillik yillarida aholini ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy turmushining farovonlashtirishga oid qilingan ishlar masalasi birlamchi hujjatlar tahliliga tayangan xolda atroflicha tadqiq etildi.

Natijalar va ularning muhokamasi (Results and its discussion).

Mustaqillik yillarida mahallalardagi Iqtisodiy ijtimoiy rivojlanishni ilmiy o'rganishda Surxandaryo viloyatining Angor tumani misolida ko'rib chiqish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.[3] Tuman qishloq xo'jaligining bir necha sohalariga ixtisoslashgan. Tumanning iqtisodiy ko'rsatgichi 1992-yilda 100 mlrd so'mlik qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarilgan bo'lsa, 2020 yilda 1105,7 mlrd.so'mlik qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarildi. Bu borada viloyat yalpi qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotining 5,5% ini tashkil etdi. Tuman yalpi qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotida qishloq xo'jaligining ulushi yuqori bo'lib, 57,4% ni tashkil etadi. 2020 yilda qishloq xo'jaligi yalpi mahsulotining 70,2% dehqon (shaxsiy yordamchi xo'jaliklar), 18,6% qishloq xo'jaligi faoliyati bilan shug'ullanuvchi

tashkilotlar, 11,2% xo'jaliklar tomonidan ishlab chiqarildi. So'nggi yillarda tumanda transport va xizmat ko'rsatish ham rivojlangan. Ayniqsa, mustaqillik yillarida tuman markazidan o'tgan Termiz-Toshkent avtomobil yo'lining aylanma yo'lini qurish va ishga tushirish hamda ichki yo'llarni ta'mirlash tumanda transportning geografik o'rnini yaxshilashga olib keldi. Muhtasar qilib aytganda, tumanda joylashgan mahallalarda ishlab chiqaruvchi kuchlarni oqilona joylashtirish va rivojlantirishda quyidagi masalalarni hal etish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Tumanning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishida uning iqtisodiy va intellektual salohiyatidan samarali foydalanish talab etiladi. Yana bir misol tariqasida Surxondaryo viloyatining Sherobot tumanida ham mustaqillik yillarida mahallalardagi aholining turmush tarzini ijtimoiy iqtisodiy hayotini farovonlashtirish maqsadida ko'pgina ishlar amalga oshirildi. N.Murodov nomli davlat xo'jaligidagi Bo'ston Yangiobod, Paxtazor, Guliston Botoshobod, va Girshak qishlog'laridagi barcha mahallalarni gazlashtirishga umumiy uzunligi 25,5 km gaz tarmoqlarini hamda mahallalarning ichki yo'llarida o'rta bosimli umumiy uzunligi 21,2 km gaz tarmog'i loyihalashtirilgan va hamda hayotga joriy etilgan.[4] Bundan tashqari 1992-1993 yillarda tumandagi har bir mahallaning fuqarolarini ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, huquqiy yashash holatini yaxshilash maqsadida tuman xokimi tomonidan quyidagi ishlar amalga oshirildi.

- Mahalla fuqarolarini yaxshi yashashi uchun ijtimoiy hayoti himoya qilindi.
- Tumandagi xo'jalik tashkilotlariga bozor iqtisodiyotiga o'tish munosabati bilan aholini oziq ovqat va sanoat mahsulotlari bilan ta'minlandi.
- Davlat bahosi bilan aholiga sotiladigan mollar sonini ko'rib chiqib ularning sonini ko'paytirishga harakat qilindi.
- Mehnatkash aholini ish bilan ta'minlandi.
- Mahalladagi ishsiz bo'lgan fuqarolar o'rganilib chiqilib, ishsizlar sonini kamaytirish maqsadida fuqarolar ish bilan ta'minlandi.

Tadbikorlarga ishlab chiqarish sanoat korxonalarini rivojlantirish uchun sharoitlar yaratib berildi.[5]

Xulosa. Xulosa qilib shuni ta’kidlab o’tishimiz lozimki mamlakatimizda ehtiyojmandlarga ijtimoiy yordam ko’rsatishning keng qamrovli mexanizmi yo’lga qo’yilishi mustaqillikning ilk kunlaridan boshlangan bo’lsada, hozirgi kungacha davom etib kelmoqda.[6] Mamlakatda ishlab chiqilayotgan har bir qilinayotgan ishlar insonga va yana insonga xizmat qilishi ham bejizga emas. Prezident farmoniga muvofiq, ijtimoiy yordamning barcha turlarini bir xil mezon va bir xil hujjatga muvofiq taqdim etish imkonini beradigan “Yagona ijtimoiy reystr” yaratilmoqda. tizim barcha hududlarda bosqichma-bosqich joriy etilmoqda. Bu tizim orqali ma’lumotlarni tizimlashtirish har bir ijtimoiy yordam oluvchining ehtiyoj darajasini hisobga olgan holda amalga oshiriladi. U oila a’zolarining daromadlari, mol-mulki, bank hisoblari, olingan kreditlar va avtomobillar to’g’risidagi turli idoralarning tegishli bazalarida mavjud bo’lgan ma’lumotlar asosida aniqlanadi. Istiqbolda “Yagona ijtimoiy reyestr” dasturining to’liq ishga tushirilishi inson omilini sezilarli darajada minimallashtiradi va natijada ijtimoiy yordamni taqsimlashdagi korrupsiya holatlarini imkon qadar bartaraf etadi. Shuni ham ta’kidlash kerakki, aholining eng kambag’al qatlamlarini ijtimoiy himoya qilish va qo’llab-quvvatlash siyosati ehtiyojmand oilalarga beriladigan yordam pullari bilan cheklanib qolmasdan maqsad — aholining iqtisodiy farovonligi darajasini oshirish uchun sharoit yaratishdir.[7] Odatda kambag’allikka tushib qolishdan ko’ra, undan chiqish anchayin mushkul hisoblanadi. Shu bois davlat tomonidan ijtimoiy qo’llab-quvvatlash odamlarni bosqichma bosqich kambag’allikdan chiqarish hisoblanadi — boshqacha aytganda, odamlarni ana shu holatda tutib turishdan ko’ra, kambag’allar toifasidan chiqarish vositasi sifatida ko’proq o’zini ko’rsatishi uchun tegishli sharoitlarni yaratish davlat ijtimoiy siyosatining ustuvor vazifasi etib belgilangan.

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WORDLY
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QADRIYATLAR TO‘G‘RISIDAGI ILMIY-NAZARIY

YONDASHUVLAR VA KONSEPTSIYALARNING TAHLILI

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada qadriyatlar to‘g‘risidagi ilmiy-nazariy yondashuvlar va konseptsiyalarning tahliliga oid ma‘lumotlar o‘rganilgan. Bunda antik davrdan boshlab qadriyat tushunchasining Yevropa falsafasida Suqrot, Demokrit, Aflotun singari yunon olimlari bildirgan fikr-mulohazalari asos qilib olingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: ilmiy-nazariy yondashuv, konseptsiya, qadriyat, umuminsoniy qadriyat, milliy qadriyat, shaxs qadriyati, jamiyat, sharq falsafasi.

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ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL APPROACHES

AND CONCEPTS ABOUT VALUES

Annotation

In this article, information on the analysis of scientific-theoretical approaches and concepts of values is studied. It is based on the opinions expressed by Greek scientists such as Socrates, Democritus, and Plato in the European philosophy of the concept of value since ancient times.

Ключевые слова: научно-теоретический подход, понятие, ценность, общечеловеческая ценность, национальная ценность, индивидуальная ценность, общество, восточная философия.

Keywords: scientific-theoretical approach, concept, value, universal value, national value, individual value, society, eastern philosophy.

Qadriyat deganda inson, uning hayoti, faoliyati, ongli mavjudot sifatida yashashi uchun zarur narsalar, voqea va hodisalar bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan keng qamrovli hodisa tushuniladi. Shu bois tadqiqot obyekti sifatida “qadriyat” mavzusi ko‘lami keng mavzulardan sanaladi. Insoniyat tarixining ilk davrlaridayoq odamlar narsalarning muayyan qimmatga ega ekanligini, insonning u yoki bu ehtiyojlarini qondira olishini, biron sohada foydali bo‘lishi

mumkinligini kashf etganlar. Shu bilan narsalarning qadriyaviy xususiyati ochilgan.

Dastlabki paytlarda bu xususiyat buyumlarning amaliy foydasi bilan bog'lanar edi. Keyinchalik qadriyat maqomi boshqa ijtimoiy institutlar va ma'naviy hodisalarda ham tan olina boshlanadi. Inson o'z faoliyatini yo'naltirishi lozim bo'lgan ne'matlar va qadriyatlar muammosi **qadimgi Sharq falsafasi** va falsafaga qadar bo'lgan fikr tarixida muhim o'rin tutadi.

Markaziy Osiyo azal-azaldan ilm-fan va madaniyatning adabiyot va san'atning markazlaridan biri bo'lib kelgan. Bu o'lkada yetishib chiqqan buyuk mutafakkirlar jahon ilm-fani va madaniyatini o'z kashfiyotlari va o'lmas asarlari bilan ijodiy boyitib, yuqori cho'qqiga ko'tardilar, uning keying taraqqiyotiga samarali ta'sir ko'rsatdilar.

Axloqiy qadriyatlar kishilarning bir-birlariga, o'zlari mansub jamoaga, vatanga nisbatan tarixan tarkib topgan munosabatlarini ifodalaydi. Axloq muayyan xulq-atvor, odob, xatti-harakat, me'yor, qoidalar majmuasidir. Axloqiy tushunchalarga yaxshilik va yomonlik, burch, vijdon, sha'n (or-nomus), baxt, adolat, ideal kabilar kiradi. Insonning oila, jamiyat, xalq manfaatlarini anglab qilayotganhar qanday xatti-harakati yaxshilik kategoriyasi nuqtai nazaridan baholanadi. Burch – kishining Vatan, xalq, jamoa, oila bilan o'zaro munosabatlarida o'z oldidagi majburiyat va mas'uliyatni sezishi, ularga nisbatan sadoqatini ifodalaydi. Vijdon – kishining xatti-harakatiga o'zining munosabatini, kishining o'z xulq-odobi uchun ma'naviy mas'uliyat hissini ifodalaydi. Sha'n – tushunchasi shaxsga jamiyat beradigan ijtimoiy bahoni belgilovchi va shaxsiy qadr-qimmatini ifoda qiluvchi kategoriyadir. Baxt tushunchasi insonning ijtimoiy va shaxsiy hayotidagi o'z faoliyati, ro'yobga chiqqan orzu-istak va maqsadlaridan mamnunligini bildiradi. Axloq kategoriyalari insonning yurish-turishiga baho beradi, uni jamiyatda mavjud, ko'pchilik ma'qullagan xatti harakatga chorlaydi.

Sharq falsafasi va islom ta'limotida axloq-odob, ta'lim-tarbiya masalalariga doimo katta e'tibor berib kelingan. Inson axloqi shunchaki salom-alik, xushmuomaladangina iborat emas. Axloq – bu avvalo insof va adolat tuyg'usi, imon, halollik degani.

Jamiyat taraqqiyotida, inson hayotida ijtimoiy-siyosiy qadriyatlar alohida o'rin tutadi. Erkinlik, tenglik, birodarlik insoniyat tomonidan hamisha e'zozlab, qadrlanib kelingan. Insonning erkinligi, uning shon-shuhrati va qadr-qimmatini jamiyatimizning oliy qadriyatidir. Boshqa xalqlar, millatlarga nisbatan do'stlik, birodarlik munosabatida bo'lishi – bu o'zbek xalqi milliy ruhiyatining ajralmas failatidir. Xalqimiz hech qachon o'zini boshqa xalqdan ustun qo'ymagan. Boshqa millatlarga, boshqa mazhab vakillariga munosib darajada ehtirom ko'rsatgan. Jahonda katta va kichik millatlar va elatlar yo'q. Ularning har biri asriy barqaror va tengi yo'q an'analari bilan, tarixiy merosining boyligi bilan, milliy madaniyati va tarixini tiklashdangina iborat emas, balki birgalikda hayot kechiruvchi kam sonli xalqlarning taqdiri uchun, ularning o'ziga xos madaniy ma'naviy xususiyatlarini saqlab qolish uchun, kamol topishi va imkoniyatlar yaratib berish borasida mas'ul bo'lishdan ham iboratdir.

Qadriyat muammosiga antik davrdayoq shakllangan yondashuvlar o'z ko'rinishlarini muayyan darajada o'zgartirgan holda keying falsafiy tizimlarda ham saqlab keldilar. Aksiologiya muammosini ishlab chiqishga I.Kant, G.Lotse, G.Rikkert, N.Gartman, F.Nitsshe va boshqalar o'z hissalarini qo'shdilar.

XIX asr o'rtasiga qadar falsafada “borliq” va “qadriyat” tushunchalari bir-biridan ajratilmagan edi. Aksiologiya (yunoncha axia – qadriyat va logos ta'limot so'zlaridan) mustaqil fan sifatida borliq tushunchasi ikki komponentga ajralgan paytda yuzaga keladi: bir narsaning mavjud bo'lishi va uning mohiyati. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, obyekt va subyektning o'zaro ta'siri paytda subyekt uchun obyektida shunday bir narsa ayon bo'ladiki, uni obyektning mavjud bo'lishining o'zigagina bog'lab bo'lmaydi, ya'ni u go'yo ushbu mavjudlik chegarasidan tashqarida turadi va u uchun muayyan ahamiyatga ega bo'ladi.

Obyekt va subyektning o‘zaro ta‘sirini ana shunday tushunish qadriyat tushunchasini hozirgi zamon falsafasining kategorial apparatining elementi sifatida shakllanishi uchun boshlang‘ich nuqta bo‘lib xizmat qiladi.

Ma‘lumki, fan nuqtayi nazaridan falsafa tarixida “qadriyat” alohida falsafiy kategoriya sifatida o‘rganilib kelinadi. Dastlab, antik davrdan boshlab qadriyat tushunchasining Yevropa falsafasida Suqrot, Demokrit, Aflotun singari yunon olimlari bildirgan mulohazalari haqida dissertatsiyaning birinchi faslida aytib o‘tdik. Falsafaga oid darslik va qo‘llanmalarda qadriyatlar turli tiplarga ajratib ko‘rsatiladi. Kelib chiqishi hamda mohiyatiga qarab qadriyatlar o‘z ichida bir necha turlarga bo‘linadi. Nima va nimaga asosan baholanishiga ko‘ra **predmetli qadriyatlar, subyektli qadriyatlar**ga ajratiladi.

“**Predmetli qadriyatlar** – qadr-qimmat munosabatlarining obyektlari, ya‘ni voqelikdagi subyekt uchun muayyan qimmatga ega bo‘lgan hodisalar. Ularga quyidagilar kiradi:

- tabiiy obyektlar, jarayonlar va hodisalar;
- ijtimoiy obyektlar, jarayonlar va hodisalar”²⁹.

Shuningdek, “**subyektli qadriyatlar** – u yoki bu hodisalarni baholash tadbirini o‘tkazishda asos bo‘lib xizmat qiluvchi usullar va mezonlar. Ularga quyidagilar kiradi: me‘yoriy taqdimnomalar sifatida bayon etilgan ko‘rsatmalar, baholar, imperativlar, maqsadlar, loyihalar”³⁰.

Qadriyatlar ijtimoiy holatiga qarab **axloqiy, badiiy, utilitar, ilmiy, diniy** kabi turlarga ajratiladi. Umumiylik darajasiga ko‘ra esa, qadriyatlar **individual, guruhliy, umuminsoniy** singari turlarga ega. Shulardan “**guruhliy qadriyatlar**(milliy, diniy, jinsiy, yosh); ushbu guruhlar doirasida G‘arb Sharq qadriyat tizimlari haqida so‘z yuritish mumkin”³¹.

²⁹Ahmedova M.A. Falsafa. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati, 2006. B. 435

³⁰ Ahmedova M.A. Falsafa. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati, 2006. B. 435

³¹ O‘sha manba.

Subyektlarning maqsadlari va tamoyillari qay darajada xususiyligiga qarab **tashqi** va **ichki** qadriyatlarga bo‘linadi. Inson hayoti va faoliyatida qadrlilik darajasiga ko‘ra ham farqlanadi:

- “**mutlaq** yoki **boqiy** qadriyatlar (konstantalar);

vaziyatli, o‘tkinchi yoki qadriyatlar va qadriyaviy mezonlarining muayyan tarixiy shakllari (empirik o‘zgaruvchan qadriyatlar)”³².

Qadriyatlar bajaradigan vazifasiga hamda ijtimoiy tartibni yaratish va saqlashda ham farqlanadi. Jamiyatning u yoki bu dolzarb masalalariga oid qadriyatlar ham yil sayin inson va jamiyat bilan birga rivojlanib, o‘zgarib boradi. “Bugungi kunda shu narsa ayon bo‘lyaptiki, biron bir sohaga aksiologik yondashuvlardan tashqarida ko‘rib chiqilishi mumkin emas”³³. Qadriyatlarni baholashda uni o‘rganishda lokal va global masalalarga birdek aloqador bo‘ladi. “O‘z navbatida qadriyatlarning o‘ziga, munosabat va qadriyaviy ongga **gnoseologik, sotsiologik, psixologik, semiotik** va boshqa yondashuvlar nuqtayi nazaridan qaralmoqda”³⁴.

Ijtimoiy falsafa bo‘yicha “Jamiyatning ma’naviy yangilanishida milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlar uyg‘unligini shakllantirish masalalari” mavzusida tadqiqot olib brogan Ruziyeva Ruxsora Xodiyevna o‘z dissertatsiyasida “qadriyatga oid ilmiy-nazariy yondashuv va konseptsiyalarni quyidagi yo‘nalishlarga ajratadi: Nigilistik yondashuv; Fenomenologik yondashuv; Ma’naviy-axloqiy yondashuv; Badiiy-estetik yondashuv; Madaniy-sivilizatsiyaviy; kontseptsiyalar; Psixologik kontseptsiyalar; Gumanistik kontseptsiyalar; Yevropotsentrizm va amerikosentrizm; Sharqona kontseptsiyalar; Antropologik kontseptsiyalar; Milliy tiklanish va rivojlanish konseptsiyasi”³⁵.

Yuqorida keltirilgan ushbu yo‘nalishlar miqdorini qadriyat mohiyatiga ko‘ra yana davom ettirish mumkin. Xulosa o‘rnida shuni aytish mumkinki,

³² Ahmedova M.A. Falsafa. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati, 2006. B. 436

³³ Ahmedova M.A. Falsafa. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati, 2006. B. 436

³⁴ O‘sha manba.

³⁵ Нитше Ф. Воля к власти. Опыт переоценки всех ценностей (1884-1888). – М.: ТОО «Транспорт», 1995. – С. 35

qadriyat nafaqat falsafaga oid tushuncha, balki pedagogika, psixologiya sohasiga doir yoʻnalishlar uchun ham birdek muhim boʻlgan masalalardan biri sanaladi.

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Mustaqil tadqiqotchi

**ONA TILI FANINI ANIQ FANLAR BILAN ALOQADORLIKDA
O‘QITISH**

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy ta’limda ommalashib borayotgan fanlararo integratsiya masalasi yoritilgan. Maqolada ona tilini aniq fanlar bilan aloqadorlikda o‘qitishning afzalliklari tahlilga tortilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: ona tili, aniq fanlar, integratsiyalashgan o‘qitish, yangilangan darsliklar, miqdor va son, grafik organayzerlar, matematika, geometriya.

Shamshieva D.

Independent researcher

**TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF MOTHER LANGUAGE IN
RELATION TO EXACT SCIENCES**

ABSTRACT

This article explained the issue of interdisciplinary integration, which is becoming popular in modern education. The article analyzed the advantages of teaching mother tongue in connection with exact sciences.

Key words: mother language, exact sciences, integrated teaching, updated textbooks, quantity and number, graphic organizers, mathematics, geometry.

Introduction

Teaching native language science in connection with mathematics creates an interesting and effective lesson. One of the interesting subjects, Mathematics, enriches the student's logical thinking, thoughtful imagination and new concepts. Teaching it in connection with the subject of the native language gives the opportunity to equally involve all students in the educational process.

First of all, by the connection of the native language and mathematics, the direct number of word categories is understood in our minds. Indeed, "number" is the object of study of both disciplines. In mathematics “ "numbers" form the basis of science, while in mother tongue science, numbers are also widely studied as a separate category. The subject of the mother tongue studies extensively the

structural aspect of the number, the types of meaning, the way it is made, its place in the sentence. In addition the study of Count words (numeratives) with numbers also falls within the scope of the word category “son”.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Historically, the fact that numbers and verbs in Uzbek belong to the pure Turkic layer is an important and interesting information for readers. For several centuries, these words have been living without losing their lexical value, significance (only having undergone some phonetic changes). While the lexical semen of numbers remains the same, introducing them to existing changes in the order of counting serves to increase their interest in the etymology of words in them. That is, memorabilia has a number-specific property, which applies to two-digit numbers with a unit higher than ten. In this case, the unit is said before, followed by the non-decimal of the same number: *baş* twenty (fifteen), *alti* twenty (16), *one ötuz* (21), *three ötuz* (23). When the decimal is said before it is followed by “*artuqi*” before the unit. For example, *like ötuz artuqi tört yaşima* (when I was thirty-four years old).

Each word category has its place and importance in the morphology of the Uzbek language and its development, development. Also, the importance of the number Word category, like that of others, is important for our linguistics. We know that the number category indicates the number, amount, amount, sum of a person or thing. In the history of Turkic languages, the origin of the number began with the person himself. Or rather, a person made a name for the numbers by counting his fingers. Note that the origin of numbers up to ten, their fundamental, lexical meanings are associated with the name, position or position of a person's fingers. For example, a number of thumbs (*başmaldaq* in vernacular) binds *qa*. The two are later (the first finger after the thumb), so named because the kite is located at the tip of the hand, etc. If the naming of numbers up to ten is etymologically researched, this idea finds its proof. This process is due to the fact that the origin of the numerical word category in Turkic languages, the main thing is that the

historical roots of Turkic languages are rooted in the early people of the human society, at the moment of the initial appearance of the language. Hence, our words in the number category are a legacy left to us from the very beginning of society, that is, when a person began to learn to count. By the time of the old Turkic language, however, the numerical series had improved and become a single-ended system. According to him, in the ancient Turks there was no number “zero”, since “Zero” is an absent number. The count began at once. At the time of the birth of a person, one age was counted, since the period in the mother's womb was calculated by adding. A year later, a person turned two years old, and at the same date went to join the age young. In some ways, the condition still survives today, due to the fact that when a person died, “How was the age of the deceased?”, when asked” mother is so old with her belly”, she is answered.

In old Turkic and old Uzbek, there was also a type of meaning of numbers called “irregular numbers”. Such numbers represented an approximate as well as an uncertain quantity and stood close to the numerical numbers in content. Irregular numbers are represented in old Uzbek, mainly by the words *kop*, *az*. Also expressed in old Uzbek is the Persian word *bisyar* (plural) in the sense of an indefinite number: *Pari paykar daği bisyar dandur*. Sources from the 13th to 14th centuries also used the words *telim* (plural), *ökush* (plural), characteristic of the language of ancient Turkic monuments in the sense of an uncertain number: *Telim kishilar öldi, talim qan töküldi*. In modern Uzbek literary language, these words are not considered to belong to the numeral category, but to the word category *ravish* (level-quantity).

Conclusion

Turkic languages, in particular Uzbek, have long and many millennia in their history. How many shells our tongue, which at first glance seemed simple, passed and polished to look like today. In particular, the numerical word category, which is considered part of the morphology of our language, is no exception. As we study the use of numbers in the history of the language, we become aware of

both the morphology of that time and the grammar of the period, the emergence of numbers among Turkic peoples. In addition, today we come across similar and different forms of counting words that have taken over from our lexicon as an archaic word or are not at all familiar to us, which are used during the stages of our language development. In modern Uzbek, we will learn about the use of some of the words considered as a word category of ravish as a number in the era of the old Turkic language. We will witness that certain features of the number in ancient, Old Turkic languages, which are not characteristic of our literary language, which is now in force, but exist in our dialect. Therefore, the importance of number was important at any time in the development of our language.

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**INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA EMOTIV SO'ZLARNING
TARJIMADAGI MUAMMOLARI**

***Annotatsiya:** maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida emotiv so'zlarning tarjimadagi muammolari hamda ularning nazariy jihatlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Emotiv so'zlarning to'g'ri tarjimasi, o'quvchi yoki tinglovchining his-tuyg'ularini to'g'ri anglashiga yordam beradi va madaniyatlararo muloqotni kuchaytiradi. Bu esa ushbu maqolada batafsil ifodalangan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** emotiv so'zlar, his-tuyg'u, kontekst, nostalgiya, o'zbek va ingliz tili.*

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**PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF EMOTIVE WORDS IN
ENGLISH AND UZBEK**

Annotation: the article provides information on the problems of translation of emotive words in English and Uzbek, as well as their theoretical aspects. The correct translation of emotive words helps the reader or listener to understand their emotions correctly and enhances intercultural communication. This is detailed in this article.

Keywords: emotive words, emotion, context, nostalgia, Uzbek and English.

Tarjima jarayoni nafaqat so'zlarni bir tildan boshqasiga o'zgartirish, balki ma'no, hissiyot va kontekstni ham saqlab qolishni talab qiladi. Emotiv so'zlar, ya'ni his-tuyg'ularni ifodalovchi so'zlar, tarjima jarayonida ko'plab muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Emotiv so'zlar — bu inson his-tuyg'ularini, kayfiyatini va hissiyotlarini ifodalovchi so'zlardir. Ular ko'pincha kuchli hissiy ta'sirga ega bo'lib, o'quvchining yoki tinglovchining his-tuyg'ularini uyg'otadi. Masalan, "love" (sevgi), "hate" (nafrat), "joy" (quvonch) kabi so'zlar emotiv so'zlar hisoblanadi. Emotiv so'zlar ko'pincha kontekstga bog'liq bo'ladi. Ingliz tilidagi "love" so'zi turli kontekstlarda turlicha ma'nolarga ega bo'lishi mumkin.

O'zbek tilida esa bu so'z "sevgi" deb tarjima qilinadi, lekin uning ma'nosi kontekstga qarab o'zgarishi mumkin. Masalan, "I love pizza" (Men pizzani

sevaman) va "I love you" (Men seni sevaman) iboralaridagi "love" soʻzining hissiyati va maʼnosi farq qiladi. Har bir til oʻz madaniyatiga xos emotiv soʻzlarni oʻz ichiga oladi. Ingliz tilida "nostalgia" (nostalgiya) soʻzi keng tarqalgan boʻlsa, oʻzbek tilida bu hissiyotni ifodalovchi aniq bir soʻz yoʻq. Bunday hollarda tarjimonlar koʻpincha soʻzlarni izohlaydilar yoki sinonimlardan foydalanadilar, bu esa asl maʼnoni yoʻqotishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Ingliz tilida bir nechta sinonimlar mavjud boʻlib, ularning har biri turli hissiy yuklamalarga ega. Masalan, "happy" (baxtli), "joyful" (quvnoq) va "content" (qoniqish) soʻzlari oʻzaro oʻxshash boʻlsa-da, ularning hissiy taʼsiri farq qiladi.

Oʻzbek tilida esa bunday farqlarni ifodalash qiyin boʻlishi mumkin, chunki baʼzi soʻzlar bir xil maʼnoni anglatishi mumkin. Emotiv soʻzlar koʻpincha rang-barang hissiyotlarni ifodalaydi. Ingliz tilida "sad" (gʻamgin) soʻzi turli darajadagi gʻamginlikni ifodalashi mumkin, masalan, "unhappy" (baxtsiz) yoki "depressed" (depressiyaga tushgan). Oʻzbek tilida esa bu hissiyotlarni ifodalovchi soʻzlar koʻproq kontekstga bogʻliq boʻladi va baʼzan aniq farqlarni koʻrsatmaydi. Tarjimonlar emotiv soʻzlarni tarjima qilishda turli usullardan foydalanadilar. Baʼzan, toʻgʻridan-toʻgʻri tarjima qilish mumkin, lekin koʻpincha izohli tarjima yoki sinonimlardan foydalanish zarur boʻladi. Bu jarayonda tarjimonning mahorati va madaniy bilimlari muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Ingliz va oʻzbek tillarida emotiv soʻzlarning tarjimasi bir qator muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Emotiv soʻzlar koʻpincha kontekstga bogʻliq boʻladi. Masalan, ingliz tilidagi "love" soʻzi turli kontekstlarda turlicha maʼnolarga ega. Oʻzbek tilida esa bu soʻz "sevgi" deb tarjima qilinadi, lekin uning maʼnosi kontekstga qarab oʻzgarishi mumkin. Tarjimon kontekstni toʻgʻri anglamasa, hissiyotlar notoʻgʻri ifodalanishi mumkin. Har bir til oʻz madaniyatiga xos emotiv soʻzlarni oʻz ichiga oladi. Ingliz tilida "nostalgia" (nostalgiya) soʻzi keng tarqalgan boʻlsa, oʻzbek tilida bu hissiyotni ifodalovchi aniq bir soʻz yoʻq.

Bunday hollarda tarjimonlar ko‘pincha so‘zlarni izohlaydilar yoki sinonimlardan foydalanadilar, bu esa asl ma‘noni yo‘qotishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Ingliz tilida bir nechta sinonimlar mavjud bo‘lib, ularning har biri turli hissiy yuklamalarga ega. Masalan, "happy" (baxtli), "joyful" (quvnoq) va "content" (qoniqish) so‘zlari o‘zaro o‘xshash bo‘lsa-da, ularning hissiy ta‘siri farq qiladi. O‘zbek tilida esa bunday farqlarni ifodalash qiyin bo‘lishi mumkin, chunki ba‘zi so‘zlar bir xil ma‘noni anglatishi mumkin. Emotiv so‘zlar ko‘pincha rang-barang hissiyotlarni ifodalaydi. Ingliz tilida "sad" (g‘amgin) so‘zi turli darajadagi g‘amginlikni ifodalashi mumkin, masalan, "unhappy" (baxtsiz) yoki "depressed" (depressiyaga tushgan). O‘zbek tilida esa bu hissiyotlarni ifodalovchi so‘zlar ko‘proq kontekstga bog‘liq bo‘ladi va ba‘zan aniq farqlarni ko‘rsatmaydi. Tarjimonlar emotiv so‘zlarni tarjima qilishda turli usullardan foydalanadilar. Ba‘zan, to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri tarjima qilish mumkin, lekin ko‘pincha izohli tarjima yoki sinonimlardan foydalanish zarur bo‘ladi. Bu jarayonda tarjimonning mahorati va madaniy bilimlari muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Emotiv so‘zlar ko‘pincha kuchli hissiy ta‘sirga ega. Tarjima jarayonida bu hissiy ta‘sirni saqlab qolish qiyin bo‘lishi mumkin. Masalan, "I am thrilled" (Men hayajondaman) iborasini o‘zbek tiliga "Men hayajonlandim" deb tarjima qilish mumkin, lekin bu ifoda asl hissiy ta‘sirni to‘liq aks ettirmasligi mumkin. Ba‘zi emotiv so‘zlar faqat bir tilga xos bo‘lishi mumkin. Masalan, ingliz tilida "schadenfreude" (boshqalarning baxtsizligidan xursand bo‘lish) so‘zi o‘zbek tilida aniq bir ekvivalentga ega emas. Bunday hollarda tarjimonlar ko‘pincha so‘zlarni izohlaydilar yoki yangi so‘zlar yaratishga harakat qiladilar. Ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida emotiv so‘zlarning tarjimasini ko‘plab muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Tarjimonlar bu muammolarni hal qilishda o‘z mahoratlarini va madaniy bilimlarini qo‘llashlari zarur. Emotiv so‘zlarning to‘g‘ri tarjimasini, o‘quvchi yoki tinglovchining his-tuyg‘ularini to‘g‘ri anglashiga yordam beradi va madaniyatlararo muloqotni kuchaytiradi.

Xulosa:

Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida emotiv so'zlarning tarjimasi ko'plab muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Kontekstga moslik, madaniy farqlar, sinonimlar va ularning hissiy yuklamasi, emotsional ranglar va tarjima usullari bu jarayonda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Tarjimonlar bu muammolarni hal qilishda o'z mahoratlarini va madaniy bilimlarini qo'llashlari zarur. Emotiv so'zlarning to'g'ri tarjimasi, o'quvchi yoki tinglovchining his-tuyg'ularini to'g'ri anglashiga yordam beradi va madaniyatlararo muloqotni kuchaytiradi.

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**CONDITION OF THE LYMPHOID-PHARYNGEAL RING AND
PHARYNX IN CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL CLEFT LIP AND
PALATE**

***Annotation.** Considering the growing number of children born with congenital cleft lip and palate (CLP), the interest of doctors of various specialties in the treatment and rehabilitation of this group of patients is increasing every year. The existing algorithms for managing such patients have been developed mainly for maxillofacial surgeons and do not cover aspects related to ENT pathology*

***Key words:** malformation, adenoid vegetation, palatine tonsils, adenoiditis, hypertrophy.*

The few publications devoted to the problems of children with CLP describe pronounced changes in the ENT organs. From the first days of life, the child has significant changes in the external nose, structures of the nasal cavity, middle ear and lymphoid-pharyngeal ring (LPR). ENT diseases are detected in children with this congenital defect in all periods of childhood. This fact indicates that surgical treatment of congenital defects performed by maxillofacial surgeons is insufficient and cannot fully solve the problem of ENT pathology in this group of patients.

The problem of congenital malformations of humans has been relevant in medicine for a long time. According to various authors, children born with congenital malformations make up from 1 to 12% of all newborns. However, there is a tendency to increase their number every year.

In the structure of congenital malformations, congenital pathology of the maxillofacial region, in particular, congenital rhinoplasty, occurs in 1.3-5% of cases. This pathology makes up 86.9% of all congenital facial defects and ranks second in frequency among congenital pathologies. According to the authors, the frequency of patients with this congenital pathology ranges from 1:500 to 1:1000 newborns. According to WHO, the worldwide birth rate of children with congenital pharyngeal tonsil defects is 0.6-1.6: 1000 newborns. In the Lipetsk region, the birth rate of such children was 1:566 in 2004 and 1:800 in 2003. Disability in this group of children occurs from the moment of birth, so information on the frequency of congenital pathology is important for understanding the health status of the population as a whole.

Hypertrophy of adenoid vegetations and palatine tonsils, acute and chronic adenoiditis and tonsillitis are often found in somatically healthy young children. And what is the situation in children with congenital pharyngeal tonsil defects? According to foreign literature, hypertrophy of adenoid vegetations is more common in patients with this congenital defect at an early age than in healthy children, but with age, the number of cases of diagnosis of hypertrophy of the pharyngeal tonsil becomes approximately equal.

Studies have shown that children with VRVGIN aged 2 to 16 months do not have hypertrophy of the adenoid vegetations, but there is moderate hyperemia of the pharyngeal tonsil in 100% of cases in children before palatal plastic surgery due to mechanical damage during feeding.

When examining children aged 3 to 13 years, it was found that in 78% of cases the volume of the pharyngeal tonsil occupied less than $\frac{1}{2}$ the height of the vomer, and in 22% of cases - half or more. The examination showed that at this age, most children either do not have hypertrophy of adenoid vegetations or do not exceed 1-2 degrees.

There are isolated studies devoted to indications for adenotomy in children with cleft lip and palate. Given the difficulty of nasal breathing due to

the curvature of the nasal septum, hypertrophy of the mucous membrane of the nasal cavity, cicatricial narrowing of the vestibule of the nose, it is obvious that even small adenoid vegetations can further complicate nasal breathing. To improve nasal breathing, it is necessary to ensure good patency of the upper respiratory tract. This can be achieved by adenotomy, but this is not always advisable in children with cleft lip and palate. There is a group of patients who develop velopharyngeal insufficiency after uranoplasty. In this case, removal of adenoids can lead to an increase in the size of the residual opening and aggravation of speech therapy problems. It turns out that, on the one hand, adenoid vegetations mechanically narrow the lumen of the airways, thereby further complicating nasal breathing, and on the other hand, they prevent the development or aggravation of clinical signs of velopharyngeal insufficiency. In this case, partial adenotomy is successfully performed. However, there are no clearly formulated indications for this operation in children with cleft lip and palate.

According to individual studies of past years, hypertrophy of the palatine tonsils occurs 2-3 times more often in children with cleft lip and palate than hypertrophy of the pharyngeal tonsil. Enlargement of the palatine tonsils is also associated with impaired nasal breathing. It was found that 1 year after uranoplasty and separation of the nasal and oral cavity, the size of the palatine tonsils remains the same.

There are works that state the fact that children with cleft lip and palate have hypertrophy of the palatine tonsils. According to the authors, hypertrophied palatine tonsils negatively affect the functioning of the soft palate and can aggravate velopharyngeal insufficiency, if any. In the presence of severe velopharyngeal insufficiency and hypertrophy of the palatine tonsils, simultaneous velopharyngoplasty and tonsillectomy are recommended. Tonsillectomy ensures better functioning of the soft palate, thereby making it possible to reduce velopharyngeal insufficiency and improve speech quality.

This is quite important, since most children with cleft lip and palate develop velopharyngeal insufficiency after uranoplasty.

Conclusion. According to the literature, when studying the microflora in this group of children, gram-negative flora predominates in the oral cavity. The results of bacteriological examination of smears from the cleft area indicate the presence of *Candida* spp., *E. coli*, *Klebsiella* spp.

Analysis of head computed tomography data indicates that the size of the nasopharynx in children with cleft lip and palate is smaller than in healthy children, a decrease in the size of the skull base in the middle cranial fossa and the height of the sphenoid bone body was noted.

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WORDLY
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**YOSHLAR HAYOTIDA VIRTUALLASHUV SABABLARI VA
OMILLARI**

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada yoshlarning virtuallashuv sabablari va omillari haqida fikr yuritilgan. Yoshlarni virtual olamdan chiqarish uchun bir qancha sabablar dalillar asosida ko'rsatib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: yoshlar, virtuallashuv, internet, telefon, vaqt taqsimoti, maqsad, kelajak, muloqot, maktab, oila, mahalla.

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**CAUSES AND FACTORS OF VIRTUALIZATION IN YOUTH
LIFE**

Annotation: this article reflects on the causes and factors of youth virtualization. Several reasons for the expulsion of young people from the virtual world have been shown on the basis of evidence.

Keywords: youth, virtualization, internet, telephone, time distribution, goal, future, communication, school, family, neighborhood.

XXI asr-texnika-taraqqiyoti asri. Ushbu davrda texnika jadal sur'atda rivojlanish barobarida uni boshqaruvchi insonlarni ham o'z to'riga yopishtirib oldi. O'rgimchak to'ri deb bejiz aytilmaganiga ko'p marta guvoh bo'lish mumkin. Kimdir internet orqali qimor o'ynaydi, yana kimdir davlatimiz kelajagiga rahna soluvchi qo'poruvchi guruhlariga a'zo bo'ladi, ba'zilar esa kundalik hayotda faqat vaqt o'tkazish uchun bir- biri bilan muloqot qiladi. Bu kabi ayanchli sabablarni qator keltirish mumkin.

Har narsadan maqsadli va samarali foydalanish juda katta mas'uliyat. Inson qilayotgan ishining naqadar ahamiyatli va hamma uchun foydali ekanligini anglab, o'sha qo'yilgan maqsad sari jadal qadam tashlasa ko'zlangan natija amalga oshadi. Maqsadsiz qilingan harakat natijasi har doim nolga teng bo'ladi. Atrofga nazar solib qaralsa, ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanuvchilarning

asosiy qismi yoshlardir. Yoshlar yurt tayanchi hisoblanadi. Agar shu asosiy qism internetdan maqsadli foydalansa, qilgan ishlari yurt taraqqiyoti, fan ravnaqi uchun xizmat qilsa nur ustiga nur. Aksi bo'lsa, mamlakat o'sish va rivojlanishi keskin pasayadi. Xo'sh, hamma ham internetdan nima maqsadda foydalanayotganligi xususida o'ylab ko'rganmi? Soatlab nima uchun qimmatli vaqtini sarflayapti? Mana shu sarf bo'lib ketgan vaqti haqida so'ralsa tayinli javob ayta oladimi? Yoki bo'lmasa, shu vaqtning xuda-bexuda sarflanganligi uchun vijdon qiynaladimi va yo mazmunli hamda barokatli o'tganidan ko'ngli to'ladimi? Ushbu savollarni har bir tarmoq foydalanuvchisi o'ziga berib kerakli xulosalarni chiqarishi darkor. O'z-o'ziga baho bera olgan inson haqiqiy ideallikka erishadi. Xo'sh, virtuellashuv sabablari nimalardan iborat? Ularni qanday bartaraf qilish zarur? Yoshlarning odamlardan ko'ra ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda bo'ladigan suhbat ko'proq qiziqtirishiga nima sabab va bunday bo'lishiga kimlar aybdor? Ijtimoiy tarmoqdagi suhbat yoshlar uchun foydalimi yoki zararli? Yoshlarni virtual hayotdan haqiqiy hayotga olib chiqish omillari bormi? Quyida ushbu savollarga javob beriladi.

Vituallashuv sabablaridan biri vaqtning to'g'ri taqsimlanmasligi. Yoshi katta insonlarda vaqtdan unumli foydalana olishlik ko'nikmasi bor. Ular xato qilganlarida ko'plab tanbehlar eshitishgan. O'zidan katta buvi va bobojonlarning aytganlarini qilib rag'bat olgan, aksini qilganlarida jazolanishgan va qilgan ishlari xato ekanligi haqida xulosa chiqarishgan. Yoshlar hali g'o'r, pishib yetilmagan. Shuning uchun o'tish davrida, ayniqsa, ko'plab muammolarga duch kelishadi. O'tish davri inqirozidan eson-omon o'tib olish uchun vaqtning to'g'ri taqsimlash va o'z-o'zini baholash kabi ko'nikmalar hosil qilishlari kerak. Bunda ularga ota-onalari, maktab muassasasida faoliyat yuritayotgan mas'ul shaxslar yordam berishlari zarur. Agar ularda sezilarli natija kuzatilmasa, shu ikkita sanalgan topshiriq ustida amallar bajarish kerak: turli xil yopiq testlar, anonim so'rovnoma va boshqalar.

Mavjud kamchiliklarni butunlay bartaraf qilish uchun yoshlar bandligini ta'minlash kerak. Bo'sh vaqt topolmagan bola bir-ikki kun qiynaladi, keyingi kunlari internetdan boshqa zarur bo'lgan ishlar borligini anglab yetadi. Ota-onalar, iloji boricha, maktab o'quvchisiga sensorli telefon ishlatishni taqiqlasalar yaxshi natijalarga erishiladi. Maktab hududiga o'quvchilarning telefon va boshqa uyali vositalar olib kirishiga to'sqinlik qilish va tartib buzilsa o'quvchining ota-onasiga jarima berish kabi maktab ichidagi qoidalarni yaratish kerak.

Ayni paytda virtuallashuvga ota-ona ham aybdor. Farzandlar nazoratiga bee'tiborlik, haddan ziyod mehr beraman deb telefon ushlatib qo'yish, pul topaman deb bolalar tarbiyasining chetda qolib ketishi kabi bir qancha misollar keltirib o'tish mumkin. Farzand tarbiyasi va kamoloti ota-ona uchun oliy vazifa bo'lishi kerak. Komil va solih farzand tarbiya qilgan inson chinakam baxtga erishadi hamda ularga ikki dunyo saodati beriladi deyilgan. Vatan ravnaqi uchun ham komillik sari yetaklovchi yo'lni ota-ona farzandiga ko'rsatib qo'ymog'i darkor. Virtuallashuvning yoshlar uchun qulay tomoni shundan iboratki, ular nojins tomon bilan bemalol suhbat olib boradi. Haqiqiy hayotda esa o'ziga nisbatan qarama-qarshi bo'lgan jins vakiliga to'g'ridan-to'g'ri muloqot olib borish noqulay. Sababi, uyat, odob, sharm kabi fazilatlari bor o'zbek bolasi suhbatdoshiga nisbatan o'ta beodob so'zlarni ishlata olmaydi. Chunki, yuqorida sanab o'tilgan fazilatlar azaldan o'zbek xalqining qon-qoniga singib ketgan. Ammo yaxshi fazilat egasi bo'lgan ayrim bolalarning ijtimoiy tarmoqdagi suhbatlariga qaralsa, ularning bu yozishmalaridan uyalib ketadi odam. Agar inson bandlik bilan ta'minlansa, ikkilamchi qiziqishlarga vaqti ham bo'lmaydi. Aniq bir maqsad qo'yilib, boshqa manbalarga chalg'imagay, faqat ko'zlangan maqsad sari internetdan foydalanish yoshlarni kamolotga yetaklaydi aksi bo'lsa berilgan vaqt uvol bo'ladi, hayotda bu vaqt uvolining badali to'lnadi. Bunga qator misol va dallilar keltirish mumkin. Yoshlarni virtuallikdan haqiqiy hayotga olib chiqishning bir qancha omillari bor. Avvalo, ijtimoiy tarmoqdan yoshlar

qay payt foydalanishiga diqqat qaratish kerak. Maktab o'quvchilari o'rgimchak to'ri bo'lmish internetdan dars paytida va kechqurun uxlashdan avval ko'proq foydalanishadi. Dars payti o'qituvchisining darsiga quloq solmay turli befoyda vidio va boshqa chalg'ituvchi materiallardan foydalanishadi. Yuqoridagi sanalgan qoidalarga amal qilinsa, o'qish sur'ati sezilarli darajada yuqorilaydi. Ba'zi bir oilalarda farzand 12 yoshga to'lishi bilan pul topish uchun safarbar qilinadi. Bu ayanchli hol odatiy tusga kirganligi hech kimga sir emas. Yoshlar o'z iqtidorini yuksaltirishi uchun sharoit u yoqda tursin, hatto ularni maktabga yubormaslik holatlari uchrab turipti. Aslida bu vaziyat bir kishining emas butun boshli xalq muammosi. Moddiyatga bo'lgan ehtiyoj ilm olishga to'siqlik qilyapti. Tanlovga qatnashmoqchi bo'lgan iste'dod egasi dalalarda mol, qo'y boqib yuripti. Yoshlarni virtuallikdan chiqarish uchun dastlab ularning qiziqish va iqtidoriga mos ravishda sharoit yaratish zarur. Qiziqishlariga qarab kasb va hunarga yo'naltirish ota-onaning vazifasi. Oila, mahalla va maktablarda "Adabiyot kechalari" tashkil qilish lozim. Haftada bir marotaba o'tkaziladigan kecha yakunida g'olib o'quvchilarga kitoblar sovg'a qilish lozim. Bu bilan odamlar kayfiyatiga kayfiyat qo'shiladi, g'oliblik insonlarga o'zgacha zavq bag'ishlaydi. Adabiyot insonni qalbini poklaydi, yaxshi va yomonning farqiga borishni ko'rsatib beradi. Bundan tashqari "Oila, mahalla, maktab" uchrashuvini tashkil qilish kerak. Bu bir loyiha bo'lib, maktab o'quvchisi va bitirib o'qishga kira olmay uyda qolib ketgan yoshlar uchun yaratiladi. Unda turli xil mablag'li yutuqlar joriy qilinadi. Yutuq fondi 5 milliondan kam bo'lmagan miqdorda belgilanadi. Bunday yutuqli tanlov yilda 2 marta o'tkazish uchun belgilangan bo'lib, bunda yoshlar bandligini ta'minlashga doir dastur va nizom ishlab chiqiladi. Bu faqat bir mahalla uchun emas, balki butun bir mamlakatdagi mahallalar uchun mosdir. Ayrim yoshlar ma'lum bir tanlovga qatnashish istagini bildirganda ota-onalari undan naf yo'qligi haqida aytib qiziqishlarini rad qilishadi va iste'dod egasi jismoniy mehnatga jalb qilinadi. Inson tirik ekan moddiyatga ehtiyoj sezadi. Pul mukofoti esa ota-onalar o'z

farzandining tanloviga qarshilik qilmasdan uni qo'llab-quvvatlashi uchun joriy qilinadi. Tanlov yutug'i uchun kitob qo'yiladigan bo'lsa, "Undan nima naf kelardi" deb ayrim insonlar rozi bo'lmasligi mumkin. Bu hammaga ayon hodisa bo'lib qoldi.

Mavjud muammo hozirgi zamonning eng dolzarb muammolaridan biri hisoblanib, yoshlarni ushbu qiyin vaziyatdan chiqarish uchun har bir mas'ul shaxs maksimal darajada harakat qilishi darkor. Yoshlar-kelajagimiz, vatanimiz gullab-yashnashi uchun, erkin va farovon hayot kechirishimiz uchun ularni yaxshi yo'lga yo'naltirish har birimizning qo'limizda. Ularga oq va qorani tanib olishlarida yordam berish zamon talabiga aylandi. Zero, O'zbekiston Respublikasi 1-prezidenti Islom Karimov "Farzandlari sog'lom yurt qudratli bo'lur, qudratli elning farzandlari sog'lom bo'lur" – deya boqiy yashovchi fikrlarni ilgari surgan. Yoshlarning aqliy hamda jismoniy salomatligi yurt uchun o'ta muhimdir. Virtuallashuv esa farzandlarni aqliy tomondan zaiflikka yetaklovchi omildir. Shuni aytib o'tish joizki, farzandlar qanday oilada kamol topmasin, qaysi oilada adabiyotdan zig'ircha bo'lsa ham adabiy muhit yaratilgan bo'lsa, o'sha oiladan nopok farzandlar yetishib chiqmaydi. Chunki adabiyot insonning ichki dunyosini poklaydi. Qalbi pok inson esa hech qachon yomonlikka ergashmaydi va Yaratgan bergan oliy ne'mat-umrni besamar ishlar bilan uvol qilmaydi. Prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoyev O'zbekiston yoshlar forumida so'zlagan nutqida: "Biz yurtimizda qanday islohotlarga qo'l urmaylik, avvalo, siz kabi yoshlarga, sizning kuch-g'ayratingiz va azmu shijoatingizga tayanamiz", - deya fikr aytganlar. Ushbu so'zlar zamirida yoshlarga qaratilgan juda katta ishonch bor. Shunday ekan yoshlar Prezident ishonchini oqlash uchun bor kuchlarini sarflashi shart. Darvoqe, har bir inson dunyoga kelarkan ma'lum bir maqsadni amalga oshirish uchun yuboriladi. Hayotdan zavq olib, umrning har bir daqiqasining qadriga yetaylik. Zero, hayot bizga ikkinchi bor berilmaydi.

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AN OVERVIEW OF SOME THEMATIC GROUPS OF EUPHIMISTIC MEANINGFUL UNITS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola evfemizmlarning turli adabiy asarlarda qo'llanilishining xilma-xilligi va ularning tematik va kontekstual farqlarini ko'rsatib beradi. Shaxsiy xususiyatlar, jismoniy nogironlik, ruhiy kamchiliklar va spirtli ichimliklarga oid evfemizmlar tahlil qilinadi, bu ifodalar qanday qilib jamiyat me'yorlari va madaniy qarashlarni aks ettirgan holda og'zaki nutqda ishlatilishi bayon qilinadi. Abdulla Qodiriy asarlaridan olingan konkret misollar va boshqa adabiy an'analardan taqqoslangan misollar bilan birgalikda, evfemizmlarning nozik mavzularni qanday yoritishi va adabiy hikoyalarni qanday shakllantirishi ko'rsatilib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: evfemizmlar, adabiyot, tematik farqlar, kontekstual farqlar, shaxsiy xususiyatlar, jismoniy nogironlik, ruhiy kamchiliklar, adabiy tahlil

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O'ZBEK TILIDAGI EVFIMISTIK MA'NOLI BIRLIKLARNING AYRIM TEMATIK GURUHLARIGA UMUMIY NUQTAI

Abstract

This article demonstrates the diversity of euphemisms used in various literary works and their thematic and contextual differences. It analyzes euphemisms related to personal characteristics, physical disabilities, mental deficiencies, and alcoholic beverages, explaining how these expressions are used in oral discourse to reflect societal norms and cultural views. Concrete examples from Abdulla Qodiriy's works, along with comparative examples from other literary traditions, illustrate how euphemisms illuminate delicate topics and shape literary narratives.

Keywords: euphemisms, literature, thematic differences, contextual differences, personal characteristics, physical disabilities, mental deficiencies, literary analysis

INTRODUCTION

Euphemisms are expressions used to address sensitive or uncomfortable topics in a more indirect or softened manner. In literature, they help navigate delicate subjects related to personal traits, physical and mental conditions, and societal behaviors. By reflecting societal norms and cultural sensitivities, euphemisms reveal how language evolves to handle various themes delicately. Their use in literary works provides insight into how language adapts to changing social and cultural contexts, enriching the narrative and thematic depth of the text.

MAIN PARTS

Euphemisms, in terms of quantity, are diverse and also varied thematically. In literary works, most euphemisms serve to express human characteristics and behaviors. This is defined by the fact that the main object of literary art is the human being. The topic is illustrated based on examples taken from the following literary works.

Euphemistic tools that convey personal meaning. Just as changes in social life lead to the emergence of new linguistic units, attempts to indirectly express political figures in terms of general ethics and cultural aspects can lead to the creation of new terms or the acquisition of new meanings and functions by existing terms. These tools, when used in political-journalistic or literary styles, reflect the demands of specific historical periods. This can be further confirmed by works created by authors in the context of significant social and political changes.

The term "valine'mat" can be encountered in two different meanings: as a metaphorical euphemism and as a traditional euphemism. Both meanings arise in context and surroundings: For example, "Bas, siz bilan biz ishchi-dehqon

xodimi bo‘la turib, nega “valine’matimizga” oyog‘ xizmatini o‘taymiz” (A. Qod. "Shallaqi"). Here, replacing Stalin's name with this expression might seem like showing respect, but it is more appropriately considered a euphemism based on metaphor. In the following sentence, the term appears in its literal sense, evoking an impression of euphemistic "tone": "Qullaridan biri valine’matimga ikki kalima arzim bor, deydir.” (A. Qod. "Mehrobdan chayon"). The use of “valine’mat” to refer to a specific person shows its euphemistic nature. The term "jannatmakon" is also used euphemistically to refer to Amir Umarxon: "Have you seen the 'jannatmakon'?" (A. Qod. "1819 yil yodgori"). Additionally, the term "katta" (person of authority) is used as a euphemistic tool to broaden the range of political figures: "Here, Rahimberdi Khudoyberdiev, Nuriddin Zokirov, Berkin Azimov, Karim Abdurahmonov, and others, like Vali Usmonov, are the ‘katta’ of the place, and they have continued to create trouble as they pleased." (A. Qod. "Qorqqan oldin musht ko'tarar").

Euphemistic expressions for human body parts. Even if a person’s body parts are expressed euphemistically with softening or delicate terms, they still retain the connotation of being embarrassing or uncomfortable to mention in a direct way, according to human consciousness.

Euphemistic expressions for physical disabilities. Terms such as "hard of hearing" for "deaf," and "one eye in the west, one eye in the east" as a euphemism for visual impairment, are examples of euphemistic phrases. Other euphemistic expressions for physical defects include "diybori nomuborak" (cold eyes) and "vaqtsizroq yaratilgan" (born with a deformity), and the term "husni Yusuf" used to describe physical appearance with a connotation of flaw or imperfection, as in: "Next to him, another 'husni Yusuf' with a goat-like beard hanging down and decorating his right cheek." (A. Qod. "Mehrobdan chayon"). The term "husni Yusuf," which softens the meaning of "ugly" or "unattractive," is used metaphorically to express such ideas.

Euphemistic expressions related to physical conditions include terms related to pregnancy, such as "yuklik" (pregnant), "homilalik" (pregnancy), "og'ir oyoq" (heavy foot), "ikkiqat" (a condition referring to multiple pregnancies), "tumsa" (a term for a woman with reproductive issues), and "qisr" (a term for a woman who cannot conceive or has reproductive issues). In speech, euphemisms like "pushtsiz" (without a belly), "bezurriyot" (without a belly), and "qizil kuyov" (red bridegroom) are used instead of more direct terms. In Abdullah Qadiri's novel *O'tkan Kunlar*, the phrase "mijozim zaif" also serves as a euphemistic expression for a man's physical condition.

Euphemistic expressions for mental deficiencies. Euphemisms related to intellectual and psychological shortcomings include terms such as "aqling oqsaydir," "aqlingiz bir oz yanglishibdir," "boshi bo'sh," "jo'n odam," "po'stak aqlini moy bosgan," "jahli basit," "soddalavh," "esi yarim," "yarim madaniy xalq," and "xom kishi." These expressions are observed in literary works. Additionally, euphemisms like "asabi og'riq" (nervous disorder or madness), "bolalik" (childishness), "botirligi etmas" (cowardice), and "vasiqasi yo'q" (unreliable or without a guardian) are also used in this context.

Euphemistic expressions for alcoholic beverages. Abdullah Qodiriy uses euphemistic expressions for alcoholic drinks through his characters. For example, one of Khomid's associates, Mutal Polvon, uses the term "dori" (medicine) for alcohol; Shirvon Khola uses "zahar" (poison) for alcohol; and Toshpolat uses expressions like "obi surx" (wine), "obirahmat" (alcohol), and "oqsoqol" (alcohol, spirit). In a humorous context, Toshpolat Tajang's expression "qirq gazlik" (forty glasses) also serves as a notable euphemism: "After all, Toshpolat Aka's back also gets some sunlight, and he might host you with his freshly acquired 'qirq gazlik' one day, such is the devil's work!" (A. Qod. "Toshpolat Tajang nima deydi?"). In the "Moscow Letters" article, the term "qizilcha" (a euphemism for "cognac") appears as a euphemistic

expression: "He was making a pilaf before that, passing by 'qizilcha' as if preparing it..." (A. Qod. "Moscow Xatlari").

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, euphemisms serve as a nuanced tool in literature, allowing writers to address sensitive or uncomfortable topics with subtlety and indirectness. Through the works of Abdulla Qodiriy, it is evident how euphemisms can shape and reflect societal attitudes towards personal traits, physical and mental conditions, and social behaviors. By softening the impact of direct language, euphemisms enable a more sensitive exploration of delicate subjects. This study highlights how literary texts use euphemisms to adapt to cultural and historical contexts, enriching the narrative and thematic depth of the works. Ultimately, euphemisms not only enhance literary expression but also offer insights into the evolving nature of language and societal norms.

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**THE WAYS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' INTERCULTURAL
COMPETENCE THROUGH FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN
THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM**

Abstract

This paper explores the concept of intercultural competency in higher education, highlighting its importance in educating students for a globalized world. It addresses the definition of intercultural competence, which includes the capacity to communicate successfully and appropriately with people from many cultures. The article discusses numerous pedagogical tactics and curriculum frameworks that institutions might use to help students improve their intercultural skills. It also investigates the difficulties that educators encounter in creating an inclusive learning environment, as well as the significance of institutional support in encouraging intercultural awareness.

Keywords: intercultural competence, intercultural education, higher education professional collaboration, educational innovation, cultural sensitivity, cross-cultural communication, cultural awareness.

Introduction.

Learning and mastering a foreign language is a lifetime process that provides diverse chances for EFL learners, whose shared objective is to successfully communicate with native speakers. It is not enough to know the language well to interact effectively. Nonetheless, being aware of cultural and disciplinary differences is critical to success in any discipline of language. As higher education institutions try to prepare students for a global workforce, including foreign teaching practices into the curriculum has emerged as a critical strategy for developing intercultural competency. Therefore, higher education should be the institution that teaches students the value of cross-cultural communication to achieve intercultural effectiveness when studying, living, traveling, or working abroad. As the topic of intercultural competence has grown in importance in recent years, the globalization era has needed individuals who possess and apply this skill effectively. Intercultural competence refers to the set of knowledge and

abilities required to successfully communicate with individuals from diverse ethnic, religious, cultural, national, and geographic groups, as well as respect for diversity and a readiness to accept the idea that there are other perspectives on the world.

1. The significance of intercultural competence. Intercultural competence comprises a variety of abilities, including cultural awareness, empathy, flexibility, and successful communication. The communicative approach, which emerged in the 1980s, increased the emphasis of culture in foreign language education. Therefore, in the higher education system, ESL students, especially graduates, need to strengthen their intercultural communication skills so that they can contribute to the development of the relationships of their countries with foreign countries.

2. Ways of avoiding obstacles in a relationship. To begin with, university students need to research the cultures and communication traditions of those with whom they intend to meet, as this will reduce the danger of making basic errors. Secondly, it is essential to establish a clear goal so that everyone understands the nature and aim of the interaction. Thirdly, students need to have background knowledge about the intended culture before socializing with its native speakers. In addition to that, to be interculturally competent, students must understand three fundamental standards:

- The ability to build and sustain good relationships.
- The ability to interact and cooperate with others.
- The ability to communicate.

2. The Foreign Language Teaching Process is a development tool.

Learners must first become familiar with their own culture in comparison with foreign culture. The development of this skill depends on the teacher's pedagogical ability.

- Factual transmission method;
- Cross-cultural contrastive method;

- communicative competence-based teaching
- Intercultural competence perspective;

Psychological and emotional resources include motivation, risk-taking delight, stress management, and ambiguity tolerance. These elements, together with the individual's cultural and racial identification and also their willingness to change, make up the individual's adaptability potential.

3. Different ways for ESL students to enhance their intercultural competence: *Display of interest:* demonstrating your respect and positive appreciation for other people and their cultures.

- ***Orientation to knowledge:*** words people use to describe themselves and their vision of the universe
- ***Empathy*** is behaving in ways that demonstrate you comprehend the world. Interaction management is a technique in which you regulate discussions.
- ***Task role behavior*** includes initiating ideas that encourage problem-solving actions.
- ***Relational role behavior*** involves interpersonal harmony and mediation.
- ***Tolerance for ambiguity:*** The ability to adjust to new conditions with ease. Interaction posture involves responding to others.

4. Best Practices for Using Foreign Language Teaching Processes in Higher Education.

Institutions should examine the following best practices for developing intercultural competency through foreign teaching processes: In addition to this, foreign teaching practices, such as study abroad programs, foreign alliances, and the hiring of diverse teaching staff, give students unique opportunities to interact with different cultures. These experiences can considerably increase students' intercultural ability in diverse ways:

1. *Exposure to diverse perspectives:* Interacting with international faculty and classmates exposes students to a variety of perspectives and cultural practices.

This exposure tests preconceived ideas. It encourages critical reflection on one's own cultural assumptions.

2. Language Acquisition: Learning a foreign language is frequently part of foreign teaching methods. Language is an important component of culture, and learning another language can help pupils grasp cultural nuances and increase their capacity to communicate across cultures.

3. Experiential Learning: Programs that include intensive experiences, including internships or community service in foreign countries, allow students to apply their knowledge in real-world situations. This hands-on approach promotes empathy and adaptability, which are critical components of intercultural competency.

4. Collaborative Learning: Group projects with students from diverse cultural backgrounds encourage teamwork and collaboration. Such interactions assist students in improving their interpersonal skills and navigating cultural variances in group dynamics.

5. Curriculum Integration: Institutions should incorporate intercultural competency training into their curriculum across disciplines. This can be accomplished through courses in global affairs, cultural studies, and language instruction.

6. Collaboration with International Institutions: Forming alliances with universities abroad can promote student exchanges and collaborative research projects. These collaborations strengthen the academic experience while also allowing students to interact with people from different cultures.

Conclusion.

As the world becomes more interconnected, the demand for intercultural competency in the workplace and society as a whole grows. Higher education institutions offer a unique opportunity to develop these critical abilities through international teaching methods. Educators may prepare children for success in a

multicultural environment by accepting diverse perspectives, encouraging experiential learning, and implementing best practices. Finally, fostering intercultural competency improves individual student results while also contributing to a more inclusive and harmonious global community.

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WORDLY
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INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION AND LANGUAGE TEACHING

Abstract

Culturally and linguistically, this thesis is concerned with language in the sphere of intercultural communication and language instruction. It describes the formation of intercultural competence during the process of language acquisition, the role of educators in the formation of this competence, and the need for an understanding of the language 'rules' for communication between people who belong to different cultures. The literature review addresses the following topics: culture and language learning and teaching, the testimonies of English language teachers from international programmes and the impact of globalization on inter-cultural communication.

Keywords

Intercultural communication, language teaching, cultural competence, linguistic differences, language policy, language and culture.

In today's global world, language teaching requires not only mastering grammar and vocabulary but also developing competencies necessary for intercultural communication. Linguistic and cultural differences can lead to misunderstandings and conflicts, which in turn disrupt effective communication.

Intercultural communication is defined as communication between two or more representatives of different cultures through language. Each culture has its own linguistic rules, which dictate how its representatives speak and interact with each other. For example, while direct communication is valued in Western countries, indirect, soft speech is common in Eastern cultures. Language teaching requires not only learning grammatical rules and vocabulary but also learning about culture. Culture is manifested through the values, traditions, and social communication rules expressed in each language. Understanding the relationship between language and culture allows learners to communicate more deeply and effectively in the language.

This section discusses the role of culture in the language teaching process and the approaches that should be applied in this process. Language and culture are closely intertwined; language reflects culture and is shaped by it. Each culture has its unique rules for language use, which reflect cultural values, social norms, and forms of speech. For example:

Pragmatics: Pragmatics reflects cultural behavioral norms in language. This, in turn, means that speech acts (such as greetings, expressing gratitude, and apologizing) are expressed differently in various cultures.

Cultural values: Cultural values are reflected in the structures and communicative styles of each language. For instance, while individualism is an important value in Western culture, collectivism is more recognized in Eastern cultures, and this difference is also expressed through language.

In language teaching, it is necessary to develop not only students' linguistic knowledge but also their intercultural competence. Intercultural competence is the ability to communicate effectively with representatives of different cultures. Developing this competence is an integral part of the language learning process because effective use of a language is not limited to mastering grammar and vocabulary. It is also important to correctly understand cultural contexts and adhere to the communication rules specific to that culture.

Intercultural competence is developed in language teaching through the following methods:

Discussing intercultural phenomena: Creating opportunities for students to learn about the differences in speech acts in different cultures and to study these differences.

Practical tasks in cultural contexts: Introducing students to the situations and speech rules they may encounter in intercultural communication and teaching them how to express speech acts in different cultures through practical assignments.

Failure to consider cultures in language teaching can lead to intercultural barriers. Intercultural barriers are misunderstandings or conflicts that arise due to cultural differences. Such barriers can occur in the following cases:

Semantic differences: Words may have different meanings in different cultures, which can lead to misunderstandings in intercultural communication.

Pragmatic rules: The usual communication methods in various cultures may differ, which can result in misunderstandings during intercultural communication.

In language teaching, it is important to teach the cultural context to overcome such barriers. It is necessary to provide students with an understanding of the cultural differences they will encounter in communication and to develop cultural sensitivity in communication.

Teaching culture in the language learning process can be carried out through the following methods:

Cultural and linguistic comparison: Providing students the opportunity to compare the cultural and linguistic differences between their native language and the language they are learning.

Analysis based on culture: Analyzing the use of language in cultural phenomena or social contexts during lessons, such as studying the expression of politeness or etiquette rules in different cultures.

Interactive games and role-playing: Using games and practical exercises to teach the communication rules of various cultures.

Assessing students' intercultural competence is also an important part of language teaching. Testing and assessment systems should be developed to measure this competence. Student assessment is carried out through the following methods:

Understanding of intercultural phenomena: Students are asked to explain cultural phenomena and how they are reflected in language.

Practical tasks: Teaching students to apply various communication rules in an intercultural environment and assessing their skills in this process.

International language teaching programs (e.g., TESOL, CELTA, DELTA) pay great attention to developing intercultural competence. These programs equip teachers not only with linguistic knowledge but also with skills for teaching cultural differences. These experiences are among the most effective methods for developing skills in intercultural communication.

The role of culture in language teaching is significant. Linguistic knowledge and cultural competencies together help students fully master a language. For successful intercultural communication, it is necessary to correctly understand and teach the cultural context during the language teaching process. Therefore, the teaching of culture should be recognized as a special part of language teaching programs.

In international language teaching programs such as TESOL or CELTA, special attention is given to developing intercultural competence. These programs teach students not only language but also the rules of cultural communication, preparing them for international communication. The programs are aimed at deeply studying the linguistic and cultural aspects of intercultural communication, which helps students to correctly handle cultural differences.

In the process of globalization, the importance of intercultural communication is increasing. The growth of the global economy and international cooperation requires effective communication between representatives of different nations. Therefore, it is necessary to form international cooperation and intercultural communication in the language teaching process. For this purpose, special modules for teaching culture have been introduced in language teaching programs.

The connection between language policy and intercultural communication affects communication between international organizations and states. In the process of multilingualism policy and intergovernmental cooperation, it is

important to consider linguistic differences and cultural barriers. The strength of relations between states depends on the effectiveness of language policy and cultural cooperation.

Language teaching plays an important role in forming intercultural communication. Considering linguistic and cultural factors, students should be taught intercultural competence during the language learning process. If this competence is developed in international language teaching programs, intercultural misunderstandings will decrease, and international cooperation will strengthen.

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Mustaqil tadqiqotchi

**TEMURIYLAR DAVLATINING YEVIROPA DAVLATLARI BILAN
ALOQALARI VA ELCHILIK**

***Annotatsiya:** Mazkur maqolada Amir Temur va uning avlodlari davrida temuriylar davlatining tashqi savdo va elchilik aloqalarini yo'lga qo'yilishi va uning rivojlanishining asosiy sabablari, hamda Buyuk ipak yo'lining temuriylar davlatining chet davlatlar bilan savdo va elchilik aloqalarida tutgan o'rni haqida, temuriylar davlatining Yevropa, Yaqin va O'rta Sharq mamlakatlari hamda Xitoy bilan birdek savdo elchilik aloqalarining yo'lga qo'yilishi temuriylar davlatining naqadar qudratli ekanligi haqida qisqacha ma'lumotlar berilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlari:** Xonbaliq, Shaxali, Nimaopuding, Chen Deven, Chjunguoga, Chjeng Xe, Shachiyeer Aliyi, Siyuan, Sixay, xuandi, Oqrobot*

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**RELATIONS OF THE TIMURID STATE WITH EUROPEAN POWERS
AND EMBASSY**

***Annotation:** this article summarizes the main reasons for the establishment and development of foreign trade and embassy relations of the Timurid state under Amir Temur and his descendants, and the role of the Great Silk Road in trade and embassy relations of the temurid state with foreign countries, how powerful the Timurid state is the establishment of similar trade*

***Keywords:** Honbaliq, Shaxali, Nimaopuding, Chen Deven, Zhunguoga, Zheng He, Shachiyeer Aliyi, Siyuan, Sixay, xuandi, Oqrobot*

XIII asrning o'rtalaridan boshlab Markaziy Osiyoda murakkab siyosiy vaziyat yuzaga keldi. Xususan, Xitoyda tashkil topgan Yuan sulolasining xoqoni Xubilay o'zini Chingizxon taxtining vorisi deb hisoblab, ushbu mintaqa hukmdorlarni o'ziga itoat qilishini talab qiladi. Ammo u o'z talabiga rad javob olgandan so'ng kuch ishlatishga urinib ko'radi. Lekin uning qilgan harbiy harakatlari natija bermadi. Xubilayga qarshi chiqishda O'qtoyning nabirasi Xaydu (1235-1301) faol harakat qiladi. 1294 yilda Xubilay vafotidan so'ng nabirasi Temur Chengzung nomi bilan taxtga o'tirib (1295-1308) buvasining

yo‘lidan boradi. Lekin uning harakatlari zoye ketgan. Natijada Xitoy bilan G‘arb o‘rtasi Buyuk ipak yo‘li orqali bo‘ladigan savdo yo‘llari qiyin bo‘lib qolgan.

XIV asrda bir tomondan Chig‘atoy avlodlari o‘rtasidagi nizolar kuchaysa, ikkinchi tomondan ular bilan Mo‘g‘iliston xonlari o‘rtasidagi ziddiyatlar avj oldi. Buning ustiga, Markaziy Osiyo xalqlari orasida mo‘g‘ul hukmdorlariga qarshi harakatlar boshlanib ketadi. Xitoyda ham mo‘g‘ullar mahalliy xalq qarshiligiga uchradi. 1368 yilda yuzaga kelgan qulay vaziyatdan foydalangan Xitoy amaldorlari va er egalari Yuan sulolasini ag‘darib, Min deb ataladigan xonlikni (1368-1644) tashkil qildilar. Mazkur voqealar Buyuk ipak yo‘lidagi osoyishtalikni buzib, Turkiston orqali amalga oshiriladigan xalqaro savdo aloqalarni nihoyatda susaytirib qo‘ydi. Shu bois Buyuk ipak yo‘lining ahamiyati keskin pasayib ketdi.

1370 yilda Movaraunnahrda Samarqand shahrini markaz qilgan sohibqiron Amir Temur (1336- 1405) davlati tashkil topdi. 35 yilga yaqin davr ichida mazkur davlat doirasi nihoyatda katta hududni o‘z nazorati ostiga olganligi hamda Buyuk ipak yo‘lining xavfsizligi ta‘minlanganligi natijasida bu yo‘lda xalqaro savdo aloqalarining qaytadan rivojlanishiga zamin yaratildi. Amir Temurning o‘zi ham bu yo‘lining rivojlanishiga katta e‘tibor berdi. U nafaqat o‘z davlati doirasidagi ichki savdo ishlarini, balki xalqaro savdo aloqalarini rivojlantirish mamlakatning iqtisodiy rivojlanishi uchun zarur ekanini yaxshi anglagan edi. Shu bois u hokimiyatga kelgan zahoti ichki va tashqi savdo ishlariga katta e‘tibor bera boshladi. Avvalo, karvon yo‘lining xavfsizligini ta‘minlab, ularda karvonsaroylar barpo etish ishlariga alohida e‘tibor berdi.

Amir Temurning Xitoy xoqoni Taytszuga yo‘llagan maktubida ”Karvonsaroylararo yo‘llar ochildi, yo‘llardagi qaroqchilar yo‘q qilindi, uzoq yurtlarga boruvchilar o‘zlarini xotirjam his etadigan bo‘ldi”, deb ta‘kidlab o‘tilgan. Shu bilan birga Amir Temur Vizantiya, Venetsiya, Ispaniya, Fransiya, Angliya kabi Yevropa mamlakatlari bilan iqtisodiy aloqalar o‘rnatdi.

Xitoy olimlarining tadqiqotlariga ko'ra, Amir Temur Min xonligining poytaxti Pekin (Xonbaliq) shahriga 8 marta elchilar yuborib, Xitoy bilan diplomatik va savdo aloqalarini rivojlantirgan. Chunonchi, 1387 va 1389 yillari kuzda Mavlono Hofiziy, 1388 yilda Toj ad-Din (Tamuding), 1391 yilda Shoxalil (Shaxali), 1392 yilda Nig'mat ad-Din (Nimaopuding), 1394 va 1395 yillarda Darvish (Dielibeyshi), 1396 yilda Alomat ad-Din (Alamadan) boshchiligida Pekinga Amir Temur nomidan elchilar kelgan. Mazkur elchilar orqali sohibqiron Xitoy xoniga ot, tuya va boshqa narsalar yuborgan. Xitoy xoni esa bular evaziga kumush pul, ipak matolar qaytargan. 1396 yil Amir Temur Alomat ad-Din orqali Xitoy xoniga maktub ham yo'llab, uning yuborgan narsalaridan mamnun bo'lganligini ta'kidlagan. Shu davrda Samarqanddan Pekinga 6 oyda etib borilgan. Kuzda yo'lga chiqqan karvon keyingi yil bahorning oxirida yoki yozning boshida manzilga etib olgan.

Amir Temur vafotidan keyingi 100 yilga yaqin davr davomida Turkistondan Xitoyga 107 marta, shu jumladan 1415-1440 yillari Ulug'bek Mirzo nomidan 22 marta elchilar guruhi kelgan.

Xitoy manbalaridan ma'lum bo'lishicha, o'sha zamonda Xitoyning boshqa shaharlariga ham samarqandlik savdogarlar kelib, bozorlarda ot sotishgan. Chunonchi, 1390 yilda erta bahorda Samarqandlik Sho Jo'raali (Shachiyeer Aliyi) Lyangchjou shahrida 670 ta ot sotgan. Mahalliy hokim bu haqda Taytszuga hisobot berib, mazkur savdogarni Pekinga yuborishni so'ragan.

Samarqanddan Xitoyga yuborilgan elchilar bilan birgalikda katta savdogarlar guruhlari ham qo'shilib borgan. Taytszuning Amir Temurga yo'llagan bir maktubida bayon etilishicha, ayrim Samarqandlik savdogarlar Xitoyga kelganidan so'ng vataniga qaytmasdan savdo ishlari bilan shug'ullangan va ayrimlari uy-joy sotib olib bola-chaqali bo'lib qolgan. Min sulolasi qo'shinlari Xitoyning Shimoliyolida yashayotgan tatarlarga qarshi yurishi chog'ida asirga tushib qolganlar orasida bir necha yuz nafar samarqandlik savdogarlar bo'lganligi aniqlangan. Ushbu misollar Amir Temur savdogarlari faqatgina

Xitoy hududida emas, balki uning Shimoliyolidagi yaylovlarda ham savdo ishlari bilan shug'ullanganligidan dalolat beradi.

Min sulolasi ham Samarqandga bir necha marta elchilar va savdogarlar yuborgan. Masalan, 1395 yilda Samarqandga Pekindan Bo An boshchiligida 1500 kishidan iborat bo'lgan elchi va savdogarlar guruhi, 1397 yilda Chen Deven boshchiligidagi Xitoy elchilari va savdogarlar kelgan.

Keltirilgan ma'lumotlardan ko'rinib turibdiki, Amir Temur davrida anchadan beri to'xtab qolgan Turkiston – Xitoy diplomatik va savdo aloqalari tiklanib, Buyuk ipak yo'li qayta ochiladi. Ammo tomonlarning amalga oshirilgan aloqalari ko'z qarashlari bir xil bo'lmaganligi tufayli Amir Temur davlati bilan Min xonligi o'rtasida yangi g'oyaviy muammo paydo bo'lgan.

Ma'lumki, Xitoy hukmdorlarining an'anaviy tushunchalariga ko'ra, xaqon "xuandi" (imperator) deb atalib, u tangrining kurrai zaminidagi o'g'loni ("tyanzi") hisoblangan. Unga barcha mamlakatlar va xonlar itoatkor bo'lishi lozim edi. Shu bois Amir Temur elchilari Min sulolasi tomonidan "gungshi", ular olib borgan sovg'alar esa "gungfu", ya'ni fuqarolar hukmdorga to'laydigan soliq, deb qabul qilindi. Shu joyda izoh berib o'tmoq lozimki, Xitoy tili lo'g'atlarida, jumladan "Xitoy tili yozuvi lo'g'ati»da sharhlanishicha "gung" deb qadimda Tangri farzandiga (Tyanzi), ya'ni imperatorga uning itoatida bo'lganlar tomonidan taqdim etiladigan narsalar va dehqonlar tomonidan hosillarning hukumatga topshiradigan qismi aytilgan. "So'zlar dengizi" ("Sixay") va "So'zlarning kelib chiqishi" ("Siyuan") lo'g'atida yozilishicha, "gunfu" so'zi hukmdor tomonidan fuqarolar zimmasiga ortilgan soliq nomi hisoblanadi[4].

Xitoy imperatorlari o'zlarini er yuzining egasi deb hisoblashlari an'anasining ta'siri Xitoy olimlari asarlarida ham o'z aksini topgan. Masalan, Vang Chjilay o'z asarida "Atrofga qilgan harbiy yurishlar g'alaba bilan yakunlangandan so'ng, Temur kuchayib ketdi. Shundan keyin u Min sulolasiga itoat qilishdan va Xitoyga (Chjunguoga) soliq to'lashdan (gunfu) bosh tordi, shu bilan birga Xitoy

elchilarini olib olib qolib, qaytishga ruxsat bermadi”, deb aytadi. Ikkinchi bir joyda tarixchi yozadi: ”Yuqorida aytib o‘tilganidek, Temur ko‘p marta Min saroyiga soliq to‘lovchi elchilar (gunshi) yubordi. Ularning ayrimlari soliq olib kelish va savdo qilish bilan cheklandi, ayrimlari [Xitoydagi] vaziyatni o‘rganish va ma‘lumot to‘plash bilan shug‘ullandi”.

Amir Temurdan Xitoyga birinchi marta (1387 yilda) elchi bo‘lib Mavlono Hofiz kelganda, Tayzu mazkur tushuncha asosida uning yuborgan sovg‘alarini o‘ziga bo‘lgan tobelik belgisi deb qabul qildi. Uning bunday munosabati Amir Temurdan keyingi yillarda yuborilgan elchilarga va sovg‘alarga nisbatan ham saqlanib qolgan. Xitoy xoqoni o‘zining Amir Temurga javoban berib yuborgan sovg‘alarini esa, uning ”tobeligini qabul qilganligi” uchun ko‘rsatilgan xizmat belgisi deb hisoblanadi. Shu asosda Tayzu Amir Temurga yo‘llagan maktubida uni Xitoy xoniga itoatkor xon sifatida ifodalagan. Xitoy xoni sohibqironning mavqei Bilan hisoblashmagan uning maktubi Bilan tanishgandan so‘ng, Amir Temur qattiq ranjib, Samarqandga 1395 va 1397 yillarda kelgan Bo An, Chin Deven boshchiligidagi Xitoy elchilarini ushlab qolgan. Ular vataniga Amir Temur vafotidan keyin qaytganlar. Elchilarni Samarqandda ushlab qolishning bundan tashqari yana ikki sababi bo‘lgan. Bularning birinchisi, Bo An 1500 kishi hamrohligida Hirotga bormoqchi bo‘lganligi Amir Temurda shubha uyg‘otganligida, ikkinchisi Min xoqoni 100 ming musulmonni qatl etish to‘g‘risida farmon bergan, degan xabarning Amir Temurga etib kelganligidadir. Xitoyda qatl etilgan musulmonlarning 100 ming bo‘lmasligi ehtimoldan holi emas, ammo mo‘g‘ullar hukmronligi davrida Turkistonlik musulmonlarning jamiyatdagi mavqei baland bo‘lganligi va ular vakillarining yuqori darajali davlat xizmatiga jalb etilganligi uchun, Min sulolasi ularning ko‘p qismini jazolaganligi tarixiy haqiqatdir[.

Aslida esa, Amir Temur Xitoy xoniga elchilar orqali sovg‘alar jo‘natib, evaziga Xitoy mollarini olib kelinishi orqali ikki davlat o‘rtasidagi teng huquqli savdo aloqalarining tiklanishi ko‘zda tutgan edi. Bu haqda mahalliy manbalarda ko‘p

ma'lumotlar uchraydi. Afsuski, Markaziy Osiyo manbalari bilan Xitoy manbalarini solishtirish asosida ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lgan ayrim tarixchilar, jumladan Xitoy tarixchilari Amir Temurning bu istagini to'g'ri bayon etolmaganlar. Ular Xitoy xonlari yorlig'i va saroy tarixchilari tomonidan bitilgan manbyualardagi amaliyotga zid ko'rsatmalarni «haqiqat» deb qabul qilganlar.

Buning ustiga turkistonlik savdogarlarga Xitoyda erkin savdo qilishga yo'l qo'yilmaganligi va turonlik musulmonlarning qatl etilishi Amir Temurning g'azabini keltirgan. Mavjud adabiyotlarda, jumladan Xitoy tarixchilarining asarlarida zikr etilishicha, Min sulolasi xonining munosabatidan ranjigan Amir Temur unga qarshi harbiy yurish qilmoqchi bo'lgan, bundan xabar topgan Min sulolasi esa tashvishga tushib, urushga tayyorgarlik ko'ra boshlagan. Ammo Amir Temurning 1405 yilda O'tror shahrida olamdan o'tishi bilan uning istagi amalga oshmay qolgan[7].

Mazkur tarixiy voqealardan ko'rinib turibdiki, Turkiston bilan Xitoy o'rtasidagi xalqaro munosabatlarning asos va huquqlarini tushunishga xamda savdo aloqalarini muntazam ravishta rivojlanishiga Amir Temur Bilan Xitoy xonlari o'srtasidagi munosabatda nomutanosiblik yo'l bermagan.

Amir Temur avlodlari ham Buyuk ipak yo'lini rivojlantirish maqsadida jiddiy harakatlar qilganlar. Ular Xitoy bilan tinchlik bitimlarini ham tuzishgan. Masalan, 1388-1500 yillar davomida Toshkent, Samarqand, Xuroson, SHeroz, Hirot, Isfaxon kabi shaharlardan 120 dan ortiq elchi guruhlari Xitoyga borgan. Ularning ko'pchiligi o'rta hisobda 8-10 kishidan iborat bo'lgan. Ayrim elchilar guruhiga 200 kishi atrofida savdogarlar qo'shilib borgan. Savdogarlar Xitoyga ot, tuya, eshak kabi chorva mollari, qimmatbaxo toshlar va ulardanyasalgan buyumlar, dorivorlar va xar xil maxalliy xunarmandchilik mahsulotlarini olib borishgan. Xitoydan esa, asosan, ipak mato, chinni idishlar, choy, ravoch va dorivorlar olib kelingan.

Manbalarda ko'rsatilishicha, shu zamonda Min sulolasi Xitoydan olib kelinadigan mollar ko'lamini cheklab qo'ygan. Ayrim maxsulotlarni, jumladan metallardan yasalgan qurollarni maxsus ruxsatsiz Xitoydan olib ketish man etilgan.

Amir Temur 1389 yilda Mo'g'uliston bo'ysundirib, Movarounnahrda Mo'g'uliston tomonidan bo'ladigan xavfni bartaraf qilgach, Mo'g'uliston va Sharqiy Turkiston orqali o'tuvchi karvon yo'li xavfsizligini ta'minlash, Xitoy bilan savdo-elchilik aloqalarini tiklash imkoniyati paydo bo'ldi. Xususan, 1389–1398 yillarda Amir Temur nomidan Xitoyga 9 marta elchilar borganligi, Xitoydan ham 1395 yilda Fu An boshchiligida Samarqandga elchilar yuborilganligi ikki mamlakat o'rtasidagi aloqalar davom etganini ko'rsatadi.

Shohrux Mirzo hukmronligi davrida ham Xitoy bilan aloqalar davom etdi. Bu davr yozma manbalarida 1409 va 1420 yillarda Hirotga Xitoy elchilari kelganligi, o'z navbatida, temuriy hukmdorlar ham Xitoyga bir necha marta o'z elchilarini yuborganliklari ma'lum. O'rta Osiyoni Xitoy bilan bog'lovchi Buyuk ipak yo'lining muhim tarmog'i bo'lgan savdo yo'llari, asosan, Movarounnahrning markazidan Farg'ona va Yettisuv orqali Sharqiy Turkistonga, bu erdagi savdo shaharlari orqali Xitoy poytaxti Pekinga olib borgan. Bu muhim savdo yo'li yo'nalishlari 1419-1422 yillarda Shohrux Mirzoning Shodixo'ja boshchiligida Xitoyga yuborgan elchilik missiyasi a'zosi G'iyosiddin Naqqosh yozib qoldirgan kundaliqda batafsil ta'riflangan[8]. Bu asarda keltirilgan ma'lumotlarga ko'ra elchilar Hirotni O'rta Osiyo orqali Xitoy bilan bog'lovchi karvon yo'li quyidagi yo'nalishda harakat qilganlar: Hirot – Balx – Kelif kechuvi – Samarqand – Sayram - Ashpara (bu shahar qo'rg'oni Amir Temur tomonidan barpo etilgan) – Mo'g'ul eli (Bilg'utu – Qo'ng'ir suvi – Yulduz yaylovi) – Turfon – Qoraxoja – Sufi Ato qishlog'i – Qumul – Qorovul – Sukju – Qamju – Pinlon – Xonbaliq (Pekin)[9].

O'rtta Osiyoni Xitoy bilan bog'lovchi yo'llar ichida Shosh vohasi ham muhim o'rin tutib, Shoshdan Turfongacha bo'lgan masofani karvonlar 3 oyda bosib o'tishgan.

Amir Temur va temuriylar davrida Yevropa mamlakatlari – Fransiya, Angliya, Ispaniya va boshqa mamlakatlar bilan ham diplomatik aloqalar o'rnatilganligi ma'lum. Bu aloqalar Xususan, O'rtta Yer dengizidan Iroq – Eron – Xuroson orqali 1402-1404 yillarda Samarqandga tashrif buyurgan Ispan elchisi Rui Gansalis de Klavixoning yuqorida keltirilgan rasmiy tashrifi yo'nalishiga nazar tashlab, Xurosondan Termiz – Darband – Temir Darvoza – Oqrobot – Kesh orqali Samarqandga kelgan savdo yo'llari faoliyati haqida ma'lumot olish mumkin.

O'zbekiston F.A Sharqshunoslik instituti xodimi Maxmud Qutluqovning Xitoy, arab, forsiy va boshqa manbalarni solishtirish asosida chiqargan xulosasiga ko'ra, ipak yo'kida o'z mavqeini o'stirish uchun Xitoy xoqonlari ko'p marta g'arb tomonga xarbiy yurishlar qilgan. Ammo ularning hammasi natijasiz tugaganligi tufayli Qumul uchun bo'lgan kurash jiddiy tus olgan. Ushbu shahar yuz yildan ortiq davr davomida gox Xitoy, gox mug'ul xukmdorlari qo'liga o'tib turgan. Albatta, bu kurashlar Buyuk ipak yo'lidagi savdo munosabatlariga salbiy tasir ko'rsatgan[10].

Xalqaro savdo aloqalarga bo'lgan ehtiyoj va Buyuk ipak yo'lidagi siyosiy vaziyatdan kelib chiqib, Min sulolasi dengiz yo'li orqali xarakat qilishga jiddiy urinadi. Dengiz yo'lini Xitoy uchun ochish vazifasini Maxmud (Chjeng Xe)ga topshiradi. Maxmud esa mo'g'illar davrida Xitoyga borib qolgan O'zbekistonliklar avlodiga mansub bo'lgan (Bu haqta quyida batafsilroq boyon etiladi).

Shundan ko'rinib turibdiki, Xitoy bilan G'arb o'rtasidagi savdo aloqalari dengiz yo'llari orqali rivojlaniushiga Buyuk ipak yo'lidagi siyosiy vaziyat turtki bo'lgan. Dengiz yo'lining rivojlanishi, albatta ushbu davrda jahon miqyosida kemasozlikning rivojlanishi bilan ham bog'liq edi. O'z navbatida, dengiz yo'li

orqali xalqaro savdo aloqalarining rivojlanishi Buyuuk ipak yo'li axamiyatining pasayishiga olib keldi.

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**THE NOTION OF CONCEPTUALIZATION, CONCEPTUAL
STRUCTURES AND CONCEPTUAL SYSTEMS**

Annotation: *in this article all general information and types of the concept in Cognitive Linguistics is given. It is considered to be one of the main notions of Cognitive Linguistics, Linguoculturology, Linguoconceptology and other linguistic disciplines of the anthropocentric paradigm.*

Key words: *“concept”, the main notion, Cognitive Linguistics, Linguoculturology, Linguoconceptology, the anthropocentric paradigm, the most controversial issues, types of the concept.*

Cognitive Linguistics viz. Cognitive Semantics is primarily concerned with investigating the process of conceptualization and categorization. Conceptualization is the fundamental semantic phenomenon. In Langacker’s words, semantics is conceptualization, which is aimed at semantic interpretations of linguistic units. It means that linguistic units reflect the nature and organization of the conceptual systems. The conceptual system is understood as regulated structural combination of concepts in the human mind. From this perspective language can be regarded as a tool for investigating the conceptual system.

The process of conceptualization is based on the assumption that meaning is encyclopedic in nature, it depends on encyclopedic knowledge. Encyclopedic knowledge, in its turn, is a structured system of knowledge, organized as a network.

So, conceptualization is a dynamic mental process of concept formation, of human cognitive activity connected with composing knowledge structures on the basis of the linguistic data and encyclopedic information. A vivid example of the word “banana” is given by V. Evans and M. Green (1988). The word involves a complex network of knowledge concerning a) the shape, colour,

smell, texture and taste of the fruit; b) whether we like or hate bananas; c) how and where bananas are grown and harvested; d) details relating to funny situations with banana skins, etc. Another example is “book”. Cognitive interpretation of this word is aimed to uncover its conceptual structure. On the ground of human experiences and encyclopedic knowledge the following parameters of BOOK can be outlined:

- edition (place, year, publishing house);
- author;
- functional style and genre;
- design (size, format, colour, illustrations);
- quality and price;
- cover (hard/soft).

So, a complex conceptual structure of the analyzed word is constructed in the process of conceptualization and categorization of the information evoked from human experiences and encyclopedic knowledge.

The encyclopedic approach to meanings denotes that linguistic units are seen as relating to thoughts, ideas, world knowledge. It should be stressed that each act of conceptualization draws upon the strategies that relate to mechanisms of inferences, making conclusions, decoding implicit information. The notion of inference is considerably important for Cognitive Linguistics. It means interpreting implications and making conclusions drawn from the cognitive processing and conceptualization of the linguistic data. The cognitive interpretation of linguistic units makes it possible to get new information, exert additional conceptual senses and draw some conclusions about the conceptual system. Inference is aimed at decoding implicit information, removing ambiguity and getting new information. In this view, indirect speech acts are understood only on the basis of the mechanisms of inference. For example, in the frame of a class-room the teacher’s remark “The blackboard is dirty.” has

inferences of reproach such as “Why didn’t you clean the blackboard?” and order “Clean the blackboard”.

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BANKLARNING AKTIVLARI TO'G'RISIDA SOLISHTIRMA

MA'LUMOT TAHLILI

Abstract: Bank assets are one of the main indicators of the bank. Because the sources of the bank's income are assets. The total assets of commercial banks increased by 30.2% during the year and reached 35.7 trillion as of January 1, 2022. amounted to soums. More than half of the assets belong to the 3 largest banks. TIF National Bank accounted for 27.5 percent, Sanoatkurilishbank for 14.6 percent, and Asaka Bank for 12.4 percent. The fact that a large part of the assets belongs to a small number of banks is a negative situation, because it increases the risk of the banking system.

Keywords: Bank assets, one of the main indicators of the bank, monetary policy of the central bank.

Introduction: Scientific and practical results expected from the research In order to ensure the implementation of this task, the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the regulation of June 13, 2015 "On the classification of asset quality in commercial banks and the formation of reserves to cover potential losses on assets and the procedure for their use" 14/5 was adopted. At the same time, according to the introduced changes, a number of innovations were introduced regarding the classification of the quality of commercial banks' assets. For example, according to the old rules, loans with a payment term of up to 30 days were classified as "standard", loans with a payment term of up to 90 days were classified as "substandard", and loans with a payment delay of more than 180 days were classified as "bad". according to the new regulation, all loans that have not been paid within the term of the contract and are delayed by 180 days in terms of principal and interest according to the schedule are classified as "bad".

In addition, assets in litigation, assets whose payment period has been extended due to the debtor's poor financial condition and inability to pay, and

assets that are not used in banking activities, acquired to cover problem loans, assets that have not been sold within three months from the date of their receipt on the bank's balance sheet are also "bad".

Comparative information on the reserve established for bank assets

The main part of reserves organized by assets is contributed by three large commercial banks. In particular, TIF National Bank accounted for 35.87 percent, Sanoatkurilishbank for 28.87 percent, and Asaka Bank for 13.22 percent. The total reserve amount has slightly increased compared to last year. This is a negative situation and requires taking measures. If we look at existing problem loans in agriculture, Kashkadarya region takes the main place in terms of problem loans among the regions. Its total share is 22 percent.

Conclusion: In short, the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan has formed the practice of regulating the activities of commercial banks by means of monetary instruments.

The main reason for this is the poor cotton and grain harvest in the region this year due to unfavorable weather. Surkhandarya, Namangan, Jizzakh (11 percent), Syrdaryo (10 percent), and Tashkent region (9 percent) took the next places. It was 2 percent in Andijan and Samarkand, and 1 percent in Navoi region. In the city of Tashkent, it is 0 percent, because loans are not given to agricultural enterprises here.

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**ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF THE CENTRAL BANK
OF JIZZAK REGION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

Abstract: *The management of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan classified the formation and use of reserves organized by commercial banks and their branches to classify the quality of assets, to compensate for possible losses on loans.*

Key words: *Loan portfolio, provided security, level coverage, economic turnover, Financially stable.*

The evaluation of the loan in this quality indicates that there is no doubt about the client's assets and their condition. It is financially stable, the business turnover is provided with a high level of equity capital, it has high profitability indicators, the turnover period of debtor and creditor debts is short and so on. These loan holders are a financially stable business entity that has a high level of security. In this case, the main attention should be focused on the relationship with the obligations of the previous activity of the borrower, reliable credit provision consisting of easily realizable assets and highly liquid funds. In this category of loans, there are no signs of non-repayment, the possibility of losses for banks is minimal, the quality of the loan collateral (collateral, guarantee, etc.) and high weight of highly liquid funds is taken into account. The loan can be considered secured only if the security received under the loan (collateral, property, etc.) is sufficient to pay the loan amount and interest rates on it.

All loan documents must be documented by law and the bank must be able to recover the bad loan (although the probability of the loan not being returned is limited). In this group of loans, the activity of the client depends on two main factors, namely:

- the attitude of the client to his previous activities and his obligations;

Particular attention is paid to the presence of clear security for the loan (collateral, guarantee, property, etc.) and its correct formalization.

Standard loans. On such loans, there is a situation of not being able to repay the loan on time. However, in case of failure to repay the loan within the specified period, the extension of the loan repayment period should be only once. The financial situation of customers whose loan is considered to be standard is usually stable, but due to certain temporary reasons, a negative financial situation may have arisen in his activity. Such loans may include loans that are not properly formalized, loans that are not properly documented as collateral, or loans with insufficient documentation. A reserve of around 10 percent is necessary for these loans.

Substandard loans. Loans belonging to this group have clear signs that their quality is not sufficient. This mainly indicates the need to find additional sources for debt repayment as a result of the existence of certain shortcomings in the repayment of loans to the bank and the fact that the initial sources accepted as loan security are not sufficient to repay the loan. Substandard loans are not secured by the borrower's sound financial condition and high level of solvency. It is characterized by the fact that the sources of securing the loan are associated with certain risks, there is insufficient information on the current state of the loan, and there are certain deficiencies in the collateral documents. These loans arise in cases where the financial situation is not stable, and there are deficiencies in the solvency of the enterprise. For substandard loans, 25 percent of the loans may be considered non-performing and a 25 percent provision may be established to cover the defaults on these loans.

Doubtful loans. These loans include all the negative aspects of loans in the above groups, as well as unsecured loans with a low probability of repayment. A reserve of up to 50% should be established for loans belonging to this group.

Unsecured loans. There is almost no chance of repayment of these loans. These assets have a very low value, and it is not appropriate to take them into

account as assets. Therefore, banks can consider these loans as losses on their balance sheets. Unsecured loans can be taken off the balance sheet at the expense of profit, and in cases where it is not profitable, at the expense of bank investment. For the bank, these loans are classified as losses. In addition, assets that have been inactive for a year or more, overdue and interest-bearing debts can also be characterized as losses. Therefore, it is necessary to organize 100 percent reserve for loans belonging to this group.

In paragraph 32 of Annex 1 of the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ1438 dated November 26, 2010, introducing a clear mechanism for the implementation of a deep factor analysis in the management of bank risks, improving the monitoring of the quality of bank assets, taking into account the formation of reserves and the diversification of the credit portfolio. It is also decided to take warning measures to prevent the emergence of problematic debts.

Analysis of the stages of development of the Central Bank in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the main administration of Jizzakh region and international relations

At the stage of modernization of the economy, the banking system plays a big role in our country. One of the important directions of the reform of the banking system is aimed at ensuring the transparency of commercial banks. One of the main pillars on which the economy of any country rests is a stable banking system. We made the following conclusions on the topic:

It is necessary to increase the level of capitalization of commercial banks of our republic.

In a number of banks of our republic, the growth rate of capital is lower than the growth rate of risky assets. Solving this problem is carried out by reducing the weight of high-risk assets in the structure of bank assets and stabilizing the growth rate of capital.

The additional capital base of commercial banks of our republic is weak, i.e., first of all, there are no subordinated debt obligations in the additional capital of commercial banks. However, in the banking practice of developed foreign countries, such debt obligations are the main component of additional capital.

The third component of the bank's additional capital is financial investments directed to credit institutions established under the bank. Such institutions include leasing companies, trusts, and factoring companies that are established under banks and do not have an independent balance sheet. Commercial banks of our republic do not have this article of capital.

Therefore, there are real opportunities to increase the gross capital of commercial banks by increasing the amount of additional capital. The main part of the current economic norms is defined in relation to the first-tier capital, i.e. the main capital of the bank.

It is necessary to increase the securities operations of the commercial banks of our country, in particular, the secondary securities market and its activities. Because securities are high-yielding assets. In foreign practice, income from securities is second only to income from loan operations. Government securities are low-risk and reliable, and the income is guaranteed.

Conclusion: Increasing the required reserve ratio reduces the lending capacity of commercial banks. Especially in conditions of high inflation, reserve allocations lose their real value. Non-payment of interest on mandatory reserve allocations by the Central Bank deepens the tendency of their value to decrease. Therefore, in our opinion, the Central Bank should pay interest on the mandatory reserve amounts.

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**COMPOSITION OF LIQUID ASSETS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS
PROFIT PROCESSING METHODS**

Abstract: *In assessing the liquidity of commercial banks, it is necessary to improve the analysis of cash flows and stable liabilities. The main shortcoming in the analysis of cash flows is the complexity of forecasting the actual repayment periods of assets and liabilities. This problem also exists in a number of foreign banks, and some of them have given up taking into account the maturity of assets and liabilities. Instead, management of bank liquidity based on analysis of liquidity of assets and stability of liabilities was introduced.*

Key words: *auction income of commercial banks, liquid assets, income-generating composition, DQMOs.*

In order to increase the weight of the income-generating assets of the commercial banks' liquid assets, the Central Bank can increase the interest of banks in purchasing DQMOs through its REPO operations. Because the auction profitability of DQMOs is observed to decrease in later times.

We propose to analyze the assets according to their level of liquidity, and the liabilities according to the level of stability, recognizing the existing deficiency of the management method abandoned by these banks.

The calculation of the period of recovery of assets and liabilities does not always reflect the actual situation. For example, the repayment term of debt obligations, including DQMOs, is taken into account only indirectly, that is, it is taken into account through the increase in their value at the time of repayment. And for shares, there is no redemption period at all. In practice, there are many cases of early withdrawal of people's deposits. Transaction deposits cannot be separated by term.

A certain part of transaction deposits can be considered as stable liabilities. Although a certain part of the deposits are placed for a short period, they can become a long-term liability as a result of their continuous extension.

In this case, instant liquidity means the ability of the bank to make timely and complete current calculations of its customers. Current liquidity management includes assessing the level of daily payments, planning the necessary reserves of funds and ensuring their daily compliance.

Cash in cash, debit balances of "Nostro" representative accounts, funds in the collection process and one-day interbank loans should be included in cash assets.

Current assets include assets that can be converted into cash assets in a short period of time.

It should be noted that the analysis of liquidity should be carried out separately for each main currency type. Currently, the main currencies of the major banks of our republic are soums and US dollars. In order to facilitate the calculations in the analysis process, it is necessary to obtain the dollar equivalent of all currencies except the soum. Thus, the analysis is performed only in two currencies.

In order to forecast liquidity, only a certain part of the balance sheet value of the assets is taken. This situation is explained in such a way that any asset that is not included in the group of cash assets can change its market price and, of course, its accounting value to one degree or another. A factor that has a strong influence on the market value of assets is the change in the economic situation. In international banking practice, the concept of asset liquidity ratio is introduced in order to take into account the change in the market value of assets. This ratio shows the extent to which the asset can be converted into cash.

The influence of the market situation on the liquidity ratio is manifested in the form of constant changes in asset prices in financial markets. This situation is especially evident in the stock market.

Accounting for loans is of great importance in the formation of estimated assets. In this case, loans granted to trade organizations for a period of 3-4 months can be included in the composition of direct assets. It is not appropriate

to include loans granted for the purpose of financing investment projects as assets.

Also, the loans granted to the client, who have been receiving continuous credit for several years, are reflected in the report in the form of short-term loans. For this reason, loans granted by opening a credit line should be evaluated as long-term loans and should not be included in the current assets.

When analyzing bank liabilities, first of all, it is necessary to divide them into one type of groups. Also, they should be divided into stable and unstable passives.

Stable liabilities include liabilities with a minimal probability of recovery. Non-permanent liabilities consist of liabilities that can be demanded by customers at once.

The level of stability of passives can be estimated through the stability coefficient. This coefficient is determined by subtracting the output coefficient from the number 1. In this case, the output coefficient shows the weight by which the passive amount can be reduced.

The amount of the coefficient of stability differs significantly according to the types of liabilities.

A number of factors affect the stability coefficient. The main of them is the economic situation and the market situation.

A deterioration in the overall economic and political situation usually results in a significant reallocation of client funds. This significantly affects the stability of passives. This situation primarily concerns savings of the population, funds of banks and unstable balances of current account numbers of legal entities.

An overview of the results obtained from the analysis

In order to create the necessary conditions for expanding the scope of credit operations of commercial banks, it is first necessary to change the methodology of calculating the current liquidity ratio of the Central Bank. In the current

methodology, the current liquidity ratio is determined by dividing liquid assets by the sum of transaction deposits and mandatory payments of the bank. Due to the large amount of mandatory payments and transaction deposits in commercial banks, large amounts of funds are accumulating in the "Nostro" representative accounts of banks. In our opinion, transaction deposits should be left in the methodology, the amount of mandatory payments should be excluded from the methodology. Because mandatory payments can be made by improving the process of managing assets and liabilities, without keeping excess funds. For example, as of January 1, 2013, transaction deposits accounted for 54.8% of the total deposits of commercial banks of our republic. This means that it is 27.8 points higher than the norm accepted in international banking practice.

It is necessary to ensure a moderate and stable level of interest income in the volume of gross income of commercial banks of our republic.

It is necessary to use the system of indicators used in international banking practice to determine the moderate level of interest income. These indicators include:

- a) interest income in the volume of gross income of a commercial bank its weight should not be less than 70 percent;
- b) interest income from loans, bank interest income the weight of the total volume should not be less than 60 percent.

When assessing the moderate level of the bank's interest income in the volume of gross income, it is necessary to form a clear and reasonable composition of interest income. According to the recommendation of the World Bank experts, three types of income should be included in the interest income of commercial banks;

- a) interest received from loans;
- b) interest received from securities with a fixed rate;
- c) received on securities purchase and sale accounts revenues.

In order to increase the competitiveness of commercial banks of our republic, it is necessary to solve the problem of debtor-creditor debt, which negatively affects their liquidity and solvency.

In the analysis of debtors, great attention should be paid to non-performing bank assets. Because in this group there may be assets that reduce the quality of assets, overdue interest-free loans, overdue loans and interest, unpaid rent, etc.

It is a normal situation in international banking practice that the weight of overdue loans in the loan portfolio does not exceed three percent.

If the amount of overdue loans exceeds the set norm by 2 or more times, the bank's activity is very problematic, its credit policy is assessed as very weak.

In most cases, there are cases of non-receipt of extended loans to "revised loans" accounts. As a result of this, the weight of loans that have practically become inactive in the composition of the given loans is growing. In addition, the amount of profit shown in the bank's profit and loss report is allowed to be unreasonably high.

Conclusion: Commercial banks should create a reserve for possible losses on the debtor. Funds are included in these reserves in the current order. The reserve for possible losses on loans should be established based on the analysis of loans given to economic bodies and the determination of factors affecting the bank's risk level. Based on the determination of reserves, the size of the reserve depends on the current debt or risk group. Provisions for possible losses on loans should be made every month in case of deterioration of the risk group included in the given loan.

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**THE NEED TO IMPROVE THE ANALYSIS OF CASH FLOWS AND
SUSTAINABLE LIABILITIES WHEN ASSESSING THE LIQUIDITY OF
COMMERCIAL BANKS**

Annotation: *If the measures to return loans that have not been returned on time are not sought and measures are not taken quickly, the bank's charter capital, deposited funds, depositors and customers will suffer great damage, and the bank may fail to fulfill its obligations and go to the level of bankruptcy. In order to avoid this, it is necessary to conduct timely control of loans by bank employees.*

Key words: *to the credit department of the bank, in the loan portfolio, problematic loans, persons guaranteeing the loan.*

Monitoring of the credit department of the bank should be carried out continuously. We believe that the loan portfolio will not be put at risk if the problem loans are returned or consultative work is carried out as a result of timely control and supervision of each loan in the loan portfolio. Before the loans turn into problem loans, they must sell the collateralized property or require the persons who guaranteed the loan to fulfill their obligations.

A brief summary of the research results

In the course of completing the master's thesis, we formed the following conclusions:

1. Regulation of the activity of commercial banks by the Central Bank is regulated through economic norms and by using monetary instruments. Due to the lack of improvement in the practice of using monetary instruments in developing countries, regulation through economic norms is considered a priority.

2. The advantage of the method of regulating the activity of commercial banks through economic standards is manifested in its low cost and inextricable connection with the results of external audit. At the same time, the disadvantage

of this method is that some of the information provided by commercial banks is not reliable.

3. During 2020-2021, a decrease in the adequacy ratio of Tier 1 capital (from 17.03 percent to 15.84 percent) was observed in all commercial banks of our republic. This decrease is explained by the fact that the rate of growth of commercial banks' capital lags behind the rate of growth of risky bank assets.

4. During 2022-2026, there was a decrease in the adequacy ratio of the total capital in all commercial banks of our republic (from 17.80 percent to 16.75 percent). These situations can seriously damage confidence in the national banking system.

5. He showed the existence of the following problems in terms of improving the regulation of banking activities in our republic:

- the presence of a tendency to decrease the capital adequacy ratio in large commercial banks of our republic.

- the fact that the weight of demand deposits in the volume of total deposits of commercial banks is high.

- the fact that the norm set for commercial banks on the current liquidity ratio is insufficient to fulfill the bank's obligations directly.

- the presence of shortcomings and errors in the lending practices of banks.

The mechanism of organizing credit operations in large banks will be improved. In these banks, an in-depth analysis of the client's creditworthiness is carried out, which is then carried out at the bank's head office, that is, highly qualified specialists are gathered here.

The share of term and savings deposits in the composition of liabilities of commercial banks of our republic is very small.

- a methodological problem related to the fluctuation of the credit multiplier.

- the fact that the environment of free competition in the banking system of our country is not fully formed.

TIF National Bank and a number of other large commercial banks have a monopoly position in the loan capital market. by the end of the year, 75 percent of the total assets of the national banking system consisted of the assets of TIF National Bank and the remaining six large commercial banks. If we take into account that more than 70 percent of the assets of large commercial banks of our republic are loans, then it becomes clear that large commercial banks have a monopoly position in the loan capital market.

Conclusion: The main shortcoming of cash flow analysis is the complexity of forecasting the actual payback periods of assets and liabilities. It is necessary to introduce a system of indexation of population deposits in order to reduce their role as a source of inflation by attracting temporary free money in the hands of the population to banking institutions on a large scale. It is necessary to ensure a moderate and stable level of interest income in the volume of gross income of commercial banks of our republic. It is necessary to use the system of indicators used in international banking practice to determine the moderate level of interest income.

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QIZIL LOVIYA (FASOL) O'SIMLIGINI BIOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI VA ORGANIZMGA FOYDALARI

Annotatsiya: Ushbuda qizil loviya (fasol) o'simligining biologik xususiyatlari va inson organizmi uchun qanaqa foydalari borligi, tarkibida mavjud vitaminlar xaqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Qizil loviya (fasol), oqsil, ateroskleroz, gipertoniya, parxez taom, vitaminlar.

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95-school biology

BIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES AND BENEFITS OF RED BEANS (BEANS) PLANT FOR THE BODY

Annotation: What are the biological properties of the real red bean (bean) plant and what are its benefits for the human body, the vitamins contained in it are mentioned below.

Keywords: red beans (beans), protein, atherosclerosis, hypertension, parchese food, vitamins.

Mavzuning dolzarbligi: Bugungi kunda aholini oziq ovqat bilan taminlash borasida muammolar bo'lmasligi uchun xam qishloq xo'jaligi va biologiya soxasida juda katta e'tibor berilmoqda. Shu bilan birga xam sifatli xam inson organizmi uchun foydali oziq ovqat mahsulotlari yetishtirish ishlab chiqarish katta vazifa bo'lib kelmoqda. Inson organizmiga barcha mahsulotlar singari dukkakli mahsulotlar xam bir qancha foydalidir Hamda dukkakli mahsulotlarning oqsilga boy ekanligi va tarkibida vitaminlar bisyorligi fikrimizni isboti bo'la oladi Ana shunday dukkakli mahsulotlardan biri qizil loviya (fasol) bu mahsulot xam oqsilga boyligi va tarkibidagi vitaminlar bilan ajralib turadi. Xattoki qizil loviya (fasol) tarkibidagi oqsil go'sht oqsilini xam o'rnini bosa oladi va birqancha

foydalidir. Qizil loviya turlari xilma xil bo'lib bizning yurtimizda yangi yaratilgan navi yo'q chet davlatlardan olib kelib ekilib kelinmoqda fasol ekilishi xam xosil berishi xam ancha oson yaxshi parvarish qilinsa namlik miqdori me'yorida bo'lsa tez va sifatli xosil olish mumkin.

Fasol oson xazm bo'ladi va chiqadi, fasoldan tayyorlangan taomlar parxez taom xisoblanib davolovchi xamdir. Fasol bir qancha kasalliklarni oldini oladi ateroskleroz, buyrakdagi toshlar, gipertoniya, pielonefrit va yurak ritmining buzulishida eng kerakli taom turiga kiradi. Bundan tashqari organizmda uglevod almashinuvini yangilaydi va tartibga soladi, organizmda gemoglobin ishlab chiqarishda xam muxim rol o'ynaydi. Uning eng muxim xususiyati moddalar almashinuvida insulin gormoni ishlab chiqaradi. Tarkibida B6, V1b, B 1vtaminlari bor.

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IQTISODIYOT YO'NALISHI TALABALARINI O'QITISHDA

INTERFAOL METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH

Annotatsiya: Iqtisodiyot sohasida ta'lim olish jarayoni o'ziga xos va murakkab bo'lib, talabalar nazariy bilimlarni amaliyot bilan bog'lashni talab qiladi. An'anaviy ta'lim usullari ko'pincha talabalarni passiv holatda qoldirib, ularning kreativ va analitik fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda cheklovlar keltirib chiqaradi. Shuning uchun, interfaol metodlardan foydalanish, talabalarni o'qitishda samarali yondashuv sifatida ko'riladi.

Key words: ta'lim, metod, raqamli texnologiya.

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THE USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS OF THE DIRECTION OF ECONOMICS

Annotation: the process of obtaining education in the field of Economics is specific and complex, requiring students to associate theoretical knowledge with practice. Traditional educational methods often leave students in a passive state, causing limitations in the development of their creative and analytical thinking skills. Therefore, the use of interactive techniques is seen as an effective approach in educating students.

Key words: education, method, digital technology.

Bugungi shiddat bilan o'zgarib borayotgan dunyoda raqamli texnologiya zamonaviy ta'limning ajralmas qismiga aylandi. Raqamli texnologiyadan foydalanish o'quvchilarning o'rganish va o'qituvchilarning dars berish usullarini inqilob qildi. Bu ta'limni yanada qulayroq, qiziqarli va interaktiv qilib, o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilar uchun cheksiz imkoniyatlar yaratdi. Ta'limda raqamli texnologiyaning eng muhim afzalliklaridan biri o'rganishni shaxsiylashtirish qobiliyatidir. Texnologiyalar yordamida o'qituvchilar har bir o'quvchining o'ziga xos ta'lim uslubi, sur'ati va qiziqishlariga mos keladigan

individual dars rejalarini yaratishi mumkin. O'quvchilar, shuningdek, o'z tezligida, o'z vaqtida va o'zlari xohlagan muhitda o'rganish imkonini beruvchi ko'plab onlayn resurslar va vositalardan foydalanishlari mumkin.

Interfaol metodlarning ahmiyati

Faollik va motivatsiya: Talabalarni faollikka undovchi metodlar, masalan, guruh ishlari yoki rol o'ynash, o'quvchilarning darsga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshiradi. Bu, o'z navbatida, o'qituvchining motivatsiyasini ham kuchaytiradi.

Talabalararo munosabatlar: Interfaol o'qitish usullari talabalar o'rtasida ijtimoiy munosabatlarni rivojlantiradi. Buning natijasida, o'quvchilar birlaridan o'rganish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar.

Shaxsiy qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish: Har bir talabani o'z qobiliyatlariga mos ravishda rivojlantirish imkonini beradi. O'quvchilar o'zlarining kuchli va zaif tomonlarini aniqlab, ularni takomillashtirishga qaratilgan strategiyalarni ishlab chiqadilar.

2. Interfaol metodlar

Guruh ishlari: Amaliy Mavzular: Talabalar iqtisodiy nazariyalar yoki muammolar bo'yicha guruhda ishlash orqali tajribalarini baham ko'radilar. Masalan, Xalqaro savdo va iqtisodiy o'zgarishlar mavzusi bo'yicha guruh ishlarini tashkil qilish mumkin.

O'quvchilar roli: Har bir talaba o'z rolini bajaradi, bu esa ularni muammoni turli nuqtai nazardan ko'rishga undaydi.

Muzokaralar fikr almashish: Talabalar o'z fikrlarini, mulohazalarini va tajribalarini muhokama qilishadi. Samarali iqtisodiy siyosat mavzusi atrofida muhokama o'tkazish orqali talabalar o'z fikrlarini ifoda etish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishadi.

Tahlil: O'quvchilar muayyan iqtisodiy vaziyatlarni tahlil qilish orqali o'z bilimlarini amaliyotda qo'llashni o'rganadilar.

Rol o'ynash, simulyatsiya: Iqtisodiy o'yinlar va simulyatsiyalar orqali talabalar real vaziyatlarga tayyorlanishadi. Masalan, bozor iqtisodiyoti

simulyatsiyasi orqali talabalar iqtisodiy faoliyatning barcha jihatlarini ko'rishadi.

Интерактив darslar: O'quvchilar o'z rollarini bajarish orqali amaliy ko'nikmalarini oshiradilar.

3. Ta'sir va natijalar

O'qitish sifatining oshishi: Interfaol metodlar dars jarayonini qiziqarli va samarali qiladi. O'quvchilar o'zaro hamkorlikda ishlashga o'rganadilar va natijada bilimlarni yaxshilaydilar.

Mustaqil fikrlash: Talabalar o'z mustaqil fikrlarini bildirishga va qarorlar qabul qilishga o'rganadilar, bu esa kelajakdagi professional faoliyatlariga ijobiy ta'sir qiladi.

Ijtimoiy ko'nikmalar: Talabalar o'zaro hamkorlik, muloqot va muammolarni hal qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradilar, bu esa ularning ish joylarida muhim ahamiyatga ega.

4. Amaliyotga tatbiq

O'qituvchilar interfaol metodlarni quyidagi tarzda amalga oshirishlari mumkin:

Vazifalar berish: O'quvchilarga real hayotdagi muammolarni hal qilishga undovchi vazifalar tayinlash. Misol uchun, Mamlakatning iqtisodiy o'sishini tahlil qilish mavzusi bo'yicha vazifalar berish.

Guruh loyihalari: Talabalar o'zaro hamkorlikda loyiha tayyorlash orqali o'z nazariy bilimlarini amaliyotga tatbiq etishlari mumkin. Masalan, Iqtisodiy islohotlar va ularning ta'siri mavzusi bo'yicha loyiha tayyorlash.

Feedback berish: O'qituvchilar o'z talabalariga dars davomida va keyinchalik mulohazalar berishlari kerak, bu esa ularning rivojlanishiga yordam beradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, bilish faoliyatini muammoli ta'lim orqali tashkil etish talabalarni erkin fikrlashga hamda o'z fikrini himoya qila iolshga, boshqalar bilan ochiq holda bahslashishga, egallagan bilimlarini tahlil qila

olishga, mantiqiy tafakkur yuritish bilan bilim va ko'nikmalarni shakllanishiga, tafakkur tezligini aniqlashga, kichik guruhlarda jamoa bo'lib ishlash malakasini egallashga, o'zaro bir-birini fikrini hurmat qilish hislarini shakllanishiga yordam beradi. Aynan yuqorida sanab o'tganimiz "FSMU", "Sinkveyn", "Breynstorming" usullari talabalarni erkin fikrlashga, o'z fikrini himoya qilishga va boshqalarga o'z fikrini o'tkazishga, ochiq holda bahslashishga, bahs-munozara madaniyatiga, shu bilan bir qatorda, metodlar orqali tegishli masalalarga doir ijobiy va salbiy jihatlar, afzallik va kamchiliklar, foyda va zararlar belgilanadi. Hamda yangi g'oyalar yaratish, ijobiy yengil yechimlar topa olish, hissiy bilishni shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, ushbu usullardan foydalanish talabalarda o'quv faoliyatidagi faollikni, ishga ijodiy yondoshishni, muammoli vaziyatlardan irrasional tarzda chiqa olishni va eng muhimi bilimlarni mustahkamlanishiga olib keladi. Interfaol metodlardan foydalanish iqtisodiyot yo'nalishi talabalarini o'qitishda o'quv jarayonining sifatini oshiradi. Talabalar yanada faol, mustaqil va kreativ shaxslar sifatida rivojlanishlariga yordam beradi. O'qituvchilar bu metodlarni amaliyotga joriy etish orqali zamonaviy ta'lim talablari darajasida samarali o'qitishni amalga oshirishlari mumkin.

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BAZALTLARNING KLASSIFIKATSIYALANISHI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bazaltlarning shakllanishi, tarqalish hududlari, klassifikatsiyasi va ularning qo'llanilishi haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: bazalt, metamorfizm, dolerit, anamezit, bazalt tolasi.

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CLASSIFICATION OF BASALTS

Annotation: this article provides information on the formation, distribution areas, classicization, and applications of basalts.

Base words: basalt, metamorphism, dolerite, anamesite, Basalt Fiber.

Iqtisodiy tejamkorlikni ta'minlash uchun ishlab chiqarishda qo'llaniladigan xom ashyo materiallarining ahamiyati katta ahamiyatga ega. Mamlakatimizda mavjud ana shunday xom ashyolardan biri – bu bazaltlardir. Bazaltlardan tayyorlangan materiallardan qurilish metariallari (kafel, g'isht, issiqlik izolyatsion qoplamalar, ...), issiqlik uzatish tizimida izolyatsion material sifatida, neft va gaz sanoatida filtrlar sifatida foydalanish mumkin.

Bazaltlarning shakllanishi asosan asosiy tarkibi SiO_2 dan iborat (45-52%) bo'lgan vulqon lavasining oqilib chiqishi va kontinentlarning sirtqi qatlamida, shuningdek okeanlarning tubida qotishi (zastıvanii) bilan bog'liq. Bazaltlar Yer sharida eng keng tarqalgan tog' jinslaridan hisoblanadi. Bazaltlarning asosiy massasi aynan okeanlarda, okean tog' tizmalari oralig'ida, okean tektonik plitalarining shakllanishida (okeandagi yer qobig'ining shakllanishida) yuzaga keladi. Bazaltlar tipik kaynotip vulqon jinsi sifatida paydo bo'lib, amalda qandaydir ikkinchi o'zgartiruvchi jarayonga duch kelmaydi (uchramaydi). Hidrotermal jarayonlarda olivin serpentin bilan, plogioklaz seritsit bilan aralashib ketadi, natijada tog' jinsi xlorlanadi, ya'ni xlorga to'yinadi va yaqqol

yashilsimon rang kasb etadi. Ushbu o'zgarishlar asosan okean tog' tizmalari oralig'ida shakllanuvchi bazaltlarga xosdir.

Metamorfizm natijasida, shart-sharoitlarga bog'liq ravishda bazaltlar amfibolitlarga, yashil va havorang slanslarga aylanadi.

Metamorfizm jarayonida bazalt-diabaz guruhiga kiruvchi tog' jinslari porforitoidlar va so'ngra ortoamfibolitlarga aylanadi.

Bazaltlarning tarqalishi. Eng ko'p hajmdagi bazaltlar kuchli va keng lava oqimi ko'rinishida G'arbiy Hindistondagi Dekan platosida va Kordileradagi (Vashington, Oregano va Aydaxo shtatlari) Kolumbiya platosida uchraydi. Koloradoda , Nyu-Meksika va Arizonada vulkanlarning otilishi bazaltli lavalarning otilishiga olib keldi. Gavayya orollari o'zining bazaltli vulqon konuslariga ega, ular Tinch okeani tubidan bir kilometr balandlikda joylashgan.

Tarkibiy tuzilishiga ko'ra bazaltlar: zich massali, g'ovakli, bodomsimontoshli turlarga bo'linadi.

Bazaltlarning klassifikatsiyalanishini quyidagicha jadval ko'rinishida ifodalash mumkin.

1-rasm. Bazaltlarning klassifikatsiyalanishi.

Bazaltlarning qo'llanilishi. Bazaltlar qurilish materiali, qoplovchi (qoplama) material va kislotabardosh materiallar sifatida, shuningdek tosh quyimakorligi uchun xom ashyo sifatida qo'llaniladi. Bazalt tolalarini (qirindilarini) qo'shish orqali beton mahsulotlarining zarbiy mustahkamligini 5 martagacha oshirish mumkin.

Ushbu tog' jinslari keng tarzda qo'llaniladigan issiqlik izolyatsion material – tosh paxta (yoki tosh momiq), boshqacha aytganda, bazalt tolasi tayyorlashda qo'llaniladi. Bazalt tolasini tayyorlash uchun bazalt shag'ali, ya'ni maydalangan bazalt toshlari suyuq oquvchan lava holiga keltiriladi. So'ngra unchalik murakkab bo'lmagan mexanizm yordamida suyuq bazalt nozik ip (tola) shakliga o'tkaziladi.

Bazalt kroshkalar va bazalt changlari ishlab chiqarishda antikorrozion qoplama sifatida qo'llaniladi. Bu qoplamalar turli agressiv muhitlar, jumladan kislotali va ishqorli muhitlarga chidamlidir. Shuningdek, ushbu qoplamalar issiqlik izolyatsion bo'lib, tovush, ya'ni shovqinni kam o'tkazuvchan va olovbardoshdir.

Xulosa. Bazaltlardan tayyorlangan materiallardan, jumladan bazalt tolalaridan amalda foydalanish turli muammolarning, masalan, issiqlik yo'qotilishini oldini olishda, neft va gaz mahsulotlarini filtrlashda foydalanish mumkin. Qurilish sanoatida zamonaviy va energiya tejamkor qurilishi materiallarini ishlab chiqarishda ham bazaltlardan keng foydalanish mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. <http://nenavigator.ru/magicheskiye-svoystva-bazalta/>
3. <http://www.basalt-tech.ru/ru/carer>

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**THE IMPLICIT USAGE OF PROHIBITIVE CONSTRUCTIONS IN
ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROVERBS**

ANNOTATION

The article is mainly focused on implicature in paremiological units, particularly, in order to express prohibitive constructions. The usage of proverbs has been clarified as a way of telling something implicitly rather than explicitly supporting your arguments in popular wisdom. Moreover, proverbs are considered part of figurative language because they represent an indirect means to communicate a set of expectations about shared thoughts between listeners and speakers, rather than directly expressing them. At the same time, it may be clear that the prohibitions can be presented both in an explicit and implicit way but by means of various structures and form.

Keywords: Prohibitive constructions, Explicit and Implicit meaning, cognitive-pragmatic features, Paremiological units, and Pragmatic intention

INTRODUCTION

The usage of proverbs has been clarified as a way of telling something implicitly rather than explicitly supporting your arguments in popular wisdom. Moreover, proverbs are considered part of figurative language because they represent an indirect means to communicate a set of expectations about shared thoughts between listeners and speakers, rather than directly expressing them. But why do speakers not choose a more explicit way of saying what they think and instead communicate their real thoughts in an implicit manner, by means of a proverb? We may take advantage of implicit communication when we are not completely sure about the mutual information that both speaker and hearer share. Regarding proverb analysis, the identification of the concepts underlying proverbs and their corresponding encyclopedic entries is one of the first stages of the proverb comprehension process. These encyclopedic entries are determined in the recognition of proverbs' meaning since to achieve some contextual effects, the hearer has to have some previous knowledge as part of this cultural knowledge.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There appears to be a lack in the literature of a unified pragmatic theory on the use of proverbs, although several authors have brought this discussion to bear in specific contexts (see Seitel 1969, Lieber 1984, Yankah 1984, Penfield & Duru 1988, Krikmann 1974, Arewa & Dundes 1964, Jesenšek 2014, Grzybek 2014, et al.). These authors begin with the importance of context as a key aspect of their analysis. One of the earlier scholars who began developing a theory of proverb meaning is Kirshenblatt-Gimblett (1973); she proposed a specific equation for determining the meaning of a proverb in context. Her hypothesis reads like this: proverb meaning is equal to the participant's evaluation of the situation plus the participants' understanding of the proverb's base plus the interactional strategy of the proverb user (1973: 119). Throughout her article, "proverb meaning" is the meaning (intended to be) communicated by a particular utterance of a proverb. We can take the sample "the participants' evaluation of the situation" as the current context. If we implement it in this way, this equation put more typically might read something like this.

Proverb meaning = context + base meaning + speaker's intention or, in Relevance Theory terms it may read like something closer to if we allow the "base meaning" to be an explicature and the "strategy" of Kirshenblatt-Gimblett's equation to be the intended emergent meaning of the proverb when applied to the situation.

Proverb meaning = context + 1 explicature + implicature(s)/explicature(s) (pragmatically derived from the speaker's intent.)

Kirshenblatt-Gimblett's theory works well within the current thesis because it shows the multiple factors that contribute to the interpretation of the utterance of a proverb. The proverb contains a "wisdom of many", or explicature, which requires knowledge of the proverb by speakers of the language. It theorizes that there will always be an explicature in any given proverb utterance that equates to the traditional meaning of the proverb. Then, there are additional implicatures

that arise due to the analogy between the explicature of the proverb and a situation in the current context.

An analogy is an essential part of proverb interpretation. Each time a proverb is uttered; there are referents in the real world to which elements of the proverb apply. For example, in the proverb too many cooks spoil the broth, the cooks may refer to (by analogy) a group of at least two people and the broth to the project/effort that the group is devoted to. The application of this analogy is essential in determining the strong implicature characterized by the utterance which will be specific to the context. Both Seitel (1969) and Lieber (1984) have discussed the importance of analogy in their work and a summary and evaluation of each follow.

METHODS

A semantic and structural analysis will be conducted not only to analyze the motivation between the components of paremiological units and their meaning, but it deals with national and cultural specificity of both languages. A structural analysis should be conducted in line with the semantic analysis because in the process of comparison of both English and Uzbek languages the discrepancy is much observed in the components of paremiological units, containing prohibitive construction. For example, while comparing proverbs in particular topic not always it is possible to find the equivalent of one proverb even presenting negative emotions or obligations. The best option will be opting for the alternative version that can substitute or give the same meaning. Sometimes with declarative tone in proverbs the messenger can refer to negative attitude and it can be revealed by approaching diachronically, namely, being acquainted with the background information of one proverbs and its utilization in different context with different emotions. Collecting dictionaries, looking through encyclopedias and relying on primary and secondary sources can assist to make the investigation more productive and effective. Proverbs which were gathered from dictionaries will serve as a valuable means of resources during the

process of comparison their similarities and differences from semantic and structural points of view. The qualitative method is used in my research to collect and analyze the data. The English proverbs make up the data of my research study. English and Uzbek proverbs are randomly chosen and analyzed in the study.

RERSULT AND DISCUSSION

Regarding proverb analysis, the identification of the concepts underlying proverbs and their corresponding encyclopedic entries is one of the first stages of the proverb comprehension process. These encyclopedic entries are determined in the recognition of proverbs' meaning since to achieve some contextual effects, the hearer has to have some previous knowledge as part of this cultural knowledge. In some cases, for example in the context of famous proverbs like "Curiosity kills a cat", information can be easily recovered at one simple stage. (Ferguson, 2000: 145). Since it is a very familiar proverb, it is easily recognized and the set of assumptions conveyed will be immediately recovered. Nevertheless, there may be cases when reaching this information may be more difficult. This would be the case of unfamiliar proverbs which involve in each step an extension of the context for the hearer to recover the speaker's meaning.

In the English language, there are so many proverbs with prohibitive meanings but without prohibitive constructions. Only after analyzing deeply, we can reveal hidden implicit meaning. For example;

- *Think twice, cut once.*
- Yetti o'lchab bir kes.

Most of us have heard the expression measure twice, cut once and although it makes sense in a literal sense, in a figurative sense it also makes sense.

To minimize the harm, "measure twice, cut once", like a careful tailor, advises Bill Coleman of Salary.com, a website that tracks employment news. (the economist)

If you've heard this said, it was probably said as a warning to another to plan and prepare for something in a careful, thorough manner before taking action. In other words, think before you act, namely, it refers not to doing anything without thinking and encourages people not to hurry in any case.

In the Uzbek language, we have the proverb "Yetti o'lchab bir kes", which gives the same meaning as the English version, only the numbers are different but it is similar to the Russian proverb.

- Curiosity killed the cat.
- Bilib o'tir o'rningni,
Har yerga suqma burningni.

It is probable that this phrase came from the works of Ben Jonson and William Shakespeare in the late 1500s. 'Curiosity killing the cat' is commonly used in casual conversations in English-speaking countries, which are usually perceived as quite cliché and therefore not a great addition to the dialogue between writers. One of the most common proverbs is, 'Curiosity killed the cat,' with the full version being, "Curiosity killed the cat, but satisfaction made it come back." It tells us that it is dangerous for you to be so interested or curious. They might find themselves in danger when they approach matters in which they do not have any interest. That could be a metaphoric threat, or it could be the case of actual danger. It is, for example, possible that someone would have lost more money than they were willing to if they had taken a number of financial risks in curiosity about the state of the market.

In the Uzbek language "Bilib o'tir o'rningni, har yerga suqma burningni" can be a semantic equivalent, but not structural. In the English version, the meaning of this proverb is expressed implicitly, namely, there is no sign of prohibition, it is written just in declarative form and in a typical structure. But the hidden

meaning refers to a prohibitive form, while in the Uzbek language prohibition is kept explicitly with the negative suffix –ma in the sentence.

- *Walls have ears.*
- Devorning ham qulog'i bor.

With this proverb, it refers to taking care of what you're saying, 'because it may be overheard by someone, through this statement we are required not to speak so loud so that someone could hear us. This means someone might still be spying on you even if you think no one's listening. Even if from the context there is no signal of prohibition explicitly in the form, semantically we can deduce that it turns out into a warning and prohibition which urge us to be careful not to hurry.

- *Walls have ears.*
- *Doors have eyes.*
- *Trees have voices.*
- *Beasts tell lies.*
- *Beware the rain.*
- *Beware the snow.*
- *Beware the man*
- *You think you know.*
- *Songs of Sapphique* (Catherine Fisher)

It is said in this and similar series of proverbs that a person should not believe too much in the chatter and "long-eared" things along with gossip he or she heard from others, should not make a firm conclusion from it, and talk about it to everyone, firstly everyone should see with his own eyes and have full confidence and only after he can be sure and come to a conclusion and act or speak. Another version of this proverb are; "O'z ko'zing o'lik o'lik turg'izur, o'lik turg'izmasa, yotganni turg'izur", "Chap ko'z bilan inon, o'ng ko'z bilan tekshir", "Ko'rgan bilan eshitgan teng emas", "Ikki quloq bilan eshitgandan, bir ko'z bilan ko'rgan yaxshi" and so on. From the context we can elicit the hidden

meaning about not concluding after what we listen from others, contrarily we are demanded to be more cautious and attentive in order not to be deceived.

The following Uzbek proverbs indicate implicit prohibitive constructions and are required to analyze the meaning deeply.

- *Kekkayish terakka yarashar*
- *Ma'nosi yo'q gapdan, donasi bor cho'p yaxshi*
- *Taqlid bilan tong otmas*
- *Sayoq yurgan tayoq yeydi*

In the English language also, we can find several proverbs that resemble this one, “Believe nothing that you hear, and only half of what you see”. This proverb belongs to Middle English and it warns that you should not believe everything that is said or that you hear, and a letter of the late 18th century has, ‘You must not consider everything to be true that is told to you.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this article is devoted to analyses of proverbs that give another hidden prohibitive meaning. Moreover, it is defined the structure of formulation of these types of proverbs with some examples in order to support the theory. At the same time, the cognitive–pragmatic features of prohibitive construction as well clarified in proverbs with implicit structure. The usage of proverbs has been clarified as a way of telling something implicitly rather than explicitly supporting your arguments in popular wisdom. Moreover, proverbs are considered part of figurative language because they represent an indirect means to communicate a set of expectations about shared thoughts between listeners and speakers, rather than directly expressing them. But why do speakers not choose a more explicit way of saying what they think and instead communicate their real thoughts in an implicit manner, by means of a proverb? We may take advantage of implicit communication when we are not completely sure about the mutual information that both speaker and hearer share. All in all, we can

conclude that the prohibitions can be presented both in an explicit and implicit way but by means of various structures and form.

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**ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ И СПОРТА В
ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ЛИДЕРСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА СТУДЕНТОВ
ВЫСШЕГО ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ**

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются возможности формирования основных лидерских качеств у студентов посредством физического воспитания и спорта. Все мы знаем, что не всем студентам высших учебных заведений присущи лидерские качества, поскольку такие учебные заведения больше ориентированы на передачу конкретных знаний, умений и компетенций, чем на развитие лидерских качеств. Потому что в современную бурно развивающуюся эпоху формирование лидерских способностей будущих педагогических кадров стать зрелым специалистом своего дела становится одним из наиболее актуальных вопросов. В этой статье мы постарались подчеркнуть важность физического воспитания и спорта, а не причины отсутствия у студентов лидерских качеств.

Ключевые слова: Физическое воспитание и спорт, Сотрудничество в команде, Самоуправление, Критическое мышление, Лидерские качества, Успеваемость.

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**THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN
THE FORMATION OF THE LEADERSHIP POTENTIAL OF
STUDENTS OF HIGHER PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION**

Abstract: This article examines the possibilities of forming the basic leadership qualities of students through physical education and sports. We all know that not all students of higher education institutions have leadership qualities, since such educational institutions are more focused on the transfer of specific knowledge, skills and competencies than on the development of leadership qualities. Because in the modern rapidly developing era, the formation of leadership abilities of future teaching staff to become a mature specialist in their field is becoming one of the most pressing issues. In this article, we tried to emphasize the importance of physical education and sports, not the reasons for the lack of leadership qualities among students.

Keywords: Physical education and sports, Teamwork, Self-management, Critical thinking, Leadership qualities, Academic performance.

Как спортивные специалисты, руководители, педагоги и спортивные тренеры, работающие в различных областях образования, спорта и физического воспитания, мы прекрасно понимаем преобразующую силу физического воспитания в развитии лидерских качеств. Помимо поддержания здорового образа жизни, занятия спортом и физическая активность помогают учащимся развивать такие навыки, как эффективное общение, работа в команде, решение проблем и настойчивость — качества, которые важны для успеха во многих сферах жизни и карьеры. В быстро развивающемся мире лидерские качества приобретают все большее значение для личностного роста, академических успехов и развития карьеры. Физическое воспитание может служить платформой для развития этих навыков, предоставляя учащимся прочную основу для решения будущих задач и достижения успеха в выбранных ими областях. В этих исследованиях не учитывалась важность развития лидерских качеств посредством физического воспитания, а важные качества, способствующие успешному лидеру, изучены недостаточно. Поэтому мы обсуждаем практические стратегии, которые родители, учителя и тренеры могут использовать для развития этих навыков у учащихся.

Важность развития лидерских качеств посредством физического воспитания. Ключевые лидерские качества посредством физического воспитания. Занятия спортом и физическая активность могут развить важные качества, которые способствуют эффективному лидерству. Некоторые из этих ключевых особенностей:

1. **Эффективное общение.** Участие в спортивных и командных мероприятиях может научить детей важности четкого и краткого общения. Это также помогает развивать навыки активного слушания, чтобы они

понимали потребности и точки зрения других и реагировали соответствующим образом.

2. Работа в команде и сотрудничество. Физическая деятельность часто требует от учащихся совместной работы для достижения общих целей. Участие в командных видах спорта помогает развивать сотрудничество, гибкость и навыки межличностного общения, которые необходимы для эффективного лидерства.

3. Принятие решений и решение проблем. Физическое воспитание часто представляет собой множество ситуаций, которые требуют от детей быстрого принятия решений и решения проблем. Этот опыт помогает студентам развивать критическое мышление и аналитические навыки, необходимые для того, чтобы стать успешными лидерами.

4. Устойчивость и гибкость. Преодоление трудностей, преодоление неудач и обучение на ошибках являются неотъемлемыми аспектами занятий спортом. Такой опыт способствует развитию стабильности и гибкости, которые ценны для процветания в качестве лидера.

5. Эмоциональный интеллект. Наконец, физическое воспитание развивает эмоциональный интеллект, поскольку дети учатся управлять своими эмоциями, сопереживать другим и соответствующим образом реагировать на различные социальные ситуации..

Практические стратегии развития лидерских качеств в сфере физического воспитания. Родители, учителя и тренеры могут принять на вооружение несколько практических стратегий развития лидерских качеств посредством физического воспитания:

Позвольте учащимся брать на себя ответственность. Поощряйте учащихся брать на себя руководящие роли во время физических упражнений, например, быть капитанами команд, тренерами или судьями. Предоставление студентам лидерских обязанностей позволяет им

развивать навыки и уверенность, необходимые для того, чтобы преуспеть в качестве лидеров.

Развивайте установку на рост. Подчеркивайте важность настойчивости, непрерывного роста и принятия вызовов. Поощрение детей воспринимать неудачи как возможность для улучшения закладывает основу для мышления роста, что является важной чертой эффективных лидеров.

Обучение эффективному разрешению конфликтов: содействие здоровому разрешению конфликтов в контексте спорта и физического воспитания, оснащение учащихся инструментами для разрешения конфликтов, развития позитивных отношений и поиска точек соприкосновения со сверстниками.

Поощряйте самоанализ и обратную связь: поощряйте учащихся размышлять о своей успеваемости, определять сильные стороны и области для роста, а также получать обратную связь от сверстников, учителей и наставников. Самосознание и постоянное совершенствование являются ключевыми аспектами эффективного лидерства.

Выделите вдохновляющих лидеров. Используйте реальные примеры успешных лидеров из разных областей, особенно спорта, чтобы вдохновить студентов и продемонстрировать различные стили и качества лидерства.

Долгосрочные преимущества лидерских навыков в дальнейшей образовательной карьере учащихся. Развитие лидерских качеств посредством физического воспитания может иметь далеко идущие последствия для личного, академического и профессионального развития учащихся:

1. Личностный рост. Лидерские качества способствуют сильному чувству самостоятельности, уверенности в себе и решимости, давая

студентам возможность преодолевать личные проблемы и достигать успеха в различных аспектах жизни.

2. Академический успех. Навыки эффективного общения, решения проблем и командной работы имеют решающее значение в академической среде и помогают улучшить успеваемость при выполнении групповых заданий, презентаций и экзаменов.

3. Внеклассные достижения: лидерские качества полезны для внеклассной деятельности учащихся, такой как участие в клубах, обществах и общественных проектах, что позволяет им эффективно управлять различными интересами и деятельностью, чтобы полностью использовать свой потенциал.

4. Карьерный рост. Эффективные лидерские навыки высоко ценятся в профессиональном мире, что увеличивает вероятность карьерного роста, удовлетворенности работой и профессионального успеха.

Краткое содержание Педагогические институты с неспециализированной подготовкой по программам физического воспитания и спорта создают основу для успеха в различных сферах жизни студентов, развивают важные лидерские качества, укрепляют их здоровье, обладают здравым смыслом и инициативой, быстрее достигают успеха, предоставляют неоценимые возможности. Зная о силе спорта и физической активности, учителя и тренеры могут дать учащимся навыки, необходимые им для того, чтобы добиться успеха в качестве будущих лидеров, предоставляя учащимся дополнительные учебные программы. Это, в свою очередь, является одним из факторов, помогающих студентам добиться успеха в личной и профессиональной жизни.

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МИНИАТЮРНАЯ ШКОЛА ЭПОХИ ТИМУРИДОВ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается об условиях развития миниатюрных школ в период правления Амира Темура и Тимуридов, об их особенностях. Кроме того, приведены некоторые копии миниатюр времен Тимуридов и их описание.

Ключевые слова: миниатюра, Восточная миниатюра, миниатюра эпохи Тимуридов, изобразительное искусство эпохи Мирзо Улугбека, Шарафиддин Али Язди, миниатюры из книги "Зафарнома".

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A MINIATURE SCHOOL OF THE TIMURID ERA

Abstract: This article talks about the conditions of development of miniature schools during the period of Amir Temur and the Timurids, and its specific aspects. In addition, some copies of the miniatures of the Timurid period and their description were given.

Key words: miniature, Eastern miniature, miniature of the Timurid era, fine art during the time of Mirzo Ulugbek, Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi, miniatures in the book "Zafarnoma".

Слово миниатюра происходит от французского миниатюра; латинский. мини-термин, означающий "красная краска", используется для обозначения произведений изобразительного искусства небольшого

объема (моджаз), художественные методы которых чрезвычайно изысканны. Термин миниатюра применяется также к изящным чудотворным картинам, созданным для украшения средневековых рукописей, а также к мелкой живописи, выполненной на кости, пергаменте, металле, фарфоре, иногда и на предметах домашнего обихода (табак, часы, кольца и т. д.).[1]

С начала XV века начинается новый этап в развитии Восточной миниатюры. Основная причина этого-централизованная система государств империи Тимуридов. В 1365 году Тимур, правивший в Мавераннахре, изгоняет монголов из Средней Азии. Покорил Хорезм и Прибалтику. Затем началась подготовка к поездке в Иран, Ирак, Сирию, Турцию, Индию. В начале XVI века Тимур основал большое государство на территории от Средиземного моря до Индии. Налажены связи со странами Восточной и Западной Европы. Информацию об этом можно увидеть в мемуарах испанского посла в Самарканде Клавихо де Гонсалеса. Он описывает Самарканд как «сияющую точку земного шара».[2] Международная торговля получает широкое распространение, столица становится центром науки, культуры и искусства. В Мавераннахр были привезены выдающиеся ученые и литераторы, архитекторы и ремесленники, художники. В результате сложились художественные культуры народов Ближнего Востока и Азии, заложившие основы нового метода в искусстве. Даже после смерти Тимура Самарканд оставался центром науки и культуры под руководством его внука Улугбека. Культура Герата была такой же, и страной правил сын Тимура Шахрух Мирза. В конце XIV-начале XV века при дворе Тимура в Самарканде творили крупные миниатюристы художники. В частности, согласно историческим источникам, славу приобрел Багдадский мастер Абдулхай, возглавлявший самаркандские художественные мастерские. Биография среднеазиатских художников основываясь на образовании Мохаммеда

Дуста, он писал, что с тех пор «по его стилю никто другой не мог писать». Друг Мухаммад, - ни один художник не мог обойти стиль Абдулхая, все стремились рисовать в этом стиле. Учениками Абдулхая также считаются шейх Мухаммад Талили, Пир Ахмад Сади Шамали, Мухаммад Ибн Махмудшах Аль-Хайям, которые творили в этот период».

При внуке Тимура Мирзе Улугбеке (1409-1449) искусство миниатюры получило высокое развитие. Его имя известно не только как правящего царя, но и как крупного ученого и покровителя науки, искусства. Период его правления характеризуется расцветом городского строительства, архитектуры, декоративно-прикладного искусства, литературы и искусства. Главным интересом Улугбека была область астрономии, с которой он привлек выдающихся ученых и построил знаменитую обсерваторию, с которой нигде не мог сравниться. Улугбек также поддерживал творчество миниатюристов. Даже в это время в Самарканде была улица художников «Куи-Наккошон». Ко второй половине XV века в искусстве среднеазиатской миниатюры заметен некоторый упадок. Это объясняется триумфом религиозного положения в стране, приходом ее представителя Ходжи Ахрара. При гуманистическом правителе Мирзо Улугбеке крупнейшие ученые, мастера, собравшиеся в столице, подвергаются гонениям. Затем они медленно перемещаются в Герат, под опеку Султана Хусейна Байкары и его министра Алишера Навои. Об уникальных миниатюрных знаках времен Амира Темура свидетельствуют выписки из «Стамбульского альбома» и необработанные миниатюрные копии, хранящиеся в библиотеках Дворца Тупкопи в Турции и Берлина, пишет академик Узфа А. Пугаченкова. В нем эти необработанные копии XIV - XV веков с особой тонкостью изображают отдельных людей, деревья, цветы, узоры и небольшие композиции, что свидетельствует о высоком мастерстве мастеров. Но следует также отметить, - подчеркивает Алима, - что по признакам Ширазской и

Гератской миниатюрных школ Самаркандская школа была определена на основе этнических признаков, характерных для среднеазиатских школ.[3]

Опираясь на мнения историков и искусствоведов, можно сказать, что при Тимуридах XV века в таких среднеазиатских городах, как Самарканд, Герат, Бухара, на высоком уровне были развиты наука и искусство, и этот период тесно связан с именем Алишера Навои и Бехзада.

Вслед за Монием на Востоке в качестве великого мусаввира известны имена Джунаида Багдади, Ходжи Абдулхая, Гиясиддина Наккаша, Мирака Наккаша, Камалиддина Бехзада, Касима Али, Махмуда Музаххиба, Абдуллы Мусаввира, Басавана, Резойи Аббаси и других. При Тимуридах сложилась традиция делать миниатюры на отдельных листах и составлять из них мурраки, получила развитие обработка изображений (портретов) отдельных лиц. В конце XIV века в Самарканде сформировалась Самаркандская школа миниатюры, которая впоследствии оказала влияние на формирование Гератской школы миниатюры; при дворах Тимуридов были созданы отдельные библиотеки, где работали искусные каллиграфы и китабхане, в том числе мусаввиры. В частности, известно, что в библиотеке Мирзы Байсунгура работало более сорока каллиграфов, более семидесяти мусаввиров.

О времени их создания свидетельствуют несколько дошедших до наших дней рукописей и надписи на страницах отдельных миниатюр, созданных, в частности, во время правления Мирзы Улугбека. Одним из первых произведений, созданных во времена Улугбека и дошедших до нас, является трактат Абдурахмана ас-Суфи о катастрофе под названием "изображение неподвижных звезд" ("Сувар Аль-кавокиб ас-Собита"), украшенный 74 картинами с символами различных созвездий. Созвездия в этом трактате – символы созвездий-одушевлены изящными красками в образе человека, существа или мифического существа, исходя из их названий. Например, в созвездии Джавза изображен символ девушек –

Близнецов, в созвездии скобок – образ юноши, дергающего лук, в созвездии Далва – образ пастуха, в созвездии Пегаса – образ крылатого коня, в созвездии Кентавра – человекоподобный конь, берущий за заднюю лапу льва и т.д. Под каждой звездой или внутри красной Иуды черными чернилами написано ее имя в арабском написании.[4]

В миниатюрах эпохи Тимуридов много похожих пейзажей. В том числе такие сцены, как охотничий пейзаж, игра в наездников, стрельба из лука, вечеринки в саду, являются обычным явлением.

“Зафарнома” (“книга побед”) историка и поэта Шарафиддина Али Язди является наиболее полным описанием жизни и деятельности великого правителя и полководца Амира Тимура. Язди описывает Амира Тимура как удачливого полководца, который заканчивает войны победителем, сострадательного к простому народу, предателя и непримиримого к врагам. Почти сразу после написания произведение стало одним из самых известных произведений эпохи Тимуридов, и для его украшения привлекались самые искусные художники того времени. До нашего времени дошло несколько рукописей произведения шарафиддина Али Язди "Зафарнома". Проект "Культурное наследие Узбекистана" Британская библиотека (I.O. Islamis 137), который опубликовал факсимиле 31 своей уникальной миниатюры, украшающей рукопись 1533 года, хранящуюся в его коллекции. В серии миниатюр можно встретить батальные сцены, банкеты (съезды), свадьбы, посиделки, сцены охоты. Еще 7 миниатюр посвящены различным другим мероприятиям. Миниатюры-яркое свидетельство величия Амира Тимура как государственного и военного деятеля, человека, занимавшего неограниченное место в истории человечества. Миниатюры выглядели гармонично с текстами, созданными на насталикском письме.[5]

Миниатюра под названием " Сахибкиран в Меджлисе"

1370 год. Амир Тему́р созвал Курултай и провозгласил своим преемником старшего сына Джахангира султана. На миниатюре изображен праздничный пейзаж. Торжество проходит на лоне природы, на красивом зеленом холме, где раскинулся первый весенний цветочный букет

Миниатюра под названием " молодежь играет в човгон"

На миниатюре изображена знаменитая игра в човгон, популярная в молодости Амира Тимура. На фоне холмов в верхней части композиции

изображен молодой Амир Тимур, коронованный на голове, восседающий на троне в желто-синем платье.

Миниатюра "свадьба сыновей Амира Темура"

Свадебная церемония проходит под открытым небом, на цветущей площади. По случаю торжества на колоннах установили крыльцо из вышитых тканей с цветными нитками. Художник изобразил фигуру Амира Темура, сидящего, глядя на гостей, главных героев мероприятия – Омара Шейха Мирзу, Амирзаду Рустама и Мирон-шаха на дорогих сиденьях, в изящных нарядах с позолоченными цветами. Миниатюра была представлена в более золотистых ярких тонах, чтобы создать настроение свадебной церемонии.

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ИЗУЧЕНИЕ КЛЕТОЧНЫХ РЕАКЦИЙ ПРИ ГЕЛЬМИНТОЗАХ

Аннотация. Клеточные реакции при гельминтозах характеризуются эозинофилией, инфильтрацией клетками фиброцитарного ряда, лимфоцитами и пролиферацией клеток ретикуло-эндотелиальной системы хозяина.

Ключевые слова: гельминтозы, инфильтрация, эозинофилия, пролиферация, эхинуриоз, лимфоцитарные и гистоцитарные элементы.

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THE STUDY OF CELLULAR REACTIONS IN HELMINTHIASIS

Annotation. Cellular reactions in helminthiasis are characterized by eosinophilia, infiltration by fibrocyte cells, lymphocytes, and proliferation of cells of the host's reticuloendothelial system.

Key words: helminthiasis, infiltration, eosinophilia, proliferation, echinuriosis, lymphocytic and histiocytic elements.

АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ ТЕМЫ

Прямое повреждающее воздействие на ткани организма хозяина оказывают многие гельминты. На фоне этого повреждения развивается воспалительный процесс, не связанный с иммунными механизмами. Гельминты не выделяют специальные вещества, оказывающие токсическое

действие на ткани, но некоторые продукты их метаболизма, такие как секреты гельминтов, обеспечивающие их внедрение в ткани, половые гормоны паразитов, экскременты являются антигенами и способствуют развитию воспалительных реакций.

В организме хозяев гельминты вызывают широкий спектр иммунных реакций, природа и механизм которых специфичны, т. к. паразитические черви могут быть источником многочисленных антигенных раздражителей. Ответная реакция хозяина на выделение антигенов паразитами проявляется появлением клеток соединительной ткани. Из них особое значение имеют клетки-резиденты (фибробласты, макрофаги, тучные и плазматические клетки) и клетки-иммигранты (лимфоциты, эозинофилы, нейтрофилы), которые выполняют защитные функции, включая иммунологические.

Типы иммунных реакций определяются, прежде всего, характером и количеством антигена. Особенности иммунных реакций при различных гельминтозах изучены недостаточно.

ЦЕЛЬ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

Изучение клеточных реакций при гельминтозах.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

Исследование проводили в виварии и центральной научно-исследовательской лаборатории (ЦНИЛ) при АГМИ (Андижанском государственном медицинском институте). Для исследования были отобраны следующие животные с различными паразитическими заболеваниями: водоплавающие птицы (утки и гуси) с эхиноуриозом – 5, собаки и кролики с трематодозом - 2. Проводились гистохимическое, микроскопическое, биохимическое исследования слизистых, подслизистых, мышечных оболочках желудка, кишечника, стенок панкреатических протоков и самой печени животных.

ПОЛУЧЕННЫЕ РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ

Большое значение в развитии иммунного ответа при гельминтозах имеют клетки, покрывающие личинки гельминта. Эти клетки нескольких типов, которые обладают способностью в присутствии антител прикрепляться к личинкам шистосом, микрофилярий, анкилостомид. Чаще всего, это эозинофилы, хотя при некоторых условиях к паразитам могут прикрепляться макрофаги и лимфоциты. Среди прикрепляющихся лимфоцитов могут быть и неспецифические К-клетки. При этом поверхность гельминта повреждается лизосомальными ферментами, которые выделяются прикрепившимися клетками, что может быть смертельным для паразита.

Для некоторых видов гельминтов характерно отложение яиц в отдельных органах, иногда в огромном количестве. Но в любом случае, выделение яиц гельминтов происходит в организме хозяина, то есть за пределами самого паразита. Влияние выброса яиц гельминта в эндостацию может играть как положительную роль, так и отрицательную. В первом случае, яйца гельминтов могут использоваться самими паразитами для поддержания трофики, особенно, если гельминт инкапсулируется, как это имеет место при парагонимозе. Во втором варианте, яйца гельминтов выделяют собственные антигены, что способствует развитию ответных реакций хозяина в виде атипичного воспаления.

При многих гельминтозах наблюдают структурные и функциональные нарушения разных отделов пищеварительного тракта человека и животных. На ранних этапах развития гельминтозов клеточные реакции характеризуются образованием клеточных инфильтратов из лейкоцитарных элементов, которые выявляются в слизистой, подслизистой и мышечной оболочках желудка, кишечника и протоках желез пищеварительного тракта. Обширные инфильтраты в слизистой оболочке состоят преимущественно из нейтрофилов со значительным включением

эозинофилов. Вокруг погибших паразитов появляются скопления гигантских клеток. Увеличение зон клеточных инфильтратов в собственной слизистой оболочке и в межмышечной ткани с преобладанием эозинофилов и множеством круглоклеточных форм было отмечено при изучении эхинуриоза гусей на 14-е сутки инвазии. Через 21 сутки было отмечено диффузная инфильтрация межмышечной клетчатки эозинофилами и лимфоидными клетками, образующие обширные скопления. На 34-е сутки после заражения в области глубоких желез установлено развитие диффузных инфильтратов с преобладанием лимфоидных клеток и лимфоподобных образований. При эхинуриозе гусей было выявлено преобладание пролиферативно-продуктивных изменений с увеличением клеток лимфоидного ряда, аллергической реакции, характеризующейся интенсивной местной тканевой и общей эозинофилией. При экспериментальном тетрамерозе отмечены десквамативное катаральное воспаление глубоких желез, а по мере роста и развития в них гельминтов – дегенерация и атрофия железистой ткани. В слизистой оболочке железистой ткани желудка наблюдали развитие умеренного катара, а в перигландулярной ткани – незначительный отек и клеточные инфильтраты из лимфоидных и гистиоцитарных элементов.

Воспалительную реакцию в виде гиперемии сосудов слизистой оболочки с образованием вокруг них круглоклеточной инфильтрации лимфоидными и гистиоцитарными клетками с присутствием эозинофильных лейкоцитов наблюдали при полиморфозе уток. Указывалось на развитие псевдоопухолевого инфильтративно-язвенного гастродуоденита при ранней стадии описторхоза у людей, который развивался внезапно на 3-м месяце заболевания. В основе данной формы гастрита лежат инфильтративные или инфильтративно-язвенные изменения аллергического генеза. Исследования показали, что инвазия стимулирует миграцию Т-лимфоцитов и делящихся клеток-

предшественников из лимфатических протоков, которые затем оседают в слизистой оболочке по всей длине кишечника, вызывая иммунную реакцию при местной антигенной стимуляции.

Дальнейшие гистологические и гистохимические исследования позволили установить, что к механическим повреждениям органов пищеварительного тракта впоследствии присоединяются воспалительные реакции с интенсивной пролиферацией клеток ретикулоэндотелиальной системы. Установлено, что при гельминтозах формируются преимущественно лимфоидные воспалительные инфильтраты, а также развиваются дистрофические, некробиотические и некротические процессы, являющиеся следствием токсического воздействия продуктов жизнедеятельности гельминтов.

Установлено, что локализацию эозинофилов около паразитов и усиление их антипаразитарных функций обеспечивают иммуноглобулин (Ig)E-зависимые реакции тучных клеток, которые вызывают дегрануляцию эозинофилов, т. е. слияние гранул с цитоплазматической мембраной, содержащих различные вещества, в том числе нейротоксин, пероксидазу, гистаминазу, фосфолипазу Д, гидролитические ферменты, кислую фосфатазу, коллагеназу, Zn, катепсин, и высвобождения их содержимого во внеклеточную среду. При изучении гиперэозинофилии было выявлено ее уменьшение, а также возможно исчезновение под влиянием кортикостероидной терапии, что связано с угнетением эозинофилопоэза. Уменьшение числа эозинофилов происходит за счет клеток с нормальной плотностью, в то время как клетки с низкой плотностью остаются малоизмененными.

ВЫВОД

Выявлено, что эозинофилоциты в стенках панкреатических протоков и печени имеют более крупные размеры (18,4–20 мкм) по сравнению с эозинофилами крови (11,5–12,5 мкм). При окраске по Маллори гранулы

эозинофилов разного размера окрашиваются в ярко-оранжевый цвет, что может свидетельствовать о наличии в них липоидов. Ядро может быть палочковидным, подковообразным, сегментированной формы, что зависит от степени зрелости клетки. Активация зрелых эозинофилов обеспечивается многими факторами, из которых отмечены вещества, выделяемые Т-лимфоцитами и макрофагами. Выявлено, что эозинофилия при трематодозах в тканях хозяина сопровождается скоплением Т-лимфоцитов, макрофагов с преобладанием их среди других клеточных элементов. Отмечено, что инфильтрация эозинофилоцитами однотипна при всех трематодозах и эозинофильная реакция происходит независимо от уровня организации хозяина (теплокровные или холоднокровные животные), обеспечивая защиту хозяина от повреждающего действия гельминтов.

При интенсивной инвазии трематодами эозинофилы усиливают свое действие на паразита, уничтожая гельминтов за счет выделения специальных веществ, имеющих в гранулах, обеспечивая механизмы формирования гомеорезиса паразитарной системы на данном уровне организации.

Таким образом, клеточные реакции при гельминтозах имеют определенную типизацию, характеризующуюся инфильтрацией клетками резидентами, среди которых встречаются фиброциты, фибробласты, макрофаги, тучные и плазматические клетки, и клетками-иммигрантами, преимущественно эозинофилами и лимфоцитами, которые выполняют защитные функции, включая иммунологические реакции хозяина.

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**ЛИНГВОМЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ РУССКИМ
МЕСТОИМЕНЕНИЯМ В АНГЛИЙСКОЙ АУДИТОРИИ**

***Аннотация:** Статья посвящена лингвометодическим основам обучения русским местоимениям в англоязычной аудитории. Рассматриваются лингвистические особенности местоимений в русском языке, которые могут вызывать трудности у студентов, такие как падежная система и разнообразие форм. Предложены методические рекомендации, включая контекстуальное обучение, визуализацию, использование аудиоматериалов, игровые элементы и пошаговое освоение тематики. Подчеркивается важность создания активной учебной среды, способствующей эффективному усвоению местоимений и улучшению навыков общения на русском языке. Статья нацелена на преподавателей, желающих улучшить качество обучения русскому языку как иностранному.*

***Ключевые слова:** Местоимения, Лингвометодические основы, Обучение языку, Англоязычные студенты, Падежная система, Личные местоимения, Притяжательные местоимения, Указательные местоимения, Неопределенные местоимения, Контекстуальное обучение, Визуализация, Аудирование, Игровые методики*

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**LINGUISTIC METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF
TEACHING RUSSIAN PRONOUNS IN AN ENGLISH CLASSROOM**

***Abstract:** This article is dedicated to the linguo-methodological foundations of teaching Russian pronouns in an English-speaking audience. It discusses the linguistic features of pronouns in the Russian language that may pose difficulties for students, such as the case system and the variety of forms. Methodological recommendations are provided, including contextual learning, visualization, the use of audio materials, game elements, and step-by-step mastery of the topic. The importance of creating an active learning environment that fosters effective pronoun acquisition and improves communication skills in*

Russian is emphasized. The article is aimed at educators looking to enhance the quality of teaching Russian as a foreign language.

Key words: *Pronouns, Linguo-methodological foundations, Language teaching, English-speaking students, Case system, Personal pronouns, Possessive pronouns, Demonstrative pronouns, Indefinite pronouns, Contextual learning, Visualization, Listening comprehension, Game-based methods*

Обучение русскому языку как иностранному представляет собой сложную задачу, особенно когда дело касается грамматических категорий, таких как местоимения. Местоимения играют ключевую роль в языке, обеспечивая связь между словами и выражая различные аспекты речи. В этой статье рассмотрим лингвометодические основы обучения русским местоимениям в английской аудитории, акцентируя внимание на особенностях восприятия и методах преподавания.

ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Русский язык отличается от английского в структуре местоимений. В частности, в русском языке существует большее количество форм и видов местоимений: личные, притяжательные, указательные, неопределенные и др. Также важно учитывать падежную систему, которая существенно влияет на употребление местоимений.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ВОСПРИЯТИЯ

Англоязычные студенты могут столкнуться с несколькими трудностями при изучении русских местоимений:

1. **Падежи:** В английском языке местоимения не изменяются по падежам, что делает трудным понимание системы склонений в русском.
2. **Разнообразие форм:** Сложность представляют разные формы одного и того же местоимения (например, "я", "меня", "мной").
3. **Контекстуальная зависимость:** Употребление местоимений в русском языке часто зависит от контекста, что требует от студентов высокой степени языковой интуиции.

МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ РЕКОМЕНДАЦИИ

1. **Контекстуальное обучение:** Использование ситуационных задач и ролевых игр поможет студентам понять, как местоимения функционируют в различных контекстах. Например, студенты могут разыгрывать диалоги, где необходимо использовать различные формы местоимений.
2. **Визуализация и схемы:** Создание наглядных материалов, таких как таблицы и схемы, может упростить запоминание и понимание местоимений. Это особенно эффективно для студентов, которые лучше воспринимают информацию визуально.
3. **Аудирование и чтение:** Включение аудиоматериалов и текстов, содержащих местоимения, поможет студентам научиться интуитивно воспринимать их в речи. Анализ различных примеров использования местоимений в контексте позволит лучше усвоить их функции.
4. **Игровые элементы:** Игровые методики, такие как викторины и кроссворды, могут сделать процесс обучения более увлекательным и повысить мотивацию студентов.
5. **Пошаговое освоение:** Рекомендуется начать с личных местоимений, затем переходить к притяжательным и указательным, уделяя внимание каждой группе отдельно, прежде чем смешивать их в заданиях.

Обучение русским местоимениям в английской аудитории требует комплексного подхода, учитывающего как лингвистические особенности русского языка, так и психологические аспекты восприятия языка. Применение различных методических приемов, направленных на активизацию студентов и создание контекстуальной среды для изучения, поможет преодолеть трудности, связанные с освоением данной темы. В результате студенты смогут не только

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запомнить формы местоимений, но и научиться эффективно использовать их в речи, что является ключевым аспектом успешного овладения русским языком.

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**ВОСПРОИЗВОДИТЕЛЬНАЯ СПОСОБНОСТЬ МОЛОДЫХ
САМЦОВ СОБОЛЯ КЛЕТОЧНОГО РАЗВЕДЕНИЯ**

Аннотация. В статье представлены результаты анализа воспроизводительной способности молодых самцов соболя разного возраста. Установлено, что с увеличением возраста самцов повышается доля оценившихся самок, покрытых этими самцами, плодовитость и полигамная способность. Таким образом, в соболеводстве для полноценного воспроизводства молодых особей важен не только возраст самки, но и возраст самца.

Ключевые слова: соболя, соболеводство, размножение, плодовитость, полигамия, самцы, самки.

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**REPRODUCTIVE CAPACITY OF YOUNG MALES OF FARM
BREEDED SABLE**

Abstract. The article presents the results of an analysis of the reproductive ability of young sable males of different ages. It has been established that with increasing age of males, the proportion of whelping females covered by these males, fertility and polygamous ability increase. Thus, in sable breeding, for the full reproduction of young individuals, not only the age of the female, but also the age of the male is important.

Keywords: sable, sable breeding, reproduction, fertility, polygamy, males, females.

Введение. Шкурки соболя отличаются особой ценностью и во все времена имели большой спрос [1]. Основной проблемой в соболеводстве является поздняя половая зрелость соболей и связанное с этим большое

количество пропустований молодых самок. Большинство исследователей считает, что нормально самки соболя начинают размножаться только с трехлетнего возраста [4, 5]. В настоящее время такого же мнения придерживается большинство специалистов соболеводческих хозяйств [2, 6, 7, 8, 9].

Принято считать, что причина большого количества пропустований ремонтных самок соболей кроется, прежде всего, в самих самках, а самцов считают половозрелыми [4]. Однако среди молодых самцов также наблюдается снижение потентности [7, 8, 9]. Поэтому может сложиться ситуация, когда половозрелая самка покрывается неполовозрелым самцом, что, в конечном счете, может привести к её пропустованию. Данных о репродуктивности самцов на современном этапе клеточного соболеводства в литературе встречается крайне мало.

Цель работы – провести анализ воспроизводительной способности молодых самцов соболя разного возраста.

Материал и методы. Исследования проводили в ООО «Зверохозяйство «Знаменское» Тверской области. Объектом исследования являлись самцы соболя породы салтыковская 1 (2010, 2011, 2012 г.р.). В ходе работы анализировали данные о репродуктивности одних и тех же самцов ($n = 322$) в возрасте одного года, двух и трех лет. Возраст зверей указан на время гона.

Воспроизводительную способность самцов соболей изучали по материалам гона и щенения самок, которых они покрывали. Учитывали число покрытых и оценившихся самок, плодовитость самок (число живых и мертвых щенков, рожденных у благополучно родившей самки) и полигамную способность самцов.

Результаты исследований. По литературным данным среди самок доля половозрелых особей больше, чем среди самцов. Это не противоречит биологической закономерности полового созревания самцов и самок

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млекопитающих, согласно которой самки становятся половозрелыми раньше, чем самцы [3, 6]. Таким образом, часть полноценных самок не имеет возможности оцениваться из-за непополовозрелых самцов.

Таблица 1. Воспроизводительная способность молодых самцов соболей в ООО «Зверохозяйство «Знаменское»

Год рождения самца	Возраст самца, лет	n	Покрыто самок		Оценилось самок		Плодовитость, гол.	Полигамия		
			гол.	%	гол.	%		среднее	min	max
2010 (n=123)	1	10	15	100	7	46,7	2,4	1,5	1	3
	2	61	120	100	52	43,3	3,0	1,9	1	5
	3	52	148	100	92	62,2	3,3	2,8	1	6
2011 (n=80)	1	11	33	100	13	39,4	2,7	1,9	1	3
	2	39	76	100	46	60,5	3,2	1,9	1	5
	3	30	68	100	48	70,6	3,3	2,3	1	7
2012 (n=119)	1	2	4	100	1	25,0	-	2	2	2
	2	61	143	100	91	63,6	3,5	2,3	1	5
	3	56	129	100	96	74,4	3,6	2,3	1	4

Данные таблицы 1 и рисунка 1 свидетельствуют о том, что по мере увеличения возраста самцов в стаде соболей повышается доля оценившихся самок, покрытых этими самцами, соответственно снижается число пропустовавших самок.

В ООО «Зверохозяйство «Знаменское» из числа самок, покрытых однолетними самцами, оценилось 25,0%-46,7%, двухлетними - 43,3%-63,6% и трехлетними – 62,2%-74,4% (таблица 1). В среднем за три года исследований доля оценившихся самок, покрытых однолетними самцами, составила 37,0%, двухлетними - 55,8% и трехлетними – 60,9% (рисунок 1).

Рисунок 1. Процентное соотношение оценившихся и не оценившихся самок соболя в зависимости от возраста самцов

По данным таблицы 1 видно, что средняя плодовитость самок, покрытых самцами более старшего возраста, имеет тенденцию к увеличению. От самок, покрытыми однолетними самцами получено 2,4-2,7 щенка, двухлетними – 3,0-3,5 щенка, трехлетними – 3,3-3,6 щенка. Средняя полигамия одно-, двух-, трехлетних самцов составила 1,5-1,9, 1,9-2,3 и 2,3-2,8, соответственно.

Заключение. Анализ воспроизводительной способности самцов в ООО «Зверохозяйство «Знаменское» показал, что для полноценного воспроизводства важен не только возраст самки, но и возраст самца. С возрастом повышается воспроизводительная способность самцов соболей. Следовательно, часть полноценных самок не имеет возможности оценить из-за не половозрелых самцов.

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**МИКРОСТРУКТУРА КОЖНОГО ПОКРОВА У ХОРЬКОВ И ЕЕ
ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ТОВАРНЫЕ СВОЙСТВА ШКУРОК**

Аннотация. Статья посвящена изучению гистологических особенностей микроструктуры кожного покрова хорьков клеточного разведения трех окрасов и их влияние на товарные свойства шкурки. Приведены результаты оценок толщины и соотношения различных составляющих слоев кожного покрова: эпидермис и дерма (сосочковый и сетчатый слои). Установлено, что у самцов хорьков трех исследованных окрасов толщина кожного покрова и густота волос статистически достоверно больше, чем у самок. У пастелевых хорьков самые прочные шкурки. Наиболее густоволосыми являются хорьки перламутровой окраски, как самцы, так и самки.

Ключевые слова: хорьки, окраска, шкурка, кожный покров, микроструктура, волосяные фолликулы

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**THE MICROSTRUCTURE OF THE SKIN IN FERRETS AND ITS
EFFECT ON THE COMMERCIAL PROPERTIES OF THE SKINS**

Abstract. The article is devoted to the study of the histological features of the microstructure of the skin of ferrets of cellular breeding of three colors and

their effect on the marketable properties of the skins. The results of estimates of the thickness and ratio of the various constituent layers of the skin: epidermis and dermis (papillary and mesh layers) are presented. It was found that male ferrets of the three studied colors have a statistically significantly greater skin thickness and hair density than females. Pastel ferrets have the most durable skins. The most densely haired ferrets are pearl-colored, both males and females.

Keywords: *ferrets, coloring, skin, skin, microstructure, hair follicles*

Введение. Разводить хорьков, как ценных пушных зверей, на фермах начали за рубежом в первой половине XX в., а в России с 1977 года [2].

Хорьки относятся к семейству куницеобразных – *Mustelidae*, подсемейству хорьков – *Mustelinae*, роду хорьков – *Mustela*.

В России обитает два вида диких хорьков: лесной – *Mustela putorius, Linnaeus, 1758* и степной (светлый) *Mustela eversmann, Lesson, 1827*.

В звероводческих хозяйствах разводят хорьков, полученных в результате скрещивания дикого черного хорька и одомашненного фуру. На начальной стадии клеточного разведения гибридных хорьков в их пометах наблюдалось расщепление по окраске волосяного покрова на альбиносую и черную. Затем при разведении стали использовать только зверей с окраской, характерной для черного хорька, а альбиносы в настоящее время выщепляются достаточно редко. Проводимая селекция хорьков по окраске волосяного покрова в основном была направлена на получение животных двух типов, представляющих крайние формы изменчивости общей окраски: с золотисто-оранжевой и бежево-серой окраской пуховых волос. Несмотря на существенную разницу в окраске волосяного покрова, эти типы не являются мутантными, так как различия в фенотипе обусловлены полигенами [4].

В настоящее время у хорьков, кроме альбиносов, известна только одна мутация окраски волосяного покрова – пастелевая, обусловленная рецессивным геном. В скандинавской системе обозначения генов окраски

пушных зверей ген пастелевой окраски волосяного покрова хорьков по аналогии с пастелевой норкой обозначен символом **b**. Однако, на основе результатов скрещивания пастелевых хорьков с фуру, установлено, что пастелевая окраска обусловлена рецессивным геном, аллельным гену альбиносовой окраски. В связи с чем, ген пастелевой окраски был обозначен символом **c^p** [5].

Основная окраска волосяного покрова пастелевых хорьков светло-коричневая. Окраска кроющих волос – коричневая различной интенсивности, окраска пуховых - от почти белой до кремовой [6].

Шкурки хорьков относятся к средневолосой пушнине, по носкости – ко второй группе (60 баллов) и имеют средний по упругости волосяной покров. В хозяйствах ведется целенаправленная селекция по улучшению признаков, обуславливающих качество опушения. К таким признакам относятся густота, длина и тонина волос, соотношение различных категорий волос по густоте и уравниности их по длине, наличие дефектов опушения. Целью данного исследования было изучение гистологических особенностей микроструктуры кожного покрова хорьков клеточного разведения и их влияние на товарные свойства шкурок.

Материалы и методы. У пресно-сухих и выделанных шкурок хорьков измеряли площадь и толщину кожной ткани в пяти точках: загривке, хребте, боку, огузке и череве.

При приготовлении вертикальных гистологических срезов из образцов кожи с волосом хорьков после отмоки в проточной воде вырезали фрагменты длиной 2 см и шириной 1 см, которые помещали в раствор формалина до момента приготовления срезов. Для приготовления срезов образцы заливали парафином.

Парафиновые блоки были нарезаны на пластины с помощью микротомы. Срезы окрашивали гематоксилин-эозином. Раствор красителя готовили следующим образом: 2 г красителя растворяли в 100 мл 96%

спирта, добавляли 100 мл дистиллированной воды, 100 мл чистого глицерина, 3 г калийных квасцов и 10 мл уксусной кислоты. Перед окраской срезы пропускали через батарею спиртов постепенно возрастающей крепости, от 40° до 96°. Данный процесс проводился для обезвоживания образцов. Обезвоженные срезы помещали в раствор красителя на 2-3 мин, затем промывали чистой водой. Окрашенные срезы помещали на предметное стекло, накрывали покровным стеклом и фиксировали канадским бальзамом [1].

Определение толщины отдельных слоев кожного покрова проводили при помощи микроскопа, для этого препарат устанавливали на предметный столик покровным стеклом вверх, чтобы срез кожной ткани находился непосредственно под фронтальной линзой объектива слабого увеличения.

Статистическую обработку материала проводили с помощью программы Microsoft Excel-2007. Вычисляли среднее значение ($\bar{X}$), ошибку средней величины (S_x), коэффициент изменчивости (C_v , %) и стандартное отклонение (δ). Разницу средней величины оценивали по критерию Стьюдента и вероятностей P , которую признавали статистически значимой при $P < 0,05$. Для изучения связи между показателями использовали корреляционный анализ с расчетом коэффициента Пирсона (значение $r = 0,1-0,3$ соответствовали слабой связи; $0,4-0,7$ – умеренной; $0,7-1,0$ – высокой).

Результаты и исследований. Кожный покров млекопитающих представляет собой трехкомпонентную систему, образованную эпидермисом, дермой и подкожно-жировой тканью, которые находятся в морфо-функциональном единстве. У хорьков, как и у большинства млекопитающих, в дерме выделяют два слоя: сосочковый (*stratum papillare*) и сетчатый (*stratum reticulare*). Они заполнены волокнистыми образованиями (коллагеновыми волокнами), которые составляют почти

90% дермы. От строения кожи, соотношения сосочкового и сетчатого слоев, характера переплетения коллагеновых волокон, от количества первичных и вторичных фолликулов зависят многие свойства шкурок [7]. Исследования микроструктуры кожного покрова хорьков разных цветовых типов показали, что самый тонкий кожный покров у хорьков перламутровой окраски (у самок 704,2; у самцов - 1077 мкм), он отличается от этого показателя у хорьков двух других окрасок ($P > 0,999$) (табл.1).

Таблица 1 – Толщина отдельных слоев кожного покрова шкурок хорьков, $n=100$

Цветовые типы хорьков	Пол	Толщина кожного покрова и основных его слоев в линейных (мкм) и относительных (% к общей толщине) единицах					
		Кожный покров в целом		Эпидермис		Дерма	
		$\bar{X} \pm S_x$	%	$\bar{X} \pm S_x$	%	$\bar{X} \pm S_x$	%
Золотистые	♂	1356,4±70,2	100	34,8±0,3	2,6	1321,6±18,4	97,4
	♀	948,8±54,3	100	24,6±2,1	2,6	924,2±9,6	97,4
Перламутровые	♂	1077,8±19,1	100	37,9±2,1	3,5	1039,9±23,0	96,5
	♀	704,2±6,6	100	25,0±0,9	3,6	679,2±7,7	96,4
Пастелевые	♂	1244,7±11,5	100	29,6±1,0	2,4	1215,1±11,2	97,7
	♀	740,0±6,5	100	29,3±1,1	4,0	710,7±6,9	96,0

У хорьков трех исследуемых цветовых форм более толстый кожный покров у самцов, чем у самок ($P > 0,999$). Толщина эпидермиса у исследованных особей варьирует от 2,4 до 4,0% от общей толщины кожного покрова. Из полученных данных следует, что соотношение слоев кожного покрова у отобранных для эксперимента хорьков неодинаково.

НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И РАЗРАБОТКИ II

У хорьков перламутровой окраски сосочковый слой лучше развит, чем у пастелевой – у самок перламутровой окраски он составляет 76,8 % от толщины дермы (521,7 мкм) против 65,6% (466,0 мкм) у самок пастелевой окраски (табл. 2). У самцов это процентное соотношение составляет 71,6 (перламутровые) против 64,9 % (пастелевые). В сосочковом слое больше содержится волосяных фолликулов, сальных и потовых желез. Следовательно, волосяной покров у хорьков перламутровой окраски в целом значительно гуще. Сетчатый слой сильнее развит у хорьков пастелевой окраски, что влияет на прочность кожной ткани, а, следовательно, и на прочность шкурки. Процентное соотношение слоев кожи по толщине подтверждает сказанное выше.

Таблица 2 – Толщина сосочкового и сетчатого слоев дермы шкурок хорьков разных типов, n=100

Цветовые типы хорьков	Пол	Дерма	Слои дермы, мм			
			сосочковый		сетчатый	
		$\bar{X} \pm S_x$	$\bar{X} \pm S_x$	%	$\bar{X} \pm S_x$	%
Золотистые	♂	1321,6±18,4	942,7±10,4	71,3	378,9±15,3	28,7
	♀	924,2±9,6	648,4±12,3	70,2	275,8±5,3	29,8
Перламутровые	♂	1069,9±23,0	774,4±16,4	71,6	295,5±17,5	28,4
	♀	679,2±7,7	521,7±7,9	76,8	157,5±4,1	23,2
Пастелевые	♂	1215,1±11,2	788,7±9,7	64,9	426,4±11,2	35,1
	♀	710,7±6,9	466,0±5,7	65,6	244,7±4,9	34,4

В результате проведенных исследований на горизонтальных срезах кожной ткани было определено количество первичных и вторичных фолликул в поле зрения микроскопа. Волосяные фолликулы являются основой для будущих волос. Из первичных фолликул развиваются кроющие волосы, а из вторичных - пуховые.

Таблица 3 - Количество волосяных фолликулов на шкурках хорьков (в поле зрения микроскопа $S=1,2 \text{ мм}^2$) и густота волос, им соответствующая

Цветовые типы хорьков	пол	Количество фолликул, шт.			Густота волос, шт. / см^2
		первичных	вторичных	общее	
Золотистые	♀	4,0±0,1	59,2±1,9	63,2±2,1	5267±33
	♂	3,8±0,1	58,1±2,1	61,9±3,8	5158±74
Перламутровые	♀	4,8±0,1	60,2±3,8	65,0±7,2	5417±60
	♂	4,6±0,1	59,7±1,8	64,3±4,4	5361±37
Пастелевые	♀	3,8±0,1	48,6±1,6	52,4±2,2	4367±38
	♂	3,3±0,1	47,4±1,1	50,7±3,4	4225±82

Данных представленные в табл. 3, указывают, что наиболее густоволосыми являются хорьки перламутровой окраски (65 фолликул в поле зрения микроскопа у самок; 64,3 у самцов), это соответствует 5417 шт. волос в расчете на 1 см^2 кожного покрова у самок и 5361 шт. у самцов. Густота волос у самцов трех цветовых типов больше, чем у самок.

Заключение. Хорьки имеют довольно толстый кожный покров 1077,8-1356,4 мкм у самцов, 704,4-848,8 мкм у самок, с хорошо развитой дермой – 1069,5 -1321,6 мкм у самцов и 679,2 – 924,2 мкм у самок, и очень тонким эпидермисом - 24,6-37,9 мкм, что делает шкурки наиболее прочными на разрыв. Наиболее густоволосыми являются хорьки перламутровой окраски, как самцы, так и самки.

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**УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИМИ ПРОЦЕССАМИ С
ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО МОДУЛЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ
И ВЛАЖНОСТИ**

Аннотация: статья посвящена вопросам управления технологическими процессами с использованием электронного измерительного модуля температуры и влажности. В ней рассматриваются современные электронные устройства, которые обеспечивают высокоточный мониторинг климатических условий в различных сферах, включая промышленность и сельское хозяйство. Обсуждаются методы интеграции данных датчиков в автоматизированные системы, позволяющие контролировать параметры в реальном времени и оптимизировать производственные процессы. Основное внимание уделяется применению измерительных модулей для повышения качества продукции, автоматизации процессов и управления ресурсами. В статье также рассматривается применение в производстве, способных реагировать на изменения окружающей среды.

Ключевые слова: влажность, температура, природное воздействие, окружающая среда, дифференциальные уравнение.

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**PROCESS CONTROL USING AN ELECTRONIC TEMPERATURE
AND HUMIDITY MODULE**

Annotation: The article is devoted to the issues of process control using an electronic temperature and humidity measuring module. It examines modern electronic devices that provide high-precision monitoring of climatic conditions in various fields, including industry and agriculture. Methods of integrating sensor data into automated systems that allow real-time monitoring of parameters and optimization of production processes are discussed. The main focus is on the use of measurement modules to improve product quality, automate processes and manage resources. The article also discusses the use in production of devices capable of responding to environmental changes.

Keywords: humidity, temperature, natural impact, environment, differential equation.

Введение. В современном мире точное управление технологическими процессами стало неотъемлемой частью производственной и сельскохозяйственной деятельности. Одним из значимых элементов эффективного управления является мониторинг параметров окружающей среды, таких как температура и влажность. Электронные измерительные модули температуры и влаги играют ключевую роль в этом процессе. В условиях современного производства управление технологическими процессами становится все более сложной задачей, требующей гибкости и точности. Электронные измерительные модули температуры и влажности играют ключевую роль в этих процессах, обеспечивая непрерывный мониторинг и контроль за параметрами, критически важными для качества продукции.

Электронные измерительные модули, такие как DHT11, DHT22 или SHT31, способны предоставлять высокоточную информацию о текущих условиях. Эти устройства интегрируются с микроконтроллерами и могут передавать данные в реальном времени для дальнейшей обработки и анализа. Учёт каждой из переменных является важным, что позволяет говорить, что исследование настоящего эффекта является **актуальным**.

Применение в производственных процессах

По своей функции электронные измерительные модули температуры и влаги предназначены для измерения и мониторинга условий окружающей среды. Они обычно используются в различных областях, таких как промышленность, сельское хозяйство, или домашнее использование для контроля и поддержания оптимальных уровней температуры и влажности. Из ходя из поставленной задачи и полученных экспериментальных значений был разработан электронный измерительный прибор температуры и влажности.

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1. Контроль качества: В большинстве производств, особенно в пищевой и фармацевтической промышленности, поддержание стабильных температурных и влажностных условий критически важно для обеспечения качества продукции. Измерительные модули позволяют контролировать эти параметры и предотвращать возможные отклонения.

2. Автоматизация процессов: с помощью датчиков можно автоматизировать системы отопления, вентиляции и кондиционирования. Программное обеспечение, связанное с модулем, может автоматически регулировать климатические условия в зависимости от полученных данных.

3. Управление ресурсами: В сельском хозяйстве управление влажностью и температурой в теплицах помогает оптимизировать использование воды и удобрений, что значительно повышает урожайность и снижает затраты.

Данный модуль собирает все данные и после математических считываний, которые записаны на микроконтроллере выдаёт оптимальное расстояние и передвигает антенны на нужные места для корректной работы считывателя. Модуль был собран из следующих комплектующих электронных устройств. Электронный измерительный модуль температуры и влаги состоит из следующих электронных устройств:

Датчики температуры и влажности - для измерения и регистрации значений этих параметров, таких как терм компенсированные датчики или сенсоры влажности.

Датчик DHT22 (также известный как AM2302) является одним из самых популярных датчиков температуры и влажности на рынке. Он состоит из одного корпуса, в котором интегрированы датчики температуры и влажности.

Рис. 1. Датчик DHT22

Датчик DHT22 обычно имеет следующие характеристики:

- Диапазон измерения температуры: от -40°C до $+80^{\circ}\text{C}$
- Диапазон измерения влажности: от 0% до 100%
- Точность измерений температуры: $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$
- Точность измерений влажности: $\pm 2\%$
- Интерфейс: цифровой (однопроводной)

Датчик DHT22 можно подключить к микроконтроллеру (например, Arduino) для считывания данных о температуре и влажности окружающей среды. С помощью специальной библиотеки и простого кода программы можно получить доступ к данным с датчика и использовать их для различных приложений, например, мониторинга условий в помещении или автоматизации системы управления климатом.

Датчик состоит из двух частей – емкостного датчика температуры и гигрометра. Первый используется для измерения температуры, второй – для влажности воздуха. Находящийся внутри чип может выполнять аналого-цифровые преобразования и выдавать цифровой сигнал, который считывается посредством микроконтроллера. Корпус датчика сравнительно большой. Из корпуса выходят 4 вывода, и они имеют следующее назначение (слева направо)

- 1 — VDD-power supply (питание)
- 2 — DATA-signal (информационный выход)
- 3 — NULL (не используется)

4 — GND (общий провод)

Микроконтроллер - управляющее устройство, которое обрабатывает данные от датчиков, осуществляет связь с другими устройствами и принимает решения на основе полученной информации.

Рис. 2. Микроконтроллер STM32F401CCU6

Микроконтроллер STM32F401CCU6 от компании STMicroelectronics принадлежит к семейству STM32F4 и обладает следующими характеристиками:

- Ядро: ARM Cortex-M4F
- Максимальная тактовая частота: до 84 МГц
- Память: 256 Кб Flash, 64 Кб RAM
- Интерфейсы: USB OTG (On-The-Go), USART, SPI, I2C, CAN, ADC, DAC
- Количество GPIO: до 51
- Поддержка USB Type-C контроллера
- Напряжение питания: от 2.0 В до 3.6 В
- Рабочая температура: от -40°C до +85°C
- Поддержка различных периферийных устройств и функциональных возможностей

. Интерфейсные модули - для передачи данных между модулем и другими устройствами как USB Type-C интерфейс.

5. Интегрированная плата

Рис. 3. Интегрированная плата

6. Система хранения данных - для записи и хранения результатов измерений, что позволяет анализировать и отслеживать изменения температуры и влажности в определенном периоде времени.

6. Блок питания - для обеспечения электропитания всем компонентам модуля.

7. Корпус и защитные элементы - для обеспечения защиты электронных компонентов от внешних факторов, таких как пыль, влага и механические повреждения.

8. Дисплей для вывода данных. Монитор LCD дисплей 2004A (или 20x4 LCD дисплей) является текстовым жидкокристаллическим дисплеем, который обычно используется в различных электронных устройствах и проектах DIY для вывода информации. Вот некоторые основные характеристики 2004A LCD дисплея:

Рис. 4. LCD дисплей 2004A

- Размер: 20 символов в 4 строках (20x4)
- Тип дисплея: Жидкокристаллический (LCD)
- Интерфейс: параллельный (обычно используется 16-pin контроллер HD44780)
- Цвет: обычно черно-белый, негативный (светлый текст на темном фоне) или позитивный (темный текст на светлом фоне)
- Управление: используется для отображения текста, символов, чисел и символов специальных символов
- Напряжение питания: обычно 5V
- Интерфейс I2C: некоторые версии 2004A LCD дисплеев имеют I2C интерфейс для упрощения подключения к микроконтроллерам

Эти дисплеи популярны в DIY проектах, различных прототипах и устройствах, таких как часы, термометры, контроллеры и многое другое. Их преимущество заключается в простоте использования и недорогой стоимости.

Эти компоненты работают вместе для проведения измерений температуры и влажности, обработки данных и передачи информации о состоянии окружающей среды.

9. AQV212S — это оптоэлектронный переключатель (оптоизолятор), производимый компанией Toshiba. Он предназначен для управления высокими напряжениями и токами с помощью низковольтных сигналов, что делает его популярным компонентом в различных электронных устройствах.

Основные характеристики AQV212S:

1. Тип устройства: Оптоэлектронный переключатель (идеальный для применения в качестве оптоизоляторов).
2. Рабочее напряжение:

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- Максимальное напряжение на выходе (на совместном использовании) — до 600 В.

3. Рабочий ток:

- Максимальный выходной ток: 2 А (при 25°C).

- Открытое состояние: ток не более 1 мА при 600 В.

4. Входные характеристики:

- Диапазон входных напряжений: 1.2 В – 1.5 В (для инициирования).

5. Скорость переключения:

- Время включения: около 1 мс.

- Время выключения: около 2 мс.

6. Температура эксплуатации:

- Диапазон рабочих температур: от -40°C до +85°C.

7. Уровень изоляции:

- Изоляция между входом и выходом: 5000 В RMS.

8. Пакет:

- Обычно поставляется в SO-16, что облегчает интеграцию в различные РСВ.

9. Значения на выходе:

- Поддерживает индуктивные и резистивные нагрузки.

Применение: используется в системах управления, таких как реле, системы автоматизации, источники света, и другие области, где требуется изоляция и управление высокими напряжениями.

Это устройство позволяет безопасно переключать высоковольтные нагрузки и является надежным компонентом в электрических схемах. Перед использованием всегда стоит обращаться к технической документации производителя для получения самых точных и актуальных данных о характеристиках устройства.

Рис. 5. оптоэлектронный переключатель

Эта плата может использоваться в различных электронных устройствах и DIY проектах для управления устройствами, светом, моторами, звуковыми сигналами и другими электронными устройствами с помощью реле. Она обеспечивает простой и удобный способ управления выходными устройствами через встроенные реле. Общий вид прибора как было собрано по детально. Нужно учитывать тот факт, что при сборке данного прибора были местонахождения датчиков и дополнительных плат.

Рис. 6. Схема электронного измерительного модуля температуры и влаги

Рис. 7. Общий вид электронного измерительного модуля температуры и влаги.

Прибор может использоваться для различных задач, таких как мониторинг окружающей среды, управление устройствами или автоматизация процессов.

Преимущества использования

- Экономия времени и ресурсов: Автоматизация процессов снижает необходимость в ручной проверке и корректировке параметров, что улучшает общую эффективность работы.

- Увеличение точности: Современные измерительные датчики обеспечивают высокую степень точности, что позволяет принимать обоснованные решения.

- Удаленный доступ: Возможность мониторинга состояния процессов через мобильные устройства или компьютеры позволяет быстро реагировать на изменения.

Мониторинг температуры и влажности поможет выявить и устранить возможные проблемы с рабочими процессами RFID систем, связанные с неблагоприятными условиями окружающей среды. При уставки влажности и температуры для электронного модуля автоматический считывает и определяет оптимальное расстояние для RFID антенн. Электронный модуль при уставки определяет все вводимые значения окружающей среды

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и передаёт сигнал на блок реле для срабатывания двигателя. Соответственно сам блок реле питается из блока питания и с помощи релейной платы срабатывается сигнал для уменьшения или увеличения расстояние антенн. Преимущества внедрения:

1. Точность измерений: Высокая степень точности позволяет получать надежные данные.
2. Автоматизация процессов: упрощает сбор данных и мониторинг условий.
3. Автоматический контролирует расстояние считывание RFID метки.

Рис. 8. Принципиальная схема подключения модуля к системе.

Проведение анализа собранных данных для принятия определенных решений (например, включение или выключение двигателя на основе полученных значений).

Рис. 9. Алгоритм ЭИМТВ модуля.

Заключение. Управление технологическим процессом с помощью электронного измерительного модуля температуры и влаги — это перспективное направление, позволяющее значительно повысить эффективность производства и улучшить качество продукции. Внедрение таких технологий способствует не только оптимизации процессов, но и созданию более устойчивых и эффективных систем в различных сферах. Таким образом, интеграция электронных модулей температуры и влажности в технологические процессы не только способствует улучшению качества продукции, но и увеличивает общую эффективность производства.

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**ИЗУЧЕНИЕ АЛКАЛОИДОВ *TRIBLUS TERRESTRIS*
ПРОИЗРАСТАЮЩЕГО В ФЕРГАНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ**

*Аннотация: В данной диссертации представлена информация об исследовании алкалоидов *Triblus terrestris*, произрастающих в Ферганской области.*

*Ключевые слова: Фергана, *Triblus terrestris*, алкалоид.*

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**STUDY OF ALKALOIDS OF *TRIBLUS TERRESTRIS* GROWING IN
THE FERGHANA REGION**

*Abstract: This dissertation provides information on the study of *Triblus terrestris* alkaloids growing in the Ferghana region.*

*Keywords: Ferghana, *Triblus terrestris*, alkaloid.*

Целью нашего исследования является изучение алкалоидного состава растения *Triblus terrestris* относящегося к семейству *Zygophylloceae*. Стимулом к изучению азотистых оснований *Triblus terrestris* послужил тот факт, что издавна это растение привлекает внимание химиков вследствие его ценных биологических свойств.[1-2] Известно также, что носителями полезных свойств этого растения являются алкалоиды. В связи с этим выделение действующего начала, изучения алкалоидов этого растения, установление их химической структуры и стереохимии, выявление среди выделенных соединений алкалоидов с ценными фармакологическими свойствами с целью получения на их основе высокоэффективных лекарственных препаратов представляется целесообразным и актуальным.

Основным объектом нашего исследования является растение *Triblus terrestris* произрастающее в естественных условиях флоры Узбекистана в

Ферганской области. Исследованию алкалоидного состава подвергнуты все органы растения (корни, корневища, стебли, цветы). Однако, исходя из экономических соображений экстракцию алкалоидов воздушно-сухого растения проводили этанолом. Ежедневно производился слив экстракта, и растение заливалось свежей порцией растворителя. Всего произведено 6 сливов. Полученные после соответствующей обработки [3] суммы алкалоидов хроматографировали на колонке с окисью алюминия. Алкалоиды с колонки элюировали последовательно гексаном, бензолом, хлороформом и хлороформ-метанолом. При хроматографировании хлороформной суммы алкалоидов растение *Tribulus terrestris* на колонке с окисью алюминия, а также рехроматографированием отдельных фракций выделен алкалоид с т.пл. 216-218⁰С.

УФ-спектр содержал максимумы поглощения при 224, 280 нм ($\lg \epsilon$ 3.50, 3.90 соответственно). В ИК спектре алкалоида присутствуют полосы поглощения активного водорода (3130 см^{-1}), ароматического кольца ($1622, 870 \text{ см}^{-1}$), в области "отпечатков пальца" – полосы поглощения ароматического кольца. В масс-спектре имеется пик молекулярного иона с m/z 186, а также пик ионов m/z 143, 116, характерные для индольного ядра [4-5].

Спектр ПМР вещества в $\text{CDCl}_3\text{-CD}_3\text{OD}$ характеризуется наличием трёхпротонного синглета при 2.35 м.д., соответствующего NCH_3 группы. Отмечено присутствие двух симметричных четырёхпротонных мультиплетов с центром при 2,80-3,30 м.д., которые по всей видимости, можно отнести к $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-}$ группе, связанной с ароматическим кольцом с одной стороны и атомом азота с другой. Протон С-1 проявляется слабо уширенным сигналом при 3,66 м.д. В интервале 6.90-7.60 м.д. проявляются сигналы четырех ароматических протонов а в области 11.67 м.д. отмечается уширенный синглетный сигнал от NH -группы.

Изложенные выше спектральные характеристики приводят к структуре алкалоида N-метил-тетрагидро-β-карболин. Интересно отметить, что обнаружение данного алкалоида в растении *Tribulus terrestris*-это первый случай выделения.[6-7]

Экспериментальная часть.

Для колоночной хроматографии применяли окись алюминия II степени активности (по Брокману) марки КСК и L 100/250 ммк. Индивидуальность полученных веществ проверяли на тонкослойной хроматограмме (ТСХ) на закреплённом слое окиси алюминия и силикагеля марки КСК и L 5/40 ммк (Чехия).

Проявитель для алкалоидов – реактив Драгендорфа, пары йода. Температуру плавления веществ определяли на приборе с конц. серной кислотой.

УФ-спектры снимали на приборе Фурье- УФ-спектрометре фирмы “Перкин-Элмер” Л 416 О. Образцы снимались в растворе этанола в кварцевых кюветах, толщина слоя 1 см.

ИК-спектры снимали на приборе Фурье- ИК-спектрометре фирмы “Перкин-Элмер” (модель 2000) в таблетках с KBr.

Масс-спектры снимали на спектрометре МХ-1310 с использованием системы прямого ввода пробы в ионный источник при температуре ионизационной камеры 150⁰С, ампулы-испарителя -70-80⁰С и ионизирующем напряжении 70 эВ.

Спектры ЯМР –регистровали на спектрометре UNITY-400 Varian с рабочей частотой протонов 400 МГц в дейтерохлороформе и дейтерометаноле.

2 кг измельченной воздушно-сухой растения *Tribulus terrestris* экстрагировали этанолом. Всего произведено 6 сливов. Экстракт сгущали и извлекали 5% -ным раствором серной кислоты. Кислый раствор промывали хлороформом, подщелачивали 25%-ным раствором аммиака, экстрагировали хлороформом. После сгущения растворителя получили хлороформная суммы алкалоидов (5 г.).

5 кг хлороформной суммы алкалоидов *Tribulus terrestris* хроматографировали на колонке с Al_2O_3 (1:20), элюировали хлороформом (объем фракций-50 мл). Фракции 1-2 (0.85 г) рехроматографировали на колонке с Al_2O_3 (1:30), элюировали с гексан, бензолом (объем фракций-8 мл). Из 7-14 бензольных фракций обработкой ацетоном выделили 25 мг основания с т.пл. 216-218° (бензол); на ТСХ значение $R_f=0.43$ (сис. хлороформ-метанол 9:1).

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